

Finite Difference Equations Obtained:

(Sorted by derivative and error)

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---"

$$\frac{d}{dx1} u(x1) = \frac{-u_{i1} + u_{i1+1}}{\Delta x1}, O(\Delta x1), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order: 1, Error: 0.0026772555082348129785, New Error: 2.6754763101945547898 × 10⁻⁶
Error order: 1, Error: 2.6754763101945547898 × 10⁻⁶, New Error: 2.6754745318842483092 × 10⁻⁹
Error order: 1, Error: 2.6754745318842483092 × 10⁻⁹, New Error: 2.6754745301059388901 × 10⁻¹²
Error order: 1, Error: 2.6754745301059388901 × 10⁻¹², New Error: 2.6754745301041605807 × 10⁻¹⁵
Error order: 1, Error: 2.6754745301041605807 × 10⁻¹⁵, New Error: 2.6754745301041588024 × 10⁻¹⁸

$$\frac{d}{dx1} u(x1) = \frac{-u_{i1-1} + u_{i1}}{\Delta x1}, O(\Delta x1), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order: 1, Error: 0.0026736953285101754006, New Error: 2.6754727500155393478 × 10⁻⁶
Error order: 1, Error: 2.6754727500155393478 × 10⁻⁶, New Error: 2.6754745283240692938 × 10⁻⁹
Error order: 1, Error: 2.6754745283240692938 × 10⁻⁹, New Error: 2.6754745301023787111 × 10⁻¹²
Error order: 1, Error: 2.6754745301023787111 × 10⁻¹², New Error: 2.6754745301041570205 × 10⁻¹⁵
Error order: 1, Error: 2.6754745301041570205 × 10⁻¹⁵, New Error: 2.6754745301041587988 × 10⁻¹⁸

$$\frac{d}{dx1} u(x1) = \frac{-3u_{i1} + 4u_{i1+1} - u_{i1+2}}{2\Delta x1}, O(\Delta x1^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 3.5655135926601426311 × 10⁻⁶, New Error: 3.5601843450555980057 × 10⁻¹²

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5601843450555980057 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $3.5601790207709383855 \times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5601790207709383855 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $3.5601790154466586853 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5601790154466586853 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $3.5601790154413344056 \times 10^{-30}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5601790154413344056 \times 10^{-30}$, *New Error:*, $3.5601790154413290813 \times 10^{-36}$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(x) = \frac{u_{i-2} - 4u_{i-1} + 3u_i}{2\Delta x}, O(\Delta x^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5548543669732285372 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $3.5601736858369888928 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5601736858369888928 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $3.5601790101117197764 \times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5601790101117197764 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $3.5601790154359994667 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5601790154359994667 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $3.5601790154413237464 \times 10^{-30}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5601790154413237464 \times 10^{-30}$, *New Error:*, $3.5601790154413290706 \times 10^{-36}$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(x) = \frac{-u_{i-1} + u_{i+1}}{2\Delta x}, O(\Delta x^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7800898623187889632 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $1.7800895077210191361 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7800895077210191361 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $1.7800895077206645383 \times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7800895077206645383 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $1.7800895077206645380 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7800895077206645380 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $1.7800895077206645380 \times 10^{-30}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7800895077206645380 \times 10^{-30}$, *New Error:*, $1.7800895077206645380 \times 10^{-36}$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(x) = \frac{-11u_i + 18u_{i+1} - 9u_{i+2} + 2u_{i+3}}{6\Delta x}, O(\Delta x^3), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.3423925485156993968 \times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, $5.3296220701018507621 \times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.3296220701018507621 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $5.3296093173184191244 \times 10^{-27}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.3296093173184191244 \times 10^{-27}$, *New Error:*, $5.3296093045656533696 \times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.3296093045656533696 \times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, $5.3296093045529006038 \times 10^{-45}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.3296093045529006038 \times 10^{-45}$, *New Error:*, $5.3296093045528878511 \times 10^{-54}$

$$\frac{d}{dxl} u(xl) = \frac{-2 u_{il-3} + 9 u_{il-2} - 18 u_{il-1} + 11 u_{il}}{6 \Delta x l}, O(\Delta x l^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.3168614496514063138 \times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, $5.3295965390393139455 \times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.3295965390393139455 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $5.3296092917873565876 \times 10^{-27}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.3296092917873565876 \times 10^{-27}$, *New Error:*, $5.3296093045401223070 \times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.3296093045401223070 \times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, $5.3296093045528750728 \times 10^{-45}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.3296093045528750728 \times 10^{-45}$, *New Error:*, $5.3296093045528878255 \times 10^{-54}$

$$\frac{d}{dxl} u(xl) = \frac{-25 u_{il} + 48 u_{il+1} - 36 u_{il+2} + 16 u_{il+3} - 3 u_{il+4}}{12 \Delta x l}, O(\Delta x l^4), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $8.5387179473549325763 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $8.5103824902040535829 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $8.5103824902040535829 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $8.5103542072379918732 \times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $8.5103542072379918732 \times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, $8.5103541789550782321 \times 10^{-48}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $8.5103541789550782321 \times 10^{-48}$, *New Error:*, $8.5103541789267953185 \times 10^{-60}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $8.5103541789267953185 \times 10^{-60}$, *New Error:*, $8.5103541789267670356 \times 10^{-72}$

$$\frac{d}{dxl} u(xl) = \frac{3 u_{il-4} - 16 u_{il-3} + 36 u_{il-2} - 48 u_{il-1} + 25 u_{il}}{12 \Delta x l}, O(\Delta x l^4), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $8.4820953567362756957 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $8.5103258677544265173 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $8.5103258677544265173 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $8.5103541506155422463 \times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $8.5103541506155422463 \times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, $8.5103541788984557824 \times 10^{-48}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $8.5103541788984557824 \times 10^{-48}$, *New Error:*, $8.5103541789267386960 \times 10^{-60}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $8.5103541789267386960 \times 10^{-60}$, *New Error:*, $8.5103541789267669789 \times 10^{-72}$

$$\frac{d}{dxl} u(xl) = \frac{u_{il-2} - 8 u_{il-1} + 8 u_{il+1} - u_{il+2}}{12 \Delta x l}, O(\Delta x l^4), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.4183930358859361482 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $1.4183923631551338992 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.4183923631551338992 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $1.4183923631544611685 \times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.4183923631544611685 \times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, $1.4183923631544611679 \times 10^{-48}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.4183923631544611679 \times 10^{-48}$, *New Error:*, $1.4183923631544611679 \times 10^{-60}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.4183923631544611679 \times 10^{-60}$, *New Error:*, $1.4183923631544611679 \times 10^{-72}$

$$\frac{d}{dxl} u(xl) = \frac{-137 u_{il} + 300 u_{il+1} - 300 u_{il+2} + 200 u_{il+3} - 75 u_{il+4} + 12 u_{il+5}}{60 \Delta x l}, O(\Delta x l^5), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $1.4216299451829263720 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155672952690818416 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $1.4155672952690818416 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612467276968198 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $1.4155612467276968198 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612406791695199 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $1.4155612406791695199 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612406731209926 \times 10^{-74}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $1.4155612406731209926 \times 10^{-74}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612406731149441 \times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d}{dxl} u(xl) = \frac{-12 u_{il-5} + 75 u_{il-4} - 200 u_{il-3} + 300 u_{il-2} - 300 u_{il-1} + 137 u_{il}}{60 \Delta x l}, O(\Delta x l^5), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $1.4095207345440249144 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155551861053463532 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $1.4155551861053463532 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612346185330844 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $1.4155612346185330844 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612406670603561 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $1.4155612406670603561 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612406731088834 \times 10^{-74}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $1.4155612406731088834 \times 10^{-74}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612406731149319 \times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d}{dxl} u(xl) = \frac{-147 u_{il} + 360 u_{il+1} - 450 u_{il+2} + 400 u_{il+3} - 225 u_{il+4} + 72 u_{il+5} - 10 u_{il+6}}{60 \Delta x l}, O(\Delta x l^6), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $2.4345577079882190135 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.4218454363673881295 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $2.4218454363673881295 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $2.4218327597775496096 \times 10^{-53}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $2.4218327597775496096 \times 10^{-53}$, *New Error:*, $2.4218327471009953820 \times 10^{-71}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $2.4218327471009953820 \times 10^{-71}$, *New Error:*, $2.4218327470883188278 \times 10^{-89}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $2.4218327470883188278 \times 10^{-89}$, *New Error:*, $2.4218327470883061513 \times 10^{-107}$

$$\frac{d}{dxl} u(xl) = \frac{10 u_{il-6} - 72 u_{il-5} + 225 u_{il-4} - 400 u_{il-3} + 450 u_{il-2} - 360 u_{il-1} + 147 u_{il}}{60 \Delta x l}, O(\Delta x l^6), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $2.4091790795644940935 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.4218200578805173021 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $2.4218200578805173021 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $2.4218327343990627389 \times 10^{-53}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $2.4218327343990627389 \times 10^{-53}$, *New Error:*, $2.4218327470756168951 \times 10^{-71}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $2.4218327470756168951 \times 10^{-71}$, *New Error:*, $2.4218327470882934493 \times 10^{-89}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $2.4218327470882934493 \times 10^{-89}$, *New Error:*, $2.4218327470883061259 \times 10^{-107}$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI-3} + 9 u_{iI-2} - 45 u_{iI-1} + 45 u_{iI+1} - 9 u_{iI+2} + u_{iI+3}}{60 \Delta xI}, O(\Delta xI^6), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2109173116123323408 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $1.2109163735450911371 \times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2109163735450911371 \times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, $1.2109163735441530702 \times 10^{-54}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2109163735441530702 \times 10^{-54}$, *New Error:*, $1.2109163735441530693 \times 10^{-72}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2109163735441530693 \times 10^{-72}$, *New Error:*, $1.2109163735441530693 \times 10^{-90}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2109163735441530693 \times 10^{-90}$, *New Error:*, $1.2109163735441530693 \times 10^{-108}$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{-1089 u_{iI} + 2940 u_{iI+1} - 4410 u_{iI+2} + 4900 u_{iI+3} - 3675 u_{iI+4} + 1764 u_{iI+5} - 490 u_{iI+6} + 60 u_{iI+7}}{420 \Delta xI}, O(\Delta xI^7), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $4.2561004154078641742 \times 10^{-20}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297740777665092504 \times 10^{-41}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $4.2297740777665092504 \times 10^{-41}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478380468729122 \times 10^{-62}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $4.2297478380468729122 \times 10^{-62}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478118072396940 \times 10^{-83}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $4.2297478118072396940 \times 10^{-83}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117810000608 \times 10^{-104}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $4.2297478117810000608 \times 10^{-104}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117809738212 \times 10^{-125}$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{-60 u_{iI-7} + 490 u_{iI-6} - 1764 u_{iI-5} + 3675 u_{iI-4} - 4900 u_{iI-3} + 4410 u_{iI-2} - 2940 u_{iI-1} + 1089 u_{iI}}{420 \Delta xI}, O(\Delta xI^7), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $4.2035682177930739660 \times 10^{-20}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297215459684472552 \times 10^{-41}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $4.2297215459684472552 \times 10^{-41}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297477855150748506 \times 10^{-62}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $4.2297477855150748506 \times 10^{-62}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117547078959 \times 10^{-83}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $4.2297478117547078959 \times 10^{-83}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117809475290 \times 10^{-104}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $4.2297478117809475290 \times 10^{-104}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117809737687 \times 10^{-125}$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{-2283 u_{iI} + 6720 u_{iI+1} - 11760 u_{iI+2} + 15680 u_{iI+3} - 14700 u_{iI+4} + 9408 u_{iI+5} - 3920 u_{iI+6} + 960 u_{iI+7} - 105 u_{iI+8}}{840 \Delta xI}, O(\Delta xI^8),$$

Forward

Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $7.5586718284108827910 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $7.5045965052886595394 \times 10^{-47}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $7.5045965052886595394 \times 10^{-47}$, *New Error:*, $7.5045426341527990415 \times 10^{-71}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $7.5045426341527990415 \times 10^{-71}$, *New Error:*, $7.5045425802818668306 \times 10^{-95}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $7.5045425802818668306 \times 10^{-95}$, *New Error:*, $7.5045425802279958985 \times 10^{-119}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $7.5045425802279958985 \times 10^{-119}$, *New Error:*, $7.5045425802279420276 \times 10^{-143}$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(x) = \frac{105 u_{i-8} - 960 u_{i-7} + 3920 u_{i-6} - 9408 u_{i-5} + 14700 u_{i-4} - 15680 u_{i-3} + 11760 u_{i-2} - 6720 u_{i-1} + 2283 u_i}{840 \Delta x}, O(\Delta x^8),$$

Backward

Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $7.4508210404832398270 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $7.5044886555749306385 \times 10^{-47}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $7.5044886555749306385 \times 10^{-47}$, *New Error:*, $7.5045425263030853136 \times 10^{-71}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $7.5045425263030853136 \times 10^{-71}$, *New Error:*, $7.5045425801740171168 \times 10^{-95}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $7.5045425801740171168 \times 10^{-95}$, *New Error:*, $7.5045425802278880488 \times 10^{-119}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $7.5045425802278880488 \times 10^{-119}$, *New Error:*, $7.5045425802279419198 \times 10^{-143}$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(x) = \frac{3 u_{i-4} - 32 u_{i-3} + 168 u_{i-2} - 672 u_{i-1} + 672 u_{i+1} - 168 u_{i+2} + 32 u_{i+3} - 3 u_{i+4}}{840 \Delta x}, O(\Delta x^8), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $1.0720786763367004677 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $1.0720775114622994426 \times 10^{-48}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $1.0720775114622994426 \times 10^{-48}$, *New Error:*, $1.0720775114611345688 \times 10^{-72}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $1.0720775114611345688 \times 10^{-72}$, *New Error:*, $1.0720775114611345677 \times 10^{-96}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $1.0720775114611345677 \times 10^{-96}$, *New Error:*, $1.0720775114611345677 \times 10^{-120}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $1.0720775114611345677 \times 10^{-120}$, *New Error:*, $1.0720775114611345677 \times 10^{-144}$

"--- Derivative Order: 2 - x1=2 ---"

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} u(x) = \frac{u_i - 2 u_{i+1} + u_{i+2}}{\Delta x^2}, O(\Delta x), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.0053464917233143205207 , *New Error:*, $5.3402747410448345674 \times 10^{-6}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.3402747410448345674 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $5.3402685293798711413 \times 10^{-9}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.3402685293798711413 \times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, $5.3402685231682114915 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.3402685231682114915 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $5.3402685231619998318 \times 10^{-15}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.3402685231619998318 \times 10^{-15}$, *New Error:*, $5.3402685231619936202 \times 10^{-18}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-2} - 2u_{iI-1} + u_{iI}}{\Delta xI^2}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.0053340559609566285739, *New Error:*, $5.3402623052897906033 \times 10^{-6}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.3402623052897906033 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $5.3402685169441160973 \times 10^{-9}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.3402685169441160973 \times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, $5.3402685231557757364 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.3402685231557757364 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $5.3402685231619873961 \times 10^{-15}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.3402685231619873961 \times 10^{-15}$, *New Error:*, $5.3402685231619936077 \times 10^{-18}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{9u_{iI} - 24u_{iI+1} + 22u_{iI+2} - 8u_{iI+3} + u_{iI+4}}{4\Delta xI^2}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.1167888654354478923 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $7.1061563773517644937 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.1061563773517644937 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $7.1061457500417931799 \times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.1061457500417931799 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $7.1061457394144883938 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.1061457394144883938 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $7.1061457394038610890 \times 10^{-30}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.1061457394038610890 \times 10^{-30}$, *New Error:*, $7.1061457394038504617 \times 10^{-36}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-4} - 8u_{iI-3} + 22u_{iI-2} - 24u_{iI-1} + 9u_{iI}}{4\Delta xI^2}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.0955129941155426051 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $7.1061351014663171909 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.1061351014663171909 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $7.1061457287659077326 \times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.1061457287659077326 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $7.1061457393932125083 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.1061457393932125083 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $7.1061457394038398131 \times 10^{-30}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.1061457394038398131 \times 10^{-30}$, *New Error:*, $7.1061457394038504404 \times 10^{-36}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{u_{il-2} - 2u_{il} + u_{il+2}}{4 \Delta xI^2}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5530747571174499006 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $3.5530728697038126405 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5530728697038126405 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $3.5530728697019252274 \times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5530728697019252274 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $3.5530728697019252255 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5530728697019252255 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $3.5530728697019252255 \times 10^{-30}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.5530728697019252255 \times 10^{-30}$, *New Error:*, $3.5530728697019252255 \times 10^{-36}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{121 u_{il} - 396 u_{il+1} + 522 u_{il+2} - 368 u_{il+3} + 153 u_{il+4} - 36 u_{il+5} + 4 u_{il+6}}{36 \Delta xI^2}, O(\Delta xI^3), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.0663458191295214989 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637968203796109316 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.0637968203796109316 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942749138561126 \times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.0637942749138561126 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723683938861 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.0637942723683938861 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723658484239 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.0637942723658484239 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723658458785 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{4 u_{il-6} - 36 u_{il-5} + 153 u_{il-4} - 368 u_{il-3} + 522 u_{il-2} - 396 u_{il-1} + 121 u_{il}}{36 \Delta xI^2}, O(\Delta xI^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.0612497892971976478 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637917243591444990 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.0637917243591444990 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942698178356462 \times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.0637942698178356462 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723632978657 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.0637942723632978657 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723658433279 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.0637942723658433279 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723658458734 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{625 u_{il} - 2400 u_{il+1} + 4104 u_{il+2} - 4256 u_{il+3} + 2982 u_{il+4} - 1440 u_{il+5} + 472 u_{il+6} - 96 u_{il+7} + 9 u_{il+8}}{144 \Delta xI^2}, O(\Delta xI^4), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.7043349196290088240 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.6986791397612881403 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.6986791397612881403 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.6986734944586810126 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.6986734944586810126 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $1.6986734888133888687 \times 10^{-47}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.6986734888133888687 \times 10^{-47}$, New Error:, $1.6986734888077435765 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.6986734888077435765 \times 10^{-59}$, New Error:, $1.6986734888077379313 \times 10^{-71}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{9 u_{iI-8} - 96 u_{iI-7} + 472 u_{iI-6} - 1440 u_{iI-5} + 2982 u_{iI-4} - 4256 u_{iI-3} + 4104 u_{iI-2} - 2400 u_{iI-1} + 625 u_{iI}}{144 \Delta xI^2}, O(\Delta xI^4), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.6930330053339036085 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $1.6986678378751350334 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.6986678378751350334 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $1.6986734831567948595 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.6986734831567948595 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $1.6986734888020869825 \times 10^{-47}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.6986734888020869825 \times 10^{-47}$, New Error:, $1.6986734888077322747 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.6986734888077322747 \times 10^{-59}$, New Error:, $1.6986734888077379199 \times 10^{-71}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-4} - 16 u_{iI-3} + 64 u_{iI-2} + 16 u_{iI-1} - 130 u_{iI} + 16 u_{iI+1} + 64 u_{iI+2} - 16 u_{iI+3} + u_{iI+4}}{144 \Delta xI^2}, O(\Delta xI^4), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $2.8311238241228760892 \times 10^{-12}$, New Error:, $2.8311224813475726531 \times 10^{-24}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $2.8311224813475726531 \times 10^{-24}$, New Error:, $2.8311224813462298773 \times 10^{-36}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $2.8311224813462298773 \times 10^{-36}$, New Error:, $2.8311224813462298760 \times 10^{-48}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $2.8311224813462298760 \times 10^{-48}$, New Error:, $2.8311224813462298760 \times 10^{-60}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $2.8311224813462298760 \times 10^{-60}$, New Error:, $2.8311224813462298760 \times 10^{-72}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{3600 \Delta xI^2} (18769 u_{iI} - 82200 u_{iI+1} + 172200 u_{iI+2} - 234800 u_{iI+3} + 230550 u_{iI+4} - 168288 u_{iI+5} + 92200 u_{iI+6} - 37200 u_{iI+7} + 10425 u_{iI+8} - 1800 u_{iI+9} + 144 u_{iI+10}), O(\Delta xI^5), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 5, Error:, $2.8375847209240122584 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $2.8254836232915805221 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 5, Error:, $2.8254836232915805221 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $2.8254715503546842711 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 5, Error:, $2.8254715503546842711 \times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, $2.8254715382817754888 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 5, Error:, $2.8254715382817754888 \times 10^{-59}$, New Error:, $2.8254715382697025800 \times 10^{-74}$

Error order:, 5, Error:, $2.8254715382697025800 \times 10^{-74}$, New Error:, $2.8254715382696905071 \times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{3600 \Delta xI^2} (144 u_{iI-10} - 1800 u_{iI-9} + 10425 u_{iI-8} - 37200 u_{iI-7} + 92200 u_{iI-6} - 168288 u_{iI-5} + 230550 u_{iI-4} - 234800 u_{iI-3} + 172200 u_{iI-2} - 82200 u_{iI-1} + 18769 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^5), \text{ Backward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 2.8134146398084255668 \times 10^{-14}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.8254594533040845372 \times 10^{-29}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 2.8254594533040845372 \times 10^{-29}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.8254715261846967752 \times 10^{-44}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 2.8254715261846967752 \times 10^{-44}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.8254715382576055013 \times 10^{-59}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 2.8254715382576055013 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.8254715382696784100 \times 10^{-74}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 2.8254715382696784100 \times 10^{-74}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.8254715382696904829 \times 10^{-89}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{3600 \Delta xI^2} (21609 u_{iI} - 105840 u_{iI+1} + 261900 u_{iI+2} - 441600 u_{iI+3} + 556650 u_{iI+4} - 543168 u_{iI+5} + 417280 u_{iI+6} - 252000 u_{iI+7} + 117225 u_{iI+8} - 40400 u_{iI+9} + 9684 u_{iI+10} - 1440 u_{iI+11} + 100 u_{iI+12}), O(\Delta xI^6), \text{ Forward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 4.8593966227309760528 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.8340228270806150290 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 4.8340228270806150290 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.8339975245060870450 \times 10^{-53}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 4.8339975245060870450 \times 10^{-53}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.8339974992035835968 \times 10^{-71}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 4.8339974992035835968 \times 10^{-71}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.8339974991782810935 \times 10^{-89}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 4.8339974991782810935 \times 10^{-89}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.8339974991782557910 \times 10^{-107}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{3600 \Delta xI^2} (100 u_{iI-12} - 1440 u_{iI-11} + 9684 u_{iI-10} - 40400 u_{iI-9} + 117225 u_{iI-8} - 252000 u_{iI-7} + 417280 u_{iI-6} - 543168 u_{iI-5} + 556650 u_{iI-4} - 441600 u_{iI-3} + 261900 u_{iI-2} - 105840 u_{iI-1} + 21609 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^6), \text{ Backward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 4.808740677734412828 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.8339721714181982079 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 4.8339721714181982079 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.8339974738504246285 \times 10^{-53}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 4.8339974738504246285 \times 10^{-53}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.8339974991529279344 \times 10^{-71}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 4.8339974991529279344 \times 10^{-71}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.8339974991782304378 \times 10^{-89}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 4.8339974991782304378 \times 10^{-89}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.8339974991782557403 \times 10^{-107}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI)$$

$$= \frac{1}{3600 \Delta xI^2} (u_{iI-6} - 18 u_{iI-5} + 171 u_{iI-4} - 810 u_{iI-3} + 1935 u_{iI-2} + 828 u_{iI-1} - 4214 u_{iI} + 828 u_{iI+1} + 1935 u_{iI+2} - 810 u_{iI+3} + 171 u_{iI+4}$$

$$- 18 u_{iI+5} + u_{iI+6}), O(\Delta xI^6), \text{ Centered}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 2.4170006219807032756 \times 10^{-18}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.4169987495910002737 \times 10^{-36}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 2.4169987495910002737 \times 10^{-36}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.4169987495891278847 \times 10^{-54}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 2.4169987495891278847 \times 10^{-54}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.4169987495891278828 \times 10^{-72}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 2.4169987495891278828 \times 10^{-72}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.4169987495891278828 \times 10^{-90}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 2.4169987495891278828 \times 10^{-90}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.4169987495891278828 \times 10^{-108}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{176400 \Delta xI^2} (1185921 u_{iI} - 6403320 u_{iI+1} + 18248580 u_{iI+2} - 36603000 u_{iI+3} + 56264250 u_{iI+4} - 68668992 u_{iI+5} + 67863040 u_{iI+6}$$

$$- 54585360 u_{iI+7} + 35467425 u_{iI+8} - 18296600 u_{iI+9} + 7301196 u_{iI+10} - 2169720 u_{iI+11} + 451780 u_{iI+12} - 58800 u_{iI+13} + 3600 u_{iI+14}),$$

$$O(\Delta xI^7), \text{ Forward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 8.4952104099957368747 \times 10^{-20}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4426628298732719569 \times 10^{-41}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 8.4426628298732719569 \times 10^{-41}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4426104551833790663 \times 10^{-62}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 8.4426104551833790663 \times 10^{-62}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4426104028088616646 \times 10^{-83}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 8.4426104028088616646 \times 10^{-83}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4426104027564871473 \times 10^{-104}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 8.4426104027564871473 \times 10^{-104}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4426104027564347728 \times 10^{-125}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{176400 \Delta xI^2} (3600 u_{iI-14} - 58800 u_{iI-13} + 451780 u_{iI-12} - 2169720 u_{iI-11} + 7301196 u_{iI-10} - 18296600 u_{iI-9} + 35467425 u_{iI-8}$$

$$- 54585360 u_{iI-7} + 67863040 u_{iI-6} - 68668992 u_{iI-5} + 56264250 u_{iI-4} - 36603000 u_{iI-3} + 18248580 u_{iI-2} - 6403320 u_{iI-1} + 1185921 u_{iI}),$$

$$O(\Delta xI^7), \text{ Backward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 8.3903557241378721876 \times 10^{-20}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4425579759849246611 \times 10^{-41}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 8.4425579759849246611 \times 10^{-41}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4426103503294907198 \times 10^{-62}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 8.4426103503294907198 \times 10^{-62}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4426104027040077762 \times 10^{-83}$$

Error order:, 7, Error:, $8.4426104027040077762 \times 10^{-83}$, New Error:, $8.4426104027563822935 \times 10^{-104}$

Error order:, 7, Error:, $8.4426104027563822935 \times 10^{-104}$, New Error:, $8.4426104027564346680 \times 10^{-125}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{705600 \Delta xI^2} (5212089 u_{il} - 30683520 u_{il+1} + 98854560 u_{il+2} - 229649280 u_{il+3} + 416157000 u_{il+4} - 609318528 u_{il+5} \\ + 735948640 u_{il+6} - 739336320 u_{il+7} + 616705110 u_{il+8} - 423516800 u_{il+9} + 236333664 u_{il+10} - 105275520 u_{il+11} + 36516760 u_{il+12} \\ - 9502080 u_{il+13} + 1744800 u_{il+14} - 201600 u_{il+15} + 11025 u_{il+16}), O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $1.5087169318185394792 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, $1.4979234541494330418 \times 10^{-46}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $1.4979234541494330418 \times 10^{-46}$, New Error:, $1.4979127014277043995 \times 10^{-70}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $1.4979127014277043995 \times 10^{-70}$, New Error:, $1.4979126906750233195 \times 10^{-94}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $1.4979126906750233195 \times 10^{-94}$, New Error:, $1.4979126906642706384 \times 10^{-118}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $1.4979126906642706384 \times 10^{-118}$, New Error:, $1.4979126906642598858 \times 10^{-142}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{705600 \Delta xI^2} (11025 u_{il-16} - 201600 u_{il-15} + 1744800 u_{il-14} - 9502080 u_{il-13} + 36516760 u_{il-12} - 105275520 u_{il-11} \\ + 236333664 u_{il-10} - 423516800 u_{il-9} + 616705110 u_{il-8} - 739336320 u_{il-7} + 735948640 u_{il-6} - 609318528 u_{il-5} + 416157000 u_{il-4} \\ - 229649280 u_{il-3} + 98854560 u_{il-2} - 30683520 u_{il-1} + 5212089 u_{il}), O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $1.4871898284397684286 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, $1.4979019272604651973 \times 10^{-46}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $1.4979019272604651973 \times 10^{-46}$, New Error:, $1.4979126799008154319 \times 10^{-70}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $1.4979126799008154319 \times 10^{-70}$, New Error:, $1.4979126906534964305 \times 10^{-94}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $1.4979126906534964305 \times 10^{-94}$, New Error:, $1.4979126906642491115 \times 10^{-118}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $1.4979126906642491115 \times 10^{-118}$, New Error:, $1.4979126906642598642 \times 10^{-142}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{705600 \Delta xI^2} (9 u_{il-8} - 192 u_{il-7} + 2032 u_{il-6} - 14784 u_{il-5} + 71232 u_{il-4} - 221760 u_{il-3} + 407568 u_{il-2} + 236736 u_{il-1} - 961682 u_{il} \\ + 236736 u_{il+1} + 407568 u_{il+2} - 221760 u_{il+3} + 71232 u_{il+4} - 14784 u_{il+5} + 2032 u_{il+6} - 192 u_{il+7} + 9 u_{il+8}), O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $2.1398775974784440472 \times 10^{-24}$, New Error:, $2.1398752723798392068 \times 10^{-48}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $2.1398752723798392068 \times 10^{-48}$, New Error:, $2.1398752723775141095 \times 10^{-72}$

Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $2.1398752723775141095 \times 10^{-72}$, *New Error:*, $2.1398752723775141071 \times 10^{-96}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $2.1398752723775141071 \times 10^{-96}$, *New Error:*, $2.1398752723775141071 \times 10^{-120}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $2.1398752723775141071 \times 10^{-120}$, *New Error:*, $2.1398752723775141071 \times 10^{-144}$

"--- Derivative Order: 2 - x1=1, x2=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{u_{i_1, i_2} - u_{i_1, i_2+1} - u_{i_1+1, i_2} + u_{i_1+1, i_2+1}}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2}, O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.017824283638589925624, *New Error:*, 0.000017798245957186211900
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000017798245957186211900, *New Error:*, $1.7798219947533810779 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.7798219947533810779 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.7798219921524186383 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.7798219921524186383 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.7798219921498176758 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.7798219921498176758 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.7798219921498150749 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - u_{i_1-1, i_2} - u_{i_1, i_2-1} + u_{i_1, i_2}}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2}, O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.017772212270031426046, *New Error:*, 0.000017798193885866155135
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000017798193885866155135, *New Error:*, $1.7798219895462490722 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.7798219895462490722 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.7798219921472115062 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.7798219921472115062 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.7798219921498124687 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.7798219921498124687 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.7798219921498150696 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{9 u_{i_1, i_2} - 12 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 3 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 12 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 16 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 3 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 4 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+2}}{4 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2}, O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2),$$

Forward

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000030826583245597757699, *New Error:*, $3.0764654236965852085 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.0764654236965852085 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.0764592359479452349 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.0764592359479452349 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.0764592297602017497 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.0764592297602017497 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $3.0764592297540140062 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.0764592297540140062 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $3.0764592297540078185 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 4u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 3u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 4u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 16u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 12u_{i_1-1, i_2} + 3u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 12u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 9u_{i_1, i_2}}{4 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2}, O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2),$$

Backward

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000030702704547468336698, New Error: 3.0764530358217502456 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order: 2, Error: 3.0764530358217502456 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 3.0764592235600704000 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order: 2, Error: 3.0764592235600704000 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 3.0764592297478138749 × 10⁻²³
Error order: 2, Error: 3.0764592297478138749 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 3.0764592297540016184 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order: 2, Error: 3.0764592297540016184 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 3.0764592297540078061 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - u_{i_1-1, i_2+1} - u_{i_1+1, i_2-1} + u_{i_1+1, i_2+1}}{4 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2}, O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000015382308920399483462, New Error: 1.5382296148782810685 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order: 2, Error: 1.5382296148782810685 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 1.5382296148770039074 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order: 2, Error: 1.5382296148770039074 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 1.5382296148770039061 × 10⁻²³
Error order: 2, Error: 1.5382296148770039061 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 1.5382296148770039061 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order: 2, Error: 1.5382296148770039061 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 1.5382296148770039061 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{36 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (121u_{i_1, i_2} - 198u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 99u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 22u_{i_1, i_2+3} - 198u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 324u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 162u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 36u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} + 99u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 162u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 81u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 18u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} - 22u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 36u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 18u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + 4u_{i_1+3, i_2+3}), O(\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order: 3, Error: 6.2145149243404709379 × 10⁻⁸, New Error: 6.1939579546527525134 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order: 3, Error: 6.1939579546527525134 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 6.1939374380210740565 × 10⁻²⁶
Error order: 3, Error: 6.1939374380210740565 × 10⁻²⁶, New Error: 6.1939374175044826469 × 10⁻³⁵
Error order: 3, Error: 6.1939374175044826469 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error: 6.1939374174839660555 × 10⁻⁴⁴
Error order: 3, Error: 6.1939374174839660555 × 10⁻⁴⁴, New Error: 6.1939374174839455389 × 10⁻⁵³

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{36 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (4u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 18u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 36u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 22u_{i_1-3, i_2} - 18u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 81u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 162u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 99u_{i_1-2, i_2}$$

$$+ 36 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 162 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 324 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 198 u_{i_l-1, i_2} - 22 u_{i_l, i_2-3} + 99 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 198 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 121 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x l^3 \Delta x 2^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $6.1734405291701220670 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $6.1939168803957568074 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $6.1939168803957568074 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $6.1939373969468170609 \times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $6.1939373969468170609 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $6.1939374174634083899 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $6.1939374174634083899 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $6.1939374174839249813 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $6.1939374174839249813 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $6.1939374174839454978 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{144 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (625 u_{i_l, i_2} - 1200 u_{i_l, i_2+1} + 900 u_{i_l, i_2+2} - 400 u_{i_l, i_2+3} + 75 u_{i_l, i_2+4} - 1200 u_{i_l+1, i_2} + 2304 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - 1728 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2}$$

$$+ 768 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} - 144 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} + 900 u_{i_l+2, i_2} - 1728 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 1296 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 576 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} + 108 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} - 400 u_{i_l+3, i_2} + 768 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1}$$

$$- 576 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 256 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} - 48 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} + 75 u_{i_l+4, i_2} - 144 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} + 108 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} - 48 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} + 9 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4}), O(\Delta x l^4 \Delta x 2^4),$$

Forward

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.3756086125065275928 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $1.3691483493322014671 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.3691483493322014671 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $1.3691419063017223141 \times 10^{-34}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.3691419063017223141 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.3691418998587090339 \times 10^{-46}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.3691418998587090339 \times 10^{-46}$, *New Error:*, $1.3691418998522660207 \times 10^{-58}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.3691418998522660207 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $1.3691418998522595777 \times 10^{-70}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{144 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (9 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} - 48 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 108 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 144 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 75 u_{i_l-4, i_2} - 48 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 256 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3}$$

$$- 576 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 768 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 400 u_{i_l-3, i_2} + 108 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} - 576 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 1296 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 1728 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 900 u_{i_l-2, i_2} - 144 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4}$$

$$+ 768 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 1728 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 2304 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 1200 u_{i_l-1, i_2} + 75 u_{i_l, i_2-4} - 400 u_{i_l, i_2-3} + 900 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 1200 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 625 u_{i_l, i_2}),$$

$O(\Delta x l^4 \Delta x 2^4), \text{ Backward}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.3627096196075685886 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $1.3691354504067499853 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.3691354504067499853 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $1.3691418934027968627 \times 10^{-34}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.3691418934027968627 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.3691418998458101085 \times 10^{-46}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.3691418998458101085 \times 10^{-46}$, *New Error:*, $1.3691418998522531218 \times 10^{-58}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.3691418998522531218 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $1.3691418998522595648 \times 10^{-70}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{144 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (u_{i-2, i2-2} - 8 u_{i-2, i2-1} + 8 u_{i-2, i2+1} - u_{i-2, i2+2} - 8 u_{i-1, i2-2} + 64 u_{i-1, i2-1} - 64 u_{i-1, i2+1} + 8 u_{i-1, i2+2} \\ + 8 u_{i+1, i2-2} - 64 u_{i+1, i2-1} + 64 u_{i+1, i2+1} - 8 u_{i+1, i2+2} - u_{i+2, i2-2} + 8 u_{i+2, i2-1} - 8 u_{i+2, i2+1} + u_{i+2, i2+2}), O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.2819053736198783309 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.2819031664226398180 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.2819031664226398180 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.2819031664204326209 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.2819031664204326209 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $2.2819031664204326187 \times 10^{-47}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.2819031664204326187 \times 10^{-47}$, *New Error:*, $2.2819031664204326187 \times 10^{-59}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.2819031664204326187 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $2.2819031664204326187 \times 10^{-71}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{3600 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (18769 u_{i, i2} - 41100 u_{i, i2+1} + 41100 u_{i, i2+2} - 27400 u_{i, i2+3} + 10275 u_{i, i2+4} - 1644 u_{i, i2+5} - 41100 u_{i+1, i2} \\ + 90000 u_{i+1, i2+1} - 90000 u_{i+1, i2+2} + 60000 u_{i+1, i2+3} - 22500 u_{i+1, i2+4} + 3600 u_{i+1, i2+5} + 41100 u_{i+2, i2} - 90000 u_{i+2, i2+1} + 90000 u_{i+2, i2+2} \\ - 60000 u_{i+2, i2+3} + 22500 u_{i+2, i2+4} - 3600 u_{i+2, i2+5} - 27400 u_{i+3, i2} + 60000 u_{i+3, i2+1} - 60000 u_{i+3, i2+2} + 40000 u_{i+3, i2+3} - 15000 u_{i+3, i2+4} \\ + 2400 u_{i+3, i2+5} + 10275 u_{i+4, i2} - 22500 u_{i+4, i2+1} + 22500 u_{i+4, i2+2} - 15000 u_{i+4, i2+3} + 5625 u_{i+4, i2+4} - 900 u_{i+4, i2+5} - 1644 u_{i+5, i2} \\ + 3600 u_{i+5, i2+1} - 3600 u_{i+5, i2+2} + 2400 u_{i+5, i2+3} - 900 u_{i+5, i2+4} + 144 u_{i+5, i2+5}), O(\Delta x_1^5 \Delta x_2^5), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.2446637698180276743 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $3.2247512277152075053 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.2247512277152075053 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $3.2247313827183751555 \times 10^{-43}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.2247313827183751555 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $3.2247313628734457032 \times 10^{-58}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.2247313628734457032 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $3.2247313628536007738 \times 10^{-73}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.2247313628536007738 \times 10^{-73}$, *New Error:*, $3.2247313628535809289 \times 10^{-88}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{3600 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (144 u_{i-5, i2-5} - 900 u_{i-5, i2-4} + 2400 u_{i-5, i2-3} - 3600 u_{i-5, i2-2} + 3600 u_{i-5, i2-1} - 1644 u_{i-5, i2} - 900 u_{i-4, i2-5} \\ + 5625 u_{i-4, i2-4} - 15000 u_{i-4, i2-3} + 22500 u_{i-4, i2-2} - 22500 u_{i-4, i2-1} + 10275 u_{i-4, i2} + 2400 u_{i-3, i2-5} - 15000 u_{i-3, i2-4} + 40000 u_{i-3, i2-3} \\ - 60000 u_{i-3, i2-2} + 60000 u_{i-3, i2-1} - 27400 u_{i-3, i2} - 3600 u_{i-2, i2-5} + 22500 u_{i-2, i2-4} - 60000 u_{i-2, i2-3} + 90000 u_{i-2, i2-2} - 90000 u_{i-2, i2-1} \\ + 41100 u_{i-2, i2} + 3600 u_{i-1, i2-5} - 22500 u_{i-1, i2-4} + 60000 u_{i-1, i2-3} - 90000 u_{i-1, i2-2} + 90000 u_{i-1, i2-1} - 41100 u_{i-1, i2} - 1644 u_{i, i2-5} \\ + 10275 u_{i, i2-4} - 27400 u_{i, i2-3} + 41100 u_{i, i2-2} - 41100 u_{i, i2-1} + 18769 u_{i, i2}), O(\Delta x_1^5 \Delta x_2^5), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.2049338514557986020 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $3.2247114981268492343 \times 10^{-28}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.2247114981268492343 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $3.2247313429887867975 \times 10^{-43}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.2247313429887867975 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $3.2247313628337161149 \times 10^{-58}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.2247313628337161149 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $3.2247313628535610443 \times 10^{-73}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.2247313628535610443 \times 10^{-73}$, *New Error:*, $3.2247313628535808892 \times 10^{-88}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{3600 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (21609 u_{i_1, i_2} - 52920 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 66150 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 58800 u_{i_1, i_2+3} + 33075 u_{i_1, i_2+4} - 10584 u_{i_1, i_2+5} + 1470 u_{i_1, i_2+6} \\ - 52920 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 129600 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 162000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 144000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} - 81000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} + 25920 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} - 3600 u_{i_1+1, i_2+6} \\ + 66150 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 162000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 202500 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 180000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} + 101250 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} - 32400 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} + 4500 u_{i_1+2, i_2+6} \\ - 58800 u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 144000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 180000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + 160000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} - 90000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} + 28800 u_{i_1+3, i_2+5} - 4000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+6} \\ + 33075 u_{i_1+4, i_2} - 81000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} + 101250 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} - 90000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} + 50625 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} - 16200 u_{i_1+4, i_2+5} + 2250 u_{i_1+4, i_2+6} - 10584 u_{i_1+5, i_2} \\ + 25920 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} - 32400 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} + 28800 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} - 16200 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} + 5184 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} - 720 u_{i_1+5, i_2+6} + 1470 u_{i_1+6, i_2} - 3600 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} \\ + 4500 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} - 4000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} + 2250 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} - 720 u_{i_1+6, i_2+5} + 100 u_{i_1+6, i_2+6}), O(\Delta x_1^6 \Delta x_2^6), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $8.0068719272053040403 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $7.9459783745536477026 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.9459783745536477026 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $7.9459177322909012994 \times 10^{-52}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.9459177322909012994 \times 10^{-52}$, *New Error:*, $7.9459176716488891051 \times 10^{-70}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.9459176716488891051 \times 10^{-70}$, *New Error:*, $7.9459176715882470932 \times 10^{-88}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.9459176715882470932 \times 10^{-88}$, *New Error:*, $7.9459176715881864512 \times 10^{-106}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{3600 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (100 u_{i_1-6, i_2-6} - 720 u_{i_1-6, i_2-5} + 2250 u_{i_1-6, i_2-4} - 4000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-3} + 4500 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 3600 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} \\ + 1470 u_{i_1-6, i_2} - 720 u_{i_1-5, i_2-6} + 5184 u_{i_1-5, i_2-5} - 16200 u_{i_1-5, i_2-4} + 28800 u_{i_1-5, i_2-3} - 32400 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 25920 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 10584 u_{i_1-5, i_2} \\ + 2250 u_{i_1-4, i_2-6} - 16200 u_{i_1-4, i_2-5} + 50625 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4} - 90000 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3} + 101250 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 81000 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 33075 u_{i_1-4, i_2} - 4000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-6} \\ + 28800 u_{i_1-3, i_2-5} - 90000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4} + 160000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 180000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 144000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 58800 u_{i_1-3, i_2} + 4500 u_{i_1-2, i_2-6} \\ - 32400 u_{i_1-2, i_2-5} + 101250 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4} - 180000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 202500 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 162000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 66150 u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 3600 u_{i_1-1, i_2-6} \\ + 25920 u_{i_1-1, i_2-5} - 81000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4} + 144000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} - 162000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 129600 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 52920 u_{i_1-1, i_2} + 1470 u_{i_1, i_2-6} - 10584 u_{i_1, i_2-5} \\ + 33075 u_{i_1, i_2-4} - 58800 u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 66150 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 52920 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 21609 u_{i_1, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1^6 \Delta x_2^6), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.8854650242531992797 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $7.9458569691243299331 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.9458569691243299331 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $7.9459176108854719831 \times 10^{-52}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.9459176108854719831 \times 10^{-52}$, *New Error:*, $7.9459176715274836758 \times 10^{-70}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.9459176715274836758 \times 10^{-70}$, *New Error:*, $7.9459176715881256877 \times 10^{-88}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.9459176715881256877 \times 10^{-88}$, *New Error:*, $7.9459176715881863297 \times 10^{-106}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{3600 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 9 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 45 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 45 u_{i_1-3, i_2+1} + 9 u_{i_1-3, i_2+2} - u_{i_1-3, i_2+3} - 9 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 81 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 405 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 405 u_{i_1-2, i_2+1} - 81 u_{i_1-2, i_2+2} + 9 u_{i_1-2, i_2+3} + 45 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} - 405 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 2025 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 2025 u_{i_1-1, i_2+1} + 405 u_{i_1-1, i_2+2} - 45 u_{i_1-1, i_2+3} - 45 u_{i_1+1, i_2-3} + 405 u_{i_1+1, i_2-2} - 2025 u_{i_1+1, i_2-1} + 2025 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 405 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 45 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} + 9 u_{i_1+2, i_2-3} - 81 u_{i_1+2, i_2-2} + 405 u_{i_1+2, i_2-1} - 405 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 81 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 9 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} - u_{i_1+3, i_2-3} + 9 u_{i_1+3, i_2-2} - 45 u_{i_1+3, i_2-1} + 45 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 9 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + u_{i_1+3, i_2+3}), O(\Delta x_1^6 \Delta x_2^6), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $3.9729654358634890549 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.9729588358006932591 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $3.9729588358006932591 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $3.9729588357940932018 \times 10^{-53}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $3.9729588357940932018 \times 10^{-53}$, *New Error:*, $3.9729588357940931952 \times 10^{-71}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $3.9729588357940931952 \times 10^{-71}$, *New Error:*, $3.9729588357940931952 \times 10^{-89}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $3.9729588357940931952 \times 10^{-89}$, *New Error:*, $3.9729588357940931952 \times 10^{-107}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{176400 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (1185921 u_{i_1, i_2} - 3201660 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 4802490 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 5336100 u_{i_1, i_2+3} + 4002075 u_{i_1, i_2+4} - 1920996 u_{i_1, i_2+5} + 533610 u_{i_1, i_2+6} - 65340 u_{i_1, i_2+7} - 3201660 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 8643600 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 12965400 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 14406000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} - 10804500 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} + 5186160 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} - 1440600 u_{i_1+1, i_2+6} + 176400 u_{i_1+1, i_2+7} + 4802490 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 12965400 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 19448100 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 21609000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} + 16206750 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} - 7779240 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} + 2160900 u_{i_1+2, i_2+6} - 264600 u_{i_1+2, i_2+7} - 5336100 u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 14406000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 21609000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + 24010000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} - 18007500 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} + 8643600 u_{i_1+3, i_2+5} - 2401000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+6} + 294000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+7} + 4002075 u_{i_1+4, i_2} - 10804500 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} + 16206750 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} - 18007500 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} + 13505625 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} - 6482700 u_{i_1+4, i_2+5} + 1800750 u_{i_1+4, i_2+6} - 220500 u_{i_1+4, i_2+7} - 1920996 u_{i_1+5, i_2} + 5186160 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} - 7779240 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} + 8643600 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} - 6482700 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} + 3111696 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} - 864360 u_{i_1+5, i_2+6} + 105840 u_{i_1+5, i_2+7} + 533610 u_{i_1+6, i_2} - 1440600 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} + 2160900 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} - 2401000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} + 1800750 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} - 864360 u_{i_1+6, i_2+5} + 240100 u_{i_1+6, i_2+6} - 29400 u_{i_1+6, i_2+7} - 65340 u_{i_1+7, i_2} + 176400 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} - 264600 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} + 294000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+3} - 220500 u_{i_1+7, i_2+4} + 105840 u_{i_1+7, i_2+5} - 29400 u_{i_1+7, i_2+6} + 3600 u_{i_1+7, i_2+7}), O(\Delta x_1^7 \Delta x_2^7), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $2.0419943657467449181 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $2.0234423022071785236 \times 10^{-39}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $2.0234423022071785236 \times 10^{-39}$, *New Error:*, $2.0234238404184437274 \times 10^{-60}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $2.0234238404184437274 \times 10^{-60}$, *New Error:*, $2.0234238219567449578 \times 10^{-81}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $2.0234238219567449578 \times 10^{-81}$, *New Error:*, $2.0234238219382832592 \times 10^{-102}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $2.0234238219382832592 \times 10^{-102}$, *New Error:*, $2.0234238219382647975 \times 10^{-123}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{176400 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (3600 u_{i_1-7, i_2-7} - 29400 u_{i_1-7, i_2-6} + 105840 u_{i_1-7, i_2-5} - 220500 u_{i_1-7, i_2-4} + 294000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-3} \\
& - 264600 u_{i_1-7, i_2-2} + 176400 u_{i_1-7, i_2-1} - 65340 u_{i_1-7, i_2} - 29400 u_{i_1-6, i_2-7} + 240100 u_{i_1-6, i_2-6} - 864360 u_{i_1-6, i_2-5} + 1800750 u_{i_1-6, i_2-4} \\
& - 2401000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-3} + 2160900 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 1440600 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 533610 u_{i_1-6, i_2} + 105840 u_{i_1-5, i_2-7} - 864360 u_{i_1-5, i_2-6} + 3111696 u_{i_1-5, i_2-5} \\
& - 6482700 u_{i_1-5, i_2-4} + 8643600 u_{i_1-5, i_2-3} - 7779240 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 5186160 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 1920996 u_{i_1-5, i_2} - 220500 u_{i_1-4, i_2-7} + 1800750 u_{i_1-4, i_2-6} \\
& - 6482700 u_{i_1-4, i_2-5} + 13505625 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4} - 18007500 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3} + 16206750 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 10804500 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 4002075 u_{i_1-4, i_2} \\
& + 294000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-7} - 2401000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-6} + 8643600 u_{i_1-3, i_2-5} - 18007500 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4} + 24010000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 21609000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} \\
& + 14406000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 5336100 u_{i_1-3, i_2} - 264600 u_{i_1-2, i_2-7} + 2160900 u_{i_1-2, i_2-6} - 7779240 u_{i_1-2, i_2-5} + 16206750 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4} \\
& - 21609000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 19448100 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 12965400 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 4802490 u_{i_1-2, i_2} + 176400 u_{i_1-1, i_2-7} - 1440600 u_{i_1-1, i_2-6} \\
& + 5186160 u_{i_1-1, i_2-5} - 10804500 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4} + 14406000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} - 12965400 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 8643600 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 3201660 u_{i_1-1, i_2} - 65340 u_{i_1, i_2-7} \\
& + 533610 u_{i_1, i_2-6} - 1920996 u_{i_1, i_2-5} + 4002075 u_{i_1, i_2-4} - 5336100 u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 4802490 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 3201660 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 1185921 u_{i_1, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1^7 \Delta x_2^7),
\end{aligned}$$

Backward

Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $2.0050333900234800856 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $2.0234053418494612614 \times 10^{-39}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $2.0234053418494612614 \times 10^{-39}$, *New Error:*, $2.0234238034580860107 \times 10^{-60}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $2.0234238034580860107 \times 10^{-60}$, *New Error:*, $2.0234238219197846001 \times 10^{-81}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $2.0234238219197846001 \times 10^{-81}$, *New Error:*, $2.0234238219382462988 \times 10^{-102}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $2.0234238219382462988 \times 10^{-102}$, *New Error:*, $2.0234238219382647605 \times 10^{-123}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{705600 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (5212089 u_{i_1, i_2} - 15341760 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 26848080 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 35797440 u_{i_1, i_2+3} + 33560100 u_{i_1, i_2+4} - 21478464 u_{i_1, i_2+5} \\
& + 8949360 u_{i_1, i_2+6} - 2191680 u_{i_1, i_2+7} + 239715 u_{i_1, i_2+8} - 15341760 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 45158400 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 79027200 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 105369600 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} \\
& - 98784000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} + 63221760 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} - 26342400 u_{i_1+1, i_2+6} + 6451200 u_{i_1+1, i_2+7} - 705600 u_{i_1+1, i_2+8} + 26848080 u_{i_1+2, i_2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 79027200 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 138297600 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 184396800 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} + 172872000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} - 110638080 u_{i_l+2, i_2+5} + 46099200 u_{i_l+2, i_2+6} \\
& - 11289600 u_{i_l+2, i_2+7} + 1234800 u_{i_l+2, i_2+8} - 35797440 u_{i_l+3, i_2} + 105369600 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - 184396800 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 245862400 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} \\
& - 230496000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} + 147517440 u_{i_l+3, i_2+5} - 61465600 u_{i_l+3, i_2+6} + 15052800 u_{i_l+3, i_2+7} - 1646400 u_{i_l+3, i_2+8} + 33560100 u_{i_l+4, i_2} \\
& - 98784000 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} + 172872000 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} - 230496000 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} + 216090000 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4} - 138297600 u_{i_l+4, i_2+5} + 57624000 u_{i_l+4, i_2+6} \\
& - 14112000 u_{i_l+4, i_2+7} + 1543500 u_{i_l+4, i_2+8} - 21478464 u_{i_l+5, i_2} + 63221760 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} - 110638080 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} + 147517440 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} \\
& - 138297600 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4} + 88510464 u_{i_l+5, i_2+5} - 36879360 u_{i_l+5, i_2+6} + 9031680 u_{i_l+5, i_2+7} - 987840 u_{i_l+5, i_2+8} + 8949360 u_{i_l+6, i_2} \\
& - 26342400 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} + 46099200 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} - 61465600 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} + 57624000 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4} - 36879360 u_{i_l+6, i_2+5} + 15366400 u_{i_l+6, i_2+6} \\
& - 3763200 u_{i_l+6, i_2+7} + 411600 u_{i_l+6, i_2+8} - 2191680 u_{i_l+7, i_2} + 6451200 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} - 11289600 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} + 15052800 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} \\
& - 14112000 u_{i_l+7, i_2+4} + 9031680 u_{i_l+7, i_2+5} - 3763200 u_{i_l+7, i_2+6} + 921600 u_{i_l+7, i_2+7} - 100800 u_{i_l+7, i_2+8} + 239715 u_{i_l+8, i_2} - 705600 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} \\
& + 1234800 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} - 1646400 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} + 1543500 u_{i_l+8, i_2+4} - 987840 u_{i_l+8, i_2+5} + 411600 u_{i_l+8, i_2+6} - 100800 u_{i_l+8, i_2+7} + 11025 u_{i_l+8, i_2+8} \Big),
\end{aligned}$$

$O(\Delta x_1^8 \Delta x_2^8)$, Forward

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order: } 8, \text{ Error: } 5.3365059041056259265 \times 10^{-21}, \text{ New Error: } 5.2801072409456361425 \times 10^{-45} \\
& \text{Error order: } 8, \text{ Error: } 5.2801072409456361425 \times 10^{-45}, \text{ New Error: } 5.2800511585160033995 \times 10^{-69} \\
& \text{Error order: } 8, \text{ Error: } 5.2800511585160033995 \times 10^{-69}, \text{ New Error: } 5.2800511024338887600 \times 10^{-93} \\
& \text{Error order: } 8, \text{ Error: } 5.2800511024338887600 \times 10^{-93}, \text{ New Error: } 5.2800511023778066456 \times 10^{-117} \\
& \text{Error order: } 8, \text{ Error: } 5.2800511023778066456 \times 10^{-117}, \text{ New Error: } 5.2800511023777505635 \times 10^{-141}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{705600 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (11025 u_{i_l-8, i_2-8} - 100800 u_{i_l-8, i_2-7} + 411600 u_{i_l-8, i_2-6} - 987840 u_{i_l-8, i_2-5} + 1543500 u_{i_l-8, i_2-4} \\
& - 1646400 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 1234800 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 705600 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 239715 u_{i_l-8, i_2} - 100800 u_{i_l-7, i_2-8} + 921600 u_{i_l-7, i_2-7} - 3763200 u_{i_l-7, i_2-6} \\
& + 9031680 u_{i_l-7, i_2-5} - 14112000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-4} + 15052800 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 11289600 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 6451200 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 2191680 u_{i_l-7, i_2} \\
& + 411600 u_{i_l-6, i_2-8} - 3763200 u_{i_l-6, i_2-7} + 15366400 u_{i_l-6, i_2-6} - 36879360 u_{i_l-6, i_2-5} + 57624000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4} - 61465600 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} \\
& + 46099200 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 26342400 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 8949360 u_{i_l-6, i_2} - 987840 u_{i_l-5, i_2-8} + 9031680 u_{i_l-5, i_2-7} - 36879360 u_{i_l-5, i_2-6} \\
& + 88510464 u_{i_l-5, i_2-5} - 138297600 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4} + 147517440 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 110638080 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 63221760 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 21478464 u_{i_l-5, i_2} \\
& + 1543500 u_{i_l-4, i_2-8} - 14112000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-7} + 57624000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-6} - 138297600 u_{i_l-4, i_2-5} + 216090000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} - 230496000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} \\
& + 172872000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 98784000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 33560100 u_{i_l-4, i_2} - 1646400 u_{i_l-3, i_2-8} + 15052800 u_{i_l-3, i_2-7} - 61465600 u_{i_l-3, i_2-6} \\
& + 147517440 u_{i_l-3, i_2-5} - 230496000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 245862400 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 184396800 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 105369600 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 35797440 u_{i_l-3, i_2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 1234800 u_{i_l-2, i_2-8} - 11289600 u_{i_l-2, i_2-7} + 46099200 u_{i_l-2, i_2-6} - 110638080 u_{i_l-2, i_2-5} + 172872000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} - 184396800 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} \\
& + 138297600 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 79027200 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 26848080 u_{i_l-2, i_2} - 705600 u_{i_l-1, i_2-8} + 6451200 u_{i_l-1, i_2-7} - 26342400 u_{i_l-1, i_2-6} \\
& + 63221760 u_{i_l-1, i_2-5} - 98784000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} + 105369600 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 79027200 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 45158400 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 15341760 u_{i_l-1, i_2} \\
& + 239715 u_{i_l, i_2-8} - 2191680 u_{i_l, i_2-7} + 8949360 u_{i_l, i_2-6} - 21478464 u_{i_l, i_2-5} + 33560100 u_{i_l, i_2-4} - 35797440 u_{i_l, i_2-3} + 26848080 u_{i_l, i_2-2} \\
& - 15341760 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 5212089 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1^8 \Delta x_2^8), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 8, \text{ Error:}, 5.2242269234235294969 \times 10^{-21}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.2799949644404800509 \times 10^{-45}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 8, \text{ Error:}, 5.2799949644404800509 \times 10^{-45}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.2800510462394982459 \times 10^{-69}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 8, \text{ Error:}, 5.2800510462394982459 \times 10^{-69}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.2800511023216122548 \times 10^{-93}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 8, \text{ Error:}, 5.2800511023216122548 \times 10^{-93}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.2800511023776943691 \times 10^{-117}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 8, \text{ Error:}, 5.2800511023776943691 \times 10^{-117}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.2800511023777504513 \times 10^{-141}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{705600 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2} (9 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} - 96 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 504 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 2016 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 2016 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1} - 504 u_{i_l-4, i_2+2} + 96 u_{i_l-4, i_2+3} \\
& - 9 u_{i_l-4, i_2+4} - 96 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 1024 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 5376 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 21504 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 21504 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1} + 5376 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2} - 1024 u_{i_l-3, i_2+3} \\
& + 96 u_{i_l-3, i_2+4} + 504 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} - 5376 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 28224 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 112896 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 112896 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1} - 28224 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2} + 5376 u_{i_l-2, i_2+3} \\
& - 504 u_{i_l-2, i_2+4} - 2016 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} + 21504 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 112896 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 451584 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 451584 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1} + 112896 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2} \\
& - 21504 u_{i_l-1, i_2+3} + 2016 u_{i_l-1, i_2+4} + 2016 u_{i_l+1, i_2-4} - 21504 u_{i_l+1, i_2-3} + 112896 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2} - 451584 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1} + 451584 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} \\
& - 112896 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} + 21504 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} - 2016 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} - 504 u_{i_l+2, i_2-4} + 5376 u_{i_l+2, i_2-3} - 28224 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2} + 112896 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1} \\
& - 112896 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 28224 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 5376 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} + 504 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} + 96 u_{i_l+3, i_2-4} - 1024 u_{i_l+3, i_2-3} + 5376 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2} - 21504 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} \\
& + 21504 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - 5376 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 1024 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} - 96 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} - 9 u_{i_l+4, i_2-4} + 96 u_{i_l+4, i_2-3} - 504 u_{i_l+4, i_2-2} + 2016 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1} \\
& - 2016 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} + 504 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} - 96 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} + 9 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4}), O(\Delta x_1^8 \Delta x_2^8), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 8, \text{ Error:}, 7.5429481638518523011 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.5429301462719468728 \times 10^{-47}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 8, \text{ Error:}, 7.5429301462719468728 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.5429301462539293143 \times 10^{-71}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 8, \text{ Error:}, 7.5429301462539293143 \times 10^{-71}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.5429301462539292963 \times 10^{-95}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 8, \text{ Error:}, 7.5429301462539292963 \times 10^{-95}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.5429301462539292963 \times 10^{-119}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 8, \text{ Error:}, 7.5429301462539292963 \times 10^{-119}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.5429301462539292963 \times 10^{-143}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 3 - x1=3 ---"

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI} + 3 u_{iI+1} - 3 u_{iI+2} + u_{iI+3}}{\Delta xI^3}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.0080077273254969408972, New Error:, $7.9944272542736614097 \times 10^{-6}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $7.9944272542736614097 \times 10^{-6}$, New Error:, $7.9944139701267601779 \times 10^{-9}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $7.9944139701267601779 \times 10^{-9}$, New Error:, $7.9944139568426291858 \times 10^{-12}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $7.9944139568426291858 \times 10^{-12}$, New Error:, $7.9944139568293450549 \times 10^{-15}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $7.9944139568293450549 \times 10^{-15}$, New Error:, $7.9944139568293317707 \times 10^{-18}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI-3} + 3 u_{iI-2} - 3 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI}}{\Delta xI^3}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.0079811324383139588231, New Error:, $7.9944006594168522331 \times 10^{-6}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $7.9944006594168522331 \times 10^{-6}$, New Error:, $7.9944139435319033688 \times 10^{-9}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $7.9944139435319033688 \times 10^{-9}$, New Error:, $7.9944139568160343290 \times 10^{-12}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $7.9944139568160343290 \times 10^{-12}$, New Error:, $7.9944139568293184600 \times 10^{-15}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $7.9944139568293184600 \times 10^{-15}$, New Error:, $7.9944139568293317441 \times 10^{-18}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{-27 u_{iI} + 108 u_{iI+1} - 171 u_{iI+2} + 136 u_{iI+3} - 57 u_{iI+4} + 12 u_{iI+5} - u_{iI+6}}{8 \Delta xI^3}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000010653868462202178043, New Error:, $1.0637958648723122668 \times 10^{-11}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.0637958648723122668 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $1.0637942739583522717 \times 10^{-17}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.0637942739583522717 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $1.0637942723674383823 \times 10^{-23}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.0637942723674383823 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $1.0637942723658474684 \times 10^{-29}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.0637942723658474684 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $1.0637942723658458775 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-6} - 12 u_{iI-5} + 57 u_{iI-4} - 136 u_{iI-3} + 171 u_{iI-2} - 108 u_{iI-1} + 27 u_{iI}}{8 \Delta xI^3}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000010622018397733361774, New Error:, $1.0637926798595207586 \times 10^{-11}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.0637926798595207586 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $1.0637942707733394802 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.0637942707733394802 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723642533695 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.0637942723642533695 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723658442834 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.0637942723658442834 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723658458743 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI-3} + 3u_{iI-1} - 3u_{iI+1} + u_{iI+3}}{8 \Delta xI^3}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.3189759532227684007 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $5.3189713618338207708 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.3189713618338207708 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $5.3189713618292293841 \times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.3189713618292293841 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $5.3189713618292293795 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.3189713618292293795 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $5.3189713618292293795 \times 10^{-30}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.3189713618292293795 \times 10^{-30}$, *New Error:*, $5.3189713618292293795 \times 10^{-36}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{-1331 u_{iI} + 6534 u_{iI+1} - 13959 u_{iI+2} + 17250 u_{iI+3} - 13797 u_{iI+4} + 7506 u_{iI+5} - 2805 u_{iI+6} + 702 u_{iI+7} - 108 u_{iI+8} + 8 u_{iI+9}}{216 \Delta xI^3},$$

$O(\Delta xI^3)$, *Forward*

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5963260781317921131 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925102101491181627 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5925102101491181627 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925063995716408872 \times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5925063995716408872 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925063957610686918 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5925063957610686918 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925063957572581196 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5925063957572581196 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925063957572543091 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{-8 u_{iI-9} + 108 u_{iI-8} - 702 u_{iI-7} + 2805 u_{iI-6} - 7506 u_{iI-5} + 13797 u_{iI-4} - 17250 u_{iI-3} + 13959 u_{iI-2} - 6534 u_{iI-1} + 1331 u_{iI}}{216 \Delta xI^3},$$

$O(\Delta xI^3)$, *Backward*

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5886972877916365247 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925025813759648173 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5925025813759648173 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925063919428677339 \times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5925063919428677339 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925063957534399187 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5925063957534399187 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925063957572504909 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5925063957572504909 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925063957572543014 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1728 \Delta xI^3} \left(-15625 u_{iI} + 90000 u_{iI+1} - 240300 u_{iI+2} + 399792 u_{iI+3} - 466857 u_{iI+4} + 405216 u_{iI+5} - 268680 u_{iI+6} + 137376 u_{iI+7} \right.$$

$$\left. - 53811 u_{iI+8} + 15760 u_{iI+9} - 3276 u_{iI+10} + 432 u_{iI+11} - 27 u_{iI+12} \right), O(\Delta xI^4), \text{ Forward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.5513995802788841000 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.5429328439540241621 \times 10^{-23}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.5429328439540241621 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.5429243929022170847 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.5429243929022170847 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.5429243844511809411 \times 10^{-47}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.5429243844511809411 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.5429243844427299050 \times 10^{-59}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.5429243844427299050 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.5429243844427214540 \times 10^{-71}$$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1728 \Delta xI^3} \left(27 u_{iI-12} - 432 u_{iI-11} + 3276 u_{iI-10} - 15760 u_{iI-9} + 53811 u_{iI-8} - 137376 u_{iI-7} + 268680 u_{iI-6} - 405216 u_{iI-5} \right.$$

$$\left. + 466857 u_{iI-4} - 399792 u_{iI-3} + 240300 u_{iI-2} - 90000 u_{iI-1} + 15625 u_{iI} \right), O(\Delta xI^4), \text{ Backward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.5344805469030317991 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.5429159249627769961 \times 10^{-23}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.5429159249627769961 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.5429243759832258376 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.5429243759832258376 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.5429243844342619499 \times 10^{-47}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.5429243844342619499 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.5429243844427129860 \times 10^{-59}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.5429243844427129860 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.5429243844427214370 \times 10^{-71}$$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-6} - 24 u_{iI-5} + 192 u_{iI-4} - 488 u_{iI-3} - 387 u_{iI-2} + 1584 u_{iI-1} - 1584 u_{iI+1} + 387 u_{iI+2} + 488 u_{iI+3} - 192 u_{iI+4} + 24 u_{iI+5} - u_{iI+6}}{1728 \Delta xI^3},$$

$$O(\Delta xI^4), \text{ Centered}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 4.2382093175480945092 \times 10^{-12}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.2382073074065458878 \times 10^{-24}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 4.2382073074065458878 \times 10^{-24}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.2382073074045357445 \times 10^{-36}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 4.2382073074045357445 \times 10^{-36}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.2382073074045357425 \times 10^{-48}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 4.2382073074045357425 \times 10^{-48}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.2382073074045357425 \times 10^{-60}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 4.2382073074045357425 \times 10^{-60}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.2382073074045357425 \times 10^{-72}$$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{216000 \Delta xI^3} \left(-2571353 u_{il} + 16892100 u_{il+1} - 53882100 u_{il+2} + 112241400 u_{il+3} - 171533025 u_{il+4} + 203490684 u_{il+5} \right. \\ \left. - 193144200 u_{il+6} + 149029200 u_{il+7} - 94014675 u_{il+8} + 48362300 u_{il+9} - 20061684 u_{il+10} + 6564600 u_{il+11} - 1631475 u_{il+12} + 288900 u_{il+13} \right. \\ \left. - 32400 u_{il+14} + 1728 u_{il+15} \right), O(\Delta xI^5), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.2478813187485326081 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297659031311085661 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.2297659031311085661 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478298722818430 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.2297478298722818430 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117990651029 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.2297478117990651029 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117809918862 \times 10^{-74}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.2297478117809918862 \times 10^{-74}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117809738130 \times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{216000 \Delta xI^3} \left(-1728 u_{il-15} + 32400 u_{il-14} - 288900 u_{il-13} + 1631475 u_{il-12} - 6564600 u_{il-11} + 20061684 u_{il-10} - 48362300 u_{il-9} \right. \\ \left. + 94014675 u_{il-8} - 149029200 u_{il-7} + 193144200 u_{il-6} - 203490684 u_{il-5} + 171533025 u_{il-4} - 112241400 u_{il-3} + 53882100 u_{il-2} \right. \\ \left. - 16892100 u_{il-1} + 2571353 u_{il} \right), O(\Delta xI^5), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.2116985625874523512 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297297205150966126 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.2297297205150966126 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297477936896658311 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.2297477936896658311 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117628824869 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.2297478117628824869 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117809557036 \times 10^{-74}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.2297478117809557036 \times 10^{-74}$, *New Error:*, $4.2297478117809737768 \times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{216000 \Delta xI^3} \left(-3176523 u_{il} + 23337720 u_{il+1} - 86325750 u_{il+2} + 215470800 u_{il+3} - 405856575 u_{il+4} + 609089544 u_{il+5} \right. \\ \left. - 750777210 u_{il+6} + 773625600 u_{il+7} - 672655725 u_{il+8} + 495159400 u_{il+9} - 308081394 u_{il+10} + 160943760 u_{il+11} - 69743325 u_{il+12} \right. \\ \left. + 24607800 u_{il+13} - 6880950 u_{il+14} + 1465248 u_{il+15} - 223020 u_{il+16} + 21600 u_{il+17} - 1000 u_{il+18} \right), O(\Delta xI^6), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.2745458424116407646 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $7.2365611183841542350 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.2365611183841542350 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $7.2365232402785734207 \times 10^{-53}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.2365232402785734207 \times 10^{-53}$, *New Error:*, $7.2365232024005742468 \times 10^{-71}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.2365232024005742468 \times 10^{-71}$, *New Error:*, $7.2365232023626962477 \times 10^{-89}$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $7.2365232023626962477 \times 10^{-89}$, New Error:, $7.2365232023626583697 \times 10^{-107}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{216000 \Delta xI^3} (1000 u_{iI-18} - 21600 u_{iI-17} + 223020 u_{iI-16} - 1465248 u_{iI-15} + 6880950 u_{iI-14} - 24607800 u_{iI-13} + 69743325 u_{iI-12} - 160943760 u_{iI-11} + 308081394 u_{iI-10} - 495159400 u_{iI-9} + 672655725 u_{iI-8} - 773625600 u_{iI-7} + 750777210 u_{iI-6} - 609089544 u_{iI-5} + 405856575 u_{iI-4} - 215470800 u_{iI-3} + 86325750 u_{iI-2} - 23337720 u_{iI-1} + 3176523 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^6), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $7.1987135894811994928 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $7.2364852865541889339 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $7.2364852865541889339 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $7.2365231644467434558 \times 10^{-53}$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $7.2365231644467434558 \times 10^{-53}$, New Error:, $7.2365232023247424168 \times 10^{-71}$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $7.2365232023247424168 \times 10^{-71}$, New Error:, $7.2365232023626204159 \times 10^{-89}$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $7.2365232023626204159 \times 10^{-89}$, New Error:, $7.2365232023626582939 \times 10^{-107}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{216000 \Delta xI^3} (-u_{iI-9} + 27 u_{iI-8} - 378 u_{iI-7} + 3159 u_{iI-6} - 16875 u_{iI-5} + 52218 u_{iI-4} - 67551 u_{iI-3} - 114021 u_{iI-2} + 289683 u_{iI-1} - 289683 u_{iI+1} + 114021 u_{iI+2} + 67551 u_{iI+3} - 52218 u_{iI+4} + 16875 u_{iI+5} - 3159 u_{iI+6} + 378 u_{iI+7} - 27 u_{iI+8} + u_{iI+9}), O(\Delta xI^6), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $3.6182644041627294554 \times 10^{-18}$, New Error:, $3.6182616011841321462 \times 10^{-36}$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $3.6182616011841321462 \times 10^{-36}$, New Error:, $3.6182616011813291687 \times 10^{-54}$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $3.6182616011813291687 \times 10^{-54}$, New Error:, $3.6182616011813291659 \times 10^{-72}$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $3.6182616011813291659 \times 10^{-72}$, New Error:, $3.6182616011813291659 \times 10^{-90}$

Error order:, 6, Error:, $3.6182616011813291659 \times 10^{-90}$, New Error:, $3.6182616011813291659 \times 10^{-108}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{74088000 \Delta xI^3} (-1291467969 u_{iI} + 10459823220 u_{iI+1} - 43928376030 u_{iI+2} + 127561146300 u_{iI+3} - 285095353725 u_{iI+4} + 516658864932 u_{iI+5} - 782209818810 u_{iI+6} + 1007401176540 u_{iI+7} - 1115523865575 u_{iI+8} + 1068088627900 u_{iI+9} - 885917051082 u_{iI+10} + 635641991460 u_{iI+11} - 392726970615 u_{iI+12} + 207359743500 u_{iI+13} - 92562027750 u_{iI+14} + 34430024244 u_{iI+15} - 10467055620 u_{iI+16} + 2531904480 u_{iI+17} - 468508600 u_{iI+18} + 62269200 u_{iI+19} - 5292000 u_{iI+20} + 216000 u_{iI+21}), O(\Delta xI^7), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 7, Error:, $1.2717380853287031250 \times 10^{-19}$, New Error:, $1.2638716811187532870 \times 10^{-40}$

Error order:, 7, Error:, $1.2638716811187532870 \times 10^{-40}$, New Error:, $1.2638638405963142315 \times 10^{-61}$

Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $1.2638638405963142315 \times 10^{-61}$, *New Error:*, $1.2638638327558176145 \times 10^{-82}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $1.2638638327558176145 \times 10^{-82}$, *New Error:*, $1.2638638327479771179 \times 10^{-103}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $1.2638638327479771179 \times 10^{-103}$, *New Error:*, $1.2638638327479692774 \times 10^{-124}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{74088000 \Delta xI^3} \left(-216000 u_{iI-21} + 5292000 u_{iI-20} - 62269200 u_{iI-19} + 468508600 u_{iI-18} - 2531904480 u_{iI-17} + 10467055620 u_{iI-16} \right. \\ \left. - 34430024244 u_{iI-15} + 92562027750 u_{iI-14} - 207359743500 u_{iI-13} + 392726970615 u_{iI-12} - 635641991460 u_{iI-11} + 885917051082 u_{iI-10} \right. \\ \left. - 1068088627900 u_{iI-9} + 1115523865575 u_{iI-8} - 1007401176540 u_{iI-7} + 782209818810 u_{iI-6} - 516658864932 u_{iI-5} + 285095353725 u_{iI-4} \right. \\ \left. - 127561146300 u_{iI-3} + 43928376030 u_{iI-2} - 10459823220 u_{iI-1} + 1291467969 u_{iI} \right), O(\Delta xI^7), \textit{Backward}$$

Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $1.2560412760685437407 \times 10^{-19}$, *New Error:*, $1.2638559844288809373 \times 10^{-40}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $1.2638559844288809373 \times 10^{-40}$, *New Error:*, $1.2638638248996243593 \times 10^{-61}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $1.2638638248996243593 \times 10^{-61}$, *New Error:*, $1.2638638327401209246 \times 10^{-82}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $1.2638638327401209246 \times 10^{-82}$, *New Error:*, $1.2638638327479614212 \times 10^{-103}$
Error order:, 7, *Error:*, $1.2638638327479614212 \times 10^{-103}$, *New Error:*, $1.2638638327479692617 \times 10^{-124}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{592704000 \Delta xI^3} \left(-11899199187 u_{iI} + 105075714240 u_{iI+1} - 493172381520 u_{iI+2} + 1631155700160 u_{iI+3} - 4213594520100 u_{iI+4} \right. \\ \left. + 8938447350336 u_{iI+5} - 16031962260720 u_{iI+6} + 24755558448960 u_{iI+7} - 33280710011955 u_{iI+8} + 39215951734400 u_{iI+9} \right. \\ \left. - 40643920439136 u_{iI+10} + 37083201160320 u_{iI+11} - 29745648726360 u_{iI+12} + 20907183991680 u_{iI+13} - 12811067028000 u_{iI+14} \right. \\ \left. + 6797342896512 u_{iI+15} - 3095877976065 u_{iI+16} + 1197063241920 u_{iI+17} - 387360103760 u_{iI+18} + 102909643200 u_{iI+19} - 21854592900 u_{iI+20} \right. \\ \left. + 3566721600 u_{iI+21} - 419958000 u_{iI+22} + 31752000 u_{iI+23} - 1157625 u_{iI+24} \right), O(\Delta xI^8), \textit{Forward}$$

Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $2.2585582811654782623 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $2.2424003804632231165 \times 10^{-46}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $2.2424003804632231165 \times 10^{-46}$, *New Error:*, $2.2423842835744077837 \times 10^{-70}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $2.2423842835744077837 \times 10^{-70}$, *New Error:*, $2.2423842674775798196 \times 10^{-94}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $2.2423842674775798196 \times 10^{-94}$, *New Error:*, $2.2423842674614829917 \times 10^{-118}$
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, $2.2423842674614829917 \times 10^{-118}$, *New Error:*, $2.2423842674614668948 \times 10^{-142}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{592704000 \Delta xI^3} (1157625 u_{iI-24} - 31752000 u_{iI-23} + 419958000 u_{iI-22} - 3566721600 u_{iI-21} + 21854592900 u_{iI-20} - 102909643200 u_{iI-19} + 387360103760 u_{iI-18} - 1197063241920 u_{iI-17} + 3095877976065 u_{iI-16} - 6797342896512 u_{iI-15} + 12811067028000 u_{iI-14} - 20907183991680 u_{iI-13} + 29745648726360 u_{iI-12} - 37083201160320 u_{iI-11} + 40643920439136 u_{iI-10} - 39215951734400 u_{iI-9} + 33280710011955 u_{iI-8} - 24755558448960 u_{iI-7} + 16031962260720 u_{iI-6} - 8938447350336 u_{iI-5} + 4213594520100 u_{iI-4} - 1631155700160 u_{iI-3} + 493172381520 u_{iI-2} - 105075714240 u_{iI-1} + 11899199187 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $2.2263320785026473481 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, $2.2423681545815347265 \times 10^{-46}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $2.2423681545815347265 \times 10^{-46}$, New Error:, $2.2423842513485260956 \times 10^{-70}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $2.2423842513485260956 \times 10^{-70}$, New Error:, $2.2423842674453539379 \times 10^{-94}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $2.2423842674453539379 \times 10^{-94}$, New Error:, $2.2423842674614507658 \times 10^{-118}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $2.2423842674614507658 \times 10^{-118}$, New Error:, $2.2423842674614668626 \times 10^{-142}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{592704000 \Delta xI^3} (27 u_{iI-12} - 864 u_{iI-11} + 13752 u_{iI-10} - 147680 u_{iI-9} + 1157184 u_{iI-8} - 6787872 u_{iI-7} + 30090312 u_{iI-6} - 96057504 u_{iI-5} + 196751151 u_{iI-4} - 152212800 u_{iI-3} - 488470896 u_{iI-2} + 985779648 u_{iI-1} - 985779648 u_{iI+1} + 488470896 u_{iI+2} + 152212800 u_{iI+3} - 196751151 u_{iI+4} + 96057504 u_{iI+5} - 30090312 u_{iI+6} + 6787872 u_{iI+7} - 1157184 u_{iI+8} + 147680 u_{iI+9} - 13752 u_{iI+10} + 864 u_{iI+11} - 27 u_{iI+12}), O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $3.2034095770635389929 \times 10^{-24}$, New Error:, $3.2034060963770048006 \times 10^{-48}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $3.2034060963770048006 \times 10^{-48}$, New Error:, $3.2034060963735241159 \times 10^{-72}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $3.2034060963735241159 \times 10^{-72}$, New Error:, $3.2034060963735241125 \times 10^{-96}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $3.2034060963735241125 \times 10^{-96}$, New Error:, $3.2034060963735241125 \times 10^{-120}$

Error order:, 8, Error:, $3.2034060963735241125 \times 10^{-120}$, New Error:, $3.2034060963735241125 \times 10^{-144}$

"--- Derivative Order: 3 - x1=2, x2=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial xI^2 \partial x2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{-u_{iI, i2} + u_{iI, i2+1} + 2 u_{iI+1, i2} - 2 u_{iI+1, i2+1} - u_{iI+2, i2} + u_{iI+2, i2+1}}{\Delta xI^2 \Delta x2}, O(\Delta xI \Delta x2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.024920534351398990525, New Error:, 0.000024872073626373029230

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000024872073626373029230, *New Error:*, $2.4872025233719715131 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.4872025233719715131 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.4872025185327129812 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.4872025185327129812 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.4872025185278737227 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.4872025185278737227 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $2.4872025185278688834 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{-u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2} + 2u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 2u_{i_1-1, i_2} - u_{i_1, i_2-1} + u_{i_1, i_2}}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2}, O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.024823652146436042254, *New Error:*, 0.000024871976744320475475
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000024871976744320475475, *New Error:*, $2.4872025136837662577 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.4872025136837662577 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.4872025185230247759 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.4872025185230247759 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.4872025185278640345 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.4872025185278640345 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $2.4872025185278688737 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{8 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2} (-27u_{i_1, i_2} + 36u_{i_1, i_2+1} - 9u_{i_1, i_2+2} + 72u_{i_1+1, i_2} - 96u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} + 24u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} - 66u_{i_1+2, i_2} + 88u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} - 22u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} + 24u_{i_1+3, i_2} - 32u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} + 8u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} - 3u_{i_1+4, i_2} + 4u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} - u_{i_1+4, i_2+2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000040239374542103039085, *New Error:*, $4.0163449066213736812 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.0163449066213736812 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.0163373164468003235 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.0163373164468003235 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $4.0163373088566281390 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.0163373088566281390 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $4.0163373088490379669 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.0163373088490379669 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $4.0163373088490303767 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{8 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2} (u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 4u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 3u_{i_1-4, i_2} - 8u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 32u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 24u_{i_1-3, i_2} + 22u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 88u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 66u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 24u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 96u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 72u_{i_1-1, i_2} + 9u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 36u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 27u_{i_1, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000040087419460639581540, *New Error:*, $4.0163297110814697126 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.0163297110814697126 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.0163373012512604195 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.0163373012512604195 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $4.0163373088414325991 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.0163373088414325991 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $4.0163373088490227713 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $4.0163373088490227713 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $4.0163373088490303615 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x^2 \partial x} u(x1, x2) = \frac{-u_{i-2, i-1} + u_{i-2, i+1} + 2u_{i, i-1} - 2u_{i, i+1} - u_{i+2, i-1} + u_{i+2, i+1}}{8 \Delta x^2 \Delta x}, O(\Delta x^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000020081710426219082241, New Error:, $2.0081686544269033803 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.0081686544269033803 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $2.0081686544245151869 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.0081686544245151869 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $2.0081686544245151845 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.0081686544245151845 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $2.0081686544245151845 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.0081686544245151845 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $2.0081686544245151845 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x^2 \partial x} u(x1, x2) = \frac{1}{216 \Delta x^2 \Delta x} (-1331 u_{i, i} + 2178 u_{i, i+1} - 1089 u_{i, i+2} + 242 u_{i, i+3} + 4356 u_{i+1, i} - 7128 u_{i+1, i+1} + 3564 u_{i+1, i+2} - 792 u_{i+1, i+3} - 5742 u_{i+2, i} + 9396 u_{i+2, i+1} - 4698 u_{i+2, i+2} + 1044 u_{i+2, i+3} + 4048 u_{i+3, i} - 6624 u_{i+3, i+1} + 3312 u_{i+3, i+2} - 736 u_{i+3, i+3} - 1683 u_{i+4, i} + 2754 u_{i+4, i+1} - 1377 u_{i+4, i+2} + 306 u_{i+4, i+3} + 396 u_{i+5, i} - 648 u_{i+5, i+1} + 324 u_{i+5, i+2} - 72 u_{i+5, i+3} - 44 u_{i+6, i} + 72 u_{i+6, i+1} - 36 u_{i+6, i+2} + 8 u_{i+6, i+3}), O(\Delta x^3 \Delta x^3), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $7.6217031904735001998 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $7.5977938402668099159 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $7.5977938402668099159 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $7.5977699758884073313 \times 10^{-26}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $7.5977699758884073313 \times 10^{-26}$, New Error:, $7.5977699520240738143 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $7.5977699520240738143 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $7.5977699520002094808 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $7.5977699520002094808 \times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, $7.5977699520001856165 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x^2 \partial x} u(x1, x2) = \frac{1}{216 \Delta x^2 \Delta x} (-8 u_{i-6, i-3} + 36 u_{i-6, i-2} - 72 u_{i-6, i-1} + 44 u_{i-6, i} + 72 u_{i-5, i-3} - 324 u_{i-5, i-2} + 648 u_{i-5, i-1} - 396 u_{i-5, i} - 306 u_{i-4, i-3} + 1377 u_{i-4, i-2} - 2754 u_{i-4, i-1} + 1683 u_{i-4, i} + 736 u_{i-3, i-3} - 3312 u_{i-3, i-2} + 6624 u_{i-3, i-1} - 4048 u_{i-3, i} - 1044 u_{i-2, i-3} + 4698 u_{i-2, i-2} - 9396 u_{i-2, i-1} + 5742 u_{i-2, i} + 792 u_{i-1, i-3} - 3564 u_{i-1, i-2} + 7128 u_{i-1, i-1} - 4356 u_{i-1, i} - 242 u_{i, i-3} + 1089 u_{i, i-2} - 2178 u_{i, i-1} + 1331 u_{i, i}), O(\Delta x^3 \Delta x^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $7.5739265749550690607 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $7.5977460638234222910 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $7.5977460638234222910 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $7.5977699281119639438 \times 10^{-26}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $7.5977699281119639438 \times 10^{-26}$, New Error:, $7.5977699519762973709 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $7.5977699519762973709 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $7.5977699520001617044 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $7.5977699520001617044 \times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, $7.5977699520001855687 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{1728 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2} \left(-15625 u_{i_1, i_2} + 30000 u_{i_1, i_2+1} - 22500 u_{i_1, i_2+2} + 10000 u_{i_1, i_2+3} - 1875 u_{i_1, i_2+4} + 60000 u_{i_1+1, i_2} - 115200 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} \right. \\ + 86400 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} - 38400 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} + 7200 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} - 102600 u_{i_1+2, i_2} + 196992 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} - 147744 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} + 65664 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} \\ - 12312 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} + 106400 u_{i_1+3, i_2} - 204288 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} + 153216 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} - 68096 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} + 12768 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} - 74550 u_{i_1+4, i_2} \\ + 143136 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} - 107352 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} + 47712 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} - 8946 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} + 36000 u_{i_1+5, i_2} - 69120 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} + 51840 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} \\ - 23040 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} + 4320 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} - 11800 u_{i_1+6, i_2} + 22656 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} - 16992 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} + 7552 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} - 1416 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} + 2400 u_{i_1+7, i_2} \\ - 4608 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} + 3456 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} - 1536 u_{i_1+7, i_2+3} + 288 u_{i_1+7, i_2+4} - 225 u_{i_1+8, i_2} + 432 u_{i_1+8, i_2+1} - 324 u_{i_1+8, i_2+2} + 144 u_{i_1+8, i_2+3} \\ \left. - 27 u_{i_1+8, i_2+4} \right), O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.5997556063419393004 \times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, $1.5925553018153996866 \times 10^{-22}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.5925553018153996866 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, $1.5925481201039722907 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.5925481201039722907 \times 10^{-34}$, New Error:, $1.5925481129222794208 \times 10^{-46}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.5925481129222794208 \times 10^{-46}$, New Error:, $1.5925481129150977280 \times 10^{-58}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.5925481129150977280 \times 10^{-58}$, New Error:, $1.5925481129150905463 \times 10^{-70}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{1728 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2} \left(27 u_{i_1-8, i_2-4} - 144 u_{i_1-8, i_2-3} + 324 u_{i_1-8, i_2-2} - 432 u_{i_1-8, i_2-1} + 225 u_{i_1-8, i_2} - 288 u_{i_1-7, i_2-4} + 1536 u_{i_1-7, i_2-3} \right. \\ - 3456 u_{i_1-7, i_2-2} + 4608 u_{i_1-7, i_2-1} - 2400 u_{i_1-7, i_2} + 1416 u_{i_1-6, i_2-4} - 7552 u_{i_1-6, i_2-3} + 16992 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 22656 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 11800 u_{i_1-6, i_2} \\ - 4320 u_{i_1-5, i_2-4} + 23040 u_{i_1-5, i_2-3} - 51840 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 69120 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 36000 u_{i_1-5, i_2} + 8946 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4} - 47712 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3} + 107352 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} \\ - 143136 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 74550 u_{i_1-4, i_2} - 12768 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4} + 68096 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 153216 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 204288 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 106400 u_{i_1-3, i_2} \\ + 12312 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4} - 65664 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 147744 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 196992 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 102600 u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 7200 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4} + 38400 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} \\ - 86400 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 115200 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 60000 u_{i_1-1, i_2} + 1875 u_{i_1, i_2-4} - 10000 u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 22500 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 30000 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 15625 u_{i_1, i_2} \left. \right), \\ O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.5853777718166359966 \times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, $1.5925409240519336252 \times 10^{-22}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $1.5925409240519336252 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, $1.5925481057262088247 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.5925481057262088247 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925481129079016574 \times 10^{-46}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.5925481129079016574 \times 10^{-46}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925481129150833502 \times 10^{-58}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.5925481129150833502 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $1.5925481129150905319 \times 10^{-70}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{1728 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2} (u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 8 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 8 u_{i_1-4, i_2+1} - u_{i_1-4, i_2+2} - 16 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 128 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 128 u_{i_1-3, i_2+1} + 16 u_{i_1-3, i_2+2} + 64 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 512 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 512 u_{i_1-2, i_2+1} - 64 u_{i_1-2, i_2+2} + 16 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} - 128 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} + 128 u_{i_1-1, i_2+1} - 16 u_{i_1-1, i_2+2} - 130 u_{i_1, i_2-2} + 1040 u_{i_1, i_2-1} - 1040 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 130 u_{i_1, i_2+2} + 16 u_{i_1+1, i_2-2} - 128 u_{i_1+1, i_2-1} + 128 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 16 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 64 u_{i_1+2, i_2-2} - 512 u_{i_1+2, i_2-1} + 512 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} - 64 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 16 u_{i_1+3, i_2-2} + 128 u_{i_1+3, i_2-1} - 128 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} + 16 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + u_{i_1+4, i_2-2} - 8 u_{i_1+4, i_2-1} + 8 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} - u_{i_1+4, i_2+2}), O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.6542492364108467509 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.6542468548608657853 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.6542468548608657853 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.6542468548584842342 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.6542468548584842342 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $2.6542468548584842318 \times 10^{-47}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.6542468548584842318 \times 10^{-47}$, *New Error:*, $2.6542468548584842318 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.6542468548584842318 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $2.6542468548584842318 \times 10^{-71}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{216000 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2} (-2571353 u_{i_1, i_2} + 5630700 u_{i_1, i_2+1} - 5630700 u_{i_1, i_2+2} + 3753800 u_{i_1, i_2+3} - 1407675 u_{i_1, i_2+4} + 225228 u_{i_1, i_2+5} + 11261400 u_{i_1+1, i_2} - 24660000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} + 24660000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} - 16440000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} + 6165000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} - 986400 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} - 23591400 u_{i_1+2, i_2} + 51660000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} - 51660000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} + 34440000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} - 12915000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} + 2066400 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} + 32167600 u_{i_1+3, i_2} - 70440000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} + 70440000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} - 46960000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} + 17610000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} - 2817600 u_{i_1+3, i_2+5} - 31585350 u_{i_1+4, i_2} + 69165000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} - 69165000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} + 46110000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} - 17291250 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} + 2766600 u_{i_1+4, i_2+5} + 23055456 u_{i_1+5, i_2} - 50486400 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} + 50486400 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} - 33657600 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} + 12621600 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} - 2019456 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} - 12631400 u_{i_1+6, i_2} + 27660000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} - 27660000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} + 18440000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} - 6915000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} + 1106400 u_{i_1+6, i_2+5} + 5096400 u_{i_1+7, i_2} - 11160000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} + 11160000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} - 7440000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+3} + 2790000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+4} - 446400 u_{i_1+7, i_2+5} - 1428225 u_{i_1+8, i_2} + 3127500 u_{i_1+8, i_2+1} - 3127500 u_{i_1+8, i_2+2} + 2085000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+3} - 781875 u_{i_1+8, i_2+4} + 125100 u_{i_1+8, i_2+5} + 246600 u_{i_1+9, i_2} - 540000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+1} + 540000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+2} - 360000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+3} + 135000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+4} - 21600 u_{i_1+9, i_2+5} - 19728 u_{i_1+10, i_2} + 43200 u_{i_1+10, i_2+1} - 43200 u_{i_1+10, i_2+2}$$

$$+ 28800 u_{i_l+10, i_2+3} - 10800 u_{i_l+10, i_2+4} + 1728 u_{i_l+10, i_2+5}), O(\Delta x I^5 \Delta x^2^5), \text{ Forward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 3.6159460779296886559 \times 10^{-13}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.5944623005495619958 \times 10^{-28}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 3.5944623005495619958 \times 10^{-28}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.5944408879315812344 \times 10^{-43}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 3.5944408879315812344 \times 10^{-43}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.5944408665190342419 \times 10^{-58}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 3.5944408665190342419 \times 10^{-58}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.5944408664976216950 \times 10^{-73}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 3.5944408664976216950 \times 10^{-73}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.5944408664976002825 \times 10^{-88}$$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x I^2 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{216000 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} \left(-1728 u_{i_l-10, i_2-5} + 10800 u_{i_l-10, i_2-4} - 28800 u_{i_l-10, i_2-3} + 43200 u_{i_l-10, i_2-2} - 43200 u_{i_l-10, i_2-1} \right. \\ + 19728 u_{i_l-10, i_2} + 21600 u_{i_l-9, i_2-5} - 135000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-4} + 360000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-3} - 540000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-2} + 540000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-1} - 246600 u_{i_l-9, i_2} \\ - 125100 u_{i_l-8, i_2-5} + 781875 u_{i_l-8, i_2-4} - 2085000 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 3127500 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 3127500 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 1428225 u_{i_l-8, i_2} + 446400 u_{i_l-7, i_2-5} \\ - 2790000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-4} + 7440000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 11160000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 11160000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 5096400 u_{i_l-7, i_2} - 1106400 u_{i_l-6, i_2-5} \\ + 6915000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4} - 18440000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 27660000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 27660000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 12631400 u_{i_l-6, i_2} + 2019456 u_{i_l-5, i_2-5} \\ - 12621600 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4} + 33657600 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 50486400 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 50486400 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 23055456 u_{i_l-5, i_2} - 2766600 u_{i_l-4, i_2-5} \\ + 17291250 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} - 46110000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 69165000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 69165000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 31585350 u_{i_l-4, i_2} + 2817600 u_{i_l-3, i_2-5} \\ - 17610000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 46960000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 70440000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 70440000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 32167600 u_{i_l-3, i_2} - 2066400 u_{i_l-2, i_2-5} \\ + 12915000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} - 34440000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 51660000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 51660000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 23591400 u_{i_l-2, i_2} + 986400 u_{i_l-1, i_2-5} \\ - 6165000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} + 16440000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 24660000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 24660000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 11261400 u_{i_l-1, i_2} - 225228 u_{i_l, i_2-5} + 1407675 u_{i_l, i_2-4} \\ \left. - 3753800 u_{i_l, i_2-3} + 5630700 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 5630700 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 2571353 u_{i_l, i_2} \right), O(\Delta x I^5 \Delta x^2^5), \text{ Backward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 3.5730777743162283483 \times 10^{-13}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.5944194325877571167 \times 10^{-28}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 3.5944194325877571167 \times 10^{-28}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.5944408450636194298 \times 10^{-43}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 3.5944408450636194298 \times 10^{-43}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.5944408664761662801 \times 10^{-58}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 3.5944408664761662801 \times 10^{-58}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.5944408664975788271 \times 10^{-73}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 3.5944408664975788271 \times 10^{-73}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.5944408664976002396 \times 10^{-88}$$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x I^2 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{216000 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} \left(-3176523 u_{i_l, i_2} + 7779240 u_{i_l, i_2+1} - 9724050 u_{i_l, i_2+2} + 8643600 u_{i_l, i_2+3} - 4862025 u_{i_l, i_2+4} + 1555848 u_{i_l, i_2+5} \right. \\ \left. - 216090 u_{i_l, i_2+6} + 15558480 u_{i_l+1, i_2} - 38102400 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} + 47628000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} - 42336000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} + 23814000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -7620480 u_{i_l+1, i_2+5} + 1058400 u_{i_l+1, i_2+6} - 38499300 u_{i_l+2, i_2} + 94284000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} - 117855000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} + 104760000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} \\
& - 58927500 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} + 18856800 u_{i_l+2, i_2+5} - 2619000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+6} + 64915200 u_{i_l+3, i_2} - 158976000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} + 198720000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} \\
& - 176640000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} + 99360000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} - 31795200 u_{i_l+3, i_2+5} + 4416000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+6} - 81827550 u_{i_l+4, i_2} + 200394000 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} \\
& - 250492500 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} + 222660000 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} - 125246250 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4} + 40078800 u_{i_l+4, i_2+5} - 5566500 u_{i_l+4, i_2+6} + 79845696 u_{i_l+5, i_2} \\
& - 195540480 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} + 244425600 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} - 217267200 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} + 122212800 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4} - 39108096 u_{i_l+5, i_2+5} + 5431680 u_{i_l+5, i_2+6} \\
& - 61340160 u_{i_l+6, i_2} + 150220800 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} - 187776000 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} + 166912000 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} - 93888000 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4} + 30044160 u_{i_l+6, i_2+5} \\
& - 4172800 u_{i_l+6, i_2+6} + 37044000 u_{i_l+7, i_2} - 90720000 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} + 113400000 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} - 100800000 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} + 56700000 u_{i_l+7, i_2+4} \\
& - 18144000 u_{i_l+7, i_2+5} + 2520000 u_{i_l+7, i_2+6} - 17232075 u_{i_l+8, i_2} + 42201000 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} - 52751250 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} + 46890000 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} \\
& - 26375625 u_{i_l+8, i_2+4} + 8440200 u_{i_l+8, i_2+5} - 1172250 u_{i_l+8, i_2+6} + 5938800 u_{i_l+9, i_2} - 14544000 u_{i_l+9, i_2+1} + 18180000 u_{i_l+9, i_2+2} \\
& - 16160000 u_{i_l+9, i_2+3} + 9090000 u_{i_l+9, i_2+4} - 2908800 u_{i_l+9, i_2+5} + 404000 u_{i_l+9, i_2+6} - 1423548 u_{i_l+10, i_2} + 3486240 u_{i_l+10, i_2+1} \\
& - 4357800 u_{i_l+10, i_2+2} + 3873600 u_{i_l+10, i_2+3} - 2178900 u_{i_l+10, i_2+4} + 697248 u_{i_l+10, i_2+5} - 96840 u_{i_l+10, i_2+6} + 211680 u_{i_l+11, i_2} - 518400 u_{i_l+11, i_2+1} \\
& + 648000 u_{i_l+11, i_2+2} - 576000 u_{i_l+11, i_2+3} + 324000 u_{i_l+11, i_2+4} - 103680 u_{i_l+11, i_2+5} + 14400 u_{i_l+11, i_2+6} - 14700 u_{i_l+12, i_2} + 36000 u_{i_l+12, i_2+1} \\
& - 45000 u_{i_l+12, i_2+2} + 40000 u_{i_l+12, i_2+3} - 22500 u_{i_l+12, i_2+4} + 7200 u_{i_l+12, i_2+5} - 1000 u_{i_l+12, i_2+6}), O(\Delta x_1^6 \Delta x_2^6), \text{ Forward} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 8.6378062563632079480 \times 10^{-16}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.5736563145328818921 \times 10^{-34} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 8.5736563145328818921 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.5735924248608230192 \times 10^{-52} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 8.5735924248608230192 \times 10^{-52}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.5735923609714104749 \times 10^{-70} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 8.5735923609714104749 \times 10^{-70}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.5735923609075210626 \times 10^{-88} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 8.5735923609075210626 \times 10^{-88}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.5735923609074571732 \times 10^{-106}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) &= \frac{1}{216000 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2} (1000 u_{i_l-12, i_2-6} - 7200 u_{i_l-12, i_2-5} + 22500 u_{i_l-12, i_2-4} - 40000 u_{i_l-12, i_2-3} + 45000 u_{i_l-12, i_2-2} \\
& - 36000 u_{i_l-12, i_2-1} + 14700 u_{i_l-12, i_2} - 14400 u_{i_l-11, i_2-6} + 103680 u_{i_l-11, i_2-5} - 324000 u_{i_l-11, i_2-4} + 576000 u_{i_l-11, i_2-3} - 648000 u_{i_l-11, i_2-2} \\
& + 518400 u_{i_l-11, i_2-1} - 211680 u_{i_l-11, i_2} + 96840 u_{i_l-10, i_2-6} - 697248 u_{i_l-10, i_2-5} + 2178900 u_{i_l-10, i_2-4} - 3873600 u_{i_l-10, i_2-3} + 4357800 u_{i_l-10, i_2-2} \\
& - 3486240 u_{i_l-10, i_2-1} + 1423548 u_{i_l-10, i_2} - 404000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-6} + 2908800 u_{i_l-9, i_2-5} - 9090000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-4} + 16160000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-3} \\
& - 18180000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-2} + 14544000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-1} - 5938800 u_{i_l-9, i_2} + 1172250 u_{i_l-8, i_2-6} - 8440200 u_{i_l-8, i_2-5} + 26375625 u_{i_l-8, i_2-4} \\
& - 46890000 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 52751250 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 42201000 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 17232075 u_{i_l-8, i_2} - 2520000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-6} + 18144000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-5} \\
& - 56700000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-4} + 100800000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 113400000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 90720000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 37044000 u_{i_l-7, i_2} + 4172800 u_{i_l-6, i_2-6}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 30044160 u_{i_l-6, i_2-5} + 93888000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4} - 166912000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 187776000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 150220800 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 61340160 u_{i_l-6, i_2} \\
& - 5431680 u_{i_l-5, i_2-6} + 39108096 u_{i_l-5, i_2-5} - 122212800 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4} + 217267200 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 244425600 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 195540480 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} \\
& - 79845696 u_{i_l-5, i_2} + 5566500 u_{i_l-4, i_2-6} - 40078800 u_{i_l-4, i_2-5} + 125246250 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} - 222660000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 250492500 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} \\
& - 200394000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 81827550 u_{i_l-4, i_2} - 4416000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-6} + 31795200 u_{i_l-3, i_2-5} - 99360000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 176640000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} \\
& - 198720000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 158976000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 64915200 u_{i_l-3, i_2} + 2619000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-6} - 18856800 u_{i_l-2, i_2-5} + 58927500 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} \\
& - 104760000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 117855000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 94284000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 38499300 u_{i_l-2, i_2} - 1058400 u_{i_l-1, i_2-6} + 7620480 u_{i_l-1, i_2-5} \\
& - 23814000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} + 42336000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 47628000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 38102400 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 15558480 u_{i_l-1, i_2} + 216090 u_{i_l, i_2-6} - 1555848 u_{i_l, i_2-5} \\
& + 4862025 u_{i_l, i_2-4} - 8643600 u_{i_l, i_2-3} + 9724050 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 7779240 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 3176523 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x l^6 \Delta x 2^6), \textit{Backward} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 8.5098980167547646057 \times 10^{-16}, \textit{New Error:}, 8.5735284078015801501 \times 10^{-34} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 8.5735284078015801501 \times 10^{-34}, \textit{New Error:}, 8.5735922969540917189 \times 10^{-52} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 8.5735922969540917189 \times 10^{-52}, \textit{New Error:}, 8.5735923608435037436 \times 10^{-70} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 8.5735923608435037436 \times 10^{-70}, \textit{New Error:}, 8.5735923609073931559 \times 10^{-88} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 8.5735923609073931559 \times 10^{-88}, \textit{New Error:}, 8.5735923609074570453 \times 10^{-106}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x l^2 \partial x 2} u(x l, x 2) &= \frac{1}{216000 \Delta x l^2 \Delta x 2} (-u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 9 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 45 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 45 u_{i_l-6, i_2+1} - 9 u_{i_l-6, i_2+2} + u_{i_l-6, i_2+3} + 18 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} \\
& - 162 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 810 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 810 u_{i_l-5, i_2+1} + 162 u_{i_l-5, i_2+2} - 18 u_{i_l-5, i_2+3} - 171 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 1539 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 7695 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} \\
& + 7695 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1} - 1539 u_{i_l-4, i_2+2} + 171 u_{i_l-4, i_2+3} + 810 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 7290 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 36450 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 36450 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1} + 7290 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2} \\
& - 810 u_{i_l-3, i_2+3} - 1935 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 17415 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 87075 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 87075 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1} - 17415 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2} + 1935 u_{i_l-2, i_2+3} - 828 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} \\
& + 7452 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} - 37260 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} + 37260 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1} - 7452 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2} + 828 u_{i_l-1, i_2+3} + 4214 u_{i_l, i_2-3} - 37926 u_{i_l, i_2-2} + 189630 u_{i_l, i_2-1} \\
& - 189630 u_{i_l, i_2+1} + 37926 u_{i_l, i_2+2} - 4214 u_{i_l, i_2+3} - 828 u_{i_l+1, i_2-3} + 7452 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2} - 37260 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1} + 37260 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - 7452 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} \\
& + 828 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} - 1935 u_{i_l+2, i_2-3} + 17415 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2} - 87075 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1} + 87075 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} - 17415 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} + 1935 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} + 810 u_{i_l+3, i_2-3} \\
& - 7290 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2} + 36450 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} - 36450 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} + 7290 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} - 810 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} - 171 u_{i_l+4, i_2-3} + 1539 u_{i_l+4, i_2-2} - 7695 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1} \\
& + 7695 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} - 1539 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} + 171 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} + 18 u_{i_l+5, i_2-3} - 162 u_{i_l+5, i_2-2} + 810 u_{i_l+5, i_2-1} - 810 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} + 162 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} \\
& - 18 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} - u_{i_l+6, i_2-3} + 9 u_{i_l+6, i_2-2} - 45 u_{i_l+6, i_2-1} + 45 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} - 9 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} + u_{i_l+6, i_2+3}), O(\Delta x l^6 \Delta x 2^6), \textit{Centered} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 4.2868030166149040920 \times 10^{-17}, \textit{New Error:}, 4.2867961804605647102 \times 10^{-35} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 4.2867961804605647102 \times 10^{-35}, \textit{New Error:}, 4.2867961804537285615 \times 10^{-53}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $4.2867961804537285615 \times 10^{-53}$, *New Error:*, $4.2867961804537285546 \times 10^{-71}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $4.2867961804537285546 \times 10^{-71}$, *New Error:*, $4.2867961804537285546 \times 10^{-89}$
Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $4.2867961804537285546 \times 10^{-89}$, *New Error:*, $4.2867961804537285546 \times 10^{-107}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{74088000 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2} \left(-1291467969 u_{i_1, i_2} + 3486607740 u_{i_1, i_2+1} - 5229911610 u_{i_1, i_2+2} + 5811012900 u_{i_1, i_2+3} - 4358259675 u_{i_1, i_2+4} \right. \\
& + 2091964644 u_{i_1, i_2+5} - 581101290 u_{i_1, i_2+6} + 71155260 u_{i_1, i_2+7} + 6973215480 u_{i_1+1, i_2} - 18825760800 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} + 28238641200 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} \\
& - 31376268000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} + 23532201000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} - 11295456480 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} + 3137626800 u_{i_1+1, i_2+6} - 384199200 u_{i_1+1, i_2+7} \\
& - 19872703620 u_{i_1+2, i_2} + 53650825200 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} - 80476237800 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} + 89418042000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} - 67063531500 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} \\
& + 32190495120 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} - 8941804200 u_{i_1+2, i_2+6} + 1094914800 u_{i_1+2, i_2+7} + 39860667000 u_{i_1+3, i_2} - 107612820000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} \\
& + 161419230000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} - 179354700000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} + 134516025000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} - 64567692000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+5} + 17935470000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+6} \\
& - 2196180000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+7} - 61271768250 u_{i_1+4, i_2} + 165416895000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} - 248125342500 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} + 275694825000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} \\
& - 206771118750 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} + 99250137000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+5} - 27569482500 u_{i_1+4, i_2+6} + 3375855000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+7} + 74780532288 u_{i_1+5, i_2} \\
& - 201886836480 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} + 302830254720 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} - 336478060800 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} + 252358545600 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} - 121132101888 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} \\
& + 33647806080 u_{i_1+5, i_2+6} - 4120139520 u_{i_1+5, i_2+7} - 73902850560 u_{i_1+6, i_2} + 199517337600 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} - 299276006400 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} \\
& + 332528896000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} - 249396672000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} + 119710402560 u_{i_1+6, i_2+5} - 33252889600 u_{i_1+6, i_2+6} + 4071782400 u_{i_1+6, i_2+7} \\
& + 59443457040 u_{i_1+7, i_2} - 160480958400 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} + 240721437600 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} - 267468264000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+3} + 200601198000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+4} \\
& - 96288575040 u_{i_1+7, i_2+5} + 26746826400 u_{i_1+7, i_2+6} - 3275121600 u_{i_1+7, i_2+7} - 38624025825 u_{i_1+8, i_2} + 104274229500 u_{i_1+8, i_2+1} \\
& - 156411344250 u_{i_1+8, i_2+2} + 173790382500 u_{i_1+8, i_2+3} - 130342786875 u_{i_1+8, i_2+4} + 62564537700 u_{i_1+8, i_2+5} - 17379038250 u_{i_1+8, i_2+6} \\
& + 2128045500 u_{i_1+8, i_2+7} + 19924997400 u_{i_1+9, i_2} - 53792004000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+1} + 80688006000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+2} - 89653340000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+3} \\
& + 67240005000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+4} - 32275202400 u_{i_1+9, i_2+5} + 8965334000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+6} - 1097796000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+7} - 7951002444 u_{i_1+10, i_2} \\
& + 21465516240 u_{i_1+10, i_2+1} - 32198274360 u_{i_1+10, i_2+2} + 35775860400 u_{i_1+10, i_2+3} - 26831895300 u_{i_1+10, i_2+4} + 12879309744 u_{i_1+10, i_2+5} \\
& - 3577586040 u_{i_1+10, i_2+6} + 438071760 u_{i_1+10, i_2+7} + 2362825080 u_{i_1+11, i_2} - 6378976800 u_{i_1+11, i_2+1} + 9568465200 u_{i_1+11, i_2+2} \\
& - 10631628000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+3} + 7973721000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+4} - 3827386080 u_{i_1+11, i_2+5} + 1063162800 u_{i_1+11, i_2+6} - 130183200 u_{i_1+11, i_2+7} \\
& - 491988420 u_{i_1+12, i_2} + 1328233200 u_{i_1+12, i_2+1} - 1992349800 u_{i_1+12, i_2+2} + 2213722000 u_{i_1+12, i_2+3} - 1660291500 u_{i_1+12, i_2+4} \\
& + 796939920 u_{i_1+12, i_2+5} - 221372200 u_{i_1+12, i_2+6} + 27106800 u_{i_1+12, i_2+7} + 64033200 u_{i_1+13, i_2} - 172872000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+1} + 259308000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+2} \\
& - 288120000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+3} + 216090000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+4} - 103723200 u_{i_1+13, i_2+5} + 28812000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+6} - 3528000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+7} - 3920400 u_{i_1+14, i_2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$+ 10584000 u_{i_l+14, i_2+1} - 15876000 u_{i_l+14, i_2+2} + 17640000 u_{i_l+14, i_2+3} - 13230000 u_{i_l+14, i_2+4} + 6350400 u_{i_l+14, i_2+5} - 1764000 u_{i_l+14, i_2+6} + 216000 u_{i_l+14, i_2+7}), O(\Delta x I^7 \Delta x^7), \text{ Forward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 2.1510125791256049295 \times 10^{-18}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1317979963316768168 \times 10^{-39}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 2.1317979963316768168 \times 10^{-39}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1317788741451313949 \times 10^{-60}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 2.1317788741451313949 \times 10^{-60}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1317788550230369316 \times 10^{-81}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 2.1317788550230369316 \times 10^{-81}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1317788550039148372 \times 10^{-102}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 2.1317788550039148372 \times 10^{-102}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1317788550038957151 \times 10^{-123}$$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x I^2 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{74088000 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} (-216000 u_{i_l-14, i_2-7} + 1764000 u_{i_l-14, i_2-6} - 6350400 u_{i_l-14, i_2-5} + 13230000 u_{i_l-14, i_2-4} - 17640000 u_{i_l-14, i_2-3} + 15876000 u_{i_l-14, i_2-2} - 10584000 u_{i_l-14, i_2-1} + 3920400 u_{i_l-14, i_2} + 3528000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-7} - 28812000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-6} + 103723200 u_{i_l-13, i_2-5} - 216090000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-4} + 288120000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-3} - 259308000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-2} + 172872000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-1} - 64033200 u_{i_l-13, i_2} - 27106800 u_{i_l-12, i_2-7} + 221372200 u_{i_l-12, i_2-6} - 796939920 u_{i_l-12, i_2-5} + 1660291500 u_{i_l-12, i_2-4} - 2213722000 u_{i_l-12, i_2-3} + 1992349800 u_{i_l-12, i_2-2} - 1328233200 u_{i_l-12, i_2-1} + 491988420 u_{i_l-12, i_2} + 130183200 u_{i_l-11, i_2-7} - 1063162800 u_{i_l-11, i_2-6} + 3827386080 u_{i_l-11, i_2-5} - 7973721000 u_{i_l-11, i_2-4} + 10631628000 u_{i_l-11, i_2-3} - 9568465200 u_{i_l-11, i_2-2} + 6378976800 u_{i_l-11, i_2-1} - 2362825080 u_{i_l-11, i_2} - 438071760 u_{i_l-10, i_2-7} + 3577586040 u_{i_l-10, i_2-6} - 12879309744 u_{i_l-10, i_2-5} + 26831895300 u_{i_l-10, i_2-4} - 35775860400 u_{i_l-10, i_2-3} + 32198274360 u_{i_l-10, i_2-2} - 21465516240 u_{i_l-10, i_2-1} + 7951002444 u_{i_l-10, i_2} + 1097796000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-7} - 8965334000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-6} + 32275202400 u_{i_l-9, i_2-5} - 67240005000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-4} + 89653340000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-3} - 80688006000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-2} + 53792004000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-1} - 19924997400 u_{i_l-9, i_2} - 2128045500 u_{i_l-8, i_2-7} + 17379038250 u_{i_l-8, i_2-6} - 62564537700 u_{i_l-8, i_2-5} + 130342786875 u_{i_l-8, i_2-4} - 173790382500 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 156411344250 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 104274229500 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 38624025825 u_{i_l-8, i_2} + 3275121600 u_{i_l-7, i_2-7} - 26746826400 u_{i_l-7, i_2-6} + 96288575040 u_{i_l-7, i_2-5} - 200601198000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-4} + 267468264000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 240721437600 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 160480958400 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 59443457040 u_{i_l-7, i_2} - 4071782400 u_{i_l-6, i_2-7} + 33252889600 u_{i_l-6, i_2-6} - 119710402560 u_{i_l-6, i_2-5} + 249396672000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4} - 332528896000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 299276006400 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 199517337600 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 73902850560 u_{i_l-6, i_2} + 4120139520 u_{i_l-5, i_2-7} - 33647806080 u_{i_l-5, i_2-6} + 121132101888 u_{i_l-5, i_2-5} - 252358545600 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4} + 336478060800 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 302830254720 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 201886836480 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 74780532288 u_{i_l-5, i_2} - 3375855000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-7} + 27569482500 u_{i_l-4, i_2-6} - 99250137000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-5} + 206771118750 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} - 275694825000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 248125342500 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 165416895000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 61271768250 u_{i_l-4, i_2} + 2196180000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-7} - 17935470000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-6} + 64567692000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 134516025000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 179354700000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 161419230000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 107612820000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 39860667000 u_{i_l-3, i_2} \\
& - 1094914800 u_{i_l-2, i_2-7} + 8941804200 u_{i_l-2, i_2-6} - 32190495120 u_{i_l-2, i_2-5} + 67063531500 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} - 89418042000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} \\
& + 80476237800 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 53650825200 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 19872703620 u_{i_l-2, i_2} + 384199200 u_{i_l-1, i_2-7} - 3137626800 u_{i_l-1, i_2-6} \\
& + 11295456480 u_{i_l-1, i_2-5} - 23532201000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} + 31376268000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 28238641200 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 18825760800 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} \\
& - 6973215480 u_{i_l-1, i_2} - 71155260 u_{i_l, i_2-7} + 581101290 u_{i_l, i_2-6} - 2091964644 u_{i_l, i_2-5} + 4358259675 u_{i_l, i_2-4} - 5811012900 u_{i_l, i_2-3} \\
& + 5229911610 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 3486607740 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 1291467969 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x I^7 \Delta x_2^7), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 2.1127294805218566912 \times 10^{-18}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1317597138604625322 \times 10^{-39}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 2.1317597138604625322 \times 10^{-39}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1317788358626601813 \times 10^{-60}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 2.1317788358626601813 \times 10^{-60}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1317788549847544603 \times 10^{-81}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 2.1317788549847544603 \times 10^{-81}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1317788550038765547 \times 10^{-102}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 7, \text{ Error:}, 2.1317788550038765547 \times 10^{-102}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1317788550038956768 \times 10^{-123}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) &= \frac{1}{592704000 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2} (27 u_{i_l-8, i_2-4} - 288 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 1512 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 6048 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 6048 u_{i_l-8, i_2+1} - 1512 u_{i_l-8, i_2+2} \\
& + 288 u_{i_l-8, i_2+3} - 27 u_{i_l-8, i_2+4} - 576 u_{i_l-7, i_2-4} + 6144 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 32256 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 129024 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 129024 u_{i_l-7, i_2+1} + 32256 u_{i_l-7, i_2+2} \\
& - 6144 u_{i_l-7, i_2+3} + 576 u_{i_l-7, i_2+4} + 6096 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4} - 65024 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 341376 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 1365504 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 1365504 u_{i_l-6, i_2+1} \\
& - 341376 u_{i_l-6, i_2+2} + 65024 u_{i_l-6, i_2+3} - 6096 u_{i_l-6, i_2+4} - 44352 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4} + 473088 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 2483712 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 9934848 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} \\
& - 9934848 u_{i_l-5, i_2+1} + 2483712 u_{i_l-5, i_2+2} - 473088 u_{i_l-5, i_2+3} + 44352 u_{i_l-5, i_2+4} + 213696 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} - 2279424 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 11966976 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} \\
& - 47867904 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 47867904 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1} - 11966976 u_{i_l-4, i_2+2} + 2279424 u_{i_l-4, i_2+3} - 213696 u_{i_l-4, i_2+4} - 665280 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} \\
& + 7096320 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 37255680 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 149022720 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 149022720 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1} + 37255680 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2} - 7096320 u_{i_l-3, i_2+3} \\
& + 665280 u_{i_l-3, i_2+4} + 1222704 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} - 13042176 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 68471424 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 273885696 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 273885696 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1} \\
& - 68471424 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2} + 13042176 u_{i_l-2, i_2+3} - 1222704 u_{i_l-2, i_2+4} + 710208 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} - 7575552 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} + 39771648 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} \\
& - 159086592 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} + 159086592 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1} - 39771648 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2} + 7575552 u_{i_l-1, i_2+3} - 710208 u_{i_l-1, i_2+4} - 2885046 u_{i_l, i_2-4} \\
& + 30773824 u_{i_l, i_2-3} - 161562576 u_{i_l, i_2-2} + 646250304 u_{i_l, i_2-1} - 646250304 u_{i_l, i_2+1} + 161562576 u_{i_l, i_2+2} - 30773824 u_{i_l, i_2+3} + 2885046 u_{i_l, i_2+4} \\
& + 710208 u_{i_l+1, i_2-4} - 7575552 u_{i_l+1, i_2-3} + 39771648 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2} - 159086592 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1} + 159086592 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - 39771648 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} \\
& + 7575552 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} - 710208 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} + 1222704 u_{i_l+2, i_2-4} - 13042176 u_{i_l+2, i_2-3} + 68471424 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2} - 273885696 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1} \\
& + 273885696 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} - 68471424 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} + 13042176 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} - 1222704 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} - 665280 u_{i_l+3, i_2-4} + 7096320 u_{i_l+3, i_2-3}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 37255680 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2} + 149022720 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} - 149022720 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} + 37255680 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} - 7096320 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} + 665280 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} \\
& + 213696 u_{i_l+4, i_2-4} - 2279424 u_{i_l+4, i_2-3} + 11966976 u_{i_l+4, i_2-2} - 47867904 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1} + 47867904 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} - 11966976 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} \\
& + 2279424 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} - 213696 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4} - 44352 u_{i_l+5, i_2-4} + 473088 u_{i_l+5, i_2-3} - 2483712 u_{i_l+5, i_2-2} + 9934848 u_{i_l+5, i_2-1} - 9934848 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} \\
& + 2483712 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} - 473088 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} + 44352 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4} + 6096 u_{i_l+6, i_2-4} - 65024 u_{i_l+6, i_2-3} + 341376 u_{i_l+6, i_2-2} - 1365504 u_{i_l+6, i_2-1} \\
& + 1365504 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} - 341376 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} + 65024 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} - 6096 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4} - 576 u_{i_l+7, i_2-4} + 6144 u_{i_l+7, i_2-3} - 32256 u_{i_l+7, i_2-2} \\
& + 129024 u_{i_l+7, i_2-1} - 129024 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} + 32256 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} - 6144 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} + 576 u_{i_l+7, i_2+4} + 27 u_{i_l+8, i_2-4} - 288 u_{i_l+8, i_2-3} + 1512 u_{i_l+8, i_2-2} \\
& - 6048 u_{i_l+8, i_2-1} + 6048 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} - 1512 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} + 288 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} - 27 u_{i_l+8, i_2+4} \Big), O(\Delta x I^8 \Delta x^2^8), \textit{Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 8, Error: 7.8127675184449526643 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 7.8127492272952540931 × 10⁻⁴⁷

Error order: 8, Error: 7.8127492272952540931 × 10⁻⁴⁷, New Error: 7.8127492272769629649 × 10⁻⁷¹

Error order: 8, Error: 7.8127492272769629649 × 10⁻⁷¹, New Error: 7.8127492272769629466 × 10⁻⁹⁵

Error order: 8, Error: 7.8127492272769629466 × 10⁻⁹⁵, New Error: 7.8127492272769629466 × 10⁻¹¹⁹

Error order: 8, Error: 7.8127492272769629466 × 10⁻¹¹⁹, New Error: 7.8127492272769629466 × 10⁻¹⁴³

"--- Derivative Order: 3 - x1=1, x2=1, x3=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{-u_{i_l, i_2, i_3} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1} + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3} - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1}}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3},$$

O(Δx1 Δx2 Δx3), Forward

Error order: 1, Error: 0.093655833831692424579, New Error: 0.000093393523974820321849

Error order: 1, Error: 0.000093393523974820321849, New Error: 9.3393262198130786882 × 10⁻⁸

Error order: 1, Error: 9.3393262198130786882 × 10⁻⁸, New Error: 9.3393261936354629649 × 10⁻¹¹

Error order: 1, Error: 9.3393261936354629649 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 9.3393261936092853493 × 10⁻¹⁴

Error order: 1, Error: 9.3393261936092853493 × 10⁻¹⁴, New Error: 9.3393261936092591716 × 10⁻¹⁷

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{-u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3} + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3}}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3},$$

O(Δx1 Δx2 Δx3), Backward

Error order: 1, Error: 0.093131755712656260658, New Error: 0.000093392999898430530868

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000093392999898430530868, *New Error:*, $9.3393261674054397093 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $9.3393261674054397093 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $9.3393261935830553260 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $9.3393261935830553260 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $9.3393261936092329416 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $9.3393261936092329416 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $9.3393261936092591192 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{8 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} \left(-27 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3} + 36 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1} - 9 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+2} + 36 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3} - 48 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 12 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 9 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3} \right. \\ \left. + 12 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 3 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 36 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3} - 48 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1} + 12 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+2} - 48 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3} + 64 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 16 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+2} \right. \\ \left. + 12 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3} - 16 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 4 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 9 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3} + 12 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1} - 3 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+2} + 12 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3} - 16 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} \right. \\ \left. + 4 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 3 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3} + 4 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+2} \right), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.00023624919018160034943, *New Error:*, $2.3550919665317548485 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.3550919665317548485 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $2.3550845746625400428 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.3550845746625400428 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $2.3550845672706789093 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.3550845672706789093 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $2.3550845672632870482 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.3550845672632870482 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $2.3550845672632796563 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{8 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} \left(u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 4 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 3 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3} - 4 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 16 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 12 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3} \right. \\ \left. + 3 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-2} - 12 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1} + 9 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3} - 4 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 16 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 12 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3} + 16 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 64 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} \right. \\ \left. + 48 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3} - 12 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2} + 48 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1} - 36 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3} + 3 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 12 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 9 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3} - 12 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-2} \right. \\ \left. + 48 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 36 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3} + 9 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-2} - 36 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1} + 27 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3} \right), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.00023476934113452166311, *New Error:*, $2.3550771680109832602 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.3550771680109832602 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $2.3550845598640192712 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.3550845598640192712 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $2.3550845672558803885 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.3550845672558803885 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $2.3550845672632722497 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.3550845672632722497 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $2.3550845672632796415 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3)$$

$$= \frac{-u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1}}{8 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3},$$

$O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2)$, Centered

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.00011775452432594223561, New Error:, $1.1775422836345994481 \times 10^{-10}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.1775422836345994481 \times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, $1.1775422836316398274 \times 10^{-16}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.1775422836316398274 \times 10^{-16}$, New Error:, $1.1775422836316398245 \times 10^{-22}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.1775422836316398245 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, $1.1775422836316398245 \times 10^{-28}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.1775422836316398245 \times 10^{-28}$, New Error:, $1.1775422836316398245 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{216 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} \left(-1331 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3} + 2178 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1} - 1089 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+2} + 242 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+3} + 2178 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3} - 3564 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1} \right. \\
+ 1782 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 396 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+3} - 1089 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3} + 1782 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 891 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 198 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+3} + 242 u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3} - 396 u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3+1} \\
+ 198 u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 44 u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3+3} + 2178 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3} - 3564 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1} + 1782 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+2} - 396 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+3} - 3564 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3} \\
+ 5832 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 2916 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 648 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+3} + 1782 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3} - 2916 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 1458 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+2} \\
- 324 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+3} - 396 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3} + 648 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 324 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 72 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3+3} - 1089 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3} + 1782 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1} \\
- 891 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+2} + 198 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+3} + 1782 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3} - 2916 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 1458 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 324 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+3} - 891 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3} \\
+ 1458 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 729 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 162 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+3} + 198 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3} - 324 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 162 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 36 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3+3} \\
+ 242 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3} - 396 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+1} + 198 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+2} - 44 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+3} - 396 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3} + 648 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 324 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+2} \\
+ 72 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+3} + 198 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3} - 324 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 162 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 36 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+3} - 44 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3} + 72 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3+1} \\
\left. - 36 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 8 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3+3} \right), O(\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3 \Delta x_3^3), Forward$$

Error order:, 3, Error:, 7.4392462093912063891 $\times 10^{-7}$, New Error:, 7.3993002417388332248 $\times 10^{-16}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 7.3993002417388332248 $\times 10^{-16}$, New Error:, 7.3992604256651128804 $\times 10^{-25}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 7.3992604256651128804 $\times 10^{-25}$, New Error:, 7.3992603858491686803 $\times 10^{-34}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 7.3992603858491686803 $\times 10^{-34}$, New Error:, 7.3992603858093527363 $\times 10^{-43}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 7.3992603858093527363 $\times 10^{-43}$, New Error:, 7.3992603858093129203 $\times 10^{-52}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{216 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} \left(-8 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3-3} + 36 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3-2} - 72 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3-1} + 44 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3} + 36 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-3} \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -162 u_{i1-3, i2-2, i3-2} + 324 u_{i1-3, i2-2, i3-1} - 198 u_{i1-3, i2-2, i3} - 72 u_{i1-3, i2-1, i3-3} + 324 u_{i1-3, i2-1, i3-2} - 648 u_{i1-3, i2-1, i3-1} + 396 u_{i1-3, i2-1, i3} \\
& + 44 u_{i1-3, i2, i3-3} - 198 u_{i1-3, i2, i3-2} + 396 u_{i1-3, i2, i3-1} - 242 u_{i1-3, i2, i3} + 36 u_{i1-2, i2-3, i3-3} - 162 u_{i1-2, i2-3, i3-2} + 324 u_{i1-2, i2-3, i3-1} \\
& - 198 u_{i1-2, i2-3, i3} - 162 u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3-3} + 729 u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3-2} - 1458 u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3-1} + 891 u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3} + 324 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3-3} - 1458 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3-2} \\
& + 2916 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3-1} - 1782 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3} - 198 u_{i1-2, i2, i3-3} + 891 u_{i1-2, i2, i3-2} - 1782 u_{i1-2, i2, i3-1} + 1089 u_{i1-2, i2, i3} - 72 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3-3} \\
& + 324 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3-2} - 648 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3-1} + 396 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3} + 324 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-3} - 1458 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-2} + 2916 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-1} - 1782 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3} \\
& - 648 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-3} + 2916 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-2} - 5832 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1} + 3564 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3} + 396 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-3} - 1782 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-2} + 3564 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-1} \\
& - 2178 u_{i1-1, i2, i3} + 44 u_{i1, i2-3, i3-3} - 198 u_{i1, i2-3, i3-2} + 396 u_{i1, i2-3, i3-1} - 242 u_{i1, i2-3, i3} - 198 u_{i1, i2-2, i3-3} + 891 u_{i1, i2-2, i3-2} - 1782 u_{i1, i2-2, i3-1} \\
& + 1089 u_{i1, i2-2, i3} + 396 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-3} - 1782 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-2} + 3564 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-1} - 2178 u_{i1, i2-1, i3} - 242 u_{i1, i2, i3-3} + 1089 u_{i1, i2, i3-2} - 2178 u_{i1, i2, i3-1} \\
& + 1331 u_{i1, i2, i3}), O(\Delta x1^3 \Delta x2^3 \Delta x3^3), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 7.3595338639001365483 \times 10^{-7}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.3992205301390919434 \times 10^{-16}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 7.3992205301390919434 \times 10^{-16}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.3992603459535131399 \times 10^{-25}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 7.3992603459535131399 \times 10^{-25}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.3992603857694570806 \times 10^{-34}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 7.3992603857694570806 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.3992603858092730247 \times 10^{-43}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 7.3992603858092730247 \times 10^{-43}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.3992603858093128406 \times 10^{-52}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x1 \partial x2 \partial x3} u(x1, x2, x3) &= \frac{1}{1728 \Delta x1 \Delta x2 \Delta x3} (-15625 u_{i1, i2, i3} + 30000 u_{i1, i2, i3+1} - 22500 u_{i1, i2, i3+2} + 10000 u_{i1, i2, i3+3} - 1875 u_{i1, i2, i3+4} \\
& + 30000 u_{i1, i2+1, i3} - 57600 u_{i1, i2+1, i3+1} + 43200 u_{i1, i2+1, i3+2} - 19200 u_{i1, i2+1, i3+3} + 3600 u_{i1, i2+1, i3+4} - 22500 u_{i1, i2+2, i3} + 43200 u_{i1, i2+2, i3+1} \\
& - 32400 u_{i1, i2+2, i3+2} + 14400 u_{i1, i2+2, i3+3} - 2700 u_{i1, i2+2, i3+4} + 10000 u_{i1, i2+3, i3} - 19200 u_{i1, i2+3, i3+1} + 14400 u_{i1, i2+3, i3+2} - 6400 u_{i1, i2+3, i3+3} \\
& + 1200 u_{i1, i2+3, i3+4} - 1875 u_{i1, i2+4, i3} + 3600 u_{i1, i2+4, i3+1} - 2700 u_{i1, i2+4, i3+2} + 1200 u_{i1, i2+4, i3+3} - 225 u_{i1, i2+4, i3+4} + 30000 u_{i1+1, i2, i3} \\
& - 57600 u_{i1+1, i2, i3+1} + 43200 u_{i1+1, i2, i3+2} - 19200 u_{i1+1, i2, i3+3} + 3600 u_{i1+1, i2, i3+4} - 57600 u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3} + 110592 u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1} \\
& - 82944 u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+2} + 36864 u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+3} - 6912 u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+4} + 43200 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3} - 82944 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3+1} + 62208 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3+2} \\
& - 27648 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3+3} + 5184 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3+4} - 19200 u_{i1+1, i2+3, i3} + 36864 u_{i1+1, i2+3, i3+1} - 27648 u_{i1+1, i2+3, i3+2} + 12288 u_{i1+1, i2+3, i3+3} \\
& - 2304 u_{i1+1, i2+3, i3+4} + 3600 u_{i1+1, i2+4, i3} - 6912 u_{i1+1, i2+4, i3+1} + 5184 u_{i1+1, i2+4, i3+2} - 2304 u_{i1+1, i2+4, i3+3} + 432 u_{i1+1, i2+4, i3+4} \\
& - 22500 u_{i1+2, i2, i3} + 43200 u_{i1+2, i2, i3+1} - 32400 u_{i1+2, i2, i3+2} + 14400 u_{i1+2, i2, i3+3} - 2700 u_{i1+2, i2, i3+4} + 43200 u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3} - 82944 u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3+1} \\
& + 62208 u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3+2} - 27648 u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3+3} + 5184 u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3+4} - 32400 u_{i1+2, i2+2, i3} + 62208 u_{i1+2, i2+2, i3+1} - 46656 u_{i1+2, i2+2, i3+2} \\
& + 20736 u_{i1+2, i2+2, i3+3} - 3888 u_{i1+2, i2+2, i3+4} + 14400 u_{i1+2, i2+3, i3} - 27648 u_{i1+2, i2+3, i3+1} + 20736 u_{i1+2, i2+3, i3+2} - 9216 u_{i1+2, i2+3, i3+3}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 1728 u_{il+2, i2+3, i3+4} - 2700 u_{il+2, i2+4, i3} + 5184 u_{il+2, i2+4, i3+1} - 3888 u_{il+2, i2+4, i3+2} + 1728 u_{il+2, i2+4, i3+3} - 324 u_{il+2, i2+4, i3+4} \\
& + 10000 u_{il+3, i2, i3} - 19200 u_{il+3, i2, i3+1} + 14400 u_{il+3, i2, i3+2} - 6400 u_{il+3, i2, i3+3} + 1200 u_{il+3, i2, i3+4} - 19200 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3} + 36864 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+1} \\
& - 27648 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+2} + 12288 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+3} - 2304 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+4} + 14400 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3} - 27648 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+1} + 20736 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+2} \\
& - 9216 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+3} + 1728 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+4} - 6400 u_{il+3, i2+3, i3} + 12288 u_{il+3, i2+3, i3+1} - 9216 u_{il+3, i2+3, i3+2} + 4096 u_{il+3, i2+3, i3+3} \\
& - 768 u_{il+3, i2+3, i3+4} + 1200 u_{il+3, i2+4, i3} - 2304 u_{il+3, i2+4, i3+1} + 1728 u_{il+3, i2+4, i3+2} - 768 u_{il+3, i2+4, i3+3} + 144 u_{il+3, i2+4, i3+4} - 1875 u_{il+4, i2, i3} \\
& + 3600 u_{il+4, i2, i3+1} - 2700 u_{il+4, i2, i3+2} + 1200 u_{il+4, i2, i3+3} - 225 u_{il+4, i2, i3+4} + 3600 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3} - 6912 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+1} + 5184 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+2} \\
& - 2304 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+3} + 432 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+4} - 2700 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3} + 5184 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+1} - 3888 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+2} + 1728 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+3} \\
& - 324 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+4} + 1200 u_{il+4, i2+3, i3} - 2304 u_{il+4, i2+3, i3+1} + 1728 u_{il+4, i2+3, i3+2} - 768 u_{il+4, i2+3, i3+3} + 144 u_{il+4, i2+3, i3+4} - 225 u_{il+4, i2+4, i3} \\
& + 432 u_{il+4, i2+4, i3+1} - 324 u_{il+4, i2+4, i3+2} + 144 u_{il+4, i2+4, i3+3} - 27 u_{il+4, i2+4, i3+4}), O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4 \Delta x_3^4), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 4, Error: $2.6778901094297171659 \times 10^{-9}$, New Error: $2.6570740687296342773 \times 10^{-21}$

Error order: 4, Error: $2.6570740687296342773 \times 10^{-21}$, New Error: $2.6570533454284740663 \times 10^{-33}$

Error order: 4, Error: $2.6570533454284740663 \times 10^{-33}$, New Error: $2.6570533247052653417 \times 10^{-45}$

Error order: 4, Error: $2.6570533247052653417 \times 10^{-45}$, New Error: $2.6570533246845421330 \times 10^{-57}$

Error order: 4, Error: $2.6570533246845421330 \times 10^{-57}$, New Error: $2.6570533246845214098 \times 10^{-69}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^3}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) &= \frac{1}{1728 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} (27 u_{il-4, i2-4, i3-4} - 144 u_{il-4, i2-4, i3-3} + 324 u_{il-4, i2-4, i3-2} - 432 u_{il-4, i2-4, i3-1} + 225 u_{il-4, i2-4, i3} \\
& - 144 u_{il-4, i2-3, i3-4} + 768 u_{il-4, i2-3, i3-3} - 1728 u_{il-4, i2-3, i3-2} + 2304 u_{il-4, i2-3, i3-1} - 1200 u_{il-4, i2-3, i3} + 324 u_{il-4, i2-2, i3-4} \\
& - 1728 u_{il-4, i2-2, i3-3} + 3888 u_{il-4, i2-2, i3-2} - 5184 u_{il-4, i2-2, i3-1} + 2700 u_{il-4, i2-2, i3} - 432 u_{il-4, i2-1, i3-4} + 2304 u_{il-4, i2-1, i3-3} \\
& - 5184 u_{il-4, i2-1, i3-2} + 6912 u_{il-4, i2-1, i3-1} - 3600 u_{il-4, i2-1, i3} + 225 u_{il-4, i2, i3-4} - 1200 u_{il-4, i2, i3-3} + 2700 u_{il-4, i2, i3-2} - 3600 u_{il-4, i2, i3-1} \\
& + 1875 u_{il-4, i2, i3} - 144 u_{il-3, i2-4, i3-4} + 768 u_{il-3, i2-4, i3-3} - 1728 u_{il-3, i2-4, i3-2} + 2304 u_{il-3, i2-4, i3-1} - 1200 u_{il-3, i2-4, i3} + 768 u_{il-3, i2-3, i3-4} \\
& - 4096 u_{il-3, i2-3, i3-3} + 9216 u_{il-3, i2-3, i3-2} - 12288 u_{il-3, i2-3, i3-1} + 6400 u_{il-3, i2-3, i3} - 1728 u_{il-3, i2-2, i3-4} + 9216 u_{il-3, i2-2, i3-3} \\
& - 20736 u_{il-3, i2-2, i3-2} + 27648 u_{il-3, i2-2, i3-1} - 14400 u_{il-3, i2-2, i3} + 2304 u_{il-3, i2-1, i3-4} - 12288 u_{il-3, i2-1, i3-3} + 27648 u_{il-3, i2-1, i3-2} \\
& - 36864 u_{il-3, i2-1, i3-1} + 19200 u_{il-3, i2-1, i3} - 1200 u_{il-3, i2, i3-4} + 6400 u_{il-3, i2, i3-3} - 14400 u_{il-3, i2, i3-2} + 19200 u_{il-3, i2, i3-1} - 10000 u_{il-3, i2, i3} \\
& + 324 u_{il-2, i2-4, i3-4} - 1728 u_{il-2, i2-4, i3-3} + 3888 u_{il-2, i2-4, i3-2} - 5184 u_{il-2, i2-4, i3-1} + 2700 u_{il-2, i2-4, i3} - 1728 u_{il-2, i2-3, i3-4} \\
& + 9216 u_{il-2, i2-3, i3-3} - 20736 u_{il-2, i2-3, i3-2} + 27648 u_{il-2, i2-3, i3-1} - 14400 u_{il-2, i2-3, i3} + 3888 u_{il-2, i2-2, i3-4} - 20736 u_{il-2, i2-2, i3-3} \\
& + 46656 u_{il-2, i2-2, i3-2} - 62208 u_{il-2, i2-2, i3-1} + 32400 u_{il-2, i2-2, i3} - 5184 u_{il-2, i2-1, i3-4} + 27648 u_{il-2, i2-1, i3-3} - 62208 u_{il-2, i2-1, i3-2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 82944 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3-1} - 43200 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3} + 2700 u_{i1-2, i2, i3-4} - 14400 u_{i1-2, i2, i3-3} + 32400 u_{i1-2, i2, i3-2} - 43200 u_{i1-2, i2, i3-1} + 22500 u_{i1-2, i2, i3} \\
& - 432 u_{i1-1, i2-4, i3-4} + 2304 u_{i1-1, i2-4, i3-3} - 5184 u_{i1-1, i2-4, i3-2} + 6912 u_{i1-1, i2-4, i3-1} - 3600 u_{i1-1, i2-4, i3} + 2304 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3-4} \\
& - 12288 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3-3} + 27648 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3-2} - 36864 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3-1} + 19200 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3} - 5184 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-4} + 27648 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-3} \\
& - 62208 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-2} + 82944 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-1} - 43200 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3} + 6912 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-4} - 36864 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-3} + 82944 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-2} \\
& - 110592 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1} + 57600 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3} - 3600 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-4} + 19200 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-3} - 43200 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-2} + 57600 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-1} - 30000 u_{i1-1, i2, i3} \\
& + 225 u_{i1, i2-4, i3-4} - 1200 u_{i1, i2-4, i3-3} + 2700 u_{i1, i2-4, i3-2} - 3600 u_{i1, i2-4, i3-1} + 1875 u_{i1, i2-4, i3} - 1200 u_{i1, i2-3, i3-4} + 6400 u_{i1, i2-3, i3-3} \\
& - 14400 u_{i1, i2-3, i3-2} + 19200 u_{i1, i2-3, i3-1} - 10000 u_{i1, i2-3, i3} + 2700 u_{i1, i2-2, i3-4} - 14400 u_{i1, i2-2, i3-3} + 32400 u_{i1, i2-2, i3-2} - 43200 u_{i1, i2-2, i3-1} \\
& + 22500 u_{i1, i2-2, i3} - 3600 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-4} + 19200 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-3} - 43200 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-2} + 57600 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-1} - 30000 u_{i1, i2-1, i3} + 1875 u_{i1, i2, i3-4} \\
& - 10000 u_{i1, i2, i3-3} + 22500 u_{i1, i2, i3-2} - 30000 u_{i1, i2, i3-1} + 15625 u_{i1, i2, i3}), O(\Delta x1^4 \Delta x2^4 \Delta x3^4), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 4, Error:, 2.6364015971429494181 $\times 10^{-9}$, New Error:, 2.6570325808244641830 $\times 10^{-21}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, 2.6570325808244641830 $\times 10^{-21}$, New Error:, 2.6570533039405688969 $\times 10^{-33}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, 2.6570533039405688969 $\times 10^{-33}$, New Error:, 2.6570533246637774365 $\times 10^{-45}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, 2.6570533246637774365 $\times 10^{-45}$, New Error:, 2.6570533246845006451 $\times 10^{-57}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, 2.6570533246845006451 $\times 10^{-57}$, New Error:, 2.6570533246845213683 $\times 10^{-69}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x1 \partial x2 \partial x3} u(x1, x2, x3) &= \frac{1}{1728 \Delta x1 \Delta x2 \Delta x3} (u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3-2} - 8 u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3-1} + 8 u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3+1} - u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3+2} - 8 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3-2} \\
& + 64 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3-1} - 64 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3+1} + 8 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3+2} + 8 u_{i1-2, i2+1, i3-2} - 64 u_{i1-2, i2+1, i3-1} + 64 u_{i1-2, i2+1, i3+1} - 8 u_{i1-2, i2+1, i3+2} \\
& - u_{i1-2, i2+2, i3-2} + 8 u_{i1-2, i2+2, i3-1} - 8 u_{i1-2, i2+2, i3+1} + u_{i1-2, i2+2, i3+2} - 8 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-2} + 64 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-1} - 64 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3+1} \\
& + 8 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3+2} + 64 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-2} - 512 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1} + 512 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+1} - 64 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+2} - 64 u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-2} + 512 u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1} \\
& - 512 u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+1} + 64 u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+2} + 8 u_{i1-1, i2+2, i3-2} - 64 u_{i1-1, i2+2, i3-1} + 64 u_{i1-1, i2+2, i3+1} - 8 u_{i1-1, i2+2, i3+2} + 8 u_{i1+1, i2-2, i3-2} \\
& - 64 u_{i1+1, i2-2, i3-1} + 64 u_{i1+1, i2-2, i3+1} - 8 u_{i1+1, i2-2, i3+2} - 64 u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-2} + 512 u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1} - 512 u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+1} + 64 u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+2} \\
& + 64 u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-2} - 512 u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1} + 512 u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1} - 64 u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+2} - 8 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3-2} + 64 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3-1} - 64 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3+1} \\
& + 8 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3+2} - u_{i1+2, i2-2, i3-2} + 8 u_{i1+2, i2-2, i3-1} - 8 u_{i1+2, i2-2, i3+1} + u_{i1+2, i2-2, i3+2} + 8 u_{i1+2, i2-1, i3-2} - 64 u_{i1+2, i2-1, i3-1} \\
& + 64 u_{i1+2, i2-1, i3+1} - 8 u_{i1+2, i2-1, i3+2} - 8 u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3-2} + 64 u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3-1} - 64 u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3+1} + 8 u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3+2} + u_{i1+2, i2+2, i3-2} \\
& - 8 u_{i1+2, i2+2, i3-1} + 8 u_{i1+2, i2+2, i3+1} - u_{i1+2, i2+2, i3+2}), O(\Delta x1^4 \Delta x2^4 \Delta x3^4), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 4, Error:, 4.4284340703553353963 $\times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, 4.4284222078193981922 $\times 10^{-22}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.4284222078193981922 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $4.4284222078075356603 \times 10^{-34}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.4284222078075356603 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $4.4284222078075356484 \times 10^{-46}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.4284222078075356484 \times 10^{-46}$, *New Error:*, $4.4284222078075356484 \times 10^{-58}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.4284222078075356484 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $4.4284222078075356484 \times 10^{-70}$

"--- Derivative Order: 4 - x1=4 ---"

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI} - 4 u_{iI+1} + 6 u_{iI+2} - 4 u_{iI+3} + u_{iI+4}}{\Delta xI^4}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.010660980955083245519, *New Error:*, 0.000010637965726563938134
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000010637965726563938134, *New Error:*, $1.0637942746661328955 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.0637942746661328955 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723681461629 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.0637942723681461629 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723658481762 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.0637942723658481762 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723658458782 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-4} - 4 u_{iI-3} + 6 u_{iI-2} - 4 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI}}{\Delta xI^4}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.010614975129108900074, *New Error:*, 0.000010637919720823616172
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000010637919720823616172, *New Error:*, $1.0637942700655588633 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.0637942700655588633 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723635455889 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.0637942723635455889 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723658435756 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.0637942723658435756 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.0637942723658458736 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{81 u_{iI} - 432 u_{iI+1} + 972 u_{iI+2} - 1200 u_{iI+3} + 886 u_{iI+4} - 400 u_{iI+5} + 108 u_{iI+6} - 16 u_{iI+7} + u_{iI+8}}{16 \Delta xI^4}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000014176794913308828061, *New Error:*, $1.4155633597759226837 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.4155633597759226837 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612427922185909 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.4155612427922185909 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612406752340417 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.4155612406752340417 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.4155612406731170571 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.4155612406731170571 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $1.4155612406731149401 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-8} - 16 u_{iI-7} + 108 u_{iI-6} - 400 u_{iI-5} + 886 u_{iI-4} - 1200 u_{iI-3} + 972 u_{iI-2} - 432 u_{iI-1} + 81 u_{iI}}{16 \Delta xI^4}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000014134412980945071004, New Error:, $1.4155591215686152932 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.4155591215686152932 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $1.4155612385540112835 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.4155612385540112835 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $1.4155612406709958343 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.4155612406709958343 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $1.4155612406731128189 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.4155612406731128189 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $1.4155612406731149359 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-4} - 4 u_{iI-2} + 6 u_{iI} - 4 u_{iI+2} + u_{iI+4}}{16 \Delta xI^4}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $7.0778146628672612348 \times 10^{-6}$, New Error:, $7.0778062033740341856 \times 10^{-12}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $7.0778062033740341856 \times 10^{-12}$, New Error:, $7.0778062033655746985 \times 10^{-18}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $7.0778062033655746985 \times 10^{-18}$, New Error:, $7.0778062033655746900 \times 10^{-24}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $7.0778062033655746900 \times 10^{-24}$, New Error:, $7.0778062033655746900 \times 10^{-30}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $7.0778062033655746900 \times 10^{-30}$, New Error:, $7.0778062033655746900 \times 10^{-36}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1296 \Delta xI^4} (14641 u_{iI} - 95832 u_{iI+1} + 283140 u_{iI+2} - 502480 u_{iI+3} + 600966 u_{iI+4} - 514080 u_{iI+5} + 324636 u_{iI+6} - 153360 u_{iI+7}$$

+ 54081 u_{iI+8} - 13960 u_{iI+9} + 2520 u_{iI+10} - 288 u_{iI+11} + 16 u_{iI+12}), O(\Delta xI^3), Forward

Error order:, 3, Error:, $2.1241864001628534660 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $2.1191087294066775306 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $2.1191087294066775306 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $2.1191036587779652524 \times 10^{-26}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $2.1191036587779652524 \times 10^{-26}$, New Error:, $2.1191036537073435686 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $2.1191036537073435686 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $2.1191036537022729470 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $2.1191036537022729470 \times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, $2.1191036537022678763 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1296 \Delta xI^4} (16 u_{iI-12} - 288 u_{iI-11} + 2520 u_{iI-10} - 13960 u_{iI-9} + 54081 u_{iI-8} - 153360 u_{iI-7} + 324636 u_{iI-6} - 514080 u_{iI-5}$$

$$+ 600966 u_{i_{l-4}} - 502480 u_{i_{l-3}} + 283140 u_{i_{l-2}} - 95832 u_{i_{l-1}} + 14641 u_{i_l}), O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Backward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 2.1140349783316177039 \times 10^{-8}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1190985780119292292 \times 10^{-17}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 2.1190985780119292292 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1191036486265705042 \times 10^{-26}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 2.1191036486265705042 \times 10^{-26}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1191036536971921739 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 2.1191036536971921739 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1191036537022627956 \times 10^{-44}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 2.1191036537022627956 \times 10^{-44}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.1191036537022678662 \times 10^{-53}$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dx I^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{20736 \Delta x I^4} (390625 u_{i_l} - 3000000 u_{i_{l+1}} + 10890000 u_{i_{l+2}} - 25019200 u_{i_{l+3}} + 40999116 u_{i_{l+4}} - 51046848 u_{i_{l+5}} + 50091792 u_{i_{l+6}}$$

$$- 39587904 u_{i_{l+7}} + 25495830 u_{i_{l+8}} - 13436992 u_{i_{l+9}} + 5779632 u_{i_{l+10}} - 2008512 u_{i_{l+11}} + 552940 u_{i_{l+12}} - 116544 u_{i_{l+13}} + 17712 u_{i_{l+14}}$$

$$- 1728 u_{i_{l+15}} + 81 u_{i_{l+16}}), O(\Delta x I^4), \text{ Forward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 3.3950759551228487808 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.3838095062595131898 \times 10^{-23}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 3.3838095062595131898 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.3837982606815929271 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 3.3837982606815929271 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.3837982494360358498 \times 10^{-47}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 3.3837982494360358498 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.3837982494247902928 \times 10^{-59}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 3.3837982494247902928 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.3837982494247790472 \times 10^{-71}$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dx I^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{20736 \Delta x I^4} (81 u_{i_{l-16}} - 1728 u_{i_{l-15}} + 17712 u_{i_{l-14}} - 116544 u_{i_{l-13}} + 552940 u_{i_{l-12}} - 2008512 u_{i_{l-11}} + 5779632 u_{i_{l-10}}$$

$$- 13436992 u_{i_{l-9}} + 25495830 u_{i_{l-8}} - 39587904 u_{i_{l-7}} + 50091792 u_{i_{l-6}} - 51046848 u_{i_{l-5}} + 40999116 u_{i_{l-4}} - 25019200 u_{i_{l-3}} + 10890000 u_{i_{l-2}}$$

$$- 3000000 u_{i_{l-1}} + 390625 u_{i_l}), O(\Delta x I^4), \text{ Backward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 3.3725622713227175890 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.3837869926317724499 \times 10^{-23}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 3.3837869926317724499 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.3837982381679651865 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 3.3837982381679651865 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.3837982494135222221 \times 10^{-47}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 3.3837982494135222221 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.3837982494247677791 \times 10^{-59}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 3.3837982494247677791 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.3837982494247790247 \times 10^{-71}$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{20736 \Delta xI^4} (u_{iI-8} - 32 u_{iI-7} + 384 u_{iI-6} - 2016 u_{iI-5} + 3324 u_{iI-4} + 6240 u_{iI-3} - 16768 u_{iI-2} - 4192 u_{iI-1} + 26118 u_{iI} - 4192 u_{iI+1} - 16768 u_{iI+2} + 6240 u_{iI+3} + 3324 u_{iI+4} - 2016 u_{iI+5} + 384 u_{iI+6} - 32 u_{iI+7} + u_{iI+8}), O(\Delta xI^4), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $5.6396664238815346853 \times 10^{-12}$, New Error:, $5.6396637490439732373 \times 10^{-24}$
 Error order:, 4, Error:, $5.6396637490439732373 \times 10^{-24}$, New Error:, $5.6396637490412983959 \times 10^{-36}$
 Error order:, 4, Error:, $5.6396637490412983959 \times 10^{-36}$, New Error:, $5.6396637490412983932 \times 10^{-48}$
 Error order:, 4, Error:, $5.6396637490412983932 \times 10^{-48}$, New Error:, $5.6396637490412983932 \times 10^{-60}$
 Error order:, 4, Error:, $5.6396637490412983932 \times 10^{-60}$, New Error:, $5.6396637490412983932 \times 10^{-72}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta xI^4} (352275361 u_{iI} - 3085623600 u_{iI+1} + 13220883600 u_{iI+2} - 37123602400 u_{iI+3} + 76908345900 u_{iI+4} - 125084734944 u_{iI+5} + 165660010800 u_{iI+6} - 182778760800 u_{iI+7} + 170442040950 u_{iI+8} - 135487835200 u_{iI+9} + 92195086416 u_{iI+10} - 53724400800 u_{iI+11} + 26723308300 u_{iI+12} - 11266087200 u_{iI+13} + 3978445200 u_{iI+14} - 1156006944 u_{iI+15} + 269154225 u_{iI+16} - 48243600 u_{iI+17} + 6242400 u_{iI+18} - 518400 u_{iI+19} + 20736 u_{iI+20}), O(\Delta xI^5), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 5, Error:, $5.6525366849614688905 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $5.6284310088238304272 \times 10^{-29}$
 Error order:, 5, Error:, $5.6284310088238304272 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $5.6284069592445533506 \times 10^{-44}$
 Error order:, 5, Error:, $5.6284069592445533506 \times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, $5.6284069351950300771 \times 10^{-59}$
 Error order:, 5, Error:, $5.6284069351950300771 \times 10^{-59}$, New Error:, $5.6284069351709805539 \times 10^{-74}$
 Error order:, 5, Error:, $5.6284069351709805539 \times 10^{-74}$, New Error:, $5.6284069351709565043 \times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta xI^4} (20736 u_{iI-20} - 518400 u_{iI-19} + 6242400 u_{iI-18} - 48243600 u_{iI-17} + 269154225 u_{iI-16} - 1156006944 u_{iI-15} + 3978445200 u_{iI-14} - 11266087200 u_{iI-13} + 26723308300 u_{iI-12} - 53724400800 u_{iI-11} + 92195086416 u_{iI-10} - 135487835200 u_{iI-9} + 170442040950 u_{iI-8} - 182778760800 u_{iI-7} + 165660010800 u_{iI-6} - 125084734944 u_{iI-5} + 76908345900 u_{iI-4} - 37123602400 u_{iI-3} + 13220883600 u_{iI-2} - 3085623600 u_{iI-1} + 352275361 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^5), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 5, Error:, $5.6043893048402412230 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $5.6283828616302017467 \times 10^{-29}$
 Error order:, 5, Error:, $5.6283828616302017467 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $5.6284069110973597221 \times 10^{-44}$
 Error order:, 5, Error:, $5.6284069110973597221 \times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, $5.6284069351468828835 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $5.6284069351468828835 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $5.6284069351709324067 \times 10^{-74}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $5.6284069351709324067 \times 10^{-74}$, *New Error:*, $5.6284069351709564562 \times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta xI^4} (466948881 u_{iI} - 4574193120 u_{iI+1} + 22520899800 u_{iI+2} - 74524060800 u_{iI+3} + 186126797700 u_{iI+4} - 372616386624 u_{iI+5} + 619595639280 u_{iI+6} - 875365444800 u_{iI+7} + 1066566054150 u_{iI+8} - 1131808425600 u_{iI+9} + 1052528550336 u_{iI+10} - 860664669120 u_{iI+11} + 619448763100 u_{iI+12} - 391960526400 u_{iI+13} + 217328655600 u_{iI+14} - 105009173824 u_{iI+15} + 43860833505 u_{iI+16} - 15662916000 u_{iI+17} + 4711789800 u_{iI+18} - 1170475200 u_{iI+19} + 233576856 u_{iI+20} - 35969920 u_{iI+21} + 4010400 u_{iI+22} - 288000 u_{iI+23} + 10000 u_{iI+24}), O(\Delta xI^6), \textit{Forward}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $9.6800343877733076933 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $9.6294891794865658484 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $9.6294891794865658484 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $9.6294387761524596417 \times 10^{-53}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $9.6294387761524596417 \times 10^{-53}$, *New Error:*, $9.6294387257492671281 \times 10^{-71}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $9.6294387257492671281 \times 10^{-71}$, *New Error:*, $9.6294387256988639357 \times 10^{-89}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $9.6294387256988639357 \times 10^{-89}$, *New Error:*, $9.6294387256988135325 \times 10^{-107}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta xI^4} (10000 u_{iI-24} - 288000 u_{iI-23} + 4010400 u_{iI-22} - 35969920 u_{iI-21} + 233576856 u_{iI-20} - 1170475200 u_{iI-19} + 4711789800 u_{iI-18} - 15662916000 u_{iI-17} + 43860833505 u_{iI-16} - 105009173824 u_{iI-15} + 217328655600 u_{iI-14} - 391960526400 u_{iI-13} + 619448763100 u_{iI-12} - 860664669120 u_{iI-11} + 1052528550336 u_{iI-10} - 1131808425600 u_{iI-9} + 1066566054150 u_{iI-8} - 875365444800 u_{iI-7} + 619595639280 u_{iI-6} - 372616386624 u_{iI-5} + 186126797700 u_{iI-4} - 74524060800 u_{iI-3} + 22520899800 u_{iI-2} - 4574193120 u_{iI-1} + 466948881 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^6), \textit{Backward}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $9.5791265329091143851 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $9.6293882721945295195 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $9.6293882721945295195 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $9.6294386752451676059 \times 10^{-53}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $9.6294386752451676059 \times 10^{-53}$, *New Error:*, $9.6294387256483598361 \times 10^{-71}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $9.6294387256483598361 \times 10^{-71}$, *New Error:*, $9.6294387256987630284 \times 10^{-89}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $9.6294387256987630284 \times 10^{-89}$, *New Error:*, $9.6294387256988134316 \times 10^{-107}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta xI^4} (u_{iI-12} - 36 u_{iI-11} + 666 u_{iI-10} - 7776 u_{iI-9} + 62271 u_{iI-8} - 345024 u_{iI-7} + 1279634 u_{iI-6} - 2698164 u_{iI-5} + 935739 u_{iI-4} + 10242936 u_{iI-3} - 16272684 u_{iI-2} - 7191936 u_{iI-1} + 27988746 u_{iI} - 7191936 u_{iI+1} - 16272684 u_{iI+2} + 10242936 u_{iI+3} + 935739 u_{iI+4} - 2698164 u_{iI+5} + 1279634 u_{iI+6} - 345024 u_{iI+7} + 62271 u_{iI+8} - 7776 u_{iI+9} + 666 u_{iI+10} - 36 u_{iI+11} + u_{iI+12}), O(\Delta xI^6),$$

Centered

Error order: 6, Error: 4.8147230926982427893 × 10⁻¹⁸, New Error: 4.8147193628531365885 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order: 6, Error: 4.8147193628531365885 × 10⁻³⁶, New Error: 4.8147193628494067448 × 10⁻⁵⁴
Error order: 6, Error: 4.8147193628494067448 × 10⁻⁵⁴, New Error: 4.8147193628494067410 × 10⁻⁷²
Error order: 6, Error: 4.8147193628494067410 × 10⁻⁷², New Error: 4.8147193628494067410 × 10⁻⁹⁰
Error order: 6, Error: 4.8147193628494067410 × 10⁻⁹⁰, New Error: 4.8147193628494067410 × 10⁻¹⁰⁸

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{31116960000 \Delta xI^4} (1406408618241 u_{iI} - 15187663315440 u_{iI+1} + 84285255506760 u_{iI+2} - 320519527297200 u_{iI+3} + 935222027184900 u_{iI+4} - 2219333541423264 u_{iI+5} + 4433644411756560 u_{iI+6} - 7623669245581440 u_{iI+7} + 11452634468418150 u_{iI+8} - 15185026178128800 u_{iI+9} + 17894027960856096 u_{iI+10} - 18825434058443040 u_{iI+11} + 17727883822391260 u_{iI+12} - 14958175758960000 u_{iI+13} + 11303913659742000 u_{iI+14} - 7637482139164864 u_{iI+15} + 4599612943024785 u_{iI+16} - 2458357762800240 u_{iI+17} + 1159343613720600 u_{iI+18} - 478879146337200 u_{iI+19} + 171659259691416 u_{iI+20} - 52779161638240 u_{iI+21} + 13711799156160 u_{iI+22} - 2950828372800 u_{iI+23} + 511832851600 u_{iI+24} - 68751312000 u_{iI+25} + 6710256000 u_{iI+26} - 423360000 u_{iI+27} + 12960000 u_{iI+28}), O(\Delta xI^7),$$

Forward

Error order: 7, Error: 1.6922662479423860612 × 10⁻¹⁹, New Error: 1.6817986442032645202 × 10⁻⁴⁰
Error order: 7, Error: 1.6817986442032645202 × 10⁻⁴⁰, New Error: 1.6817882110396729627 × 10⁻⁶¹
Error order: 7, Error: 1.6817882110396729627 × 10⁻⁶¹, New Error: 1.6817882006065437318 × 10⁻⁸²
Error order: 7, Error: 1.6817882006065437318 × 10⁻⁸², New Error: 1.6817882005961106026 × 10⁻¹⁰³
Error order: 7, Error: 1.6817882005961106026 × 10⁻¹⁰³, New Error: 1.6817882005961001695 × 10⁻¹²⁴

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{31116960000 \Delta xI^4} (12960000 u_{iI-28} - 423360000 u_{iI-27} + 6710256000 u_{iI-26} - 68751312000 u_{iI-25} + 511832851600 u_{iI-24} - 2950828372800 u_{iI-23} + 13711799156160 u_{iI-22} - 52779161638240 u_{iI-21} + 171659259691416 u_{iI-20} - 478879146337200 u_{iI-19} + 1159343613720600 u_{iI-18} - 2458357762800240 u_{iI-17} + 4599612943024785 u_{iI-16} - 7637482139164864 u_{iI-15} + 11303913659742000 u_{iI-14}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 14958175758960000 u_{i_l-13} + 17727883822391260 u_{i_l-12} - 18825434058443040 u_{i_l-11} + 17894027960856096 u_{i_l-10} - 15185026178128800 u_{i_l-9} \\
& + 11452634468418150 u_{i_l-8} - 7623669245581440 u_{i_l-7} + 4433644411756560 u_{i_l-6} - 2219333541423264 u_{i_l-5} + 935222027184900 u_{i_l-4} \\
& - 320519527297200 u_{i_l-3} + 84285255506760 u_{i_l-2} - 15187663315440 u_{i_l-1} + 1406408618241 u_{i_l}), O(\Delta x I^7), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 7, Error: 1.6713789435376496881 × 10⁻¹⁹, New Error: 1.6817777570577257981 × 10⁻⁴⁰

Error order: 7, Error: 1.6817777570577257981 × 10⁻⁴⁰, New Error: 1.6817881901525274242 × 10⁻⁶¹

Error order: 7, Error: 1.6817881901525274242 × 10⁻⁶¹, New Error: 1.6817882005856565863 × 10⁻⁸²

Error order: 7, Error: 1.6817882005856565863 × 10⁻⁸², New Error: 1.6817882005960897155 × 10⁻¹⁰³

Error order: 7, Error: 1.6817882005960897155 × 10⁻¹⁰³, New Error: 1.6817882005961001486 × 10⁻¹²⁴

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^4}{dx I^4} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{497871360000 \Delta x I^4} (81 u_{i_l-16} - 3456 u_{i_l-15} + 73440 u_{i_l-14} - 1046400 u_{i_l-13} + 11088256 u_{i_l-12} - 91426944 u_{i_l-11} + 600545568 u_{i_l-10} \\
& - 3159665280 u_{i_l-9} + 13179136956 u_{i_l-8} - 42308145024 u_{i_l-7} + 96249609056 u_{i_l-6} - 117801591168 u_{i_l-5} - 81147556224 u_{i_l-4} \\
& + 640243771776 u_{i_l-3} - 767938868064 u_{i_l-2} - 476881893504 u_{i_l-1} + 1478091941862 u_{i_l} - 476881893504 u_{i_l+1} - 767938868064 u_{i_l+2} \\
& + 640243771776 u_{i_l+3} - 81147556224 u_{i_l+4} - 117801591168 u_{i_l+5} + 96249609056 u_{i_l+6} - 42308145024 u_{i_l+7} + 13179136956 u_{i_l+8} \\
& - 3159665280 u_{i_l+9} + 600545568 u_{i_l+10} - 91426944 u_{i_l+11} + 11088256 u_{i_l+12} - 1046400 u_{i_l+13} + 73440 u_{i_l+14} - 3456 u_{i_l+15} + 81 u_{i_l+16}),
\end{aligned}$$

O(ΔxI⁸), Centered

Error order: 8, Error: 4.2626873946287944017 × 10⁻²⁴, New Error: 4.2626827629767196282 × 10⁻⁴⁸

Error order: 8, Error: 4.2626827629767196282 × 10⁻⁴⁸, New Error: 4.2626827629720879786 × 10⁻⁷²

Error order: 8, Error: 4.2626827629720879786 × 10⁻⁷², New Error: 4.2626827629720879740 × 10⁻⁹⁶

Error order: 8, Error: 4.2626827629720879740 × 10⁻⁹⁶, New Error: 4.2626827629720879740 × 10⁻¹²⁰

Error order: 8, Error: 4.2626827629720879740 × 10⁻¹²⁰, New Error: 4.2626827629720879740 × 10⁻¹⁴⁴

"--- Derivative Order: 4 - x1=3, x2=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x I^3 \partial x 2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{u_{i_l, i_2} - u_{i_l, i_2+1} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2} + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} + 3 u_{i_l+2, i_2} - 3 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} - u_{i_l+3, i_2} + u_{i_l+3, i_2+1}}{\Delta x I^3 \Delta x 2}, O(\Delta x I \Delta x 2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order: 1, Error: 0.031995493819914674889, New Error: 0.000031917598634490678332

Error order: 1, Error: 0.000031917598634490678332, New Error: 3.1917520874368856123 × 10⁻⁸

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1917520874368856123 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.1917520796608869179 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1917520796608869179 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.1917520796531109192 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1917520796531109192 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $3.1917520796531031432 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - u_{i_1-3, i_2} - 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2} + 3 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 3 u_{i_1-1, i_2} - u_{i_1, i_2-1} + u_{i_1, i_2}}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2}, O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.031839817800426108011, *New Error:*, 0.000031917442958841411232
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000031917442958841411232, *New Error:*, $3.1917520718693206856 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1917520718693206856 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.1917520796453193530 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1917520796453193530 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.1917520796530953517 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1917520796530953517 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $3.1917520796531031277 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{16 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2} (81 u_{i_1, i_2} - 108 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 27 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 324 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 432 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 108 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 513 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 684 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 171 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 408 u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 544 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 136 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + 171 u_{i_1+4, i_2} - 228 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} + 57 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} - 36 u_{i_1+5, i_2} + 48 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} - 12 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} + 3 u_{i_1+6, i_2} - 4 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} + u_{i_1+6, i_2+2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000049614454435113761038, *New Error:*, $4.9524601188554914166 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.9524601188554914166 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.9524511318793975045 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.9524511318793975045 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $4.9524511228924197921 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.9524511228924197921 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $4.9524511228834328144 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.9524511228834328144 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $4.9524511228834238274 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{16 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2} (u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 4 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 3 u_{i_1-6, i_2} - 12 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 48 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 36 u_{i_1-5, i_2} + 57 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 228 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 171 u_{i_1-4, i_2} - 136 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 544 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 408 u_{i_1-3, i_2} + 171 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 684 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 513 u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 108 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 432 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 324 u_{i_1-1, i_2} + 27 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 108 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 81 u_{i_1, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000049434535620304199470, *New Error:*, $4.9524421269081161246 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.9524421269081161246 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.9524511138874501291 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.9524511138874501291 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $4.9524511228744278447 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $4.9524511228744278447 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $4.9524511228834148224 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $4.9524511228834148224 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $4.9524511228834238094 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - u_{i_l-3, i_2+1} - 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} + 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1} + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} + u_{i_l+3, i_2+1}}{16 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2}, O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2),$$

Centered

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000024762293696890760626, New Error:, $2.4762255614455201531 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.4762255614455201531 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $2.4762255614417119130 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.4762255614417119130 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $2.4762255614417119092 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.4762255614417119092 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $2.4762255614417119092 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.4762255614417119092 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $2.4762255614417119092 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{1296 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2} (14641 u_{i_l, i_2} - 23958 u_{i_l, i_2+1} + 11979 u_{i_l, i_2+2} - 2662 u_{i_l, i_2+3} - 71874 u_{i_l+1, i_2} + 117612 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} \\ & - 58806 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} + 13068 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} + 153549 u_{i_l+2, i_2} - 251262 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 125631 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 27918 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} - 189750 u_{i_l+3, i_2} \\ & + 310500 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - 155250 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 34500 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} + 151767 u_{i_l+4, i_2} - 248346 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} + 124173 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} - 27594 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} \\ & - 82566 u_{i_l+5, i_2} + 135108 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} - 67554 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} + 15012 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} + 30855 u_{i_l+6, i_2} - 50490 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} + 25245 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} - 5610 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} \\ & - 7722 u_{i_l+7, i_2} + 12636 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} - 6318 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} + 1404 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} + 1188 u_{i_l+8, i_2} - 1944 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} + 972 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} - 216 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} \\ & - 88 u_{i_l+9, i_2} + 144 u_{i_l+9, i_2+1} - 72 u_{i_l+9, i_2+2} + 16 u_{i_l+9, i_2+3}), O(\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3), \text{ Forward} \end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $9.0232491824764327614 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $8.9960009135839444473 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $8.9960009135839444473 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $8.9959737149048153547 \times 10^{-26}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $8.9959737149048153547 \times 10^{-26}$, New Error:, $8.9959736877061857094 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $8.9959736877061857094 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $8.9959736876789870798 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $8.9959736876789870798 \times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, $8.9959736876789598812 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{1296 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2} (16 u_{i_l-9, i_2-3} - 72 u_{i_l-9, i_2-2} + 144 u_{i_l-9, i_2-1} - 88 u_{i_l-9, i_2} - 216 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 972 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 1944 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} \\ & + 1188 u_{i_l-8, i_2} + 1404 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 6318 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 12636 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 7722 u_{i_l-7, i_2} - 5610 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 25245 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 50490 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 30855 u_{i_l-6, i_2} + 15012 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 67554 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 135108 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 82566 u_{i_l-5, i_2} - 27594 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 124173 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} \\
& - 248346 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 151767 u_{i_l-4, i_2} + 34500 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 155250 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 310500 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 189750 u_{i_l-3, i_2} - 27918 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} \\
& + 125631 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 251262 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 153549 u_{i_l-2, i_2} + 13068 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 58806 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 117612 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 71874 u_{i_l-1, i_2} - 2662 u_{i_l, i_2-3} \\
& + 11979 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 23958 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 14641 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x l^3 \Delta x 2^3), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 8.9687972600031673518 \times 10^{-8}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.9959464618730418016 \times 10^{-17}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 8.9959464618730418016 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.9959736604531044523 \times 10^{-26}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 8.9959736604531044523 \times 10^{-26}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.9959736876517339985 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 8.9959736876517339985 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.9959736876789326281 \times 10^{-44}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 8.9959736876789326281 \times 10^{-44}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.9959736876789598267 \times 10^{-53}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x l^3 \partial x 2} u(x l, x 2) &= \frac{1}{20736 \Delta x l^3 \Delta x 2} (390625 u_{i_l, i_2} - 750000 u_{i_l, i_2+1} + 562500 u_{i_l, i_2+2} - 250000 u_{i_l, i_2+3} + 46875 u_{i_l, i_2+4} - 2250000 u_{i_l+1, i_2} \\
& + 4320000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - 3240000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} + 1440000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} - 270000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} + 6007500 u_{i_l+2, i_2} - 11534400 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 8650800 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} \\
& - 3844800 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} + 720900 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} - 9994800 u_{i_l+3, i_2} + 19190016 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - 14392512 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 6396672 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} - 1199376 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} \\
& + 11671425 u_{i_l+4, i_2} - 22409136 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} + 16806852 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} - 7469712 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} + 1400571 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4} - 10130400 u_{i_l+5, i_2} \\
& + 19450368 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} - 14587776 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} + 6483456 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} - 1215648 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4} + 6717000 u_{i_l+6, i_2} - 12896640 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} \\
& + 9672480 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} - 4298880 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} + 806040 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4} - 3434400 u_{i_l+7, i_2} + 6594048 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} - 4945536 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} + 2198016 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} \\
& - 412128 u_{i_l+7, i_2+4} + 1345275 u_{i_l+8, i_2} - 2582928 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} + 1937196 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} - 860976 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} + 161433 u_{i_l+8, i_2+4} - 394000 u_{i_l+9, i_2} \\
& + 756480 u_{i_l+9, i_2+1} - 567360 u_{i_l+9, i_2+2} + 252160 u_{i_l+9, i_2+3} - 47280 u_{i_l+9, i_2+4} + 81900 u_{i_l+10, i_2} - 157248 u_{i_l+10, i_2+1} + 117936 u_{i_l+10, i_2+2} \\
& - 52416 u_{i_l+10, i_2+3} + 9828 u_{i_l+10, i_2+4} - 10800 u_{i_l+11, i_2} + 20736 u_{i_l+11, i_2+1} - 15552 u_{i_l+11, i_2+2} + 6912 u_{i_l+11, i_2+3} - 1296 u_{i_l+11, i_2+4} + 675 u_{i_l+12, i_2} \\
& - 1296 u_{i_l+12, i_2+1} + 972 u_{i_l+12, i_2+2} - 432 u_{i_l+12, i_2+3} + 81 u_{i_l+12, i_2+4}), O(\Delta x l^4 \Delta x 2^4), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.8230023213074794942 \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8150649554243404458 \times 10^{-22}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.8150649554243404458 \times 10^{-22}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8150570380064602894 \times 10^{-34}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.8150570380064602894 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8150570300890623199 \times 10^{-46}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.8150570300890623199 \times 10^{-46}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8150570300811449219 \times 10^{-58}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.8150570300811449219 \times 10^{-58}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8150570300811370045 \times 10^{-70}$$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{20736 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2} (81 u_{i_1-12, i_2-4} - 432 u_{i_1-12, i_2-3} + 972 u_{i_1-12, i_2-2} - 1296 u_{i_1-12, i_2-1} + 675 u_{i_1-12, i_2} - 1296 u_{i_1-11, i_2-4} + 6912 u_{i_1-11, i_2-3} - 15552 u_{i_1-11, i_2-2} + 20736 u_{i_1-11, i_2-1} - 10800 u_{i_1-11, i_2} + 9828 u_{i_1-10, i_2-4} - 52416 u_{i_1-10, i_2-3} + 117936 u_{i_1-10, i_2-2} - 157248 u_{i_1-10, i_2-1} + 81900 u_{i_1-10, i_2} - 47280 u_{i_1-9, i_2-4} + 252160 u_{i_1-9, i_2-3} - 567360 u_{i_1-9, i_2-2} + 756480 u_{i_1-9, i_2-1} - 394000 u_{i_1-9, i_2} + 161433 u_{i_1-8, i_2-4} - 860976 u_{i_1-8, i_2-3} + 1937196 u_{i_1-8, i_2-2} - 2582928 u_{i_1-8, i_2-1} + 1345275 u_{i_1-8, i_2} - 412128 u_{i_1-7, i_2-4} + 2198016 u_{i_1-7, i_2-3} - 4945536 u_{i_1-7, i_2-2} + 6594048 u_{i_1-7, i_2-1} - 3434400 u_{i_1-7, i_2} + 806040 u_{i_1-6, i_2-4} - 4298880 u_{i_1-6, i_2-3} + 9672480 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 12896640 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 6717000 u_{i_1-6, i_2} - 1215648 u_{i_1-5, i_2-4} + 6483456 u_{i_1-5, i_2-3} - 14587776 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 19450368 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 10130400 u_{i_1-5, i_2} + 1400571 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4} - 7469712 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3} + 16806852 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 22409136 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 11671425 u_{i_1-4, i_2} - 1199376 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4} + 6396672 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 14392512 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 19190016 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 9994800 u_{i_1-3, i_2} + 720900 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4} - 3844800 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 8650800 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 11534400 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 6007500 u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 270000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4} + 1440000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} - 3240000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 4320000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 2250000 u_{i_1-1, i_2} + 46875 u_{i_1, i_2-4} - 250000 u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 562500 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 750000 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 390625 u_{i_1, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.8071516001054332426 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $1.8150491047777947095 \times 10^{-22}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.8150491047777947095 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $1.8150570221558137437 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.8150570221558137437 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.8150570300732116733 \times 10^{-46}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.8150570300732116733 \times 10^{-46}$, *New Error:*, $1.8150570300811290713 \times 10^{-58}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.8150570300811290713 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $1.8150570300811369887 \times 10^{-70}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{20736 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2} (u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 8 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 8 u_{i_1-6, i_2+1} - u_{i_1-6, i_2+2} - 24 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 192 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 192 u_{i_1-5, i_2+1} + 24 u_{i_1-5, i_2+2} + 192 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 1536 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 1536 u_{i_1-4, i_2+1} - 192 u_{i_1-4, i_2+2} - 488 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 3904 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 3904 u_{i_1-3, i_2+1} + 488 u_{i_1-3, i_2+2} - 387 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} + 3096 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} - 3096 u_{i_1-2, i_2+1} + 387 u_{i_1-2, i_2+2} + 1584 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} - 12672 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} + 12672 u_{i_1-1, i_2+1} - 1584 u_{i_1-1, i_2+2} - 1584 u_{i_1+1, i_2-2} + 12672 u_{i_1+1, i_2-1} - 12672 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} + 1584 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 387 u_{i_1+2, i_2-2} - 3096 u_{i_1+2, i_2-1} + 3096 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} - 387 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} + 488 u_{i_1+3, i_2-2} - 3904 u_{i_1+3, i_2-1} + 3904 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 488 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} - 192 u_{i_1+4, i_2-2} + 1536 u_{i_1+4, i_2-1} - 1536 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} + 192 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} + 24 u_{i_1+5, i_2-2} - 192 u_{i_1+5, i_2-1} + 192 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} - 24 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} - u_{i_1+6, i_2-2} + 8 u_{i_1+6, i_2-1} - 8 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} + u_{i_1+6, i_2+2}),$$

$O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4)$, *Centered*

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $3.0250976053354954228 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.0250950501377835304 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $3.0250950501377835304 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $3.0250950501352283303 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $3.0250950501352283303 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $3.0250950501352283277 \times 10^{-47}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $3.0250950501352283277 \times 10^{-47}$, *New Error:*, $3.0250950501352283277 \times 10^{-59}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $3.0250950501352283277 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $3.0250950501352283277 \times 10^{-71}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2} (352275361 u_{i_1, i_2} - 771405900 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 771405900 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 514270600 u_{i_1, i_2+3} + 192851475 u_{i_1, i_2+4} \\
& - 30856236 u_{i_1, i_2+5} - 2314217700 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 5067630000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 5067630000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 3378420000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} - 1266907500 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} \\
& + 202705200 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} + 7381847700 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 16164630000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 16164630000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 10776420000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} \\
& + 4041157500 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} - 646585200 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} - 15377071800 u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 33672420000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 33672420000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} \\
& + 22448280000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} - 8418105000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} + 1346896800 u_{i_1+3, i_2+5} + 23500024425 u_{i_1+4, i_2} - 51459907500 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} \\
& + 51459907500 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} - 34306605000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} + 12864976875 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} - 2058396300 u_{i_1+4, i_2+5} - 27878223708 u_{i_1+5, i_2} \\
& + 61047205200 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} - 61047205200 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} + 40698136800 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} - 15261801300 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} + 2441888208 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} \\
& + 26460755400 u_{i_1+6, i_2} - 57943260000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} + 57943260000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} - 38628840000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} + 14485815000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} \\
& - 2317730400 u_{i_1+6, i_2+5} - 20417000400 u_{i_1+7, i_2} + 44708760000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} - 44708760000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} + 29805840000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+3} \\
& - 11177190000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+4} + 1788350400 u_{i_1+7, i_2+5} + 12880010475 u_{i_1+8, i_2} - 28204402500 u_{i_1+8, i_2+1} + 28204402500 u_{i_1+8, i_2+2} \\
& - 18802935000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+3} + 7051100625 u_{i_1+8, i_2+4} - 1128176100 u_{i_1+8, i_2+5} - 6625635100 u_{i_1+9, i_2} + 14508690000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+1} \\
& - 14508690000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+2} + 9672460000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+3} - 3627172500 u_{i_1+9, i_2+4} + 580347600 u_{i_1+9, i_2+5} + 2748450708 u_{i_1+10, i_2} - 6018505200 u_{i_1+10, i_2+1} \\
& + 6018505200 u_{i_1+10, i_2+2} - 4012336800 u_{i_1+10, i_2+3} + 1504626300 u_{i_1+10, i_2+4} - 240740208 u_{i_1+10, i_2+5} - 899350200 u_{i_1+11, i_2} \\
& + 1969380000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+1} - 1969380000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+2} + 1312920000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+3} - 492345000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+4} + 78775200 u_{i_1+11, i_2+5} + 223512075 u_{i_1+12, i_2} \\
& - 489442500 u_{i_1+12, i_2+1} + 489442500 u_{i_1+12, i_2+2} - 326295000 u_{i_1+12, i_2+3} + 122360625 u_{i_1+12, i_2+4} - 19577700 u_{i_1+12, i_2+5} - 39579300 u_{i_1+13, i_2} \\
& + 86670000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+1} - 86670000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+2} + 57780000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+3} - 21667500 u_{i_1+13, i_2+4} + 3466800 u_{i_1+13, i_2+5} + 4438800 u_{i_1+14, i_2} \\
& - 9720000 u_{i_1+14, i_2+1} + 9720000 u_{i_1+14, i_2+2} - 6480000 u_{i_1+14, i_2+3} + 2430000 u_{i_1+14, i_2+4} - 388800 u_{i_1+14, i_2+5} - 236736 u_{i_1+15, i_2} \\
& + 518400 u_{i_1+15, i_2+1} - 518400 u_{i_1+15, i_2+2} + 345600 u_{i_1+15, i_2+3} - 129600 u_{i_1+15, i_2+4} + 20736 u_{i_1+15, i_2+5}), O(\Delta x_1^5 \Delta x_2^5), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.9857332942429217407 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $3.9626846333143241802 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.9626846333143241802 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $3.9626616594122270810 \times 10^{-43}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.9626616594122270810 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $3.9626616364383995658 \times 10^{-58}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $3.9626616364383995658 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $3.9626616364154257383 \times 10^{-73}$

Error order:, 5, Error:., 3.9626616364154257383 $\times 10^{-73}$, New Error:., 3.9626616364154027645 $\times 10^{-88}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2} (20736 u_{i_1-15, i_2-5} - 129600 u_{i_1-15, i_2-4} + 345600 u_{i_1-15, i_2-3} - 518400 u_{i_1-15, i_2-2} + 518400 u_{i_1-15, i_2-1} - 236736 u_{i_1-15, i_2} - 388800 u_{i_1-14, i_2-5} + 2430000 u_{i_1-14, i_2-4} - 6480000 u_{i_1-14, i_2-3} + 9720000 u_{i_1-14, i_2-2} - 9720000 u_{i_1-14, i_2-1} + 4438800 u_{i_1-14, i_2} + 3466800 u_{i_1-13, i_2-5} - 21667500 u_{i_1-13, i_2-4} + 57780000 u_{i_1-13, i_2-3} - 86670000 u_{i_1-13, i_2-2} + 86670000 u_{i_1-13, i_2-1} - 39579300 u_{i_1-13, i_2} - 19577700 u_{i_1-12, i_2-5} + 122360625 u_{i_1-12, i_2-4} - 326295000 u_{i_1-12, i_2-3} + 489442500 u_{i_1-12, i_2-2} - 489442500 u_{i_1-12, i_2-1} + 223512075 u_{i_1-12, i_2} + 78775200 u_{i_1-11, i_2-5} - 492345000 u_{i_1-11, i_2-4} + 1312920000 u_{i_1-11, i_2-3} - 1969380000 u_{i_1-11, i_2-2} + 1969380000 u_{i_1-11, i_2-1} - 899350200 u_{i_1-11, i_2} - 240740208 u_{i_1-10, i_2-5} + 1504626300 u_{i_1-10, i_2-4} - 4012336800 u_{i_1-10, i_2-3} + 6018505200 u_{i_1-10, i_2-2} - 6018505200 u_{i_1-10, i_2-1} + 2748450708 u_{i_1-10, i_2} + 580347600 u_{i_1-9, i_2-5} - 3627172500 u_{i_1-9, i_2-4} + 9672460000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-3} - 14508690000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-2} + 14508690000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-1} - 6625635100 u_{i_1-9, i_2} - 1128176100 u_{i_1-8, i_2-5} + 7051100625 u_{i_1-8, i_2-4} - 18802935000 u_{i_1-8, i_2-3} + 28204402500 u_{i_1-8, i_2-2} - 28204402500 u_{i_1-8, i_2-1} + 12880010475 u_{i_1-8, i_2} + 1788350400 u_{i_1-7, i_2-5} - 11177190000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-4} + 29805840000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-3} - 44708760000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-2} + 44708760000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-1} - 20417000400 u_{i_1-7, i_2} - 2317730400 u_{i_1-6, i_2-5} + 14485815000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-4} - 38628840000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-3} + 57943260000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 57943260000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 26460755400 u_{i_1-6, i_2} + 2441888208 u_{i_1-5, i_2-5} - 15261801300 u_{i_1-5, i_2-4} + 40698136800 u_{i_1-5, i_2-3} - 61047205200 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 61047205200 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 27878223708 u_{i_1-5, i_2} - 2058396300 u_{i_1-4, i_2-5} + 12864976875 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4} - 34306605000 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3} + 51459907500 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 51459907500 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 23500024425 u_{i_1-4, i_2} + 1346896800 u_{i_1-3, i_2-5} - 8418105000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4} + 22448280000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 33672420000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 33672420000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 15377071800 u_{i_1-3, i_2} - 646585200 u_{i_1-2, i_2-5} + 4041157500 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4} - 10776420000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 16164630000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 16164630000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 7381847700 u_{i_1-2, i_2} + 202705200 u_{i_1-1, i_2-5} - 1266907500 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4} + 3378420000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} - 5067630000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 5067630000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 2314217700 u_{i_1-1, i_2} - 30856236 u_{i_1, i_2-5} + 192851475 u_{i_1, i_2-4} - 514270600 u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 771405900 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 771405900 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 352275361 u_{i_1, i_2}), $O(\Delta x_1^5 \Delta x_2^5)$, Backward$$

Error order:, 5, Error:., 3.9397392921481598030 $\times 10^{-13}$, New Error:., 3.9626386396657941875 $\times 10^{-28}$

Error order:, 5, Error:., 3.9626386396657941875 $\times 10^{-28}$, New Error:., 3.9626616134185785513 $\times 10^{-43}$

Error order:, 5, Error:., 3.9626616134185785513 $\times 10^{-43}$, New Error:., 3.9626616363924059172 $\times 10^{-58}$

Error order:, 5, Error:., 3.9626616363924059172 $\times 10^{-58}$, New Error:., 3.9626616364153797447 $\times 10^{-73}$

Error order:, 5, Error:., 3.9626616364153797447 $\times 10^{-73}$, New Error:., 3.9626616364154027185 $\times 10^{-88}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2} (466948881 u_{i_1, i_2} - 1143548280 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 1429435350 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 1270609200 u_{i_1, i_2+3} + 714717675 u_{i_1, i_2+4} \\
& - 228709656 u_{i_1, i_2+5} + 31765230 u_{i_1, i_2+6} - 3430644840 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 8401579200 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 10501974000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 9335088000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} \\
& - 5250987000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} + 1680315840 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} - 233377200 u_{i_1+1, i_2+6} + 12689885250 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 31077270000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} \\
& + 38846587500 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 34530300000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} + 19423293750 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} - 6215454000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} + 863257500 u_{i_1+2, i_2+6} \\
& - 31674207600 u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 77569488000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 96961860000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + 86188320000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} - 48480930000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} \\
& + 15513897600 u_{i_1+3, i_2+5} - 2154708000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+6} + 59660916525 u_{i_1+4, i_2} - 146108367000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} + 182635458750 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} \\
& - 162342630000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} + 91317729375 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} - 29221673400 u_{i_1+4, i_2+5} + 4058565750 u_{i_1+4, i_2+6} - 89536162968 u_{i_1+5, i_2} \\
& + 219272235840 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} - 274090294800 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} + 243635817600 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} - 137045147400 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} + 43854447168 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} \\
& - 6090895440 u_{i_1+5, i_2+6} + 110364249870 u_{i_1+6, i_2} - 270279795600 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} + 337849744500 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} - 300310884000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} \\
& + 168924872250 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} - 54055959120 u_{i_1+6, i_2+5} + 7507772100 u_{i_1+6, i_2+6} - 113722963200 u_{i_1+7, i_2} + 278505216000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} \\
& - 348131520000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} + 309450240000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+3} - 174065760000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+4} + 55701043200 u_{i_1+7, i_2+5} - 7736256000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+6} \\
& + 98880391575 u_{i_1+8, i_2} - 242156061000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+1} + 302695076250 u_{i_1+8, i_2+2} - 269062290000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+3} + 151347538125 u_{i_1+8, i_2+4} \\
& - 48431212200 u_{i_1+8, i_2+5} + 6726557250 u_{i_1+8, i_2+6} - 72788431800 u_{i_1+9, i_2} + 178257384000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+1} - 222821730000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+2} \\
& + 198063760000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+3} - 111410865000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+4} + 35651476800 u_{i_1+9, i_2+5} - 4951594000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+6} + 45287964918 u_{i_1+10, i_2} \\
& - 110909301840 u_{i_1+10, i_2+1} + 138636627300 u_{i_1+10, i_2+2} - 123232557600 u_{i_1+10, i_2+3} + 69318313650 u_{i_1+10, i_2+4} - 22181860368 u_{i_1+10, i_2+5} \\
& + 3080813940 u_{i_1+10, i_2+6} - 23658732720 u_{i_1+11, i_2} + 57939753600 u_{i_1+11, i_2+1} - 72424692000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+2} + 64377504000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+3} \\
& - 36212346000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+4} + 11587950720 u_{i_1+11, i_2+5} - 1609437600 u_{i_1+11, i_2+6} + 10252268775 u_{i_1+12, i_2} - 25107597000 u_{i_1+12, i_2+1} \\
& + 31384496250 u_{i_1+12, i_2+2} - 27897330000 u_{i_1+12, i_2+3} + 15692248125 u_{i_1+12, i_2+4} - 5021519400 u_{i_1+12, i_2+5} + 697433250 u_{i_1+12, i_2+6} \\
& - 3617346600 u_{i_1+13, i_2} + 8858808000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+1} - 11073510000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+2} + 9843120000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+3} - 5536755000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+4} \\
& + 1771761600 u_{i_1+13, i_2+5} - 246078000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+6} + 1011499650 u_{i_1+14, i_2} - 2477142000 u_{i_1+14, i_2+1} + 3096427500 u_{i_1+14, i_2+2} \\
& - 2752380000 u_{i_1+14, i_2+3} + 1548213750 u_{i_1+14, i_2+4} - 495428400 u_{i_1+14, i_2+5} + 68809500 u_{i_1+14, i_2+6} - 215391456 u_{i_1+15, i_2} + 527489280 u_{i_1+15, i_2+1} \\
& - 659361600 u_{i_1+15, i_2+2} + 586099200 u_{i_1+15, i_2+3} - 329680800 u_{i_1+15, i_2+4} + 105497856 u_{i_1+15, i_2+5} - 14652480 u_{i_1+15, i_2+6} + 32783940 u_{i_1+16, i_2} \\
& - 80287200 u_{i_1+16, i_2+1} + 100359000 u_{i_1+16, i_2+2} - 89208000 u_{i_1+16, i_2+3} + 50179500 u_{i_1+16, i_2+4} - 16057440 u_{i_1+16, i_2+5} + 2230200 u_{i_1+16, i_2+6} \\
& - 3175200 u_{i_1+17, i_2} + 7776000 u_{i_1+17, i_2+1} - 9720000 u_{i_1+17, i_2+2} + 8640000 u_{i_1+17, i_2+3} - 4860000 u_{i_1+17, i_2+4} + 1555200 u_{i_1+17, i_2+5} \\
& - 216000 u_{i_1+17, i_2+6} + 147000 u_{i_1+18, i_2} - 360000 u_{i_1+18, i_2+1} + 450000 u_{i_1+18, i_2+2} - 400000 u_{i_1+18, i_2+3} + 225000 u_{i_1+18, i_2+4} - 72000 u_{i_1+18, i_2+5}
\end{aligned}$$

+ 10000 u_{i_l+18, i_2+6}), $O(\Delta x I^6 \Delta x^6)$, Forward

Error order: 6, Error: $9.2661899858432483153 \times 10^{-16}$, New Error: $9.1987968969946809068 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order: 6, Error: $9.1987968969946809068 \times 10^{-34}$, New Error: $9.1987297731186210722 \times 10^{-52}$

Error order: 6, Error: $9.1987297731186210722 \times 10^{-52}$, New Error: $9.1987297059950134528 \times 10^{-70}$

Error order: 6, Error: $9.1987297059950134528 \times 10^{-70}$, New Error: $9.1987297059278898454 \times 10^{-88}$

Error order: 6, Error: $9.1987297059278898454 \times 10^{-88}$, New Error: $9.1987297059278227218 \times 10^{-106}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x I^3 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2} (10000 u_{i_l-18, i_2-6} - 72000 u_{i_l-18, i_2-5} + 225000 u_{i_l-18, i_2-4} - 400000 u_{i_l-18, i_2-3} + 450000 u_{i_l-18, i_2-2} - 360000 u_{i_l-18, i_2-1} + 147000 u_{i_l-18, i_2} - 216000 u_{i_l-17, i_2-6} + 1555200 u_{i_l-17, i_2-5} - 4860000 u_{i_l-17, i_2-4} + 8640000 u_{i_l-17, i_2-3} - 9720000 u_{i_l-17, i_2-2} + 7776000 u_{i_l-17, i_2-1} - 3175200 u_{i_l-17, i_2} + 2230200 u_{i_l-16, i_2-6} - 16057440 u_{i_l-16, i_2-5} + 50179500 u_{i_l-16, i_2-4} - 89208000 u_{i_l-16, i_2-3} + 100359000 u_{i_l-16, i_2-2} - 80287200 u_{i_l-16, i_2-1} + 32783940 u_{i_l-16, i_2} - 14652480 u_{i_l-15, i_2-6} + 105497856 u_{i_l-15, i_2-5} - 329680800 u_{i_l-15, i_2-4} + 586099200 u_{i_l-15, i_2-3} - 659361600 u_{i_l-15, i_2-2} + 527489280 u_{i_l-15, i_2-1} - 215391456 u_{i_l-15, i_2} + 68809500 u_{i_l-14, i_2-6} - 495428400 u_{i_l-14, i_2-5} + 1548213750 u_{i_l-14, i_2-4} - 2752380000 u_{i_l-14, i_2-3} + 3096427500 u_{i_l-14, i_2-2} - 2477142000 u_{i_l-14, i_2-1} + 1011499650 u_{i_l-14, i_2} - 246078000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-6} + 1771761600 u_{i_l-13, i_2-5} - 5536755000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-4} + 9843120000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-3} - 11073510000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-2} + 8858808000 u_{i_l-13, i_2-1} - 3617346600 u_{i_l-13, i_2} + 697433250 u_{i_l-12, i_2-6} - 5021519400 u_{i_l-12, i_2-5} + 15692248125 u_{i_l-12, i_2-4} - 27897330000 u_{i_l-12, i_2-3} + 31384496250 u_{i_l-12, i_2-2} - 25107597000 u_{i_l-12, i_2-1} + 10252268775 u_{i_l-12, i_2} - 1609437600 u_{i_l-11, i_2-6} + 11587950720 u_{i_l-11, i_2-5} - 36212346000 u_{i_l-11, i_2-4} + 64377504000 u_{i_l-11, i_2-3} - 72424692000 u_{i_l-11, i_2-2} + 57939753600 u_{i_l-11, i_2-1} - 23658732720 u_{i_l-11, i_2} + 3080813940 u_{i_l-10, i_2-6} - 22181860368 u_{i_l-10, i_2-5} + 69318313650 u_{i_l-10, i_2-4} - 123232557600 u_{i_l-10, i_2-3} + 138636627300 u_{i_l-10, i_2-2} - 110909301840 u_{i_l-10, i_2-1} + 45287964918 u_{i_l-10, i_2} - 4951594000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-6} + 35651476800 u_{i_l-9, i_2-5} - 111410865000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-4} + 198063760000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-3} - 222821730000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-2} + 178257384000 u_{i_l-9, i_2-1} - 72788431800 u_{i_l-9, i_2} + 6726557250 u_{i_l-8, i_2-6} - 48431212200 u_{i_l-8, i_2-5} + 151347538125 u_{i_l-8, i_2-4} - 269062290000 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 302695076250 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 242156061000 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 98880391575 u_{i_l-8, i_2} - 7736256000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-6} + 55701043200 u_{i_l-7, i_2-5} - 174065760000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-4} + 309450240000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 348131520000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 278505216000 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 113722963200 u_{i_l-7, i_2} + 7507772100 u_{i_l-6, i_2-6} - 54055959120 u_{i_l-6, i_2-5} + 168924872250 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4} - 300310884000 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 337849744500 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 270279795600 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 110364249870 u_{i_l-6, i_2} - 6090895440 u_{i_l-5, i_2-6} + 43854447168 u_{i_l-5, i_2-5} - 137045147400 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4} + 243635817600 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 274090294800 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 219272235840 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 89536162968 u_{i_l-5, i_2} + 4058565750 u_{i_l-4, i_2-6}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 29221673400 u_{iI-4, i2-5} + 91317729375 u_{iI-4, i2-4} - 162342630000 u_{iI-4, i2-3} + 182635458750 u_{iI-4, i2-2} - 146108367000 u_{iI-4, i2-1} \\
& + 59660916525 u_{iI-4, i2} - 2154708000 u_{iI-3, i2-6} + 15513897600 u_{iI-3, i2-5} - 48480930000 u_{iI-3, i2-4} + 86188320000 u_{iI-3, i2-3} \\
& - 96961860000 u_{iI-3, i2-2} + 77569488000 u_{iI-3, i2-1} - 31674207600 u_{iI-3, i2} + 863257500 u_{iI-2, i2-6} - 6215454000 u_{iI-2, i2-5} \\
& + 19423293750 u_{iI-2, i2-4} - 34530300000 u_{iI-2, i2-3} + 38846587500 u_{iI-2, i2-2} - 31077270000 u_{iI-2, i2-1} + 12689885250 u_{iI-2, i2} \\
& - 233377200 u_{iI-1, i2-6} + 1680315840 u_{iI-1, i2-5} - 5250987000 u_{iI-1, i2-4} + 9335088000 u_{iI-1, i2-3} - 10501974000 u_{iI-1, i2-2} \\
& + 8401579200 u_{iI-1, i2-1} - 3430644840 u_{iI-1, i2} + 31765230 u_{iI, i2-6} - 228709656 u_{iI, i2-5} + 714717675 u_{iI, i2-4} - 1270609200 u_{iI, i2-3} \\
& + 1429435350 u_{iI, i2-2} - 1143548280 u_{iI, i2-1} + 466948881 u_{iI, i2}), O(\Delta x I^6 \Delta x 2^6), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:., 6, Error:., 9.1318068467091256452 $\times 10^{-16}$, New Error:., 9.1986625153983815679 $\times 10^{-34}$

Error order:., 6, Error:., 9.1986625153983815679 $\times 10^{-34}$, New Error:., 9.1987296387370247744 $\times 10^{-52}$

Error order:., 6, Error:., 9.1987296387370247744 $\times 10^{-52}$, New Error:., 9.1987297058606318565 $\times 10^{-70}$

Error order:., 6, Error:., 9.1987297058606318565 $\times 10^{-70}$, New Error:., 9.1987297059277554638 $\times 10^{-88}$

Error order:., 6, Error:., 9.1987297059277554638 $\times 10^{-88}$, New Error:., 9.1987297059278225874 $\times 10^{-106}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x I^3 \partial x 2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta x I^3 \Delta x 2} (u_{iI-9, i2-3} - 9 u_{iI-9, i2-2} + 45 u_{iI-9, i2-1} - 45 u_{iI-9, i2+1} + 9 u_{iI-9, i2+2} - u_{iI-9, i2+3} - 27 u_{iI-8, i2-3} \\
& + 243 u_{iI-8, i2-2} - 1215 u_{iI-8, i2-1} + 1215 u_{iI-8, i2+1} - 243 u_{iI-8, i2+2} + 27 u_{iI-8, i2+3} + 378 u_{iI-7, i2-3} - 3402 u_{iI-7, i2-2} + 17010 u_{iI-7, i2-1} \\
& - 17010 u_{iI-7, i2+1} + 3402 u_{iI-7, i2+2} - 378 u_{iI-7, i2+3} - 3159 u_{iI-6, i2-3} + 28431 u_{iI-6, i2-2} - 142155 u_{iI-6, i2-1} + 142155 u_{iI-6, i2+1} \\
& - 28431 u_{iI-6, i2+2} + 3159 u_{iI-6, i2+3} + 16875 u_{iI-5, i2-3} - 151875 u_{iI-5, i2-2} + 759375 u_{iI-5, i2-1} - 759375 u_{iI-5, i2+1} + 151875 u_{iI-5, i2+2} \\
& - 16875 u_{iI-5, i2+3} - 52218 u_{iI-4, i2-3} + 469962 u_{iI-4, i2-2} - 2349810 u_{iI-4, i2-1} + 2349810 u_{iI-4, i2+1} - 469962 u_{iI-4, i2+2} + 52218 u_{iI-4, i2+3} \\
& + 67551 u_{iI-3, i2-3} - 607959 u_{iI-3, i2-2} + 3039795 u_{iI-3, i2-1} - 3039795 u_{iI-3, i2+1} + 607959 u_{iI-3, i2+2} - 67551 u_{iI-3, i2+3} + 114021 u_{iI-2, i2-3} \\
& - 1026189 u_{iI-2, i2-2} + 5130945 u_{iI-2, i2-1} - 5130945 u_{iI-2, i2+1} + 1026189 u_{iI-2, i2+2} - 114021 u_{iI-2, i2+3} - 289683 u_{iI-1, i2-3} + 2607147 u_{iI-1, i2-2} \\
& - 13035735 u_{iI-1, i2-1} + 13035735 u_{iI-1, i2+1} - 2607147 u_{iI-1, i2+2} + 289683 u_{iI-1, i2+3} + 289683 u_{iI+1, i2-3} - 2607147 u_{iI+1, i2-2} \\
& + 13035735 u_{iI+1, i2-1} - 13035735 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + 2607147 u_{iI+1, i2+2} - 289683 u_{iI+1, i2+3} - 114021 u_{iI+2, i2-3} + 1026189 u_{iI+2, i2-2} \\
& - 5130945 u_{iI+2, i2-1} + 5130945 u_{iI+2, i2+1} - 1026189 u_{iI+2, i2+2} + 114021 u_{iI+2, i2+3} - 67551 u_{iI+3, i2-3} + 607959 u_{iI+3, i2-2} - 3039795 u_{iI+3, i2-1} \\
& + 3039795 u_{iI+3, i2+1} - 607959 u_{iI+3, i2+2} + 67551 u_{iI+3, i2+3} + 52218 u_{iI+4, i2-3} - 469962 u_{iI+4, i2-2} + 2349810 u_{iI+4, i2-1} - 2349810 u_{iI+4, i2+1} \\
& + 469962 u_{iI+4, i2+2} - 52218 u_{iI+4, i2+3} - 16875 u_{iI+5, i2-3} + 151875 u_{iI+5, i2-2} - 759375 u_{iI+5, i2-1} + 759375 u_{iI+5, i2+1} - 151875 u_{iI+5, i2+2} \\
& + 16875 u_{iI+5, i2+3} + 3159 u_{iI+6, i2-3} - 28431 u_{iI+6, i2-2} + 142155 u_{iI+6, i2-1} - 142155 u_{iI+6, i2+1} + 28431 u_{iI+6, i2+2} - 3159 u_{iI+6, i2+3}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 378 u_{i_l+7, i_2-3} + 3402 u_{i_l+7, i_2-2} - 17010 u_{i_l+7, i_2-1} + 17010 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} - 3402 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} + 378 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} + 27 u_{i_l+8, i_2-3} - 243 u_{i_l+8, i_2-2} \\
& + 1215 u_{i_l+8, i_2-1} - 1215 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} + 243 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} - 27 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} - u_{i_l+9, i_2-3} + 9 u_{i_l+9, i_2-2} - 45 u_{i_l+9, i_2-1} + 45 u_{i_l+9, i_2+1} - 9 u_{i_l+9, i_2+2} \\
& + u_{i_l+9, i_2+3}), O(\Delta x_1^6 \Delta x_2^6), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $4.5993719242480893958 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $4.5993648529709826058 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $4.5993648529709826058 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $4.5993648529639113344 \times 10^{-53}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $4.5993648529639113344 \times 10^{-53}$, *New Error:*, $4.5993648529639113273 \times 10^{-71}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $4.5993648529639113273 \times 10^{-71}$, *New Error:*, $4.5993648529639113273 \times 10^{-89}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $4.5993648529639113273 \times 10^{-89}$, *New Error:*, $4.5993648529639113273 \times 10^{-107}$

"--- Derivative Order: 4 - x1=2, x2=2 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{u_{i_l, i_2} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2+1} + u_{i_l, i_2+2} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2} + 4 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} + u_{i_l+2, i_2} - 2 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + u_{i_l+2, i_2+2}}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2}, O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2),$$

Forward

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.035515287993306394284, *New Error:*, 0.000035419227641102886062

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000035419227641102886062, *New Error:*, $3.5419131765828058410 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.5419131765828058410 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.5419131669952968377 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.5419131669952968377 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.5419131669857093287 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.5419131669857093287 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $3.5419131669856997412 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 2 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + u_{i_l-2, i_2} - 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 4 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2} + u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + u_{i_l, i_2}}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2}, O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2),$$

Backward

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.035323345307772577932, *New Error:*, 0.000035419035698981069218

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000035419035698981069218, *New Error:*, $3.5419131573885936593 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.5419131573885936593 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.5419131669761026255 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.5419131669761026255 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.5419131669856901345 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.5419131669856901345 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $3.5419131669856997220 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\delta^4}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{16 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} (81 u_{il, i2} - 216 u_{il, i2+1} + 198 u_{il, i2+2} - 72 u_{il, i2+3} + 9 u_{il, i2+4} - 216 u_{il+1, i2} + 576 u_{il+1, i2+1} - 528 u_{il+1, i2+2} + 192 u_{il+1, i2+3} - 24 u_{il+1, i2+4} + 198 u_{il+2, i2} - 528 u_{il+2, i2+1} + 484 u_{il+2, i2+2} - 176 u_{il+2, i2+3} + 22 u_{il+2, i2+4} - 72 u_{il+3, i2} + 192 u_{il+3, i2+1} - 176 u_{il+3, i2+2} + 64 u_{il+3, i2+3} - 8 u_{il+3, i2+4} + 9 u_{il+4, i2} - 24 u_{il+4, i2+1} + 22 u_{il+4, i2+2} - 8 u_{il+4, i2+3} + u_{il+4, i2+4}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000061345935604282412103, New Error: 6.1222827001827954529 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order: 2, Error: 6.1222827001827954529 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 6.1222703863418630900 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order: 2, Error: 6.1222703863418630900 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 6.1222703740280192351 × 10⁻²³
Error order: 2, Error: 6.1222703740280192351 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 6.1222703740157053913 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order: 2, Error: 6.1222703740157053913 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 6.1222703740156930774 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{\delta^4}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{16 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} (u_{il-4, i2-4} - 8 u_{il-4, i2-3} + 22 u_{il-4, i2-2} - 24 u_{il-4, i2-1} + 9 u_{il-4, i2} - 8 u_{il-3, i2-4} + 64 u_{il-3, i2-3} - 176 u_{il-3, i2-2} + 192 u_{il-3, i2-1} - 72 u_{il-3, i2} + 22 u_{il-2, i2-4} - 176 u_{il-2, i2-3} + 484 u_{il-2, i2-2} - 528 u_{il-2, i2-1} + 198 u_{il-2, i2} - 24 u_{il-1, i2-4} + 192 u_{il-1, i2-3} - 528 u_{il-1, i2-2} + 576 u_{il-1, i2-1} - 216 u_{il-1, i2} + 9 u_{il, i2-4} - 72 u_{il, i2-3} + 198 u_{il, i2-2} - 216 u_{il, i2-1} + 81 u_{il, i2}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000061099413366207484050, New Error: 6.1222580478427399518 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order: 2, Error: 6.1222580478427399518 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 6.1222703616895230344 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order: 2, Error: 6.1222703616895230344 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 6.1222703740033668951 × 10⁻²³
Error order: 2, Error: 6.1222703740033668951 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 6.1222703740156807389 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order: 2, Error: 6.1222703740156807389 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 6.1222703740156930528 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{\delta^4}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{u_{il-2, i2-2} - 2 u_{il-2, i2} + u_{il-2, i2+2} - 2 u_{il, i2-2} + 4 u_{il, i2} - 2 u_{il, i2+2} + u_{il+2, i2-2} - 2 u_{il+2, i2} + u_{il+2, i2+2}}{16 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2}, O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2),$$

Centered

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000030611410270630668781, New Error: 3.0611351870136865812 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order: 2, Error: 3.0611351870136865812 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 3.0611351870078465384 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order: 2, Error: 3.0611351870078465384 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 3.0611351870078465325 × 10⁻²³
Error order: 2, Error: 3.0611351870078465325 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 3.0611351870078465325 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order: 2, Error: 3.0611351870078465325 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 3.0611351870078465325 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{\delta^4}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{1296 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} (14641 u_{iI, i2} - 47916 u_{iI, i2+1} + 63162 u_{iI, i2+2} - 44528 u_{iI, i2+3} + 18513 u_{iI, i2+4} - 4356 u_{iI, i2+5} + 484 u_{iI, i2+6} - 47916 u_{iI+1, i2} + 156816 u_{iI+1, i2+1} - 206712 u_{iI+1, i2+2} + 145728 u_{iI+1, i2+3} - 60588 u_{iI+1, i2+4} + 14256 u_{iI+1, i2+5} - 1584 u_{iI+1, i2+6} + 63162 u_{iI+2, i2} - 206712 u_{iI+2, i2+1} + 272484 u_{iI+2, i2+2} - 192096 u_{iI+2, i2+3} + 79866 u_{iI+2, i2+4} - 18792 u_{iI+2, i2+5} + 2088 u_{iI+2, i2+6} - 44528 u_{iI+3, i2} + 145728 u_{iI+3, i2+1} - 192096 u_{iI+3, i2+2} + 135424 u_{iI+3, i2+3} - 56304 u_{iI+3, i2+4} + 13248 u_{iI+3, i2+5} - 1472 u_{iI+3, i2+6} + 18513 u_{iI+4, i2} - 60588 u_{iI+4, i2+1} + 79866 u_{iI+4, i2+2} - 56304 u_{iI+4, i2+3} + 23409 u_{iI+4, i2+4} - 5508 u_{iI+4, i2+5} + 612 u_{iI+4, i2+6} - 4356 u_{iI+5, i2} + 14256 u_{iI+5, i2+1} - 18792 u_{iI+5, i2+2} + 13248 u_{iI+5, i2+3} - 5508 u_{iI+5, i2+4} + 1296 u_{iI+5, i2+5} - 144 u_{iI+5, i2+6} + 484 u_{iI+6, i2} - 1584 u_{iI+6, i2+1} + 2088 u_{iI+6, i2+2} - 1472 u_{iI+6, i2+3} + 612 u_{iI+6, i2+4} - 144 u_{iI+6, i2+5} + 16 u_{iI+6, i2+6}), O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^3), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.2367120099569107618 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $1.2326210897552357977 \times 10^{-16}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.2326210897552357977 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $1.2326170068678344321 \times 10^{-25}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.2326170068678344321 \times 10^{-25}$, *New Error:*, $1.2326170027849550444 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.2326170027849550444 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.2326170027808721650 \times 10^{-43}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.2326170027808721650 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $1.2326170027808680822 \times 10^{-52}$

$$\frac{\delta^4}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{1296 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} (16 u_{iI-6, i2-6} - 144 u_{iI-6, i2-5} + 612 u_{iI-6, i2-4} - 1472 u_{iI-6, i2-3} + 2088 u_{iI-6, i2-2} - 1584 u_{iI-6, i2-1} + 484 u_{iI-6, i2} - 144 u_{iI-5, i2-6} + 1296 u_{iI-5, i2-5} - 5508 u_{iI-5, i2-4} + 13248 u_{iI-5, i2-3} - 18792 u_{iI-5, i2-2} + 14256 u_{iI-5, i2-1} - 4356 u_{iI-5, i2} + 612 u_{iI-4, i2-6} - 5508 u_{iI-4, i2-5} + 23409 u_{iI-4, i2-4} - 56304 u_{iI-4, i2-3} + 79866 u_{iI-4, i2-2} - 60588 u_{iI-4, i2-1} + 18513 u_{iI-4, i2} - 1472 u_{iI-3, i2-6} + 13248 u_{iI-3, i2-5} - 56304 u_{iI-3, i2-4} + 135424 u_{iI-3, i2-3} - 192096 u_{iI-3, i2-2} + 145728 u_{iI-3, i2-1} - 44528 u_{iI-3, i2} + 2088 u_{iI-2, i2-6} - 18792 u_{iI-2, i2-5} + 79866 u_{iI-2, i2-4} - 192096 u_{iI-2, i2-3} + 272484 u_{iI-2, i2-2} - 206712 u_{iI-2, i2-1} + 63162 u_{iI-2, i2} - 1584 u_{iI-1, i2-6} + 14256 u_{iI-1, i2-5} - 60588 u_{iI-1, i2-4} + 145728 u_{iI-1, i2-3} - 206712 u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 156816 u_{iI-1, i2-1} - 47916 u_{iI-1, i2} + 484 u_{iI, i2-6} - 4356 u_{iI, i2-5} + 18513 u_{iI, i2-4} - 44528 u_{iI, i2-3} + 63162 u_{iI, i2-2} - 47916 u_{iI, i2-1} + 14641 u_{iI, i2}), O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.2285380390710602119 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $1.2326129158225437023 \times 10^{-16}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.2326129158225437023 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $1.2326169986939017401 \times 10^{-25}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.2326169986939017401 \times 10^{-25}$, *New Error:*, $1.2326170027767811117 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.2326170027767811117 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.2326170027808639911 \times 10^{-43}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.2326170027808639911 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $1.2326170027808680740 \times 10^{-52}$

$$\frac{\delta^4}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{20736 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} (390625 u_{il, i2} - 1500000 u_{il, i2+1} + 2565000 u_{il, i2+2} - 2660000 u_{il, i2+3} + 1863750 u_{il, i2+4} - 900000 u_{il, i2+5} + 295000 u_{il, i2+6} - 60000 u_{il, i2+7} + 5625 u_{il, i2+8} - 1500000 u_{il+1, i2} + 5760000 u_{il+1, i2+1} - 9849600 u_{il+1, i2+2} + 10214400 u_{il+1, i2+3} - 7156800 u_{il+1, i2+4} + 3456000 u_{il+1, i2+5} - 1132800 u_{il+1, i2+6} + 230400 u_{il+1, i2+7} - 21600 u_{il+1, i2+8} + 2565000 u_{il+2, i2} - 9849600 u_{il+2, i2+1} + 16842816 u_{il+2, i2+2} - 17466624 u_{il+2, i2+3} + 12238128 u_{il+2, i2+4} - 5909760 u_{il+2, i2+5} + 1937088 u_{il+2, i2+6} - 393984 u_{il+2, i2+7} + 36936 u_{il+2, i2+8} - 2660000 u_{il+3, i2} + 10214400 u_{il+3, i2+1} - 17466624 u_{il+3, i2+2} + 18113536 u_{il+3, i2+3} - 12691392 u_{il+3, i2+4} + 6128640 u_{il+3, i2+5} - 2008832 u_{il+3, i2+6} + 408576 u_{il+3, i2+7} - 38304 u_{il+3, i2+8} + 1863750 u_{il+4, i2} - 7156800 u_{il+4, i2+1} + 12238128 u_{il+4, i2+2} - 12691392 u_{il+4, i2+3} + 8892324 u_{il+4, i2+4} - 4294080 u_{il+4, i2+5} + 1407504 u_{il+4, i2+6} - 286272 u_{il+4, i2+7} + 26838 u_{il+4, i2+8} - 900000 u_{il+5, i2} + 3456000 u_{il+5, i2+1} - 5909760 u_{il+5, i2+2} + 6128640 u_{il+5, i2+3} - 4294080 u_{il+5, i2+4} + 2073600 u_{il+5, i2+5} - 679680 u_{il+5, i2+6} + 138240 u_{il+5, i2+7} - 12960 u_{il+5, i2+8} + 295000 u_{il+6, i2} - 1132800 u_{il+6, i2+1} + 1937088 u_{il+6, i2+2} - 2008832 u_{il+6, i2+3} + 1407504 u_{il+6, i2+4} - 679680 u_{il+6, i2+5} + 222784 u_{il+6, i2+6} - 45312 u_{il+6, i2+7} + 4248 u_{il+6, i2+8} - 60000 u_{il+7, i2} + 230400 u_{il+7, i2+1} - 393984 u_{il+7, i2+2} + 408576 u_{il+7, i2+3} - 286272 u_{il+7, i2+4} + 138240 u_{il+7, i2+5} - 45312 u_{il+7, i2+6} + 9216 u_{il+7, i2+7} - 864 u_{il+7, i2+8} + 5625 u_{il+8, i2} - 21600 u_{il+8, i2+1} + 36936 u_{il+8, i2+2} - 38304 u_{il+8, i2+3} + 26838 u_{il+8, i2+4} - 12960 u_{il+8, i2+5} + 4248 u_{il+8, i2+6} - 864 u_{il+8, i2+7} + 81 u_{il+8, i2+8}), O(\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^4), Forward$$

Error order: 4, Error: 2.7375132337384495374 × 10⁻¹⁰, New Error: 2.7246570653950353870 × 10⁻²²
Error order: 4, Error: 2.7246570653950353870 × 10⁻²², New Error: 2.7246442435203815980 × 10⁻³⁴
Error order: 4, Error: 2.7246442435203815980 × 10⁻³⁴, New Error: 2.7246442306985411708 × 10⁻⁴⁶
Error order: 4, Error: 2.7246442306985411708 × 10⁻⁴⁶, New Error: 2.7246442306857193304 × 10⁻⁵⁸
Error order: 4, Error: 2.7246442306857193304 × 10⁻⁵⁸, New Error: 2.7246442306857065085 × 10⁻⁷⁰

$$\frac{\delta^4}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{20736 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} (81 u_{il-8, i2-8} - 864 u_{il-8, i2-7} + 4248 u_{il-8, i2-6} - 12960 u_{il-8, i2-5} + 26838 u_{il-8, i2-4} - 38304 u_{il-8, i2-3} + 36936 u_{il-8, i2-2} - 21600 u_{il-8, i2-1} + 5625 u_{il-8, i2} - 864 u_{il-7, i2-8} + 9216 u_{il-7, i2-7} - 45312 u_{il-7, i2-6} + 138240 u_{il-7, i2-5} - 286272 u_{il-7, i2-4} + 408576 u_{il-7, i2-3} - 393984 u_{il-7, i2-2} + 230400 u_{il-7, i2-1} - 60000 u_{il-7, i2} + 4248 u_{il-6, i2-8} - 45312 u_{il-6, i2-7} + 222784 u_{il-6, i2-6} - 679680 u_{il-6, i2-5} + 1407504 u_{il-6, i2-4} - 2008832 u_{il-6, i2-3} + 1937088 u_{il-6, i2-2} - 1132800 u_{il-6, i2-1} + 295000 u_{il-6, i2} - 12960 u_{il-5, i2-8} + 138240 u_{il-5, i2-7} - 679680 u_{il-5, i2-6} + 2073600 u_{il-5, i2-5} - 4294080 u_{il-5, i2-4} + 6128640 u_{il-5, i2-3} - 5909760 u_{il-5, i2-2} + 3456000 u_{il-5, i2-1} - 900000 u_{il-5, i2} + 26838 u_{il-4, i2-8} - 286272 u_{il-4, i2-7} + 1407504 u_{il-4, i2-6} - 4294080 u_{il-4, i2-5} + 8892324 u_{il-4, i2-4} - 12691392 u_{il-4, i2-3} + 12238128 u_{il-4, i2-2} - 7156800 u_{il-4, i2-1} + 1863750 u_{il-4, i2} - 38304 u_{il-3, i2-8} + 408576 u_{il-3, i2-7} - 2008832 u_{il-3, i2-6} + 6128640 u_{il-3, i2-5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 12691392 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 18113536 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 17466624 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 10214400 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 2660000 u_{i_l-3, i_2} + 36936 u_{i_l-2, i_2-8} - 393984 u_{i_l-2, i_2-7} \\
& + 1937088 u_{i_l-2, i_2-6} - 5909760 u_{i_l-2, i_2-5} + 12238128 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} - 17466624 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 16842816 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 9849600 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} \\
& + 2565000 u_{i_l-2, i_2} - 21600 u_{i_l-1, i_2-8} + 230400 u_{i_l-1, i_2-7} - 1132800 u_{i_l-1, i_2-6} + 3456000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-5} - 7156800 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} + 10214400 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} \\
& - 9849600 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 5760000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 1500000 u_{i_l-1, i_2} + 5625 u_{i_l, i_2-8} - 60000 u_{i_l, i_2-7} + 295000 u_{i_l, i_2-6} - 900000 u_{i_l, i_2-5} + 1863750 u_{i_l, i_2-4} \\
& - 2660000 u_{i_l, i_2-3} + 2565000 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 1500000 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 390625 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x l^4 \Delta x^4), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.7118437493797261506 \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.7246313960448992051 \times 10^{-22}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.7246313960448992051 \times 10^{-22}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.7246442178510314619 \times 10^{-34}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.7246442178510314619 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.7246442306728718206 \times 10^{-46}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.7246442306728718206 \times 10^{-46}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.7246442306856936610 \times 10^{-58}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.7246442306856936610 \times 10^{-58}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.7246442306857064829 \times 10^{-70}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x l^2 \partial x^2} u(xl, x2) &= \frac{1}{20736 \Delta x l^2 \Delta x^2} (u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} - 16 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 64 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} + 16 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} - 130 u_{i_l-4, i_2} + 16 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1} + 64 u_{i_l-4, i_2+2} \\
& - 16 u_{i_l-4, i_2+3} + u_{i_l-4, i_2+4} - 16 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 256 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 1024 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} - 256 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} + 2080 u_{i_l-3, i_2} - 256 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1} - 1024 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2} \\
& + 256 u_{i_l-3, i_2+3} - 16 u_{i_l-3, i_2+4} + 64 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} - 1024 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 4096 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} + 1024 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} - 8320 u_{i_l-2, i_2} + 1024 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1} \\
& + 4096 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2} - 1024 u_{i_l-2, i_2+3} + 64 u_{i_l-2, i_2+4} + 16 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} - 256 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} + 1024 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 256 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 2080 u_{i_l-1, i_2} \\
& + 256 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1} + 1024 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2} - 256 u_{i_l-1, i_2+3} + 16 u_{i_l-1, i_2+4} - 130 u_{i_l, i_2-4} + 2080 u_{i_l, i_2-3} - 8320 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 2080 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 16900 u_{i_l, i_2} \\
& - 2080 u_{i_l, i_2+1} - 8320 u_{i_l, i_2+2} + 2080 u_{i_l, i_2+3} - 130 u_{i_l, i_2+4} + 16 u_{i_l+1, i_2-4} - 256 u_{i_l+1, i_2-3} + 1024 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2} + 256 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1} - 2080 u_{i_l+1, i_2} \\
& + 256 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} + 1024 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} - 256 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} + 16 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} + 64 u_{i_l+2, i_2-4} - 1024 u_{i_l+2, i_2-3} + 4096 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2} + 1024 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1} \\
& - 8320 u_{i_l+2, i_2} + 1024 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 4096 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 1024 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} + 64 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} - 16 u_{i_l+3, i_2-4} + 256 u_{i_l+3, i_2-3} - 1024 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2} \\
& - 256 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} + 2080 u_{i_l+3, i_2} - 256 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - 1024 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 256 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} - 16 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} + u_{i_l+4, i_2-4} - 16 u_{i_l+4, i_2-3} + 64 u_{i_l+4, i_2-2} \\
& + 16 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1} - 130 u_{i_l+4, i_2} + 16 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} + 64 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} - 16 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} + u_{i_l+4, i_2+4}), O(\Delta x l^4 \Delta x^4), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 4.5410781102127366048 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.5410737178139032365 \times 10^{-23}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 4.5410737178139032365 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.5410737178095108306 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 4.5410737178095108306 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.5410737178095108262 \times 10^{-47}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 4.5410737178095108262 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.5410737178095108262 \times 10^{-59}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 4.5410737178095108262 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.5410737178095108262 \times 10^{-71}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2} (352275361 u_{i_1, i_2} - 1542811800 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 3232021800 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 4406961200 u_{i_1, i_2+3} + 4327192950 u_{i_1, i_2+4} \\
& - 3158597472 u_{i_1, i_2+5} + 1730501800 u_{i_1, i_2+6} - 698206800 u_{i_1, i_2+7} + 195666825 u_{i_1, i_2+8} - 33784200 u_{i_1, i_2+9} + 2702736 u_{i_1, i_2+10} \\
& - 1542811800 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 6756840000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 14154840000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 19300560000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} - 18951210000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} \\
& + 13833273600 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} - 7578840000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+6} + 3057840000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+7} - 856935000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+8} + 147960000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+9} - 11836800 u_{i_1+1, i_2+10} \\
& + 3232021800 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 14154840000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 29652840000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 40432560000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} + 39700710000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} \\
& - 28979193600 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} + 15876840000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+6} - 6405840000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+7} + 1795185000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+8} - 309960000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+9} \\
& + 24796800 u_{i_1+2, i_2+10} - 4406961200 u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 19300560000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 40432560000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + 55131040000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} \\
& - 54133140000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} + 39514022400 u_{i_1+3, i_2+5} - 21648560000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+6} + 8734560000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+7} - 2447790000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+8} \\
& + 422640000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+9} - 33811200 u_{i_1+3, i_2+10} + 4327192950 u_{i_1+4, i_2} - 18951210000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} + 39700710000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} - 54133140000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} \\
& + 53153302500 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} - 38798798400 u_{i_1+4, i_2+5} + 21256710000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+6} - 8576460000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+7} + 2403483750 u_{i_1+4, i_2+8} \\
& - 414990000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+9} + 33199200 u_{i_1+4, i_2+10} - 3158597472 u_{i_1+5, i_2} + 13833273600 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} - 28979193600 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} + 39514022400 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} \\
& - 38798798400 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} + 28320850944 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} - 15516153600 u_{i_1+5, i_2+6} + 6260313600 u_{i_1+5, i_2+7} - 1754402400 u_{i_1+5, i_2+8} \\
& + 302918400 u_{i_1+5, i_2+9} - 24233472 u_{i_1+5, i_2+10} + 1730501800 u_{i_1+6, i_2} - 7578840000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} + 15876840000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} - 21648560000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} \\
& + 21256710000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} - 15516153600 u_{i_1+6, i_2+5} + 8500840000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+6} - 3429840000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+7} + 961185000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+8} \\
& - 165960000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+9} + 13276800 u_{i_1+6, i_2+10} - 698206800 u_{i_1+7, i_2} + 3057840000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} - 6405840000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} + 8734560000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+3} \\
& - 8576460000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+4} + 6260313600 u_{i_1+7, i_2+5} - 3429840000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+6} + 1383840000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+7} - 387810000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+8} + 66960000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+9} \\
& - 5356800 u_{i_1+7, i_2+10} + 195666825 u_{i_1+8, i_2} - 856935000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+1} + 1795185000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+2} - 2447790000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+3} + 2403483750 u_{i_1+8, i_2+4} \\
& - 1754402400 u_{i_1+8, i_2+5} + 961185000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+6} - 387810000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+7} + 108680625 u_{i_1+8, i_2+8} - 18765000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+9} + 1501200 u_{i_1+8, i_2+10} \\
& - 33784200 u_{i_1+9, i_2} + 147960000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+1} - 309960000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+2} + 422640000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+3} - 414990000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+4} + 302918400 u_{i_1+9, i_2+5} \\
& - 165960000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+6} + 66960000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+7} - 18765000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+8} + 3240000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+9} - 259200 u_{i_1+9, i_2+10} + 2702736 u_{i_1+10, i_2} \\
& - 11836800 u_{i_1+10, i_2+1} + 24796800 u_{i_1+10, i_2+2} - 33811200 u_{i_1+10, i_2+3} + 33199200 u_{i_1+10, i_2+4} - 24233472 u_{i_1+10, i_2+5} + 13276800 u_{i_1+10, i_2+6} \\
& - 5356800 u_{i_1+10, i_2+7} + 1501200 u_{i_1+10, i_2+8} - 259200 u_{i_1+10, i_2+9} + 20736 u_{i_1+10, i_2+10}), O(\Delta x_1^5 \Delta x_2^5), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 5, Error: $6.4570037787199308690 \times 10^{-13}$, New Error: $6.4173770658388258483 \times 10^{-28}$

Error order: 5, Error: $6.4173770658388258483 \times 10^{-28}$, New Error: $6.4173375735435910939 \times 10^{-43}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $6.4173375735435910939 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $6.4173375340514299481 \times 10^{-58}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $6.4173375340514299481 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $6.4173375340119377871 \times 10^{-73}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $6.4173375340119377871 \times 10^{-73}$, *New Error:*, $6.4173375340118982950 \times 10^{-88}$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{12960000 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2} (20736 u_{i_1-10, i_2-10} - 259200 u_{i_1-10, i_2-9} + 1501200 u_{i_1-10, i_2-8} - 5356800 u_{i_1-10, i_2-7} + 13276800 u_{i_1-10, i_2-6} \\ & - 24233472 u_{i_1-10, i_2-5} + 33199200 u_{i_1-10, i_2-4} - 33811200 u_{i_1-10, i_2-3} + 24796800 u_{i_1-10, i_2-2} - 11836800 u_{i_1-10, i_2-1} + 2702736 u_{i_1-10, i_2} \\ & - 259200 u_{i_1-9, i_2-10} + 3240000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-9} - 18765000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-8} + 66960000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-7} - 165960000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-6} + 302918400 u_{i_1-9, i_2-5} \\ & - 414990000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-4} + 422640000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-3} - 309960000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-2} + 147960000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-1} - 33784200 u_{i_1-9, i_2} + 1501200 u_{i_1-8, i_2-10} \\ & - 18765000 u_{i_1-8, i_2-9} + 108680625 u_{i_1-8, i_2-8} - 387810000 u_{i_1-8, i_2-7} + 961185000 u_{i_1-8, i_2-6} - 1754402400 u_{i_1-8, i_2-5} + 2403483750 u_{i_1-8, i_2-4} \\ & - 2447790000 u_{i_1-8, i_2-3} + 1795185000 u_{i_1-8, i_2-2} - 856935000 u_{i_1-8, i_2-1} + 195666825 u_{i_1-8, i_2} - 5356800 u_{i_1-7, i_2-10} + 66960000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-9} \\ & - 387810000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-8} + 1383840000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-7} - 3429840000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-6} + 6260313600 u_{i_1-7, i_2-5} - 8576460000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-4} + 8734560000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-3} \\ & - 6405840000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-2} + 3057840000 u_{i_1-7, i_2-1} - 698206800 u_{i_1-7, i_2} + 13276800 u_{i_1-6, i_2-10} - 165960000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-9} + 961185000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-8} \\ & - 3429840000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-7} + 8500840000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-6} - 15516153600 u_{i_1-6, i_2-5} + 21256710000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-4} - 21648560000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-3} \\ & + 15876840000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 7578840000 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 1730501800 u_{i_1-6, i_2} - 24233472 u_{i_1-5, i_2-10} + 302918400 u_{i_1-5, i_2-9} - 1754402400 u_{i_1-5, i_2-8} \\ & + 6260313600 u_{i_1-5, i_2-7} - 15516153600 u_{i_1-5, i_2-6} + 28320850944 u_{i_1-5, i_2-5} - 38798798400 u_{i_1-5, i_2-4} + 39514022400 u_{i_1-5, i_2-3} \\ & - 28979193600 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 13833273600 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 3158597472 u_{i_1-5, i_2} + 33199200 u_{i_1-4, i_2-10} - 414990000 u_{i_1-4, i_2-9} + 2403483750 u_{i_1-4, i_2-8} \\ & - 8576460000 u_{i_1-4, i_2-7} + 21256710000 u_{i_1-4, i_2-6} - 38798798400 u_{i_1-4, i_2-5} + 53153302500 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4} - 54133140000 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3} \\ & + 39700710000 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 18951210000 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 4327192950 u_{i_1-4, i_2} - 33811200 u_{i_1-3, i_2-10} + 422640000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-9} - 2447790000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-8} \\ & + 8734560000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-7} - 21648560000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-6} + 39514022400 u_{i_1-3, i_2-5} - 54133140000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4} + 55131040000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} \\ & - 40432560000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 19300560000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 4406961200 u_{i_1-3, i_2} + 24796800 u_{i_1-2, i_2-10} - 309960000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-9} + 1795185000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-8} \\ & - 6405840000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-7} + 15876840000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-6} - 28979193600 u_{i_1-2, i_2-5} + 39700710000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4} - 40432560000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} \\ & + 29652840000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 14154840000 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 3232021800 u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 11836800 u_{i_1-1, i_2-10} + 147960000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-9} - 856935000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-8} \\ & + 3057840000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-7} - 7578840000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-6} + 13833273600 u_{i_1-1, i_2-5} - 18951210000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4} + 19300560000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} \\ & - 14154840000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 6756840000 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 1542811800 u_{i_1-1, i_2} + 2702736 u_{i_1, i_2-10} - 33784200 u_{i_1, i_2-9} + 195666825 u_{i_1, i_2-8} \\ & - 698206800 u_{i_1, i_2-7} + 1730501800 u_{i_1, i_2-6} - 3158597472 u_{i_1, i_2-5} + 4327192950 u_{i_1, i_2-4} - 4406961200 u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 3232021800 u_{i_1, i_2-2} \end{aligned}$$

$- 1542811800 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 352275361 u_{i_1, i_2}$), $O(\Delta x_1^5 \Delta x_2^5)$, *Backward*

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $6.3779397365900833424 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $6.4172980024534166648 \times 10^{-28}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $6.4172980024534166648 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $6.4173374944802056854 \times 10^{-43}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $6.4173374944802056854 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $6.4173375339723665627 \times 10^{-58}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $6.4173375339723665627 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $6.4173375340118587238 \times 10^{-73}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $6.4173375340118587238 \times 10^{-73}$, *New Error:*, $6.4173375340118982159 \times 10^{-88}$

"--- Derivative Order: 4 - x1=2, x2=1, x3=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} (u_{i_1, i_2, i_3} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1} - u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3} + u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3}$$

$- 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3} - u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1}$), $O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3)$, *Forward*

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.11224949992131587345, *New Error:*, 0.00011188204341873068901

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00011188204341873068901, *New Error:*, $1.1188167682382424092 \times 10^{-7}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.1188167682382424092 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $1.1188167645723019447 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.1188167645723019447 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $1.1188167645686360042 \times 10^{-13}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.1188167645686360042 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $1.1188167645686323383 \times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} (u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3} - u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3} + 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1}$$

$- 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3} + u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1} - u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3}$), $O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3)$, *Backward*

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.11151557470688526899, *New Error:*, 0.00011188130949671748740

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00011188130949671748740, *New Error:*, $1.1188167608990222772 \times 10^{-7}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.1188167608990222772 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $1.1188167645649627245 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.1188167645649627245 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $1.1188167645686286650 \times 10^{-13}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.1188167645686286650 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $1.1188167645686323309 \times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{16 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} (81 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3} - 108 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1} + 27 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+2} - 108 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3} + 144 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 36 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 27 u_{il, i2+2, i3} - 36 u_{il, i2+2, i3+1} + 9 u_{il, i2+2, i3+2} - 216 u_{il+1, i2, i3} + 288 u_{il+1, i2, i3+1} - 72 u_{il+1, i2, i3+2} + 288 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3} - 384 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3+1} \\
& + 96 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3+2} - 72 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3} + 96 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3+1} - 24 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3+2} + 198 u_{il+2, i2, i3} - 264 u_{il+2, i2, i3+1} + 66 u_{il+2, i2, i3+2} - 264 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3} \\
& + 352 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3+1} - 88 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3+2} + 66 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3} - 88 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3+1} + 22 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3+2} - 72 u_{il+3, i2, i3} + 96 u_{il+3, i2, i3+1} - 24 u_{il+3, i2, i3+2} \\
& + 96 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3} - 128 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+1} + 32 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+2} - 24 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3} + 32 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+1} - 8 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+2} + 9 u_{il+4, i2, i3} - 12 u_{il+4, i2, i3+1} \\
& + 3 u_{il+4, i2, i3+2} - 12 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3} + 16 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+1} - 4 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+2} + 3 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3} - 4 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+1} + u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+2} \Big),
\end{aligned}$$

$O(\Delta x l^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3)$, Forward

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.00026066462752172850646, *New Error:*, $2.5988922643147387771 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5988922643147387771 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $2.5988845155674877100 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5988845155674877100 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $2.5988845078187457520 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5988845078187457520 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $2.5988845078109970100 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5988845078109970100 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $2.5988845078109892613 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x l^2 \partial x^2 \partial x^3} u(xl, x2, x3) &= \frac{1}{16 \Delta x l^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3} (u_{il-4, i2-2, i3-2} - 4 u_{il-4, i2-2, i3-1} + 3 u_{il-4, i2-2, i3} - 4 u_{il-4, i2-1, i3-2} + 16 u_{il-4, i2-1, i3-1} - 12 u_{il-4, i2-1, i3} \\
& + 3 u_{il-4, i2, i3-2} - 12 u_{il-4, i2, i3-1} + 9 u_{il-4, i2, i3} - 8 u_{il-3, i2-2, i3-2} + 32 u_{il-3, i2-2, i3-1} - 24 u_{il-3, i2-2, i3} + 32 u_{il-3, i2-1, i3-2} - 128 u_{il-3, i2-1, i3-1} \\
& + 96 u_{il-3, i2-1, i3} - 24 u_{il-3, i2, i3-2} + 96 u_{il-3, i2, i3-1} - 72 u_{il-3, i2, i3} + 22 u_{il-2, i2-2, i3-2} - 88 u_{il-2, i2-2, i3-1} + 66 u_{il-2, i2-2, i3} - 88 u_{il-2, i2-1, i3-2} \\
& + 352 u_{il-2, i2-1, i3-1} - 264 u_{il-2, i2-1, i3} + 66 u_{il-2, i2, i3-2} - 264 u_{il-2, i2, i3-1} + 198 u_{il-2, i2, i3} - 24 u_{il-1, i2-2, i3-2} + 96 u_{il-1, i2-2, i3-1} \\
& - 72 u_{il-1, i2-2, i3} + 96 u_{il-1, i2-1, i3-2} - 384 u_{il-1, i2-1, i3-1} + 288 u_{il-1, i2-1, i3} - 72 u_{il-1, i2, i3-2} + 288 u_{il-1, i2, i3-1} - 216 u_{il-1, i2, i3} + 9 u_{il, i2-2, i3-2} \\
& - 36 u_{il, i2-2, i3-1} + 27 u_{il, i2-2, i3} - 36 u_{il, i2-1, i3-2} + 144 u_{il, i2-1, i3-1} - 108 u_{il, i2-1, i3} + 27 u_{il, i2, i3-2} - 108 u_{il, i2, i3-1} + 81 u_{il, i2, i3} \Big),
\end{aligned}$$

$O(\Delta x l^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3)$, Backward

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.00025911333370201706641, *New Error:*, $2.5988767513178365806 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5988767513178365806 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $2.5988845000544908077 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5988845000544908077 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $2.5988845078032327551 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5988845078032327551 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $2.5988845078109814970 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5988845078109814970 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $2.5988845078109892458 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x l^2 \partial x^2 \partial x^3} u(xl, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{16 \Delta x l^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3} (u_{il-2, i2-1, i3-1} - u_{il-2, i2-1, i3+1} - u_{il-2, i2+1, i3-1} + u_{il-2, i2+1, i3+1} - 2 u_{il, i2-1, i3-1} + 2 u_{il, i2-1, i3+1}$$

$$+ 2 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3-1} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1} + u_{i_l+2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - u_{i_l+2, i_2-1, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3-1} + u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.00012994460127157215163, New Error: $1.2994422539092534307 \times 10^{-10}$
 Error order: 2, Error: $1.2994422539092534307 \times 10^{-10}$, New Error: $1.2994422539054946305 \times 10^{-16}$
 Error order: 2, Error: $1.2994422539054946305 \times 10^{-16}$, New Error: $1.2994422539054946268 \times 10^{-22}$
 Error order: 2, Error: $1.2994422539054946268 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error: $1.2994422539054946268 \times 10^{-28}$
 Error order: 2, Error: $1.2994422539054946268 \times 10^{-28}$, New Error: $1.2994422539054946268 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x I^2 \partial x^2 \partial x^3} u(xI, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{1296 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3} (14641 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3} - 23958 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1} + 11979 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+2} - 2662 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+3} - 23958 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3}$$

$$+ 39204 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 19602 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 4356 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+3} + 11979 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3} - 19602 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 9801 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 2178 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+3}$$

$$- 2662 u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3} + 4356 u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 2178 u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 484 u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3+3} - 47916 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3} + 78408 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1} - 39204 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+2}$$

$$+ 8712 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+3} + 78408 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3} - 128304 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 64152 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 14256 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+3} - 39204 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3}$$

$$+ 64152 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 32076 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 7128 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+3} + 8712 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3} - 14256 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 7128 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3+2}$$

$$- 1584 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3+3} + 63162 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3} - 103356 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1} + 51678 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+2} - 11484 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+3} - 103356 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3}$$

$$+ 169128 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 84564 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 18792 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+3} + 51678 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3} - 84564 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 42282 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+2}$$

$$- 9396 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+3} - 11484 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3} + 18792 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 9396 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 2088 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3+3} - 44528 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3}$$

$$+ 72864 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+1} - 36432 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+2} + 8096 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+3} + 72864 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3} - 119232 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 59616 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+2}$$

$$- 13248 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+3} - 36432 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3} + 59616 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 29808 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 6624 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+3} + 8096 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3}$$

$$- 13248 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 6624 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 1472 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3+3} + 18513 u_{i_l+4, i_2, i_3} - 30294 u_{i_l+4, i_2, i_3+1} + 15147 u_{i_l+4, i_2, i_3+2} - 3366 u_{i_l+4, i_2, i_3+3}$$

$$- 30294 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3} + 49572 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 24786 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 5508 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3+3} + 15147 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3} - 24786 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3+1}$$

$$+ 12393 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 2754 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3+3} - 3366 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3, i_3} + 5508 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 2754 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 612 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3, i_3+3}$$

$$- 4356 u_{i_l+5, i_2, i_3} + 7128 u_{i_l+5, i_2, i_3+1} - 3564 u_{i_l+5, i_2, i_3+2} + 792 u_{i_l+5, i_2, i_3+3} + 7128 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1, i_3} - 11664 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 5832 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1, i_3+2}$$

$$- 1296 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1, i_3+3} - 3564 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2, i_3} + 5832 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 2916 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 648 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2, i_3+3} + 792 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3, i_3}$$

$$- 1296 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 648 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 144 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3, i_3+3} + 484 u_{i_l+6, i_2, i_3} - 792 u_{i_l+6, i_2, i_3+1} + 396 u_{i_l+6, i_2, i_3+2} - 88 u_{i_l+6, i_2, i_3+3}$$

$$- 792 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1, i_3} + 1296 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 648 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 144 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1, i_3+3} + 396 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2, i_3} - 648 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 324 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2, i_3+2}$$

$$- 72 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2, i_3+3} - 88 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3, i_3} + 144 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 72 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 16 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3, i_3+3}), O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^3 \Delta x^3), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order: 3, Error: 7.7972967486747860149 $\times 10^{-7}$, New Error: 7.7565391185404616264 $\times 10^{-16}$

Error order:, 3, Error:., 7.7565391185404616264 × 10⁻¹⁶, New Error:., 7.7564984917948962667 × 10⁻²⁵

Error order:, 3, Error:., 7.7564984917948962667 × 10⁻²⁵, New Error:., 7.7564984511682811970 × 10⁻³⁴

Error order:, 3, Error:., 7.7564984511682811970 × 10⁻³⁴, New Error:., 7.7564984511276545821 × 10⁻⁴³

Error order:, 3, Error:., 7.7564984511276545821 × 10⁻⁴³, New Error:., 7.7564984511276139555 × 10⁻⁵²

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{1296 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} (16 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3, i_3-3} - 72 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3, i_3-2} + 144 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 88 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3, i_3} - 72 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2, i_3-3} + 324 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 648 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 396 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2, i_3} + 144 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1, i_3-3} - 648 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 1296 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 792 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1, i_3} - 88 u_{i_l-6, i_2, i_3-3} + 396 u_{i_l-6, i_2, i_3-2} - 792 u_{i_l-6, i_2, i_3-1} + 484 u_{i_l-6, i_2, i_3} - 144 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3, i_3-3} + 648 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3, i_3-2} - 1296 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3, i_3-1} + 792 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3, i_3} + 648 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2, i_3-3} - 2916 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 5832 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 3564 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2, i_3} - 1296 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1, i_3-3} + 5832 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 11664 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 7128 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1, i_3} + 792 u_{i_l-5, i_2, i_3-3} - 3564 u_{i_l-5, i_2, i_3-2} + 7128 u_{i_l-5, i_2, i_3-1} - 4356 u_{i_l-5, i_2, i_3} + 612 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3, i_3-3} - 2754 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3, i_3-2} + 5508 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 3366 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3, i_3} - 2754 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-3} + 12393 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 24786 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 15147 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3} + 5508 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-3} - 24786 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 49572 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 30294 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3} - 3366 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-3} + 15147 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-2} - 30294 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-1} + 18513 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3} - 1472 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3-3} + 6624 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3-2} - 13248 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3-1} + 8096 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3} + 6624 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-3} - 29808 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 59616 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 36432 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3} - 13248 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-3} + 59616 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 119232 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 72864 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3} + 8096 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-3} - 36432 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-2} + 72864 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-1} - 44528 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3} + 2088 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3, i_3-3} - 9396 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3, i_3-2} + 18792 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 11484 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3, i_3} - 9396 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-3} + 42282 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 84564 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 51678 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3} + 18792 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-3} - 84564 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 169128 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 103356 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3} - 11484 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-3} + 51678 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-2} - 103356 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1} + 63162 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3} - 1584 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3, i_3-3} + 7128 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3, i_3-2} - 14256 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3, i_3-1} + 8712 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3, i_3} + 7128 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-3} - 32076 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 64152 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 39204 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3} - 14256 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-3} + 64152 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 128304 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 78408 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3} + 8712 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-3} - 39204 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2} + 78408 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1} - 47916 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3} + 484 u_{i_l, i_2-3, i_3-3} - 2178 u_{i_l, i_2-3, i_3-2} + 4356 u_{i_l, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 2662 u_{i_l, i_2-3, i_3} - 2178 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-3} + 9801 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 19602 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 11979 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3} + 4356 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-3} - 19602 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 39204 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 23958 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3} - 2662 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-3} + 11979 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-2} - 23958 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1} + 14641 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3}), O(\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3 \Delta x_3^3), Backward$$

Error order:, 3, Error:., 7.7159614080720310994 × 10⁻⁷, New Error:., 7.7564577839760182033 × 10⁻¹⁶

Error order:, 3, Error:., 7.7564577839760182033 × 10⁻¹⁶, New Error:., 7.7564984104603318241 × 10⁻²⁵

Error order:, 3, Error:., 7.7564984104603318241 × 10⁻²⁵, New Error:., 7.7564984510869466326 × 10⁻³⁴

Error order:, 3, Error:., 7.7564984510869466326 $\times 10^{-34}$, New Error:., 7.7564984511275732475 $\times 10^{-43}$

Error order:, 3, Error:., 7.7564984511275732475 $\times 10^{-43}$, New Error:., 7.7564984511276138741 $\times 10^{-52}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3^2} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{20736 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} (u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 8 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 8 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3+1} - u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3+2} - 8 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-2}$$

$$+ 64 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 64 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3+1} + 8 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3+2} + 8 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1, i_3-2} - 64 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1, i_3-1} + 64 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 8 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1, i_3+2}$$

$$- u_{i_l-4, i_2+2, i_3-2} + 8 u_{i_l-4, i_2+2, i_3-1} - 8 u_{i_l-4, i_2+2, i_3+1} + u_{i_l-4, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 16 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3+1}$$

$$+ 16 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3+2} + 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 1024 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 1024 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3+1} - 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3+2} - 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1, i_3-2}$$

$$+ 1024 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1, i_3-1} - 1024 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 16 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2, i_3-2} - 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2, i_3-1} + 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 16 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2, i_3+2}$$

$$+ 64 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 512 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 512 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3+1} - 64 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3+2} - 512 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 4096 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 4096 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3+1}$$

$$+ 512 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3+2} + 512 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1, i_3-2} - 4096 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1, i_3-1} + 4096 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 512 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 64 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2, i_3-2}$$

$$+ 512 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2, i_3-1} - 512 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 64 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 16 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 128 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 128 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3+1} - 16 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3+2}$$

$$- 128 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 1024 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 1024 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1} + 128 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+2} + 128 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-2} - 1024 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1}$$

$$+ 1024 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 128 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 16 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2, i_3-2} + 128 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2, i_3-1} - 128 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 16 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 130 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2}$$

$$+ 1040 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 1040 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3+1} + 130 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3+2} + 1040 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 8320 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 8320 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3+1} - 1040 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3+2}$$

$$- 1040 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3-2} + 8320 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3-1} - 8320 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 1040 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 130 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3-2} - 1040 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3-1} + 1040 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+1}$$

$$- 130 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 16 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 128 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 128 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2, i_3+1} - 16 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2, i_3+2} - 128 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 1024 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1}$$

$$- 1024 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1} + 128 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+2} + 128 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-2} - 1024 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1} + 1024 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 128 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+2}$$

$$- 16 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3-2} + 128 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3-1} - 128 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 16 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 64 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 512 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 512 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2, i_3+1}$$

$$- 64 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2, i_3+2} - 512 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 4096 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 4096 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1, i_3+1} + 512 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1, i_3+2} + 512 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3-2}$$

$$- 4096 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3-1} + 4096 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 512 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 64 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3-2} + 512 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3-1} - 512 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 64 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+2}$$

$$- 16 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 128 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 128 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2, i_3+1} + 16 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2, i_3+2} + 128 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 1024 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 1024 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1, i_3+1}$$

$$- 128 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1, i_3+2} - 128 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3-2} + 1024 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3-1} - 1024 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 128 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 16 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3-2}$$

$$- 128 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3-1} + 128 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 16 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+2} + u_{i_l+4, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 8 u_{i_l+4, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 8 u_{i_l+4, i_2-2, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+4, i_2-2, i_3+2}$$

$$- 8 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 64 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 64 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1, i_3+1} + 8 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1, i_3+2} + 8 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3-2} - 64 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3-1} + 64 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3+1}$$

$$- 8 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3+2} - u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3-2} + 8 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3-1} - 8 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3+1} + u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3+2}), O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4 \Delta x_3^4), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.5185987993048086911 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $4.5185869134922760631 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.5185869134922760631 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $4.5185869134803902523 \times 10^{-34}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.5185869134803902523 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $4.5185869134803902405 \times 10^{-46}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.5185869134803902405 \times 10^{-46}$, *New Error:*, $4.5185869134803902405 \times 10^{-58}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.5185869134803902405 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $4.5185869134803902405 \times 10^{-70}$

"--- Derivative Order: 4 - x1=1, x2=1, x3=1, x4=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} + u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} - u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} + u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} - u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} - u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} + u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.41293325131388292553, *New Error:*, 0.00041101668626854689363

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00041101668626854689363, *New Error:*, $4.1101477608593045071 \times 10^{-7}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.1101477608593045071 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $4.1101477417575419983 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.1101477417575419983 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $4.1101477417384402358 \times 10^{-13}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.1101477417384402358 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $4.1101477417384211340 \times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} - u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} + u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} + u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} - u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} - u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.40910904095598431624, *New Error:*, 0.00041101286209188117698

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00041101286209188117698, *New Error:*, $4.1101477226175378502 \times 10^{-7}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.1101477226175378502 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $4.1101477417193002316 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.1101477417193002316 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $4.1101477417384019940 \times 10^{-13}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.1101477417384019940 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $4.1101477417384210958 \times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{\delta^4}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{16 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (81 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4} - 108 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} + 27 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+2} - 108 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} + 144 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 36 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+2} + 27 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+2, i_4} - 36 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+2, i_4+1} + 9 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+2, i_4+2} - 108 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} + 144 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} - 36 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+2} + 144 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} - 192 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} + 48 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+2} - 36 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+2, i_4} + 48 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+2, i_4+1} - 12 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+2, i_4+2} + 27 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3, i_4} - 36 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3, i_4+1} + 9 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3, i_4+2} - 36 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4} + 48 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 12 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+2} + 9 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+2, i_4} - 12 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+2, i_4+1} + 3 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+2, i_4+2} - 108 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4} + 144 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} - 36 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+2} + 144 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} - 192 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + 48 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+2} - 36 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+2, i_4} + 48 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+2, i_4+1} - 12 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+2, i_4+2} + 144 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} - 192 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} + 48 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+2} - 192 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} + 256 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 64 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+2} + 48 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+2, i_4} - 64 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+2, i_4+1} + 16 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+2, i_4+2} - 36 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3, i_4} + 48 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3, i_4+1} - 12 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3, i_4+2} + 48 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4} - 64 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + 16 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+2} - 12 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+2, i_4} + 16 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+2, i_4+1} - 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+2, i_4+2} + 27 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4} - 36 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} + 9 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4+2} - 36 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} + 48 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 12 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+2} + 9 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+2, i_4} - 12 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+2, i_4+1} + 3 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+2, i_4+2} - 36 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} + 48 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} - 12 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+2} + 48 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} - 64 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} + 16 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+2} - 12 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+2, i_4} + 16 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+2, i_4+1} - 4 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+2, i_4+2} + 9 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3, i_4} - 12 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3, i_4+1} + 3 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3, i_4+2} - 12 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4} + 16 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 4 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+2} + 3 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+2, i_4} - 4 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+2, i_4+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+2, i_4+2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2 \Delta x_4^2), Forward$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.0013993147491392397000, New Error: 1.3933159806849167895 $\times 10^{-9}$

Error order: 2, Error: 1.3933159806849167895 $\times 10^{-9}$, New Error: 1.3933099873609682166 $\times 10^{-15}$

Error order: 2, Error: 1.3933099873609682166 $\times 10^{-15}$, New Error: 1.3933099813676497660 $\times 10^{-21}$

Error order: 2, Error: 1.3933099813676497660 $\times 10^{-21}$, New Error: 1.3933099813616564475 $\times 10^{-27}$

Error order: 2, Error: 1.3933099813616564475 $\times 10^{-27}$, New Error: 1.3933099813616504542 $\times 10^{-33}$

$$\frac{\delta^4}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{16 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-2} - 4 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4} - 4 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-2} + 16 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 12 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} + 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-2} - 12 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1} + 9 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3, i_4} - 4 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-2} + 16 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-1} - 12 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4} + 16 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-2} - 64 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 48 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} - 12 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-2} + 48 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} - 36 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} + 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-2} - 12 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 9 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-2, i_4} - 12 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-2} + 48 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 36 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} + 9 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4-2} - 36 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + 27 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4} - 4 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-2} + 16 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-1} - 12 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4} + 16 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-2} - 64 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 48 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} - 12 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-2} + 48 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1} - 36 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3, i_4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 16 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-2} - 64 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 48 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4} - 64 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-2} + 256 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 192 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} \\
& + 48 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-2} - 192 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} + 144 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} - 12 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-2} + 48 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-1} - 36 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2, i_4} \\
& + 48 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-2} - 192 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 144 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} - 36 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-2} + 144 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} - 108 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4} + 3 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-2} \\
& - 12 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 9 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4} - 12 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-2} + 48 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 36 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} + 9 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-2} - 36 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1} \\
& + 27 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3, i_4} - 12 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-2} + 48 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-1} - 36 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4} + 48 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-2} - 192 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 144 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} \\
& - 36 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-2} + 144 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} - 108 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} + 9 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-2} - 36 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 27 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-2, i_4} - 36 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-2} \\
& + 144 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 108 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} + 27 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4-2} - 108 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + 81 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2 \Delta x_4^2), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.0013873162200472445914, New Error: 1.3933039820493912032 $\times 10^{-9}$

Error order: 2, Error: 1.3933039820493912032 $\times 10^{-9}$, New Error: 1.3933099753623326909 $\times 10^{-15}$

Error order: 2, Error: 1.3933099753623326909 $\times 10^{-15}$, New Error: 1.3933099813556511305 $\times 10^{-21}$

Error order: 2, Error: 1.3933099813556511305 $\times 10^{-21}$, New Error: 1.3933099813616444489 $\times 10^{-27}$

Error order: 2, Error: 1.3933099813616444489 $\times 10^{-27}$, New Error: 1.3933099813616504422 $\times 10^{-33}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\delta^4}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) &= \frac{1}{16 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1} \\
& - u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1} \\
& + u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1}), \\
& O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2 \Delta x_4^2), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.00069665916180310125787, New Error: 6.9665499068499633210 $\times 10^{-10}$

Error order: 2, Error: 6.9665499068499633210 $\times 10^{-10}$, New Error: 6.9665499068082522828 $\times 10^{-16}$

Error order: 2, Error: 6.9665499068082522828 $\times 10^{-16}$, New Error: 6.9665499068082522411 $\times 10^{-22}$

Error order: 2, Error: 6.9665499068082522411 $\times 10^{-22}$, New Error: 6.9665499068082522411 $\times 10^{-28}$

Error order: 2, Error: 6.9665499068082522411 $\times 10^{-28}$, New Error: 6.9665499068082522411 $\times 10^{-34}$

"--- Derivative Order: 5 - x1=5 ---"

$$\frac{d^5}{dx_1^5} u(x_1) = \frac{-u_{i_l} + 5 u_{i_l+1} - 10 u_{i_l+2} + 10 u_{i_l+3} - 5 u_{i_l+4} + u_{i_l+5}}{\Delta x_1^5}, O(\Delta x_1), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.013306271212498385240, *New Error:*, 0.000013270921949770770821
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000013270921949770770821, *New Error:*, $1.3270886666628846838 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.3270886666628846838 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.3270886631345770938 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.3270886631345770938 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.3270886631310487862 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.3270886631310487862 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.3270886631310452579 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI-5} + 5 u_{iI-4} - 10 u_{iI-3} + 10 u_{iI-2} - 5 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI}}{\Delta xI^5}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.013235634229978612704, *New Error:*, 0.000013270851312982313885
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000013270851312982313885, *New Error:*, $1.3270886595992058381 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.3270886595992058381 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.3270886631275134150 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.3270886631275134150 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.3270886631310417225 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.3270886631310417225 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.3270886631310452508 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{-243 u_{iI} + 1620 u_{iI+1} - 4725 u_{iI+2} + 7920 u_{iI+3} - 8430 u_{iI+4} + 5944 u_{iI+5} - 2810 u_{iI+6} + 880 u_{iI+7} - 175 u_{iI+8} + 20 u_{iI+9} - u_{iI+10}}{32 \Delta xI^5},$$

$O(\Delta xI^2)$, Forward

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000017685610635859472771, *New Error:*, $1.7659223550087109991 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7659223550087109991 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.7659197140621489395 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7659197140621489395 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.7659197114212001518 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7659197114212001518 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.7659197114185592030 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7659197114185592030 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $1.7659197114185565620 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-10} - 20 u_{iI-9} + 175 u_{iI-8} - 880 u_{iI-7} + 2810 u_{iI-6} - 5944 u_{iI-5} + 8430 u_{iI-4} - 7920 u_{iI-3} + 4725 u_{iI-2} - 1620 u_{iI-1} + 243 u_{iI}}{32 \Delta xI^5},$$

$O(\Delta xI^2)$, Backward

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000017632739033963519568, *New Error:*, $1.7659170678239462975 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7659170678239462975 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.7659197087749641748 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7659197087749641748 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.7659197114159129670 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7659197114159129670 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.7659197114185539158 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7659197114185539158 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $1.7659197114185565567 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI-5} + 5 u_{iI-3} - 10 u_{iI-1} + 10 u_{iI+1} - 5 u_{iI+3} + u_{iI+5}}{32 \Delta xI^5}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $8.8296120418303561866 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $8.8295985571062675219 \times 10^{-12}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $8.8295985571062675219 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $8.8295985570927828104 \times 10^{-18}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $8.8295985570927828104 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $8.8295985570927827969 \times 10^{-24}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $8.8295985570927827969 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $8.8295985570927827969 \times 10^{-30}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $8.8295985570927827969 \times 10^{-30}$, *New Error:*, $8.8295985570927827969 \times 10^{-36}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{7776 \Delta xI^5} (-161051 u_{iI} + 1317690 u_{iI+1} - 4971285 u_{iI+2} + 11515570 u_{iI+3} - 18395190 u_{iI+4} + 21560868 u_{iI+5} - 19238090 u_{iI+6} + 13359060 u_{iI+7} - 7305255 u_{iI+8} + 3156530 u_{iI+9} - 1072449 u_{iI+10} + 282330 u_{iI+11} - 55960 u_{iI+12} + 7920 u_{iI+13} - 720 u_{iI+14} + 32 u_{iI+15}),$$

$O(\Delta xI^3)$, *Forward*

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $2.6499331365761103349 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.6435987143296875408 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $2.6435987143296875408 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.6435923886950664327 \times 10^{-26}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $2.6435923886950664327 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $2.6435923823694405796 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $2.6435923823694405796 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $2.6435923823631149538 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $2.6435923823631149538 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $2.6435923823631086282 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{7776 \Delta xI^5} (-32 u_{iI-15} + 720 u_{iI-14} - 7920 u_{iI-13} + 55960 u_{iI-12} - 282330 u_{iI-11} + 1072449 u_{iI-10} - 3156530 u_{iI-9} + 7305255 u_{iI-8} - 13359060 u_{iI-7} + 19238090 u_{iI-6} - 21560868 u_{iI-5} + 18395190 u_{iI-4} - 11515570 u_{iI-3} + 4971285 u_{iI-2} - 1317690 u_{iI-1} + 161051 u_{iI}),$$

$O(\Delta xI^3)$, *Backward*

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $2.6372691819301929844 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.6435860504140833672 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $2.6435860504140833672 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.6435923760311508285 \times 10^{-26}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $2.6435923760311508285 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $2.6435923823567766640 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $2.6435923823567766640 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $2.6435923823631022899 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $2.6435923823631022899 \times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, $2.6435923823631086155 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{248832 \Delta xI^5} \left(-9765625 u_{iI} + 93750000 u_{iI+1} - 430312500 u_{iI+2} + 1262450000 u_{iI+3} - 2667111375 u_{iI+4} + 4328059968 u_{iI+5} \right. \\ \left. - 5611488880 u_{iI+6} + 5962833600 u_{iI+7} - 5280666570 u_{iI+8} + 3939498400 u_{iI+9} - 2490998136 u_{iI+10} + 1338063840 u_{iI+11} - 609778190 u_{iI+12} \right. \\ \left. + 234546240 u_{iI+13} - 75417840 u_{iI+14} + 19961536 u_{iI+15} - 4246125 u_{iI+16} + 699120 u_{iI+17} - 83700 u_{iI+18} + 6480 u_{iI+19} - 243 u_{iI+20} \right),$$

$O(\Delta xI^4)$, Forward

Error order:, 4, Error:, $4.2353741955057908426 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $4.2213192443357200471 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $4.2213192443357200471 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $4.2213052154211488612 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $4.2213052154211488612 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $4.2213052013922602917 \times 10^{-47}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $4.2213052013922602917 \times 10^{-47}$, New Error:, $4.2213052013782314031 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $4.2213052013782314031 \times 10^{-59}$, New Error:, $4.2213052013782173742 \times 10^{-71}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{248832 \Delta xI^5} \left(243 u_{iI-20} - 6480 u_{iI-19} + 83700 u_{iI-18} - 699120 u_{iI-17} + 4246125 u_{iI-16} - 19961536 u_{iI-15} + 75417840 u_{iI-14} \right. \\ \left. - 234546240 u_{iI-13} + 609778190 u_{iI-12} - 1338063840 u_{iI-11} + 2490998136 u_{iI-10} - 3939498400 u_{iI-9} + 5280666570 u_{iI-8} - 5962833600 u_{iI-7} \right. \\ \left. + 5611488880 u_{iI-6} - 4328059968 u_{iI-5} + 2667111375 u_{iI-4} - 1262450000 u_{iI-3} + 430312500 u_{iI-2} - 93750000 u_{iI-1} + 9765625 u_{iI} \right), O(\Delta xI^4),$$

Backward

Error order:, 4, Error:, $4.2072882626214848034 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $4.2212911584727700223 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $4.2212911584727700223 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $4.2213051873352859113 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $4.2213051873352859113 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $4.2213052013641744287 \times 10^{-47}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $4.2213052013641744287 \times 10^{-47}$, New Error:, $4.2213052013782033173 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 4, Error:, $4.2213052013782033173 \times 10^{-59}$, New Error:, $4.2213052013782173462 \times 10^{-71}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{248832 \Delta xI^5} \left(u_{iI-10} - 40 u_{iI-9} + 640 u_{iI-8} - 5080 u_{iI-7} + 19195 u_{iI-6} - 17248 u_{iI-5} - 83200 u_{iI-4} + 158560 u_{iI-3} + 106250 u_{iI-2} \right. \\ \left. - 353520 u_{iI-1} + 353520 u_{iI+1} - 106250 u_{iI+2} - 158560 u_{iI+3} + 83200 u_{iI+4} + 17248 u_{iI+5} - 19195 u_{iI+6} + 5080 u_{iI+7} - 640 u_{iI+8} + 40 u_{iI+9} \right. \\ \left. - u_{iI+10} \right), O(\Delta xI^4), Centered$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $7.0355120058383766778 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $7.0355086689670324817 \times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $7.0355086689670324817 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, $7.0355086689636956037 \times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $7.0355086689636956037 \times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, $7.0355086689636956003 \times 10^{-48}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $7.0355086689636956003 \times 10^{-48}$, *New Error:*, $7.0355086689636956003 \times 10^{-60}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $7.0355086689636956003 \times 10^{-60}$, *New Error:*, $7.0355086689636956003 \times 10^{-72}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{777600000 \Delta x I^5} \left(-48261724457 u_{iI} + 528413041500 u_{iI+1} - 2842630741500 u_{iI+2} + 10048340761000 u_{iI+3} - 26283334560375 u_{iI+4} \right.$$

$$+ 54226018971660 u_{iI+5} - 91746659966000 u_{iI+6} + 130588703916000 u_{iI+7} - 159112747250250 u_{iI+8} + 167964331379000 u_{iI+9}$$

$$- 154890959473320 u_{iI+10} + 125449854774000 u_{iI+11} - 89511004642750 u_{iI+12} + 56323676091000 u_{iI+13} - 31227231306000 u_{iI+14}$$

$$+ 15212065428320 u_{iI+15} - 6479368144125 u_{iI+16} + 2395483003500 u_{iI+17} - 760852381500 u_{iI+18} + 204689529000 u_{iI+19} - 45738451035 u_{iI+20}$$

$$+ 8258341500 u_{iI+21} - 1157004000 u_{iI+22} + 117936000 u_{iI+23} - 7776000 u_{iI+24} + 248832 u_{iI+25} \left. \right), O(\Delta x I^5), \textit{Forward}$$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $7.0515677207603341793 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $7.0214957694908064212 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $7.0214957694908064212 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $7.0214657675206503874 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $7.0214657675206503874 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $7.0214657375187500962 \times 10^{-59}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $7.0214657375187500962 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $7.0214657374887481959 \times 10^{-74}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $7.0214657374887481959 \times 10^{-74}$, *New Error:*, $7.0214657374887181940 \times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{777600000 \Delta x I^5} \left(-248832 u_{iI-25} + 7776000 u_{iI-24} - 117936000 u_{iI-23} + 1157004000 u_{iI-22} - 8258341500 u_{iI-21} + 45738451035 u_{iI-20} \right.$$

$$- 204689529000 u_{iI-19} + 760852381500 u_{iI-18} - 2395483003500 u_{iI-17} + 6479368144125 u_{iI-16} - 15212065428320 u_{iI-15} + 31227231306000 u_{iI-14}$$

$$- 56323676091000 u_{iI-13} + 89511004642750 u_{iI-12} - 125449854774000 u_{iI-11} + 154890959473320 u_{iI-10} - 167964331379000 u_{iI-9}$$

$$+ 159112747250250 u_{iI-8} - 130588703916000 u_{iI-7} + 91746659966000 u_{iI-6} - 54226018971660 u_{iI-5} + 26283334560375 u_{iI-4}$$

$$- 10048340761000 u_{iI-3} + 2842630741500 u_{iI-2} - 528413041500 u_{iI-1} + 48261724457 u_{iI} \left. \right), O(\Delta x I^5), \textit{Backward}$$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $6.9915036238026777566 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $7.0214357056264991850 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $7.0214357056264991850 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $7.0214657074567860804 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $7.0214657074567860804 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $7.0214657374586862319 \times 10^{-59}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $7.0214657374586862319 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $7.0214657374886881321 \times 10^{-74}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $7.0214657374886881321 \times 10^{-74}$, *New Error:*, $7.0214657374887181340 \times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{777600000 \Delta xI^5} \left(-68641485507 u_{iI} + 840507985800 u_{iI+1} - 5167408790250 u_{iI+2} + 21307727322000 u_{iI+3} - 66258446806125 u_{iI+4} \right. \\ + 165387257057160 u_{iI+5} - 344190355292250 u_{iI+6} + 612296403984000 u_{iI+7} - 947250833271750 u_{iI+8} + 1290077380962000 u_{iI+9} \\ - 1560372299054820 u_{iI+10} + 1686662472636000 u_{iI+11} - 1636459097552250 u_{iI+12} + 1429133579442000 u_{iI+13} - 1125045703930500 u_{iI+14} \\ + 798586097120320 u_{iI+15} - 510702064059375 u_{iI+16} + 293676015249000 u_{iI+17} - 151386920509250 u_{iI+18} + 69655282362000 u_{iI+19} \\ - 28443813289785 u_{iI+20} + 10233032857000 u_{iI+21} - 3213329357250 u_{iI+22} + 870338232000 u_{iI+23} - 200244703000 u_{iI+24} + 38352877632 u_{iI+25} \\ \left. - 5947642800 u_{iI+26} + 717248000 u_{iI+27} - 63090000 u_{iI+28} + 3600000 u_{iI+29} - 100000 u_{iI+30} \right), O(\Delta xI^6), \textit{Forward}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2075891202312010541 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $1.2012835802752701907 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2012835802752701907 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.2012772924341890771 \times 10^{-52}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2012772924341890771 \times 10^{-52}$, *New Error:*, $1.2012772861463656597 \times 10^{-70}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2012772861463656597 \times 10^{-70}$, *New Error:*, $1.2012772861400778363 \times 10^{-88}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2012772861400778363 \times 10^{-88}$, *New Error:*, $1.2012772861400715485 \times 10^{-106}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{777600000 \Delta xI^5} \left(100000 u_{iI-30} - 3600000 u_{iI-29} + 63090000 u_{iI-28} - 717248000 u_{iI-27} + 5947642800 u_{iI-26} - 38352877632 u_{iI-25} \right. \\ + 200244703000 u_{iI-24} - 870338232000 u_{iI-23} + 3213329357250 u_{iI-22} - 10233032857000 u_{iI-21} + 28443813289785 u_{iI-20} \\ - 69655282362000 u_{iI-19} + 151386920509250 u_{iI-18} - 293676015249000 u_{iI-17} + 510702064059375 u_{iI-16} - 798586097120320 u_{iI-15} \\ + 1125045703930500 u_{iI-14} - 1429133579442000 u_{iI-13} + 1636459097552250 u_{iI-12} - 1686662472636000 u_{iI-11} + 1560372299054820 u_{iI-10} \\ - 1290077380962000 u_{iI-9} + 947250833271750 u_{iI-8} - 612296403984000 u_{iI-7} + 344190355292250 u_{iI-6} - 165387257057160 u_{iI-5} \\ \left. + 66258446806125 u_{iI-4} - 21307727322000 u_{iI-3} + 5167408790250 u_{iI-2} - 840507985800 u_{iI-1} + 68641485507 u_{iI} \right), O(\Delta xI^6), \textit{Backward}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.1950008149836719489 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $1.2012709920402357185 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2012709920402357185 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.2012772798459540427 \times 10^{-52}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2012772798459540427 \times 10^{-52}$, *New Error:*, $1.2012772861337774247 \times 10^{-70}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2012772861337774247 \times 10^{-70}$, *New Error:*, $1.2012772861400652481 \times 10^{-88}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $1.2012772861400652481 \times 10^{-88}$, *New Error:*, $1.2012772861400715359 \times 10^{-106}$

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{777600000 \Delta xI^5} \left(-u_{iI-15} + 45 u_{iI-14} - 1035 u_{iI-13} + 15390 u_{iI-12} - 162180 u_{iI-11} + 1253754 u_{iI-10} - 7156750 u_{iI-9} + 29385000 u_{iI-8} \right. \\ \left. - 79929900 u_{iI-7} + 103501800 u_{iI-6} + 127101870 u_{iI-5} - 733473450 u_{iI-4} + 707225975 u_{iI-3} + 1032540075 u_{iI-2} - 2131469775 u_{iI-1} \right. \\ \left. + 2131469775 u_{iI+1} - 1032540075 u_{iI+2} - 707225975 u_{iI+3} + 733473450 u_{iI+4} - 127101870 u_{iI+5} - 103501800 u_{iI+6} + 79929900 u_{iI+7} \right. \\ \left. - 29385000 u_{iI+8} + 7156750 u_{iI+9} - 1253754 u_{iI+10} + 162180 u_{iI+11} - 15390 u_{iI+12} + 1035 u_{iI+13} - 45 u_{iI+14} + u_{iI+15} \right), O(\Delta xI^6), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order: 6, Error: 6.0063910837053927026 × 10⁻¹⁸, New Error: 6.0063864307050107141 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order: 6, Error: 6.0063864307050107141 × 10⁻³⁶, New Error: 6.0063864307003577155 × 10⁻⁵⁴
Error order: 6, Error: 6.0063864307003577155 × 10⁻⁵⁴, New Error: 6.0063864307003577109 × 10⁻⁷²
Error order: 6, Error: 6.0063864307003577109 × 10⁻⁷², New Error: 6.0063864307003577109 × 10⁻⁹⁰
Error order: 6, Error: 6.0063864307003577109 × 10⁻⁹⁰, New Error: 6.0063864307003577109 × 10⁻¹⁰⁸

$$\frac{d^5}{dxI^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{418211942400000 \Delta xI^5} \left(243 u_{iI-20} - 12960 u_{iI-19} + 344520 u_{iI-18} - 6124320 u_{iI-17} + 81409920 u_{iI-16} - 854197472 u_{iI-15} \right. \\ \left. + 7290970680 u_{iI-14} - 51457553760 u_{iI-13} + 302261632065 u_{iI-12} - 1475417742720 u_{iI-11} + 5916664106208 u_{iI-10} - 18978256350080 u_{iI-9} \right. \\ \left. + 45900070375680 u_{iI-8} - 70546255946880 u_{iI-7} + 11990183127840 u_{iI-6} + 257454226566528 u_{iI-5} - 636289049688450 u_{iI-4} \right. \\ \left. + 355675594868800 u_{iI-3} + 1021558686990000 u_{iI-2} - 1672758357969600 u_{iI-1} + 1672758357969600 u_{iI+1} - 1021558686990000 u_{iI+2} \right. \\ \left. - 355675594868800 u_{iI+3} + 636289049688450 u_{iI+4} - 257454226566528 u_{iI+5} - 11990183127840 u_{iI+6} + 70546255946880 u_{iI+7} \right. \\ \left. - 45900070375680 u_{iI+8} + 18978256350080 u_{iI+9} - 5916664106208 u_{iI+10} + 1475417742720 u_{iI+11} - 302261632065 u_{iI+12} + 51457553760 u_{iI+13} \right. \\ \left. - 7290970680 u_{iI+14} + 854197472 u_{iI+15} - 81409920 u_{iI+16} + 6124320 u_{iI+17} - 344520 u_{iI+18} + 12960 u_{iI+19} - 243 u_{iI+20} \right), O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order: 8, Error: 5.3177237956946037945 × 10⁻²⁴, New Error: 5.3177180176855284783 × 10⁻⁴⁸
Error order: 8, Error: 5.3177180176855284783 × 10⁻⁴⁸, New Error: 5.3177180176797504724 × 10⁻⁷²
Error order: 8, Error: 5.3177180176797504724 × 10⁻⁷², New Error: 5.3177180176797504666 × 10⁻⁹⁶
Error order: 8, Error: 5.3177180176797504666 × 10⁻⁹⁶, New Error: 5.3177180176797504666 × 10⁻¹²⁰
Error order: 8, Error: 5.3177180176797504666 × 10⁻¹²⁰, New Error: 5.3177180176797504666 × 10⁻¹⁴⁴

"--- Derivative Order: 5 - x1=4, x2=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{-u_{i_1, i_2} + u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 4u_{i_1+1, i_2} - 4u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 6u_{i_1+2, i_2} + 6u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 4u_{i_1+3, i_2} - 4u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - u_{i_1+4, i_2} + u_{i_1+4, i_2+1}}{\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2},$$

$O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2)$, Forward

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.039049211663948053709, New Error:, 0.000038934905769619320716

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000038934905769619320716, New Error:, $3.8934791699645233431 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $3.8934791699645233431 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $3.8934791585575494882 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $3.8934791585575494882 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $3.8934791585461425144 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $3.8934791585461425144 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $3.8934791585461311074 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{-u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + u_{i_1-4, i_2} + 4u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 4u_{i_1-3, i_2} - 6u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 6u_{i_1-2, i_2} + 4u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 4u_{i_1-1, i_2} - u_{i_1, i_2-1} + u_{i_1, i_2}}{\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2},$$

$O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2)$, Backward

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.038820843054893070516, New Error:, 0.000038934677401774848090

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000038934677401774848090, New Error:, $3.8934791471277388960 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $3.8934791471277388960 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $3.8934791585347127037 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $3.8934791585347127037 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $3.8934791585461196776 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $3.8934791585461196776 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $3.8934791585461310846 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2} (-243 u_{i_1, i_2} + 324 u_{i_1, i_2+1} - 81 u_{i_1, i_2+2} + 1296 u_{i_1+1, i_2} - 1728 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} + 432 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} - 2916 u_{i_1+2, i_2} + 3888 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} - 972 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} + 3600 u_{i_1+3, i_2} - 4800 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} + 1200 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} - 2658 u_{i_1+4, i_2} + 3544 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} - 886 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} + 1200 u_{i_1+5, i_2} - 1600 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} + 400 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} - 324 u_{i_1+6, i_2} + 432 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} - 108 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} + 48 u_{i_1+7, i_2} - 64 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} + 16 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} - 3 u_{i_1+8, i_2} + 4 u_{i_1+8, i_2+1} - u_{i_1+8, i_2+2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2), Forward$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000058951935993261707284, New Error:, $5.8848223429027920068 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8848223429027920068 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $5.8848119647327224535 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8848119647327224535 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $5.8848119543545455240 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8848119543545455240 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $5.8848119543441673471 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8848119543441673471 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $5.8848119543441569689 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} (u_{iI-8, i2-2} - 4 u_{iI-8, i2-1} + 3 u_{iI-8, i2} - 16 u_{iI-7, i2-2} + 64 u_{iI-7, i2-1} - 48 u_{iI-7, i2} + 108 u_{iI-6, i2-2} - 432 u_{iI-6, i2-1} + 324 u_{iI-6, i2} - 400 u_{iI-5, i2-2} + 1600 u_{iI-5, i2-1} - 1200 u_{iI-5, i2} + 886 u_{iI-4, i2-2} - 3544 u_{iI-4, i2-1} + 2658 u_{iI-4, i2} - 1200 u_{iI-3, i2-2} + 4800 u_{iI-3, i2-1} - 3600 u_{iI-3, i2} + 972 u_{iI-2, i2-2} - 3888 u_{iI-2, i2-1} + 2916 u_{iI-2, i2} - 432 u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 1728 u_{iI-1, i2-1} - 1296 u_{iI-1, i2} + 81 u_{iI, i2-2} - 324 u_{iI, i2-1} + 243 u_{iI, i2}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000058744165757101071977, New Error: 5.8848015657717884360 × 10⁻¹¹

Error order: 2, Error: 5.8848015657717884360 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 5.8848119439555914498 × 10⁻¹⁷

Error order: 2, Error: 5.8848119439555914498 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 5.8848119543337683930 × 10⁻²³

Error order: 2, Error: 5.8848119543337683930 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 5.8848119543441465699 × 10⁻²⁹

Error order: 2, Error: 5.8848119543441465699 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 5.8848119543441569481 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{-u_{iI-4, i2-1} + u_{iI-4, i2+1} + 4 u_{iI-2, i2-1} - 4 u_{iI-2, i2+1} - 6 u_{iI, i2-1} + 6 u_{iI, i2+1} + 4 u_{iI+2, i2-1} - 4 u_{iI+2, i2+1} - u_{iI+4, i2-1} + u_{iI+4, i2+1}}{32 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2},$$

O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), Centered

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000029424115126214622328, New Error: 2.9424059771776139223 × 10⁻¹¹

Error order: 2, Error: 2.9424059771776139223 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 2.9424059771720784848 × 10⁻¹⁷

Error order: 2, Error: 2.9424059771720784848 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 2.9424059771720784793 × 10⁻²³

Error order: 2, Error: 2.9424059771720784793 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 2.9424059771720784793 × 10⁻²⁹

Error order: 2, Error: 2.9424059771720784793 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 2.9424059771720784793 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{7776 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} (-161051 u_{iI, i2} + 263538 u_{iI, i2+1} - 131769 u_{iI, i2+2} + 29282 u_{iI, i2+3} + 1054152 u_{iI+1, i2} - 1724976 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + 862488 u_{iI+1, i2+2} - 191664 u_{iI+1, i2+3} - 3114540 u_{iI+2, i2} + 5096520 u_{iI+2, i2+1} - 2548260 u_{iI+2, i2+2} + 566280 u_{iI+2, i2+3} + 5527280 u_{iI+3, i2} - 9044640 u_{iI+3, i2+1} + 4522320 u_{iI+3, i2+2} - 1004960 u_{iI+3, i2+3} - 6610626 u_{iI+4, i2} + 10817388 u_{iI+4, i2+1} - 5408694 u_{iI+4, i2+2} + 1201932 u_{iI+4, i2+3} + 5654880 u_{iI+5, i2} - 9253440 u_{iI+5, i2+1} + 4626720 u_{iI+5, i2+2} - 1028160 u_{iI+5, i2+3} - 3570996 u_{iI+6, i2} + 5843448 u_{iI+6, i2+1} - 2921724 u_{iI+6, i2+2} + 649272 u_{iI+6, i2+3} + 1686960 u_{iI+7, i2} - 2760480 u_{iI+7, i2+1} + 1380240 u_{iI+7, i2+2} - 306720 u_{iI+7, i2+3} - 594891 u_{iI+8, i2} + 973458 u_{iI+8, i2+1})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -486729 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} + 108162 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} + 153560 u_{i_l+9, i_2} - 251280 u_{i_l+9, i_2+1} + 125640 u_{i_l+9, i_2+2} - 27920 u_{i_l+9, i_2+3} - 27720 u_{i_l+10, i_2} \\
& + 45360 u_{i_l+10, i_2+1} - 22680 u_{i_l+10, i_2+2} + 5040 u_{i_l+10, i_2+3} + 3168 u_{i_l+11, i_2} - 5184 u_{i_l+11, i_2+1} + 2592 u_{i_l+11, i_2+2} - 576 u_{i_l+11, i_2+3} - 176 u_{i_l+12, i_2} \\
& + 288 u_{i_l+12, i_2+1} - 144 u_{i_l+12, i_2+2} + 32 u_{i_l+12, i_2+3}), O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2^3), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.0419169818086639118 \times 10^{-7}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.0388596051963353492 \times 10^{-16}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.0388596051963353492 \times 10^{-16}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.0388565532389156457 \times 10^{-25}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.0388565532389156457 \times 10^{-25}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.0388565501869636324 \times 10^{-34}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.0388565501869636324 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.0388565501839116803 \times 10^{-43}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.0388565501839116803 \times 10^{-43}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.0388565501839086284 \times 10^{-52}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{7776 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} (-32 u_{i_l-12, i_2-3} + 144 u_{i_l-12, i_2-2} - 288 u_{i_l-12, i_2-1} + 176 u_{i_l-12, i_2} + 576 u_{i_l-11, i_2-3} - 2592 u_{i_l-11, i_2-2} \\
& + 5184 u_{i_l-11, i_2-1} - 3168 u_{i_l-11, i_2} - 5040 u_{i_l-10, i_2-3} + 22680 u_{i_l-10, i_2-2} - 45360 u_{i_l-10, i_2-1} + 27720 u_{i_l-10, i_2} + 27920 u_{i_l-9, i_2-3} \\
& - 125640 u_{i_l-9, i_2-2} + 251280 u_{i_l-9, i_2-1} - 153560 u_{i_l-9, i_2} - 108162 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 486729 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 973458 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 594891 u_{i_l-8, i_2} \\
& + 306720 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 1380240 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 2760480 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 1686960 u_{i_l-7, i_2} - 649272 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 2921724 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 5843448 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} \\
& + 3570996 u_{i_l-6, i_2} + 1028160 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 4626720 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 9253440 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 5654880 u_{i_l-5, i_2} - 1201932 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 5408694 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} \\
& - 10817388 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 6610626 u_{i_l-4, i_2} + 1004960 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 4522320 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 9044640 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 5527280 u_{i_l-3, i_2} - 566280 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} \\
& + 2548260 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 5096520 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 3114540 u_{i_l-2, i_2} + 191664 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 862488 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 1724976 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 1054152 u_{i_l-1, i_2} \\
& - 29282 u_{i_l, i_2-3} + 131769 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 263538 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 161051 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2^3), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.0358069421326275638 \times 10^{-7}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.0388534951823053968 \times 10^{-16}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.0388534951823053968 \times 10^{-16}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.0388565471289016158 \times 10^{-25}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.0388565471289016158 \times 10^{-25}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.0388565501808536183 \times 10^{-34}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.0388565501808536183 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.0388565501839055703 \times 10^{-43}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.0388565501839055703 \times 10^{-43}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.0388565501839086223 \times 10^{-52}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{248832 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} (-9765625 u_{i_l, i_2} + 18750000 u_{i_l, i_2+1} - 14062500 u_{i_l, i_2+2} + 6250000 u_{i_l, i_2+3} - 1171875 u_{i_l, i_2+4} \\
& + 75000000 u_{i_l+1, i_2} - 144000000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} + 108000000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} - 48000000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} + 9000000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} - 272250000 u_{i_l+2, i_2} \\
& + 522720000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} - 392040000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} + 174240000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} - 32670000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} + 625480000 u_{i_l+3, i_2} - 1200921600 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 900691200 u_{il+3, i2+2} - 400307200 u_{il+3, i2+3} + 75057600 u_{il+3, i2+4} - 1024977900 u_{il+4, i2} + 1967957568 u_{il+4, i2+1} - 1475968176 u_{il+4, i2+2} \\
& + 655985856 u_{il+4, i2+3} - 122997348 u_{il+4, i2+4} + 1276171200 u_{il+5, i2} - 2450248704 u_{il+5, i2+1} + 1837686528 u_{il+5, i2+2} - 816749568 u_{il+5, i2+3} \\
& + 153140544 u_{il+5, i2+4} - 1252294800 u_{il+6, i2} + 2404406016 u_{il+6, i2+1} - 1803304512 u_{il+6, i2+2} + 801468672 u_{il+6, i2+3} - 150275376 u_{il+6, i2+4} \\
& + 989697600 u_{il+7, i2} - 1900219392 u_{il+7, i2+1} + 1425164544 u_{il+7, i2+2} - 633406464 u_{il+7, i2+3} + 118763712 u_{il+7, i2+4} - 637395750 u_{il+8, i2} \\
& + 1223799840 u_{il+8, i2+1} - 917849880 u_{il+8, i2+2} + 407933280 u_{il+8, i2+3} - 76487490 u_{il+8, i2+4} + 335924800 u_{il+9, i2} - 644975616 u_{il+9, i2+1} \\
& + 483731712 u_{il+9, i2+2} - 214991872 u_{il+9, i2+3} + 40310976 u_{il+9, i2+4} - 144490800 u_{il+10, i2} + 277422336 u_{il+10, i2+1} - 208066752 u_{il+10, i2+2} \\
& + 92474112 u_{il+10, i2+3} - 17338896 u_{il+10, i2+4} + 50212800 u_{il+11, i2} - 96408576 u_{il+11, i2+1} + 72306432 u_{il+11, i2+2} - 32136192 u_{il+11, i2+3} \\
& + 6025536 u_{il+11, i2+4} - 13823500 u_{il+12, i2} + 26541120 u_{il+12, i2+1} - 19905840 u_{il+12, i2+2} + 8847040 u_{il+12, i2+3} - 1658820 u_{il+12, i2+4} \\
& + 2913600 u_{il+13, i2} - 5594112 u_{il+13, i2+1} + 4195584 u_{il+13, i2+2} - 1864704 u_{il+13, i2+3} + 349632 u_{il+13, i2+4} - 442800 u_{il+14, i2} + 850176 u_{il+14, i2+1} \\
& - 637632 u_{il+14, i2+2} + 283392 u_{il+14, i2+3} - 53136 u_{il+14, i2+4} + 43200 u_{il+15, i2} - 82944 u_{il+15, i2+1} + 62208 u_{il+15, i2+2} - 27648 u_{il+15, i2+3} \\
& + 5184 u_{il+15, i2+4} - 2025 u_{il+16, i2} + 3888 u_{il+16, i2+1} - 2916 u_{il+16, i2+2} + 1296 u_{il+16, i2+3} - 243 u_{il+16, i2+4} \Big), O(\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^4), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.0453514583184199747 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $2.0366800021264642041 \times 10^{-22}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.0366800021264642041 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $2.0366713519676954766 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.0366713519676954766 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $2.0366713433175579661 \times 10^{-46}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.0366713433175579661 \times 10^{-46}$, *New Error:*, $2.0366713433089078286 \times 10^{-58}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $2.0366713433089078286 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $2.0366713433088991785 \times 10^{-70}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{248832 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} (243 u_{il-16, i2-4} - 1296 u_{il-16, i2-3} + 2916 u_{il-16, i2-2} - 3888 u_{il-16, i2-1} + 2025 u_{il-16, i2} - 5184 u_{il-15, i2-4} \\
& + 27648 u_{il-15, i2-3} - 62208 u_{il-15, i2-2} + 82944 u_{il-15, i2-1} - 43200 u_{il-15, i2} + 53136 u_{il-14, i2-4} - 283392 u_{il-14, i2-3} + 637632 u_{il-14, i2-2} \\
& - 850176 u_{il-14, i2-1} + 442800 u_{il-14, i2} - 349632 u_{il-13, i2-4} + 1864704 u_{il-13, i2-3} - 4195584 u_{il-13, i2-2} + 5594112 u_{il-13, i2-1} - 2913600 u_{il-13, i2} \\
& + 1658820 u_{il-12, i2-4} - 8847040 u_{il-12, i2-3} + 19905840 u_{il-12, i2-2} - 26541120 u_{il-12, i2-1} + 13823500 u_{il-12, i2} - 6025536 u_{il-11, i2-4} \\
& + 32136192 u_{il-11, i2-3} - 72306432 u_{il-11, i2-2} + 96408576 u_{il-11, i2-1} - 50212800 u_{il-11, i2} + 17338896 u_{il-10, i2-4} - 92474112 u_{il-10, i2-3} \\
& + 208066752 u_{il-10, i2-2} - 277422336 u_{il-10, i2-1} + 144490800 u_{il-10, i2} - 40310976 u_{il-9, i2-4} + 214991872 u_{il-9, i2-3} - 483731712 u_{il-9, i2-2} \\
& + 644975616 u_{il-9, i2-1} - 335924800 u_{il-9, i2} + 76487490 u_{il-8, i2-4} - 407933280 u_{il-8, i2-3} + 917849880 u_{il-8, i2-2} - 1223799840 u_{il-8, i2-1} \\
& + 637395750 u_{il-8, i2} - 118763712 u_{il-7, i2-4} + 633406464 u_{il-7, i2-3} - 1425164544 u_{il-7, i2-2} + 1900219392 u_{il-7, i2-1} - 989697600 u_{il-7, i2} \\
& + 150275376 u_{il-6, i2-4} - 801468672 u_{il-6, i2-3} + 1803304512 u_{il-6, i2-2} - 2404406016 u_{il-6, i2-1} + 1252294800 u_{il-6, i2} - 153140544 u_{il-5, i2-4}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 816749568 u_{iI-5, i2-3} - 1837686528 u_{iI-5, i2-2} + 2450248704 u_{iI-5, i2-1} - 1276171200 u_{iI-5, i2} + 122997348 u_{iI-4, i2-4} - 655985856 u_{iI-4, i2-3} \\
& + 1475968176 u_{iI-4, i2-2} - 1967957568 u_{iI-4, i2-1} + 1024977900 u_{iI-4, i2} - 75057600 u_{iI-3, i2-4} + 400307200 u_{iI-3, i2-3} - 900691200 u_{iI-3, i2-2} \\
& + 1200921600 u_{iI-3, i2-1} - 625480000 u_{iI-3, i2} + 32670000 u_{iI-2, i2-4} - 174240000 u_{iI-2, i2-3} + 392040000 u_{iI-2, i2-2} - 522720000 u_{iI-2, i2-1} \\
& + 272250000 u_{iI-2, i2} - 9000000 u_{iI-1, i2-4} + 48000000 u_{iI-1, i2-3} - 108000000 u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 144000000 u_{iI-1, i2-1} - 75000000 u_{iI-1, i2} \\
& + 1171875 u_{iI, i2-4} - 6250000 u_{iI, i2-3} + 14062500 u_{iI, i2-2} - 18750000 u_{iI, i2-1} + 9765625 u_{iI, i2}), O(\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^4), \textit{Backward} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 4, \textit{Error:}, 2.0280337875087540454 \times 10^{-10}, \textit{New Error:}, 2.0366626845338932641 \times 10^{-22} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 4, \textit{Error:}, 2.0366626845338932641 \times 10^{-22}, \textit{New Error:}, 2.0366713346501029057 \times 10^{-34} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 4, \textit{Error:}, 2.0366713346501029057 \times 10^{-34}, \textit{New Error:}, 2.0366713433002403736 \times 10^{-46} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 4, \textit{Error:}, 2.0366713433002403736 \times 10^{-46}, \textit{New Error:}, 2.0366713433088905110 \times 10^{-58} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 4, \textit{Error:}, 2.0366713433088905110 \times 10^{-58}, \textit{New Error:}, 2.0366713433088991612 \times 10^{-70}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{248832 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} (u_{iI-8, i2-2} - 8 u_{iI-8, i2-1} + 8 u_{iI-8, i2+1} - u_{iI-8, i2+2} - 32 u_{iI-7, i2-2} + 256 u_{iI-7, i2-1} - 256 u_{iI-7, i2+1} \\
& + 32 u_{iI-7, i2+2} + 384 u_{iI-6, i2-2} - 3072 u_{iI-6, i2-1} + 3072 u_{iI-6, i2+1} - 384 u_{iI-6, i2+2} - 2016 u_{iI-5, i2-2} + 16128 u_{iI-5, i2-1} - 16128 u_{iI-5, i2+1} \\
& + 2016 u_{iI-5, i2+2} + 3324 u_{iI-4, i2-2} - 26592 u_{iI-4, i2-1} + 26592 u_{iI-4, i2+1} - 3324 u_{iI-4, i2+2} + 6240 u_{iI-3, i2-2} - 49920 u_{iI-3, i2-1} + 49920 u_{iI-3, i2+1} \\
& - 6240 u_{iI-3, i2+2} - 16768 u_{iI-2, i2-2} + 134144 u_{iI-2, i2-1} - 134144 u_{iI-2, i2+1} + 16768 u_{iI-2, i2+2} - 4192 u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 33536 u_{iI-1, i2-1} \\
& - 33536 u_{iI-1, i2+1} + 4192 u_{iI-1, i2+2} + 26118 u_{iI, i2-2} - 208944 u_{iI, i2-1} + 208944 u_{iI, i2+1} - 26118 u_{iI, i2+2} - 4192 u_{iI+1, i2-2} + 33536 u_{iI+1, i2-1} \\
& - 33536 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + 4192 u_{iI+1, i2+2} - 16768 u_{iI+2, i2-2} + 134144 u_{iI+2, i2-1} - 134144 u_{iI+2, i2+1} + 16768 u_{iI+2, i2+2} + 6240 u_{iI+3, i2-2} \\
& - 49920 u_{iI+3, i2-1} + 49920 u_{iI+3, i2+1} - 6240 u_{iI+3, i2+2} + 3324 u_{iI+4, i2-2} - 26592 u_{iI+4, i2-1} + 26592 u_{iI+4, i2+1} - 3324 u_{iI+4, i2+2} - 2016 u_{iI+5, i2-2} \\
& + 16128 u_{iI+5, i2-1} - 16128 u_{iI+5, i2+1} + 2016 u_{iI+5, i2+2} + 384 u_{iI+6, i2-2} - 3072 u_{iI+6, i2-1} + 3072 u_{iI+6, i2+1} - 384 u_{iI+6, i2+2} - 32 u_{iI+7, i2-2} \\
& + 256 u_{iI+7, i2-1} - 256 u_{iI+7, i2+1} + 32 u_{iI+7, i2+2} + u_{iI+8, i2-2} - 8 u_{iI+8, i2-1} + 8 u_{iI+8, i2+1} - u_{iI+8, i2+2}), O(\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^4), \textit{Centered} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 4, \textit{Error:}, 3.3944549669934449103 \times 10^{-11}, \textit{New Error:}, 3.3944522388508934323 \times 10^{-23} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 4, \textit{Error:}, 3.3944522388508934323 \times 10^{-23}, \textit{New Error:}, 3.3944522388481652858 \times 10^{-35} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 4, \textit{Error:}, 3.3944522388481652858 \times 10^{-35}, \textit{New Error:}, 3.3944522388481652831 \times 10^{-47} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 4, \textit{Error:}, 3.3944522388481652831 \times 10^{-47}, \textit{New Error:}, 3.3944522388481652831 \times 10^{-59} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 4, \textit{Error:}, 3.3944522388481652831 \times 10^{-59}, \textit{New Error:}, 3.3944522388481652831 \times 10^{-71}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{777600000 \Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2} (-48261724457 u_{i_1, i_2} + 105682608300 u_{i_1, i_2+1} - 105682608300 u_{i_1, i_2+2} + 70455072200 u_{i_1, i_2+3} \\
& - 26420652075 u_{i_1, i_2+4} + 4227304332 u_{i_1, i_2+5} + 422730433200 u_{i_1+1, i_2} - 925687080000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} + 925687080000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} \\
& - 617124720000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} + 231421770000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} - 37027483200 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} - 1811261053200 u_{i_1+2, i_2} + 3966265080000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} \\
& - 3966265080000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} + 2644176720000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} - 991566270000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} + 158650603200 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} + 5085933528800 u_{i_1+3, i_2} \\
& - 11137080720000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} + 11137080720000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} - 7424720480000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} + 2784270180000 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} - 445483228800 u_{i_1+3, i_2+5} \\
& - 10536443388300 u_{i_1+4, i_2} + 23072503770000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} - 23072503770000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} + 15381669180000 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} - 5768125942500 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} \\
& + 922900150800 u_{i_1+4, i_2+5} + 17136608687328 u_{i_1+5, i_2} - 37525420483200 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} + 37525420483200 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} - 25016946988800 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} \\
& + 9381355120800 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} - 1501016819328 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} - 22695421479600 u_{i_1+6, i_2} + 49698003240000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} - 49698003240000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} \\
& + 33132002160000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} - 12424500810000 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} + 1987920129600 u_{i_1+6, i_2+5} + 25040690229600 u_{i_1+7, i_2} - 54833628240000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} \\
& + 54833628240000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} - 36555752160000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+3} + 13708407060000 u_{i_1+7, i_2+4} - 2193345129600 u_{i_1+7, i_2+5} - 23350559610150 u_{i_1+8, i_2} \\
& + 51132612285000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+1} - 51132612285000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+2} + 34088408190000 u_{i_1+8, i_2+3} - 12783153071250 u_{i_1+8, i_2+4} + 2045304491400 u_{i_1+8, i_2+5} \\
& + 18561833422400 u_{i_1+9, i_2} - 40646350560000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+1} + 40646350560000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+2} - 27097567040000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+3} + 10161587640000 u_{i_1+9, i_2+4} \\
& - 1625854022400 u_{i_1+9, i_2+5} - 12630726838992 u_{i_1+10, i_2} + 27658525924800 u_{i_1+10, i_2+1} - 27658525924800 u_{i_1+10, i_2+2} + 18439017283200 u_{i_1+10, i_2+3} \\
& - 6914631481200 u_{i_1+10, i_2+4} + 1106341036992 u_{i_1+10, i_2+5} + 7360242909600 u_{i_1+11, i_2} - 16117320240000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+1} + 16117320240000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+2} \\
& - 10744880160000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+3} + 4029330060000 u_{i_1+11, i_2+4} - 644692809600 u_{i_1+11, i_2+5} - 3661093237100 u_{i_1+12, i_2} + 8016992490000 u_{i_1+12, i_2+1} \\
& - 8016992490000 u_{i_1+12, i_2+2} + 5344661660000 u_{i_1+12, i_2+3} - 2004248122500 u_{i_1+12, i_2+4} + 320679699600 u_{i_1+12, i_2+5} + 1543453946400 u_{i_1+13, i_2} \\
& - 3379826160000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+1} + 3379826160000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+2} - 2253217440000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+3} + 844956540000 u_{i_1+13, i_2+4} - 135193046400 u_{i_1+13, i_2+5} \\
& - 545046992400 u_{i_1+14, i_2} + 1193533560000 u_{i_1+14, i_2+1} - 1193533560000 u_{i_1+14, i_2+2} + 795689040000 u_{i_1+14, i_2+3} - 298383390000 u_{i_1+14, i_2+4} \\
& + 47741342400 u_{i_1+14, i_2+5} + 158372951328 u_{i_1+15, i_2} - 346802083200 u_{i_1+15, i_2+1} + 346802083200 u_{i_1+15, i_2+2} - 231201388800 u_{i_1+15, i_2+3} \\
& + 86700520800 u_{i_1+15, i_2+4} - 13872083328 u_{i_1+15, i_2+5} - 36874128825 u_{i_1+16, i_2} + 80746267500 u_{i_1+16, i_2+1} - 80746267500 u_{i_1+16, i_2+2} \\
& + 53830845000 u_{i_1+16, i_2+3} - 20186566875 u_{i_1+16, i_2+4} + 3229850700 u_{i_1+16, i_2+5} + 6609373200 u_{i_1+17, i_2} - 14473080000 u_{i_1+17, i_2+1} \\
& + 14473080000 u_{i_1+17, i_2+2} - 9648720000 u_{i_1+17, i_2+3} + 3618270000 u_{i_1+17, i_2+4} - 578923200 u_{i_1+17, i_2+5} - 855208800 u_{i_1+18, i_2} \\
& + 1872720000 u_{i_1+18, i_2+1} - 1872720000 u_{i_1+18, i_2+2} + 1248480000 u_{i_1+18, i_2+3} - 468180000 u_{i_1+18, i_2+4} + 74908800 u_{i_1+18, i_2+5} + 71020800 u_{i_1+19, i_2} \\
& - 155520000 u_{i_1+19, i_2+1} + 155520000 u_{i_1+19, i_2+2} - 103680000 u_{i_1+19, i_2+3} + 38880000 u_{i_1+19, i_2+4} - 6220800 u_{i_1+19, i_2+5} - 2840832 u_{i_1+20, i_2} \\
& + 6220800 u_{i_1+20, i_2+1} - 6220800 u_{i_1+20, i_2+2} + 4147200 u_{i_1+20, i_2+3} - 1555200 u_{i_1+20, i_2+4} + 248832 u_{i_1+20, i_2+5}), O(\Delta x_1^5 \Delta x_2^5), Forward
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.3540299079815703082 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $4.3294226961370110691 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.3294226961370110691 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $4.3293981672687776502 \times 10^{-43}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.3293981672687776502 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $4.3293981427399875776 \times 10^{-58}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.3293981427399875776 \times 10^{-58}$, *New Error:*, $4.3293981427154587876 \times 10^{-73}$
Error order:, 5, *Error:*, $4.3293981427154587876 \times 10^{-73}$, *New Error:*, $4.3293981427154342588 \times 10^{-88}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x^4 \partial x^2} u(x1, x2) = & \frac{1}{777600000 \Delta x^4 \Delta x^2} (-248832 u_{i1-20, i2-5} + 1555200 u_{i1-20, i2-4} - 4147200 u_{i1-20, i2-3} + 6220800 u_{i1-20, i2-2} \\
& - 6220800 u_{i1-20, i2-1} + 2840832 u_{i1-20, i2} + 6220800 u_{i1-19, i2-5} - 38880000 u_{i1-19, i2-4} + 103680000 u_{i1-19, i2-3} - 155520000 u_{i1-19, i2-2} \\
& + 155520000 u_{i1-19, i2-1} - 71020800 u_{i1-19, i2} - 74908800 u_{i1-18, i2-5} + 468180000 u_{i1-18, i2-4} - 1248480000 u_{i1-18, i2-3} + 1872720000 u_{i1-18, i2-2} \\
& - 1872720000 u_{i1-18, i2-1} + 855208800 u_{i1-18, i2} + 578923200 u_{i1-17, i2-5} - 3618270000 u_{i1-17, i2-4} + 9648720000 u_{i1-17, i2-3} \\
& - 14473080000 u_{i1-17, i2-2} + 14473080000 u_{i1-17, i2-1} - 6609373200 u_{i1-17, i2} - 3229850700 u_{i1-16, i2-5} + 20186566875 u_{i1-16, i2-4} \\
& - 53830845000 u_{i1-16, i2-3} + 80746267500 u_{i1-16, i2-2} - 80746267500 u_{i1-16, i2-1} + 36874128825 u_{i1-16, i2} + 13872083328 u_{i1-15, i2-5} \\
& - 86700520800 u_{i1-15, i2-4} + 231201388800 u_{i1-15, i2-3} - 346802083200 u_{i1-15, i2-2} + 346802083200 u_{i1-15, i2-1} - 158372951328 u_{i1-15, i2} \\
& - 47741342400 u_{i1-14, i2-5} + 298383390000 u_{i1-14, i2-4} - 795689040000 u_{i1-14, i2-3} + 1193533560000 u_{i1-14, i2-2} - 1193533560000 u_{i1-14, i2-1} \\
& + 545046992400 u_{i1-14, i2} + 135193046400 u_{i1-13, i2-5} - 844956540000 u_{i1-13, i2-4} + 2253217440000 u_{i1-13, i2-3} - 3379826160000 u_{i1-13, i2-2} \\
& + 3379826160000 u_{i1-13, i2-1} - 1543453946400 u_{i1-13, i2} - 320679699600 u_{i1-12, i2-5} + 2004248122500 u_{i1-12, i2-4} - 5344661660000 u_{i1-12, i2-3} \\
& + 8016992490000 u_{i1-12, i2-2} - 8016992490000 u_{i1-12, i2-1} + 3661093237100 u_{i1-12, i2} + 644692809600 u_{i1-11, i2-5} - 4029330060000 u_{i1-11, i2-4} \\
& + 10744880160000 u_{i1-11, i2-3} - 16117320240000 u_{i1-11, i2-2} + 16117320240000 u_{i1-11, i2-1} - 7360242909600 u_{i1-11, i2} - 1106341036992 u_{i1-10, i2-5} \\
& + 6914631481200 u_{i1-10, i2-4} - 18439017283200 u_{i1-10, i2-3} + 27658525924800 u_{i1-10, i2-2} - 27658525924800 u_{i1-10, i2-1} + 12630726838992 u_{i1-10, i2} \\
& + 1625854022400 u_{i1-9, i2-5} - 10161587640000 u_{i1-9, i2-4} + 27097567040000 u_{i1-9, i2-3} - 40646350560000 u_{i1-9, i2-2} + 40646350560000 u_{i1-9, i2-1} \\
& - 18561833422400 u_{i1-9, i2} - 2045304491400 u_{i1-8, i2-5} + 12783153071250 u_{i1-8, i2-4} - 34088408190000 u_{i1-8, i2-3} + 51132612285000 u_{i1-8, i2-2} \\
& - 51132612285000 u_{i1-8, i2-1} + 23350559610150 u_{i1-8, i2} + 2193345129600 u_{i1-7, i2-5} - 13708407060000 u_{i1-7, i2-4} + 36555752160000 u_{i1-7, i2-3} \\
& - 54833628240000 u_{i1-7, i2-2} + 54833628240000 u_{i1-7, i2-1} - 25040690229600 u_{i1-7, i2} - 1987920129600 u_{i1-6, i2-5} + 12424500810000 u_{i1-6, i2-4} \\
& - 33132002160000 u_{i1-6, i2-3} + 49698003240000 u_{i1-6, i2-2} - 49698003240000 u_{i1-6, i2-1} + 22695421479600 u_{i1-6, i2} + 1501016819328 u_{i1-5, i2-5} \\
& - 9381355120800 u_{i1-5, i2-4} + 25016946988800 u_{i1-5, i2-3} - 37525420483200 u_{i1-5, i2-2} + 37525420483200 u_{i1-5, i2-1} - 17136608687328 u_{i1-5, i2} \\
& - 922900150800 u_{i1-4, i2-5} + 5768125942500 u_{i1-4, i2-4} - 15381669180000 u_{i1-4, i2-3} + 23072503770000 u_{i1-4, i2-2} - 23072503770000 u_{i1-4, i2-1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 10536443388300 u_{i_l-4, i_2} + 445483228800 u_{i_l-3, i_2-5} - 2784270180000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 7424720480000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 11137080720000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} \\
& + 11137080720000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 5085933528800 u_{i_l-3, i_2} - 158650603200 u_{i_l-2, i_2-5} + 991566270000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} - 2644176720000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} \\
& + 3966265080000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 3966265080000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 1811261053200 u_{i_l-2, i_2} + 37027483200 u_{i_l-1, i_2-5} - 231421770000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} \\
& + 617124720000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 925687080000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 925687080000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 422730433200 u_{i_l-1, i_2} - 4227304332 u_{i_l, i_2-5} \\
& + 26420652075 u_{i_l, i_2-4} - 70455072200 u_{i_l, i_2-3} + 105682608300 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 105682608300 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 48261724457 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x I^5 \Delta x^5), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 4.3049228560331252939 \times 10^{-13}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.3293735894503352927 \times 10^{-28}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 4.3293735894503352927 \times 10^{-28}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.3293981181620909748 \times 10^{-43}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 4.3293981181620909748 \times 10^{-43}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.3293981426908808909 \times 10^{-58}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 4.3293981426908808909 \times 10^{-58}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.3293981427154096809 \times 10^{-73}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 5, \text{ Error:}, 4.3293981427154096809 \times 10^{-73}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.3293981427154342097 \times 10^{-88}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{777600000 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} \left(-u_{i_l-12, i_2-3} + 9 u_{i_l-12, i_2-2} - 45 u_{i_l-12, i_2-1} + 45 u_{i_l-12, i_2+1} - 9 u_{i_l-12, i_2+2} + u_{i_l-12, i_2+3} + 36 u_{i_l-11, i_2-3} \right. \\
& - 324 u_{i_l-11, i_2-2} + 1620 u_{i_l-11, i_2-1} - 1620 u_{i_l-11, i_2+1} + 324 u_{i_l-11, i_2+2} - 36 u_{i_l-11, i_2+3} - 666 u_{i_l-10, i_2-3} + 5994 u_{i_l-10, i_2-2} - 29970 u_{i_l-10, i_2-1} \\
& + 29970 u_{i_l-10, i_2+1} - 5994 u_{i_l-10, i_2+2} + 666 u_{i_l-10, i_2+3} + 7776 u_{i_l-9, i_2-3} - 69984 u_{i_l-9, i_2-2} + 349920 u_{i_l-9, i_2-1} - 349920 u_{i_l-9, i_2+1} \\
& + 69984 u_{i_l-9, i_2+2} - 7776 u_{i_l-9, i_2+3} - 62271 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 560439 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 2802195 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 2802195 u_{i_l-8, i_2+1} - 560439 u_{i_l-8, i_2+2} \\
& + 62271 u_{i_l-8, i_2+3} + 345024 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 3105216 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 15526080 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 15526080 u_{i_l-7, i_2+1} + 3105216 u_{i_l-7, i_2+2} - 345024 u_{i_l-7, i_2+3} \\
& - 1279634 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 11516706 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 57583530 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 57583530 u_{i_l-6, i_2+1} - 11516706 u_{i_l-6, i_2+2} + 1279634 u_{i_l-6, i_2+3} \\
& + 2698164 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 24283476 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 121417380 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 121417380 u_{i_l-5, i_2+1} + 24283476 u_{i_l-5, i_2+2} - 2698164 u_{i_l-5, i_2+3} \\
& - 935739 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 8421651 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 42108255 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 42108255 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1} - 8421651 u_{i_l-4, i_2+2} + 935739 u_{i_l-4, i_2+3} \\
& - 10242936 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} + 92186424 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} - 460932120 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} + 460932120 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1} - 92186424 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2} + 10242936 u_{i_l-3, i_2+3} \\
& + 16272684 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} - 146454156 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} + 732270780 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} - 732270780 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1} + 146454156 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2} - 16272684 u_{i_l-2, i_2+3} \\
& + 7191936 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 64727424 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 323637120 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 323637120 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1} + 64727424 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2} - 7191936 u_{i_l-1, i_2+3} \\
& - 27988746 u_{i_l, i_2-3} + 251898714 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 1259493570 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 1259493570 u_{i_l, i_2+1} - 251898714 u_{i_l, i_2+2} + 27988746 u_{i_l, i_2+3} + 7191936 u_{i_l+1, i_2-3} \\
& - 64727424 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2} + 323637120 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1} - 323637120 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} + 64727424 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} - 7191936 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} + 16272684 u_{i_l+2, i_2-3} \\
& - 146454156 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2} + 732270780 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1} - 732270780 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 146454156 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 16272684 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} - 10242936 u_{i_l+3, i_2-3} \\
& + 92186424 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2} - 460932120 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} + 460932120 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - 92186424 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 10242936 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} - 935739 u_{i_l+4, i_2-3}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 8421651 u_{il+4, i2-2} - 42108255 u_{il+4, i2-1} + 42108255 u_{il+4, i2+1} - 8421651 u_{il+4, i2+2} + 935739 u_{il+4, i2+3} + 2698164 u_{il+5, i2-3} \\
& - 24283476 u_{il+5, i2-2} + 121417380 u_{il+5, i2-1} - 121417380 u_{il+5, i2+1} + 24283476 u_{il+5, i2+2} - 2698164 u_{il+5, i2+3} - 1279634 u_{il+6, i2-3} \\
& + 11516706 u_{il+6, i2-2} - 57583530 u_{il+6, i2-1} + 57583530 u_{il+6, i2+1} - 11516706 u_{il+6, i2+2} + 1279634 u_{il+6, i2+3} + 345024 u_{il+7, i2-3} \\
& - 3105216 u_{il+7, i2-2} + 15526080 u_{il+7, i2-1} - 15526080 u_{il+7, i2+1} + 3105216 u_{il+7, i2+2} - 345024 u_{il+7, i2+3} - 62271 u_{il+8, i2-3} + 560439 u_{il+8, i2-2} \\
& - 2802195 u_{il+8, i2-1} + 2802195 u_{il+8, i2+1} - 560439 u_{il+8, i2+2} + 62271 u_{il+8, i2+3} + 7776 u_{il+9, i2-3} - 69984 u_{il+9, i2-2} + 349920 u_{il+9, i2-1} \\
& - 349920 u_{il+9, i2+1} + 69984 u_{il+9, i2+2} - 7776 u_{il+9, i2+3} - 666 u_{il+10, i2-3} + 5994 u_{il+10, i2-2} - 29970 u_{il+10, i2-1} + 29970 u_{il+10, i2+1} \\
& - 5994 u_{il+10, i2+2} + 666 u_{il+10, i2+3} + 36 u_{il+11, i2-3} - 324 u_{il+11, i2-2} + 1620 u_{il+11, i2-1} - 1620 u_{il+11, i2+1} + 324 u_{il+11, i2+2} - 36 u_{il+11, i2+3} \\
& - u_{il+12, i2-3} + 9 u_{il+12, i2-2} - 45 u_{il+12, i2-1} + 45 u_{il+12, i2+1} - 9 u_{il+12, i2+2} + u_{il+12, i2+3} \Big), O(\Delta x l^6 \Delta x 2^6), \textit{Centered} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 4.9106759729824453461 \times 10^{-17}, \textit{New Error:}, 4.9106686675484205559 \times 10^{-35} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 4.9106686675484205559 \times 10^{-35}, \textit{New Error:}, 4.9106686675411151277 \times 10^{-53} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 4.9106686675411151277 \times 10^{-53}, \textit{New Error:}, 4.9106686675411151203 \times 10^{-71} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 4.9106686675411151203 \times 10^{-71}, \textit{New Error:}, 4.9106686675411151203 \times 10^{-89} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 6, \textit{Error:}, 4.9106686675411151203 \times 10^{-89}, \textit{New Error:}, 4.9106686675411151203 \times 10^{-107}
\end{aligned}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 5 - x1=3, x2=2 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x l^3 \partial x 2^2} u(x l, x 2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& = \frac{1}{\Delta x l^3 \Delta x 2^2} \left(-u_{il, i2} + 2 u_{il, i2+1} - u_{il, i2+2} + 3 u_{il+1, i2} - 6 u_{il+1, i2+1} + 3 u_{il+1, i2+2} - 3 u_{il+2, i2} + 6 u_{il+2, i2+1} - 3 u_{il+2, i2+2} + u_{il+3, i2} \right. \\
& \left. - 2 u_{il+3, i2+1} + u_{il+3, i2+2} \right), O(\Delta x l \Delta x 2), \textit{Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \textit{Error order:}, 1, \textit{Error:}, 0.042558423892358766347, \textit{New Error:}, 0.000042422489180728574735 \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 1, \textit{Error:}, 0.000042422489180728574735, \textit{New Error:}, 4.2422353552272843171 \times 10^{-8} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 1, \textit{Error:}, 4.2422353552272843171 \times 10^{-8}, \textit{New Error:}, 4.2422353416644693154 \times 10^{-11} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 1, \textit{Error:}, 4.2422353416644693154 \times 10^{-11}, \textit{New Error:}, 4.2422353416509065004 \times 10^{-14} \\
& \textit{Error order:}, 1, \textit{Error:}, 4.2422353416509065004 \times 10^{-14}, \textit{New Error:}, 4.2422353416508929376 \times 10^{-17}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^2} (-u_{i-3, i-2} + 2u_{i-3, i-1} - u_{i-3, i} + 3u_{i-2, i-2} - 6u_{i-2, i-1} + 3u_{i-2, i} - 3u_{i-1, i-2} + 6u_{i-1, i-1} - 3u_{i-1, i} + u_{i, i-2} - 2u_{i, i-1} + u_{i, i}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.042286894981532709385, *New Error:*, 0.000042422217652901323022

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000042422217652901323022, *New Error:*, $4.2422353280745015921 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.2422353280745015921 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $4.2422353416373165326 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.2422353416373165326 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.2422353416508793476 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.2422353416508793476 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $4.2422353416508929104 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^2} (-243 u_{i, i} + 648 u_{i, i+1} - 594 u_{i, i+2} + 216 u_{i, i+3} - 27 u_{i, i+4} + 972 u_{i+1, i} - 2592 u_{i+1, i+1} +$$

$$+ 2376 u_{i+1, i+2} - 864 u_{i+1, i+3} + 108 u_{i+1, i+4} - 1539 u_{i+2, i} + 4104 u_{i+2, i+1} - 3762 u_{i+2, i+2} + 1368 u_{i+2, i+3} - 171 u_{i+2, i+4} +$$

$$+ 1224 u_{i+3, i} - 3264 u_{i+3, i+1} + 2992 u_{i+3, i+2} - 1088 u_{i+3, i+3} + 136 u_{i+3, i+4} - 513 u_{i+4, i} + 1368 u_{i+4, i+1} - 1254 u_{i+4, i+2} +$$

$$+ 456 u_{i+4, i+3} - 57 u_{i+4, i+4} + 108 u_{i+5, i} - 288 u_{i+5, i+1} + 264 u_{i+5, i+2} - 96 u_{i+5, i+3} + 12 u_{i+5, i+4} - 9 u_{i+6, i} + 24 u_{i+6, i+1} -$$

$$- 22 u_{i+6, i+2} + 8 u_{i+6, i+3} - u_{i+6, i+4}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000070650577107355562079, *New Error:*, $7.0513705199295839456 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.0513705199295839456 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $7.0513568229415990078 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.0513568229415990078 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $7.0513568092446013113 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.0513568092446013113 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $7.0513568092309043136 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.0513568092309043136 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $7.0513568092308906166 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^2} (u_{i-6, i-4} - 8 u_{i-6, i-3} + 22 u_{i-6, i-2} - 24 u_{i-6, i-1} + 9 u_{i-6, i} - 12 u_{i-5, i-4} + 96 u_{i-5, i-3} - 264 u_{i-5, i-2} +$$

$$+ 288 u_{i-5, i-1} - 108 u_{i-5, i} + 57 u_{i-4, i-4} - 456 u_{i-4, i-3} + 1254 u_{i-4, i-2} - 1368 u_{i-4, i-1} + 513 u_{i-4, i} - 136 u_{i-3, i-4} + 1088 u_{i-3, i-3} -$$

$$- 2992 u_{i-3, i-2} + 3264 u_{i-3, i-1} - 1224 u_{i-3, i} + 171 u_{i-2, i-4} - 1368 u_{i-2, i-3} + 3762 u_{i-2, i-2} - 4104 u_{i-2, i-1} + 1539 u_{i-2, i} -$$

$$- 108 u_{i-1, i-4} + 864 u_{i-1, i-3} - 2376 u_{i-1, i-2} + 2592 u_{i-1, i-1} - 972 u_{i-1, i} + 27 u_{i, i-4} - 216 u_{i, i-3} + 594 u_{i, i-2} - 648 u_{i, i-1}$$

+ 243 u_{i_l, i_2}), $O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2)$, Backward

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000070376364650184351064, New Error:, $7.0513430985127548715 \times 10^{-11}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $7.0513430985127548715 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $7.0513567955201821785 \times 10^{-17}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $7.0513567955201821785 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $7.0513568092171798945 \times 10^{-23}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $7.0513568092171798945 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $7.0513568092308768922 \times 10^{-29}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $7.0513568092308768922 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $7.0513568092308905892 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^3 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2} (-u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 2 u_{i_l-3, i_2} - u_{i_l-3, i_2+2} + 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} - 6 u_{i_l-1, i_2} + 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2} + 6 u_{i_l+1, i_2} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} + u_{i_l+3, i_2-2} - 2 u_{i_l+3, i_2} + u_{i_l+3, i_2+2}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), Centered$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000035256863553344753980, New Error:, $3.5256784046233960096 \times 10^{-11}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.5256784046233960096 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $3.5256784046154453094 \times 10^{-17}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.5256784046154453094 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $3.5256784046154453014 \times 10^{-23}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.5256784046154453014 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $3.5256784046154453014 \times 10^{-29}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.5256784046154453014 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $3.5256784046154453014 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^3 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{7776 \Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2} (-161051 u_{i_l, i_2} + 527076 u_{i_l, i_2+1} - 694782 u_{i_l, i_2+2} + 489808 u_{i_l, i_2+3} - 203643 u_{i_l, i_2+4} + 47916 u_{i_l, i_2+5} - 5324 u_{i_l, i_2+6} + 790614 u_{i_l+1, i_2} - 2587464 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} + 3410748 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} - 2404512 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} + 999702 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} - 235224 u_{i_l+1, i_2+5} + 26136 u_{i_l+1, i_2+6} - 1689039 u_{i_l+2, i_2} + 5527764 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} - 7286598 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} + 5136912 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} - 2135727 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} + 502524 u_{i_l+2, i_2+5} - 55836 u_{i_l+2, i_2+6} + 2087250 u_{i_l+3, i_2} - 6831000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} + 9004500 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} - 6348000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} + 2639250 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} - 621000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+5} + 69000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+6} - 1669437 u_{i_l+4, i_2} + 5463612 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} - 7202034 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} + 5077296 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} - 2110941 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4} + 496692 u_{i_l+4, i_2+5} - 55188 u_{i_l+4, i_2+6} + 908226 u_{i_l+5, i_2} - 2972376 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} + 3918132 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} - 2762208 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} + 1148418 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4} - 270216 u_{i_l+5, i_2+5} + 30024 u_{i_l+5, i_2+6} - 339405 u_{i_l+6, i_2} + 1110780 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} - 1464210 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} + 1032240 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} - 429165 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4} + 100980 u_{i_l+6, i_2+5} - 11220 u_{i_l+6, i_2+6} + 84942 u_{i_l+7, i_2} - 277992 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} + 366444 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} - 258336 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} + 107406 u_{i_l+7, i_2+4} - 25272 u_{i_l+7, i_2+5} + 2808 u_{i_l+7, i_2+6} - 13068 u_{i_l+8, i_2} + 42768 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} - 56376 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} + 39744 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} - 16524 u_{i_l+8, i_2+4} + 3888 u_{i_l+8, i_2+5} - 432 u_{i_l+8, i_2+6} + 968 u_{i_l+9, i_2} - 3168 u_{i_l+9, i_2+1} + 4176 u_{i_l+9, i_2+2} - 2944 u_{i_l+9, i_2+3} + 1224 u_{i_l+9, i_2+4} - 288 u_{i_l+9, i_2+5} + 32 u_{i_l+9, i_2+6}), $O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^3)$, Forward$$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $1.3754956646792536998 \times 10^{-7}$, New Error:, $1.3710752577983929927 \times 10^{-16}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.3710752577983929927 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $1.3710708458785914719 \times 10^{-25}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.3710708458785914719 \times 10^{-25}$, *New Error:*, $1.3710708414666801355 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.3710708414666801355 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.3710708414622682241 \times 10^{-43}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.3710708414622682241 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $1.3710708414622638122 \times 10^{-52}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{7776 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^2} \left(-32 u_{i_1-9, i_2-6} + 288 u_{i_1-9, i_2-5} - 1224 u_{i_1-9, i_2-4} + 2944 u_{i_1-9, i_2-3} - 4176 u_{i_1-9, i_2-2} + 3168 u_{i_1-9, i_2-1} \right. \\ - 968 u_{i_1-9, i_2} + 432 u_{i_1-8, i_2-6} - 3888 u_{i_1-8, i_2-5} + 16524 u_{i_1-8, i_2-4} - 39744 u_{i_1-8, i_2-3} + 56376 u_{i_1-8, i_2-2} - 42768 u_{i_1-8, i_2-1} + 13068 u_{i_1-8, i_2} \\ - 2808 u_{i_1-7, i_2-6} + 25272 u_{i_1-7, i_2-5} - 107406 u_{i_1-7, i_2-4} + 258336 u_{i_1-7, i_2-3} - 366444 u_{i_1-7, i_2-2} + 277992 u_{i_1-7, i_2-1} - 84942 u_{i_1-7, i_2} \\ + 11220 u_{i_1-6, i_2-6} - 100980 u_{i_1-6, i_2-5} + 429165 u_{i_1-6, i_2-4} - 1032240 u_{i_1-6, i_2-3} + 1464210 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 1110780 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 339405 u_{i_1-6, i_2} \\ - 30024 u_{i_1-5, i_2-6} + 270216 u_{i_1-5, i_2-5} - 1148418 u_{i_1-5, i_2-4} + 2762208 u_{i_1-5, i_2-3} - 3918132 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 2972376 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 908226 u_{i_1-5, i_2} \\ + 55188 u_{i_1-4, i_2-6} - 496692 u_{i_1-4, i_2-5} + 2110941 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4} - 5077296 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3} + 7202034 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 5463612 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 1669437 u_{i_1-4, i_2} \\ - 69000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-6} + 621000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-5} - 2639250 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4} + 6348000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 9004500 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 6831000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 2087250 u_{i_1-3, i_2} \\ + 55836 u_{i_1-2, i_2-6} - 502524 u_{i_1-2, i_2-5} + 2135727 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4} - 5136912 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 7286598 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 5527764 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 1689039 u_{i_1-2, i_2} \\ - 26136 u_{i_1-1, i_2-6} + 235224 u_{i_1-1, i_2-5} - 999702 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4} + 2404512 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} - 3410748 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 2587464 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 790614 u_{i_1-1, i_2} \\ \left. + 5324 u_{i_1, i_2-6} - 47916 u_{i_1, i_2-5} + 203643 u_{i_1, i_2-4} - 489808 u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 694782 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 527076 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 161051 u_{i_1, i_2} \right), O(\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.3666629653985697944 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $1.3710664251430816253 \times 10^{-16}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.3710664251430816253 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $1.3710708370459361606 \times 10^{-25}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.3710708370459361606 \times 10^{-25}$, *New Error:*, $1.3710708414578474801 \times 10^{-34}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.3710708414578474801 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.3710708414622593915 \times 10^{-43}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.3710708414622593915 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $1.3710708414622638034 \times 10^{-52}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{248832 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^2} \left(-9765625 u_{i_1, i_2} + 37500000 u_{i_1, i_2+1} - 64125000 u_{i_1, i_2+2} + 66500000 u_{i_1, i_2+3} - 46593750 u_{i_1, i_2+4} \right. \\ + 22500000 u_{i_1, i_2+5} - 7375000 u_{i_1, i_2+6} + 1500000 u_{i_1, i_2+7} - 140625 u_{i_1, i_2+8} + 56250000 u_{i_1+1, i_2} - 216000000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} + 369360000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} \\ - 383040000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} + 268380000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} - 129600000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} + 42480000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+6} - 8640000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+7} + 810000 u_{i_1+1, i_2+8} \\ - 150187500 u_{i_1+2, i_2} + 576720000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} - 986191200 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} + 1022716800 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} - 716574600 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} + 346032000 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} \\ \left. - 113421600 u_{i_1+2, i_2+6} + 23068800 u_{i_1+2, i_2+7} - 2162700 u_{i_1+2, i_2+8} + 249870000 u_{i_1+3, i_2} - 959500800 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} + 1640746368 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -1701514752 u_{i+3, i+3} + 1192179744 u_{i+3, i+4} - 575700480 u_{i+3, i+5} + 188701824 u_{i+3, i+6} - 38380032 u_{i+3, i+7} + 3598128 u_{i+3, i+8} \\
& -291785625 u_{i+4, i} + 1120456800 u_{i+4, i+1} - 1915981128 u_{i+4, i+2} + 1986943392 u_{i+4, i+3} - 1392167574 u_{i+4, i+4} + 672274080 u_{i+4, i+5} \\
& -220356504 u_{i+4, i+6} + 44818272 u_{i+4, i+7} - 4201713 u_{i+4, i+8} + 253260000 u_{i+5, i} - 972518400 u_{i+5, i+1} + 1663006464 u_{i+5, i+2} \\
& -1724599296 u_{i+5, i+3} + 1208354112 u_{i+5, i+4} - 583511040 u_{i+5, i+5} + 191261952 u_{i+5, i+6} - 38900736 u_{i+5, i+7} + 3646944 u_{i+5, i+8} \\
& -167925000 u_{i+6, i} + 644832000 u_{i+6, i+1} - 1102662720 u_{i+6, i+2} + 1143502080 u_{i+6, i+3} - 801203760 u_{i+6, i+4} + 386899200 u_{i+6, i+5} \\
& -126816960 u_{i+6, i+6} + 25793280 u_{i+6, i+7} - 2418120 u_{i+6, i+8} + 85860000 u_{i+7, i} - 329702400 u_{i+7, i+1} + 563791104 u_{i+7, i+2} \\
& -584672256 u_{i+7, i+3} + 409655232 u_{i+7, i+4} - 197821440 u_{i+7, i+5} + 64841472 u_{i+7, i+6} - 13188096 u_{i+7, i+7} + 1236384 u_{i+7, i+8} \\
& -33631875 u_{i+8, i} + 129146400 u_{i+8, i+1} - 220840344 u_{i+8, i+2} + 229019616 u_{i+8, i+3} - 160464402 u_{i+8, i+4} + 77487840 u_{i+8, i+5} \\
& -25398792 u_{i+8, i+6} + 5165856 u_{i+8, i+7} - 484299 u_{i+8, i+8} + 9850000 u_{i+9, i} - 37824000 u_{i+9, i+1} + 64679040 u_{i+9, i+2} \\
& -67074560 u_{i+9, i+3} + 46996320 u_{i+9, i+4} - 22694400 u_{i+9, i+5} + 7438720 u_{i+9, i+6} - 1512960 u_{i+9, i+7} + 141840 u_{i+9, i+8} \\
& -2047500 u_{i+10, i} + 7862400 u_{i+10, i+1} - 13444704 u_{i+10, i+2} + 13942656 u_{i+10, i+3} - 9769032 u_{i+10, i+4} + 4717440 u_{i+10, i+5} \\
& -1546272 u_{i+10, i+6} + 314496 u_{i+10, i+7} - 29484 u_{i+10, i+8} + 270000 u_{i+11, i} - 1036800 u_{i+11, i+1} + 1772928 u_{i+11, i+2} - 1838592 u_{i+11, i+3} \\
& + 1288224 u_{i+11, i+4} - 622080 u_{i+11, i+5} + 203904 u_{i+11, i+6} - 41472 u_{i+11, i+7} + 3888 u_{i+11, i+8} - 16875 u_{i+12, i} + 64800 u_{i+12, i+1} \\
& -110808 u_{i+12, i+2} + 114912 u_{i+12, i+3} - 80514 u_{i+12, i+4} + 38880 u_{i+12, i+5} - 12744 u_{i+12, i+6} + 2592 u_{i+12, i+7} - 243 u_{i+12, i+8}),
\end{aligned}$$

$O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4)$, Forward

$$\text{Error order: } 4, \text{ Error: } 2.9578116877353667544 \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error: } 2.9442319947453148869 \times 10^{-22}$$

$$\text{Error order: } 4, \text{ Error: } 2.9442319947453148869 \times 10^{-22}, \text{ New Error: } 2.9442184506654126066 \times 10^{-34}$$

$$\text{Error order: } 4, \text{ Error: } 2.9442184506654126066 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error: } 2.9442184371213682485 \times 10^{-46}$$

$$\text{Error order: } 4, \text{ Error: } 2.9442184371213682485 \times 10^{-46}, \text{ New Error: } 2.9442184371078242042 \times 10^{-58}$$

$$\text{Error order: } 4, \text{ Error: } 2.9442184371078242042 \times 10^{-58}, \text{ New Error: } 2.9442184371078106602 \times 10^{-70}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) &= \frac{1}{248832 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^2} (243 u_{i-12, i-8} - 2592 u_{i-12, i-7} + 12744 u_{i-12, i-6} - 38880 u_{i-12, i-5} + 80514 u_{i-12, i-4} \\
& -114912 u_{i-12, i-3} + 110808 u_{i-12, i-2} - 64800 u_{i-12, i-1} + 16875 u_{i-12, i} - 3888 u_{i-11, i-8} + 41472 u_{i-11, i-7} - 203904 u_{i-11, i-6} \\
& + 622080 u_{i-11, i-5} - 1288224 u_{i-11, i-4} + 1838592 u_{i-11, i-3} - 1772928 u_{i-11, i-2} + 1036800 u_{i-11, i-1} - 270000 u_{i-11, i} + 29484 u_{i-10, i-8} \\
& -314496 u_{i-10, i-7} + 1546272 u_{i-10, i-6} - 4717440 u_{i-10, i-5} + 9769032 u_{i-10, i-4} - 13942656 u_{i-10, i-3} + 13444704 u_{i-10, i-2} \\
& -7862400 u_{i-10, i-1} + 2047500 u_{i-10, i} - 141840 u_{i-9, i-8} + 1512960 u_{i-9, i-7} - 7438720 u_{i-9, i-6} + 22694400 u_{i-9, i-5}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -46996320 u_{iI-9, i2-4} + 67074560 u_{iI-9, i2-3} - 64679040 u_{iI-9, i2-2} + 37824000 u_{iI-9, i2-1} - 9850000 u_{iI-9, i2} + 484299 u_{iI-8, i2-8} \\
& - 5165856 u_{iI-8, i2-7} + 25398792 u_{iI-8, i2-6} - 77487840 u_{iI-8, i2-5} + 160464402 u_{iI-8, i2-4} - 229019616 u_{iI-8, i2-3} + 220840344 u_{iI-8, i2-2} \\
& - 129146400 u_{iI-8, i2-1} + 33631875 u_{iI-8, i2} - 1236384 u_{iI-7, i2-8} + 13188096 u_{iI-7, i2-7} - 64841472 u_{iI-7, i2-6} + 197821440 u_{iI-7, i2-5} \\
& - 409655232 u_{iI-7, i2-4} + 584672256 u_{iI-7, i2-3} - 563791104 u_{iI-7, i2-2} + 329702400 u_{iI-7, i2-1} - 85860000 u_{iI-7, i2} + 2418120 u_{iI-6, i2-8} \\
& - 25793280 u_{iI-6, i2-7} + 126816960 u_{iI-6, i2-6} - 386899200 u_{iI-6, i2-5} + 801203760 u_{iI-6, i2-4} - 1143502080 u_{iI-6, i2-3} + 1102662720 u_{iI-6, i2-2} \\
& - 644832000 u_{iI-6, i2-1} + 167925000 u_{iI-6, i2} - 3646944 u_{iI-5, i2-8} + 38900736 u_{iI-5, i2-7} - 191261952 u_{iI-5, i2-6} + 583511040 u_{iI-5, i2-5} \\
& - 1208354112 u_{iI-5, i2-4} + 1724599296 u_{iI-5, i2-3} - 1663006464 u_{iI-5, i2-2} + 972518400 u_{iI-5, i2-1} - 253260000 u_{iI-5, i2} + 4201713 u_{iI-4, i2-8} \\
& - 44818272 u_{iI-4, i2-7} + 220356504 u_{iI-4, i2-6} - 672274080 u_{iI-4, i2-5} + 1392167574 u_{iI-4, i2-4} - 1986943392 u_{iI-4, i2-3} + 1915981128 u_{iI-4, i2-2} \\
& - 1120456800 u_{iI-4, i2-1} + 291785625 u_{iI-4, i2} - 3598128 u_{iI-3, i2-8} + 38380032 u_{iI-3, i2-7} - 188701824 u_{iI-3, i2-6} + 575700480 u_{iI-3, i2-5} \\
& - 1192179744 u_{iI-3, i2-4} + 1701514752 u_{iI-3, i2-3} - 1640746368 u_{iI-3, i2-2} + 959500800 u_{iI-3, i2-1} - 249870000 u_{iI-3, i2} + 2162700 u_{iI-2, i2-8} \\
& - 23068800 u_{iI-2, i2-7} + 113421600 u_{iI-2, i2-6} - 346032000 u_{iI-2, i2-5} + 716574600 u_{iI-2, i2-4} - 1022716800 u_{iI-2, i2-3} + 986191200 u_{iI-2, i2-2} \\
& - 576720000 u_{iI-2, i2-1} + 150187500 u_{iI-2, i2} - 810000 u_{iI-1, i2-8} + 8640000 u_{iI-1, i2-7} - 42480000 u_{iI-1, i2-6} + 129600000 u_{iI-1, i2-5} \\
& - 268380000 u_{iI-1, i2-4} + 383040000 u_{iI-1, i2-3} - 369360000 u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 216000000 u_{iI-1, i2-1} - 56250000 u_{iI-1, i2} + 140625 u_{iI, i2-8} \\
& - 1500000 u_{iI, i2-7} + 7375000 u_{iI, i2-6} - 22500000 u_{iI, i2-5} + 46593750 u_{iI, i2-4} - 66500000 u_{iI, i2-3} + 64125000 u_{iI, i2-2} - 37500000 u_{iI, i2-1} \\
& + 9765625 u_{iI, i2}), O(\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^4), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.9306963462041854255 \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.9442048795414659978 \times 10^{-22} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.9442048795414659978 \times 10^{-22}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.9442184235502087578 \times 10^{-34} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.9442184235502087578 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.9442184370942530447 \times 10^{-46} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.9442184370942530447 \times 10^{-46}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.9442184371077970890 \times 10^{-58} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.9442184371077970890 \times 10^{-58}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.9442184371078106331 \times 10^{-70}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x I^3 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{248832 \Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2} (u_{iI-6, i2-4} - 16 u_{iI-6, i2-3} + 64 u_{iI-6, i2-2} + 16 u_{iI-6, i2-1} - 130 u_{iI-6, i2} + 16 u_{iI-6, i2+1} + 64 u_{iI-6, i2+2} \\
& - 16 u_{iI-6, i2+3} + u_{iI-6, i2+4} - 24 u_{iI-5, i2-4} + 384 u_{iI-5, i2-3} - 1536 u_{iI-5, i2-2} - 384 u_{iI-5, i2-1} + 3120 u_{iI-5, i2} - 384 u_{iI-5, i2+1} - 1536 u_{iI-5, i2+2} \\
& + 384 u_{iI-5, i2+3} - 24 u_{iI-5, i2+4} + 192 u_{iI-4, i2-4} - 3072 u_{iI-4, i2-3} + 12288 u_{iI-4, i2-2} + 3072 u_{iI-4, i2-1} - 24960 u_{iI-4, i2} + 3072 u_{iI-4, i2+1} \\
& + 12288 u_{iI-4, i2+2} - 3072 u_{iI-4, i2+3} + 192 u_{iI-4, i2+4} - 488 u_{iI-3, i2-4} + 7808 u_{iI-3, i2-3} - 31232 u_{iI-3, i2-2} - 7808 u_{iI-3, i2-1} + 63440 u_{iI-3, i2} \\
& - 7808 u_{iI-3, i2+1} - 31232 u_{iI-3, i2+2} + 7808 u_{iI-3, i2+3} - 488 u_{iI-3, i2+4} - 387 u_{iI-2, i2-4} + 6192 u_{iI-2, i2-3} - 24768 u_{iI-2, i2-2} - 6192 u_{iI-2, i2-1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 50310 u_{i_l-2, i_2} - 6192 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1} - 24768 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2} + 6192 u_{i_l-2, i_2+3} - 387 u_{i_l-2, i_2+4} + 1584 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} - 25344 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} + 101376 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} \\
& + 25344 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 205920 u_{i_l-1, i_2} + 25344 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1} + 101376 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2} - 25344 u_{i_l-1, i_2+3} + 1584 u_{i_l-1, i_2+4} - 1584 u_{i_l+1, i_2-4} \\
& + 25344 u_{i_l+1, i_2-3} - 101376 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2} - 25344 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1} + 205920 u_{i_l+1, i_2} - 25344 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - 101376 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} + 25344 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} \\
& - 1584 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} + 387 u_{i_l+2, i_2-4} - 6192 u_{i_l+2, i_2-3} + 24768 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2} + 6192 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1} - 50310 u_{i_l+2, i_2} + 6192 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 24768 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} \\
& - 6192 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} + 387 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} + 488 u_{i_l+3, i_2-4} - 7808 u_{i_l+3, i_2-3} + 31232 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2} + 7808 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} - 63440 u_{i_l+3, i_2} + 7808 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} \\
& + 31232 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} - 7808 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} + 488 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} - 192 u_{i_l+4, i_2-4} + 3072 u_{i_l+4, i_2-3} - 12288 u_{i_l+4, i_2-2} - 3072 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1} + 24960 u_{i_l+4, i_2} \\
& - 3072 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} - 12288 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} + 3072 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} - 192 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4} + 24 u_{i_l+5, i_2-4} - 384 u_{i_l+5, i_2-3} + 1536 u_{i_l+5, i_2-2} + 384 u_{i_l+5, i_2-1} \\
& - 3120 u_{i_l+5, i_2} + 384 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} + 1536 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} - 384 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} + 24 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4} - u_{i_l+6, i_2-4} + 16 u_{i_l+6, i_2-3} - 64 u_{i_l+6, i_2-2} - 16 u_{i_l+6, i_2-1} \\
& + 130 u_{i_l+6, i_2} - 16 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} - 64 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} + 16 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} - u_{i_l+6, i_2+4}), O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.9070352900158695278 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.9070307285175792566 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.9070307285175792566 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $4.9070307285130177489 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.9070307285130177489 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $4.9070307285130177443 \times 10^{-47}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.9070307285130177443 \times 10^{-47}$, *New Error:*, $4.9070307285130177443 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $4.9070307285130177443 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $4.9070307285130177443 \times 10^{-71}$

"--- Derivative Order: 5 - x1=3, x2=1, x3=1 ---"

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) &= \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} (-u_{i_l, i_2, i_3} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1} + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3} \\
& + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 3 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3} + 3 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1} + 3 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3} - 3 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} + u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3} - u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3} + u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+1}), \\
& O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.13078728482770564472, *New Error:*, 0.00013029640291399443376

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00013029640291399443376, *New Error:*, $1.3029591333848054416 \times 10^{-7}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.3029591333848054416 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $1.3029591284890633393 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.3029591284890633393 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $1.3029591284841675972 \times 10^{-13}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.3029591284841675972 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $1.3029591284841627014 \times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} \left(-u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3-1} + u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3} + u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3-1} - u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3} + 3u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 3u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3} - 3u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1} + 3u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3} - 3u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 3u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3} + 3u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1} - 3u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3} + u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1} - u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3} \right),$$

$O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3)$, Backward

Error order: 1, Error: 0.12980715080632529009, New Error: 0.00013029542278544803318

Error order: 1, Error: 0.00013029542278544803318, New Error: $1.3029591235835199776 \times 10^{-7}$

Error order: 1, Error: $1.3029591235835199776 \times 10^{-7}$, New Error: $1.3029591284792620538 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order: 1, Error: $1.3029591284792620538 \times 10^{-10}$, New Error: $1.3029591284841577959 \times 10^{-13}$

Error order: 1, Error: $1.3029591284841577959 \times 10^{-13}$, New Error: $1.3029591284841626916 \times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} \left(-243 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3} + 324 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1} - 81 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+2} + 324 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3} - 432 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 108 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 81 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3} + 108 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 27 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 972 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3} - 1296 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1} + 324 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+2} - 1296 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3} + 1728 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 432 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 324 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3} - 432 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 108 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 1539 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3} + 2052 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1} - 513 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+2} + 2052 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3} - 2736 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 684 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 513 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3} + 684 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 171 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 1224 u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3} - 1632 u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3+1} + 408 u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3+2} - 1632 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3} + 2176 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 544 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 408 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2, i_3} - 544 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 136 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 513 u_{i_1+4, i_2, i_3} + 684 u_{i_1+4, i_2, i_3+1} - 171 u_{i_1+4, i_2, i_3+2} + 684 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1, i_3} - 912 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 228 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 171 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2, i_3} + 228 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 57 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 108 u_{i_1+5, i_2, i_3} - 144 u_{i_1+5, i_2, i_3+1} + 36 u_{i_1+5, i_2, i_3+2} - 144 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1, i_3} + 192 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 48 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 36 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2, i_3} - 48 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 12 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 9 u_{i_1+6, i_2, i_3} + 12 u_{i_1+6, i_2, i_3+1} - 3 u_{i_1+6, i_2, i_3+2} + 12 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1, i_3} - 16 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 4 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 3 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2, i_3} + 4 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2, i_3+1} - u_{i_1+6, i_2+2, i_3+2} \right),$$

$O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2)$, Forward

Error order: 2, Error: 0.00028498162378426571623, New Error: $2.8417099246164865746 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order: 2, Error: $2.8417099246164865746 \times 10^{-10}$, New Error: $2.8417018204456409811 \times 10^{-16}$

Error order: 2, Error: $2.8417018204456409811 \times 10^{-16}$, New Error: $2.8417018123414723225 \times 10^{-22}$

Error order: 2, Error: $2.8417018123414723225 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error: $2.8417018123333681538 \times 10^{-28}$

Error order: 2, Error: $2.8417018123333681538 \times 10^{-28}$, New Error: $2.8417018123333600497 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} \left(u_{i_1-6, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 4 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 3 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2, i_3} - 4 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 16 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 12 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1, i_3} \right),$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 3 u_{i_l-6, i_2, i_3-2} - 12 u_{i_l-6, i_2, i_3-1} + 9 u_{i_l-6, i_2, i_3} - 12 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 48 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 36 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2, i_3} + 48 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 192 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1, i_3-1} \\
& + 144 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1, i_3} - 36 u_{i_l-5, i_2, i_3-2} + 144 u_{i_l-5, i_2, i_3-1} - 108 u_{i_l-5, i_2, i_3} + 57 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 228 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 171 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3} \\
& - 228 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 912 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 684 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3} + 171 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-2} - 684 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-1} + 513 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3} - 136 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-2} \\
& + 544 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 408 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3} + 544 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 2176 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 1632 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3} - 408 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-2} + 1632 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-1} \\
& - 1224 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3} + 171 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 684 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 513 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3} - 684 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 2736 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 2052 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3} \\
& + 513 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-2} - 2052 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1} + 1539 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3} - 108 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 432 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 324 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3} + 432 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2} \\
& - 1728 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 1296 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3} - 324 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2} + 1296 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1} - 972 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3} + 27 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 108 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 81 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3} \\
& - 108 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 432 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 324 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3} + 81 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-2} - 324 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1} + 243 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.00028335917649359756601, New Error:, 2.8416937000546119092 $\times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 2.8416937000546119092 $\times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, 2.8417018042210791064 $\times 10^{-16}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 2.8417018042210791064 $\times 10^{-16}$, New Error:, 2.8417018123252477606 $\times 10^{-22}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 2.8417018123252477606 $\times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, 2.8417018123333519293 $\times 10^{-28}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 2.8417018123333519293 $\times 10^{-28}$, New Error:, 2.8417018123333600334 $\times 10^{-34}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) &= \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} (-u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-1} + u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3+1} + u_{i_l-3, i_2+1, i_3-1} - u_{i_l-3, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1} \\
& - 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1} + 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1} + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + u_{i_l+3, i_2-1, i_3-1} - u_{i_l+3, i_2-1, i_3+1} \\
& - u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3-1} + u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+1}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.00014208555432963101762, New Error:, 1.4208509061713171415 $\times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 1.4208509061713171415 $\times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, 1.4208509061666800254 $\times 10^{-16}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 1.4208509061666800254 $\times 10^{-16}$, New Error:, 1.4208509061666800208 $\times 10^{-22}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 1.4208509061666800208 $\times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, 1.4208509061666800208 $\times 10^{-28}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 1.4208509061666800208 $\times 10^{-28}$, New Error:, 1.4208509061666800208 $\times 10^{-34}$

"--- Derivative Order: 5 - x1=2, x2=2, x3=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3} (-u_{i_l, i_2, i_3} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1} + 2 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1} - u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3} + u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1}$$

$$-4u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3} + 4u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 2u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3} - 2u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3} + u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1} + 2u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3} - 2u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3} + u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+1}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order: 1, Error: 0.14000974417682123362, New Error: 0.00013944820788589433842

Error order: 1, Error: 0.00013944820788589433842, New Error: 1.3944764794413280164 × 10⁻⁷

Error order: 1, Error: 1.3944764794413280164 × 10⁻⁷, New Error: 1.3944764738419263106 × 10⁻¹⁰

Error order: 1, Error: 1.3944764738419263106 × 10⁻¹⁰, New Error: 1.3944764738363269089 × 10⁻¹³

Error order: 1, Error: 1.3944764738363269089 × 10⁻¹³, New Error: 1.3944764738363213095 × 10⁻¹⁶

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3} (-u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3} + 2u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 2u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3} - u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3} + 2u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 2u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3} - 4u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 4u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3} + 2u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1} - 2u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3} - u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3} + 2u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 2u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order: 1, Error: 0.13888873571405683091, New Error: 0.00013944708688455503271

Error order: 1, Error: 0.00013944708688455503271, New Error: 1.3944764682313146234 × 10⁻⁷

Error order: 1, Error: 1.3944764682313146234 × 10⁻⁷, New Error: 1.3944764738307162972 × 10⁻¹⁰

Error order: 1, Error: 1.3944764738307162972 × 10⁻¹⁰, New Error: 1.3944764738363156989 × 10⁻¹³

Error order: 1, Error: 1.3944764738363156989 × 10⁻¹³, New Error: 1.3944764738363212983 × 10⁻¹⁶

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3} (-243u_{i_l, i_2, i_3} + 324u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1} - 81u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+2} + 648u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3} - 864u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 216u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 594u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3} + 792u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 198u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 216u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3} - 288u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 72u_{i_l, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 27u_{i_l, i_2+4, i_3} + 36u_{i_l, i_2+4, i_3+1} - 9u_{i_l, i_2+4, i_3+2} + 648u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3} - 864u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1} + 216u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+2} - 1728u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3} + 2304u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 576u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 1584u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3} - 2112u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 528u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 576u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3} + 768u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 192u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 72u_{i_l+1, i_2+4, i_3} - 96u_{i_l+1, i_2+4, i_3+1} + 24u_{i_l+1, i_2+4, i_3+2} - 594u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3} + 792u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1} - 198u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+2} + 1584u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3} - 2112u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 528u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 1452u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3} + 1936u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 484u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 528u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3} - 704u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 176u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 66u_{i_l+2, i_2+4, i_3} + 88u_{i_l+2, i_2+4, i_3+1} - 22u_{i_l+2, i_2+4, i_3+2} + 216u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3} - 288u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+1} + 72u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+2} - 576u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3} + 768u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 192u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 528u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3} - 704u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 176u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 192u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3} + 256u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 64u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 24u_{i_l+3, i_2+4, i_3} - 32u_{i_l+3, i_2+4, i_3+1} + 8u_{i_l+3, i_2+4, i_3+2} - 27u_{i_l+4, i_2, i_3} + 36u_{i_l+4, i_2, i_3+1} - 9u_{i_l+4, i_2, i_3+2} + 72u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3}$$

$$- 96 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 24 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 66 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3} + 88 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 22 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 24 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3, i_3} - 32 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 8 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 3 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4, i_3} + 4 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+4, i_2+4, i_3+2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.00031564349416896251093, *New Error:*, $3.1474633666374748593 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1474633666374748593 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $3.1474543942928080913 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1474543942928080913 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $3.1474543853204627228 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1474543853204627228 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $3.1474543853114903775 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1474543853114903775 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $3.1474543853114814051 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3} (u_{i_l-4, i_2-4, i_3-2} - 4 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4, i_3-1} + 3 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4, i_3} - 8 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3, i_3-2} + 32 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 24 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3, i_3} + 22 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 88 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 66 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3} - 24 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 96 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 72 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3} + 9 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-2} - 36 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-1} + 27 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3} - 8 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4, i_3-2} + 32 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4, i_3-1} - 24 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4, i_3} + 64 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3-2} - 256 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3-1} + 192 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3, i_3} - 176 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 704 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 528 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3} + 192 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 768 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 576 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3} - 72 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-2} + 288 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-1} - 216 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3} + 22 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4, i_3-2} - 88 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4, i_3-1} + 66 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4, i_3} - 176 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3, i_3-2} + 704 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 528 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3, i_3} + 484 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 1936 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 1452 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3} - 528 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 2112 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 1584 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3} + 198 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-2} - 792 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1} + 594 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3} - 24 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4, i_3-2} + 96 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4, i_3-1} - 72 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4, i_3} + 192 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3, i_3-2} - 768 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3, i_3-1} + 576 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3, i_3} - 528 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 2112 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 1584 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3} + 576 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 2304 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 1728 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3} - 216 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2} + 864 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1} - 648 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3} + 9 u_{i_l, i_2-4, i_3-2} - 36 u_{i_l, i_2-4, i_3-1} + 27 u_{i_l, i_2-4, i_3} - 72 u_{i_l, i_2-3, i_3-2} + 288 u_{i_l, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 216 u_{i_l, i_2-3, i_3} + 198 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 792 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 594 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3} - 216 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 864 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 648 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3} + 81 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-2} - 324 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1} + 243 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.00031384724238955618978, *New Error:*, $3.1474454039840833096 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1474454039840833096 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $3.1474543763301546996 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1474543763301546996 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $3.1474543853025000694 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1474543853025000694 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $3.1474543853114724148 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1474543853114724148 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $3.1474543853114813871 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3} (-u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3+1} + 2 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1} - 2 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3+1} - u_{i_l-2, i_2+2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l-2, i_2+2, i_3+1})$$

$$+ 2 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3+1} - 4 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1} + 4 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1} + 2 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3-1} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l+2, i_2-2, i_3+1} + 2 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3-1} - 2 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1} - u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+1}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.00015737329963849101792, *New Error:*, $1.5737271926615444145 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.5737271926615444145 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $1.5737271926557407039 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.5737271926557407039 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $1.5737271926557406981 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.5737271926557406981 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $1.5737271926557406981 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.5737271926557406981 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $1.5737271926557406981 \times 10^{-34}$

"--- Derivative Order: 5 - x1=2, x2=1, x3=1, x4=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (-u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} + 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} + 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} + 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} + 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} - u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} + u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} - u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} - u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} + u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.46096096892076636860, *New Error:*, 0.00045860488693560077208
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00045860488693560077208, *New Error:*, $4.5860253942179461405 \times 10^{-7}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5860253942179461405 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $4.5860253707428935147 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5860253707428935147 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $4.5860253707194184622 \times 10^{-13}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5860253707194184622 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $4.5860253707193949871 \times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (-u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} + u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} - u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} - u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3, i_4} + 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} - 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} + 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} - 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} + 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} - 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.45626120956552110049, *New Error:*, 0.00045860018722538244526
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00045860018722538244526, *New Error:*, $4.5860253472208439578 \times 10^{-7}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5860253472208439578 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $4.5860253706958964125 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5860253706958964125 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $4.5860253707193714651 \times 10^{-13}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5860253707193714651 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $4.5860253707193949401 \times 10^{-16}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = & \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} \left(-243 u_{il, i2, i3, i4} + 324 u_{il, i2, i3, i4+1} - 81 u_{il, i2, i3, i4+2} + 324 u_{il, i2, i3+1, i4} - 432 u_{il, i2, i3+1, i4+1} \right. \\
& + 108 u_{il, i2, i3+1, i4+2} - 81 u_{il, i2, i3+2, i4} + 108 u_{il, i2, i3+2, i4+1} - 27 u_{il, i2, i3+2, i4+2} + 324 u_{il, i2+1, i3, i4} - 432 u_{il, i2+1, i3, i4+1} + 108 u_{il, i2+1, i3, i4+2} \\
& - 432 u_{il, i2+1, i3+1, i4} + 576 u_{il, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1} - 144 u_{il, i2+1, i3+1, i4+2} + 108 u_{il, i2+1, i3+2, i4} - 144 u_{il, i2+1, i3+2, i4+1} + 36 u_{il, i2+1, i3+2, i4+2} \\
& - 81 u_{il, i2+2, i3, i4} + 108 u_{il, i2+2, i3, i4+1} - 27 u_{il, i2+2, i3, i4+2} + 108 u_{il, i2+2, i3+1, i4} - 144 u_{il, i2+2, i3+1, i4+1} + 36 u_{il, i2+2, i3+1, i4+2} - 27 u_{il, i2+2, i3+2, i4} \\
& + 36 u_{il, i2+2, i3+2, i4+1} - 9 u_{il, i2+2, i3+2, i4+2} + 648 u_{il+1, i2, i3, i4} - 864 u_{il+1, i2, i3, i4+1} + 216 u_{il+1, i2, i3, i4+2} - 864 u_{il+1, i2, i3+1, i4} + 1152 u_{il+1, i2, i3+1, i4+1} \\
& - 288 u_{il+1, i2, i3+1, i4+2} + 216 u_{il+1, i2, i3+2, i4} - 288 u_{il+1, i2, i3+2, i4+1} + 72 u_{il+1, i2, i3+2, i4+2} - 864 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3, i4} + 1152 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3, i4+1} \\
& - 288 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3, i4+2} + 1152 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4} - 1536 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1} + 384 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+2} - 288 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3+2, i4} \\
& + 384 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3+2, i4+1} - 96 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3+2, i4+2} + 216 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3, i4} - 288 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3, i4+1} + 72 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3, i4+2} - 288 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3+1, i4} \\
& + 384 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3+1, i4+1} - 96 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3+1, i4+2} + 72 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3+2, i4} - 96 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3+2, i4+1} + 24 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3+2, i4+2} - 594 u_{il+2, i2, i3, i4} \\
& + 792 u_{il+2, i2, i3, i4+1} - 198 u_{il+2, i2, i3, i4+2} + 792 u_{il+2, i2, i3+1, i4} - 1056 u_{il+2, i2, i3+1, i4+1} + 264 u_{il+2, i2, i3+1, i4+2} - 198 u_{il+2, i2, i3+2, i4} \\
& + 264 u_{il+2, i2, i3+2, i4+1} - 66 u_{il+2, i2, i3+2, i4+2} + 792 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3, i4} - 1056 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3, i4+1} + 264 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3, i4+2} - 1056 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3+1, i4} \\
& + 1408 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1} - 352 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3+1, i4+2} + 264 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3+2, i4} - 352 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3+2, i4+1} + 88 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3+2, i4+2} - 198 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3, i4} \\
& + 264 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3, i4+1} - 66 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3, i4+2} + 264 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3+1, i4} - 352 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3+1, i4+1} + 88 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3+1, i4+2} - 66 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3+2, i4} \\
& + 88 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3+2, i4+1} - 22 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3+2, i4+2} + 216 u_{il+3, i2, i3, i4} - 288 u_{il+3, i2, i3, i4+1} + 72 u_{il+3, i2, i3, i4+2} - 288 u_{il+3, i2, i3+1, i4} \\
& + 384 u_{il+3, i2, i3+1, i4+1} - 96 u_{il+3, i2, i3+1, i4+2} + 72 u_{il+3, i2, i3+2, i4} - 96 u_{il+3, i2, i3+2, i4+1} + 24 u_{il+3, i2, i3+2, i4+2} - 288 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3, i4} \\
& + 384 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3, i4+1} - 96 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3, i4+2} + 384 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+1, i4} - 512 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1} + 128 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+1, i4+2} - 96 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+2, i4} \\
& + 128 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+2, i4+1} - 32 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+2, i4+2} + 72 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3, i4} - 96 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3, i4+1} + 24 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3, i4+2} - 96 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+1, i4} \\
& + 128 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+1, i4+1} - 32 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+1, i4+2} + 24 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+2, i4} - 32 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+2, i4+1} + 8 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+2, i4+2} - 27 u_{il+4, i2, i3, i4} \\
& + 36 u_{il+4, i2, i3, i4+1} - 9 u_{il+4, i2, i3, i4+2} + 36 u_{il+4, i2, i3+1, i4} - 48 u_{il+4, i2, i3+1, i4+1} + 12 u_{il+4, i2, i3+1, i4+2} - 9 u_{il+4, i2, i3+2, i4} + 12 u_{il+4, i2, i3+2, i4+1} \\
& - 3 u_{il+4, i2, i3+2, i4+2} + 36 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3, i4} - 48 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3, i4+1} + 12 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3, i4+2} - 48 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+1, i4} + 64 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1} \\
& - 16 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+1, i4+2} + 12 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+2, i4} - 16 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+2, i4+1} + 4 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+2, i4+2} - 9 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3, i4} + 12 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3, i4+1} \\
& - 3 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3, i4+2} + 12 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+1, i4} - 16 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+1, i4+1} + 4 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+1, i4+2} - 3 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+2, i4} + 4 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+2, i4+1}
\end{aligned}$$

$-u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3+2, i_4+2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2 \Delta x_4^2), \text{ Forward}$

Error order.: 2, Error.: 0.0014610317399107454152, New Error.: 1.4549503787738705340 $\times 10^{-9}$
Error order.: 2, Error.: 1.4549503787738705340 $\times 10^{-9}$, New Error.: 1.4549443010806346121 $\times 10^{-15}$
Error order.: 2, Error.: 1.4549443010806346121 $\times 10^{-15}$, New Error.: 1.4549442950029451081 $\times 10^{-21}$
Error order.: 2, Error.: 1.4549442950029451081 $\times 10^{-21}$, New Error.: 1.4549442949968674186 $\times 10^{-27}$
Error order.: 2, Error.: 1.4549442949968674186 $\times 10^{-27}$, New Error.: 1.4549442949968613409 $\times 10^{-33}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-2} - 4 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 3 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4} - 4 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-2} \\ + 16 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 12 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} + 3 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-2} - 12 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1} + 9 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3, i_4} - 4 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-2} \\ + 16 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-1} - 12 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4} + 16 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-2} - 64 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 48 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} - 12 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-2} \\ + 48 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} - 36 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} + 3 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-2} - 12 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 9 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-2, i_4} - 12 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-2} + 48 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} \\ - 36 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} + 9 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3, i_4-2} - 36 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + 27 u_{i_l-4, i_2, i_3, i_4} - 8 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-2} + 32 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-1} - 24 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4} \\ + 32 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-2} - 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 96 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} - 24 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-2} + 96 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1} - 72 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2, i_3, i_4} \\ + 32 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-2} - 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 96 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4} - 128 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-2} + 512 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 384 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} \\ + 96 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-2} - 384 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} + 288 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} - 24 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-2} + 96 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-1} - 72 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-2, i_4} \\ + 96 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-2} - 384 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 288 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} - 72 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3, i_4-2} + 288 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} - 216 u_{i_l-3, i_2, i_3, i_4} + 22 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-2} \\ - 88 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 66 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4} - 88 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-2} + 352 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 264 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} + 66 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-2} \\ - 264 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1} + 198 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3, i_4} - 88 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-2} + 352 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-1} - 264 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4} + 352 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-2} \\ - 1408 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 1056 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} - 264 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-2} + 1056 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} - 792 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} + 66 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-2} \\ - 264 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 198 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-2, i_4} - 264 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-2} + 1056 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 792 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} + 198 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3, i_4-2} \\ - 792 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + 594 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3, i_4} - 24 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-2} + 96 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-1} - 72 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4} + 96 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-2} \\ - 384 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 288 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} - 72 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-2} + 288 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1} - 216 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3, i_4} + 96 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-2} \\ - 384 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 288 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2, i_4} - 384 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-2} + 1536 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 1152 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} \\ + 288 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-2} - 1152 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} + 864 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} - 72 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-2} + 288 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2, i_4-1} - 216 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2, i_4} \\ + 288 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-2} - 1152 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 864 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} - 216 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-2} + 864 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} - 648 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4} + 9 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-2} \\ - 36 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4-1} + 27 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2, i_4} - 36 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-2} + 144 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 108 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} + 27 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-2} - 108 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 81 u_{i1, i2-2, i3, i4} - 36 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-2, i4-2} + 144 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-2, i4-1} - 108 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-2, i4} + 144 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-2} - 576 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1} \\
& + 432 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-1, i4} - 108 u_{i1, i2-1, i3, i4-2} + 432 u_{i1, i2-1, i3, i4-1} - 324 u_{i1, i2-1, i3, i4} + 27 u_{i1, i2, i3-2, i4-2} - 108 u_{i1, i2, i3-2, i4-1} + 81 u_{i1, i2, i3-2, i4} \\
& - 108 u_{i1, i2, i3-1, i4-2} + 432 u_{i1, i2, i3-1, i4-1} - 324 u_{i1, i2, i3-1, i4} + 81 u_{i1, i2, i3, i4-2} - 324 u_{i1, i2, i3, i4-1} + 243 u_{i1, i2, i3, i4}), O(\Delta x1^2 \Delta x2^2 \Delta x3^2 \Delta x4^2),
\end{aligned}$$

Backward

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 0.0014488643208882512524, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4549382112273236161 \times 10^{-9} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 1.4549382112273236161 \times 10^{-9}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4549442889130880650 \times 10^{-15} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 1.4549442889130880650 \times 10^{-15}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4549442949907775615 \times 10^{-21} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 1.4549442949907775615 \times 10^{-21}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4549442949968552510 \times 10^{-27} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 1.4549442949968552510 \times 10^{-27}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4549442949968613287 \times 10^{-33}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x1^2 \partial x2 \partial x3 \partial x4} u(x1, x2, x3, x4) &= \frac{1}{32 \Delta x1^2 \Delta x2 \Delta x3 \Delta x4} \left(-u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1} + u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1} + u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1} - u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1} \right. \\
& + u_{i1-2, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1} - u_{i1-2, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1} - u_{i1-2, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1} + u_{i1-2, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1} + 2 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1} - 2 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1} \\
& - 2 u_{i1, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1} + 2 u_{i1, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1} - 2 u_{i1, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1} + 2 u_{i1, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1} + 2 u_{i1, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1} - 2 u_{i1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1} - u_{i1+2, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1} \\
& + u_{i1+2, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1} + u_{i1+2, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1} - u_{i1+2, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1} + u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1} - u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1} - u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1} \\
& \left. + u_{i1+2, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1} \right), O(\Delta x1^2 \Delta x2^2 \Delta x3^2 \Delta x4^2), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 0.00072747677837496805890, \text{ New Error:}, 7.2747214750306152684 \times 10^{-10} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 7.2747214750306152684 \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.2747214749843067204 \times 10^{-16} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 7.2747214749843067204 \times 10^{-16}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.2747214749843066741 \times 10^{-22} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 7.2747214749843066741 \times 10^{-22}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.2747214749843066741 \times 10^{-28} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 7.2747214749843066741 \times 10^{-28}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.2747214749843066741 \times 10^{-34}
\end{aligned}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 5 - x1=1, x2=1, x3=1, x4=1, x5=1 ---"

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x1 \partial x2 \partial x3 \partial x4 \partial x5} u(x1, x2, x3, x4, x5) &= \frac{1}{\Delta x1 \Delta x2 \Delta x3 \Delta x4 \Delta x5} \left(-u_{i1, i2, i3, i4, i5} + u_{i1, i2, i3, i4, i5+1} + u_{i1, i2, i3, i4+1, i5} - u_{i1, i2, i3, i4+1, i5+1} + u_{i1, i2, i3+1, i4, i5} \right. \\
& - u_{i1, i2, i3+1, i4, i5+1} - u_{i1, i2, i3+1, i4+1, i5} + u_{i1, i2, i3+1, i4+1, i5+1} + u_{i1, i2+1, i3, i4, i5} - u_{i1, i2+1, i3, i4, i5+1} - u_{i1, i2+1, i3, i4+1, i5} + u_{i1, i2+1, i3, i4+1, i5+1} \\
& \left. - u_{i1, i2+1, i3+1, i4, i5} + u_{i1, i2+1, i3+1, i4, i5+1} + u_{i1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1, i5} - u_{i1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1, i5+1} + u_{i1+1, i2, i3, i4, i5} - u_{i1+1, i2, i3, i4, i5+1} - u_{i1+1, i2, i3, i4+1, i5} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$+ u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5} - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5+1} \\ + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1}),$$

$O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5)$, Forward

Error order:, 1, Error:, 1.7190348094079119055, New Error:, 0.0017060779789469794586

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.0017060779789469794586, New Error:, $1.7060650917861126774 \times 10^{-6}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $1.7060650917861126774 \times 10^{-6}$, New Error:, $1.7060650788990211840 \times 10^{-9}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $1.7060650788990211840 \times 10^{-9}$, New Error:, $1.7060650788861340925 \times 10^{-12}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $1.7060650788861340925 \times 10^{-12}$, New Error:, $1.7060650788861212055 \times 10^{-15}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4 \partial x_5} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5} \left(-u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1} \right. \\ - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} \\ - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5} + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5} \\ + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5-1} \\ - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5-1} \\ \left. + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5} \right), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5)$$
, Backward

Error order:, 1, Error:, 1.6932342356496405103, New Error:, 0.0017060521789641481124

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.0017060521789641481124, New Error:, $1.7060650659861298466 \times 10^{-6}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $1.7060650659861298466 \times 10^{-6}$, New Error:, $1.7060650788732212011 \times 10^{-9}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $1.7060650788732212011 \times 10^{-9}$, New Error:, $1.7060650788861082926 \times 10^{-12}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $1.7060650788861082926 \times 10^{-12}$, New Error:, $1.7060650788861211797 \times 10^{-15}$

$$\frac{\partial^5}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4 \partial x_5} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5} \left(-u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5+1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5-1} \right. \\ - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5+1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5+1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} \\ + u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5+1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5-1} \\ + u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5+1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5+1} \\ - u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5-1} \left. \right)$$

$$- u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5-1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5+1} \\ + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5-1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2 \Delta x_4^2 \Delta x_5^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.0041819656593371301068, *New Error:*, $4.1819060663312655041 \times 10^{-9}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.1819060663312655041 \times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, $4.1819060662716729881 \times 10^{-15}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.1819060662716729881 \times 10^{-15}$, *New Error:*, $4.1819060662716729285 \times 10^{-21}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.1819060662716729285 \times 10^{-21}$, *New Error:*, $4.1819060662716729285 \times 10^{-27}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.1819060662716729285 \times 10^{-27}$, *New Error:*, $4.1819060662716729285 \times 10^{-33}$

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=6 ---"

$$\frac{d^6}{dx I^6} u(xI) = \frac{u_{i_l} - 6 u_{i_l+1} + 15 u_{i_l+2} - 20 u_{i_l+3} + 15 u_{i_l+4} - 6 u_{i_l+5} + u_{i_l+6}}{\Delta x I^6}, O(\Delta x I), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.015943616658374349463, *New Error:*, 0.000015893327631133083386
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000015893327631133083386, *New Error:*, $1.5893277452995264410 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.5893277452995264410 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.5893277402817237290 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.5893277402817237290 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.5893277402767059263 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.5893277402767059263 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.5893277402767009085 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dx I^6} u(xI) = \frac{u_{i_l-6} - 6 u_{i_l-5} + 15 u_{i_l-4} - 20 u_{i_l-3} + 15 u_{i_l-2} - 6 u_{i_l-1} + u_{i_l}}{\Delta x I^6}, O(\Delta x I), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.015843159766227220615, *New Error:*, 0.000015893227174622553206
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000015893227174622553206, *New Error:*, $1.5893277352538753880 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.5893277352538753880 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.5893277402716780779 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.5893277402716780779 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.5893277402766958806 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.5893277402766958806 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.5893277402767008984 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dx I^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x I^6} (729 u_{i_l} - 5832 u_{i_l+1} + 20898 u_{i_l+2} - 44280 u_{i_l+3} + 61695 u_{i_l+4} - 59472 u_{i_l+5} + 40636 u_{i_l+6} - 19824 u_{i_l+7} + 6855 u_{i_l+8} \\ - 1640 u_{i_l+9} + 258 u_{i_l+10} - 24 u_{i_l+11} + u_{i_l+12}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000021180357933996435066, *New Error:*, $2.1148770718653154621 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.1148770718653154621 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.1148739090564657944 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.1148739090564657944 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.1148739058936528764 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.1148739058936528764 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.1148739058904900634 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.1148739058904900634 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $2.1148739058904869006 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta xI^6} (u_{iI-12} - 24 u_{iI-11} + 258 u_{iI-10} - 1640 u_{iI-9} + 6855 u_{iI-8} - 19824 u_{iI-7} + 40636 u_{iI-6} - 59472 u_{iI-5} + 61695 u_{iI-4} - 44280 u_{iI-3} + 20898 u_{iI-2} - 5832 u_{iI-1} + 729 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000021117038734377843112, *New Error:*, $2.1148707399075134326 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.1148707399075134326 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.1148739027245079924 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.1148739027245079924 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.1148739058873209186 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.1148739058873209186 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.1148739058904837315 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.1148739058904837315 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $2.1148739058904868943 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-6} - 6 u_{iI-4} + 15 u_{iI-2} - 20 u_{iI} + 15 u_{iI+2} - 6 u_{iI+4} + u_{iI+6}}{64 \Delta xI^6}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000010574389189579233782, *New Error:*, $1.0574369529472094591 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.0574369529472094591 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.0574369529452434507 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.0574369529452434507 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.0574369529452434487 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.0574369529452434487 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.0574369529452434487 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.0574369529452434487 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $1.0574369529452434487 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{46656 \Delta xI^6} (1771561 u_{iI} - 17393508 u_{iI+1} + 79852014 u_{iI+2} - 228335712 u_{iI+3} + 457004295 u_{iI+4} - 681865668 u_{iI+5} + 788302464 u_{iI+6} - 724073472 u_{iI+7} + 537085431 u_{iI+8} - 324924140 u_{iI+9} + 161079894 u_{iI+10} - 65428992 u_{iI+11} + 21662601 u_{iI+12} - 5780268 u_{iI+13} + 1218780 u_{iI+14} - 196512 u_{iI+15} + 22896 u_{iI+16} - 1728 u_{iI+17} + 64 u_{iI+18}), O(\Delta xI^3), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.1735726218161978822 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.1659864842271707107 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.1659864842271707107 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.1659789086168460272 \times 10^{-26}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.1659789086168460272 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $3.1659789010412462031 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.1659789010412462031 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $3.1659789010336706033 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.1659789010336706033 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $3.1659789010336630277 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{46656 \Delta xI^6} (64 u_{iI-18} - 1728 u_{iI-17} + 22896 u_{iI-16} - 196512 u_{iI-15} + 1218780 u_{iI-14} - 5780268 u_{iI-13} + 21662601 u_{iI-12} \\ - 65428992 u_{iI-11} + 161079894 u_{iI-10} - 324924140 u_{iI-9} + 537085431 u_{iI-8} - 724073472 u_{iI-7} + 788302464 u_{iI-6} - 681865668 u_{iI-5} \\ + 457004295 u_{iI-4} - 228335712 u_{iI-3} + 79852014 u_{iI-2} - 17393508 u_{iI-1} + 1771561 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.1584062027724008442 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.1659713178611776821 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.1659713178611776821 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.1659788934504800342 \times 10^{-26}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.1659788934504800342 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $3.1659789010260798372 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.1659789010260798372 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $3.1659789010336554370 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.1659789010336554370 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $3.1659789010336630126 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{2985984 \Delta xI^6} (244140625 u_{iI} - 2812500000 u_{iI+1} + 15609375000 u_{iI+2} - 55747500000 u_{iI+3} + 144295931250 u_{iI+4} \\ - 288837295200 u_{iI+5} + 465540247464 u_{iI+6} - 620693597088 u_{iI+7} + 697496570343 u_{iI+8} - 669389466944 u_{iI+9} + 553714677360 u_{iI+10} \\ - 397220614848 u_{iI+11} + 248021426076 u_{iI+12} - 134977772736 u_{iI+13} + 63977696208 u_{iI+14} - 26333401920 u_{iI+15} + 9361423503 u_{iI+16} \\ - 2850231456 u_{iI+17} + 734148856 u_{iI+18} - 157170528 u_{iI+19} + 27254610 u_{iI+20} - 3681504 u_{iI+21} + 363528 u_{iI+22} - 23328 u_{iI+23} + 729 u_{iI+24}),$$

$O(\Delta xI^4)$, Forward

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $5.0723044257473602168 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $5.0554721489050539487 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $5.0554721489050539487 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $5.0554553478097591152 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $5.0554553478097591152 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $5.0554553310086949601 \times 10^{-47}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $5.0554553310086949601 \times 10^{-47}$, *New Error:*, $5.0554553309918938960 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $5.0554553309918938960 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $5.0554553309918770949 \times 10^{-71}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{2985984 \Delta xI^6} (729 u_{iI-24} - 23328 u_{iI-23} + 363528 u_{iI-22} - 3681504 u_{iI-21} + 27254610 u_{iI-20} - 157170528 u_{iI-19} + 734148856 u_{iI-18}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 2850231456 u_{iI-17} + 9361423503 u_{iI-16} - 26333401920 u_{iI-15} + 63977696208 u_{iI-14} - 134977772736 u_{iI-13} + 248021426076 u_{iI-12} \\
& - 397220614848 u_{iI-11} + 553714677360 u_{iI-10} - 669389466944 u_{iI-9} + 697496570343 u_{iI-8} - 620693597088 u_{iI-7} + 465540247464 u_{iI-6} \\
& - 288837295200 u_{iI-5} + 144295931250 u_{iI-4} - 55747500000 u_{iI-3} + 15609375000 u_{iI-2} - 2812500000 u_{iI-1} + 244140625 u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^4),
\end{aligned}$$

Backward

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 5.0386685779818310203 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.0554385131410419429 \times 10^{-23} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 5.0554385131410419429 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.0554553141739951033 \times 10^{-35} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 5.0554553141739951033 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.0554553309750591961 \times 10^{-47} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 5.0554553309750591961 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.0554553309918602602 \times 10^{-59} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 5.0554553309918602602 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.0554553309918770613 \times 10^{-71}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = & \frac{1}{2985984 \Delta x I^6} (u_{iI-12} - 48 u_{iI-11} + 960 u_{iI-10} - 10192 u_{iI-9} + 59514 u_{iI-8} - 165648 u_{iI-7} + 13504 u_{iI-6} + 982800 u_{iI-5} \\
& - 1319409 u_{iI-4} - 1851872 u_{iI-3} + 4179840 u_{iI-2} + 1044960 u_{iI-1} - 5868820 u_{iI} + 1044960 u_{iI+1} + 4179840 u_{iI+2} - 1851872 u_{iI+3} \\
& - 1319409 u_{iI+4} + 982800 u_{iI+5} + 13504 u_{iI+6} - 165648 u_{iI+7} + 59514 u_{iI+8} - 10192 u_{iI+9} + 960 u_{iI+10} - 48 u_{iI+11} + u_{iI+12}), O(\Delta x I^4),
\end{aligned}$$

Centered

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 8.4257628812413358979 \times 10^{-12}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4257588849904580619 \times 10^{-24} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 8.4257588849904580619 \times 10^{-24}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4257588849864618008 \times 10^{-36} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 8.4257588849864618008 \times 10^{-36}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4257588849864617968 \times 10^{-48} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 8.4257588849864617968 \times 10^{-48}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4257588849864617968 \times 10^{-60} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 8.4257588849864617968 \times 10^{-60}, \text{ New Error:}, 8.4257588849864617968 \times 10^{-72}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = & \frac{1}{46656000000 \Delta x I^6} (6611856250609 u_{iI} - 86871104022600 u_{iI+1} + 562442841372600 u_{iI+2} - 2397588164048400 u_{iI+3} \\
& + 7577410523155650 u_{iI+4} - 18937203462635904 u_{iI+5} + 38951304889263000 u_{iI+6} - 67726860155838000 u_{iI+7} + 101436089513376375 u_{iI+8} \\
& - 132653232179597000 u_{iI+9} + 152992637544929760 u_{iI+10} - 156760879523076000 u_{iI+11} + 143458638676813500 u_{iI+12} \\
& - 117689471164584000 u_{iI+13} + 86750899800894000 u_{iI+14} - 57518956733059680 u_{iI+15} + 34302921279735375 u_{iI+16} - 18379465266951000 u_{iI+17} \\
& + 8827031667259000 u_{iI+18} - 3786448392594000 u_{iI+19} + 1443522737591010 u_{iI+20} - 485843906088000 u_{iI+21} + 143105177763000 u_{iI+22} \\
& - 36470394342000 u_{iI+23} + 7921873787625 u_{iI+24} - 1437385514904 u_{iI+25} + 211870047600 u_{iI+26} - 24359097600 u_{iI+27} + 2048198400 u_{iI+28}
\end{aligned}$$

– 111974400 u_{i_l+29} + 2985984 u_{i_l+30}), $O(\Delta x I^5)$, *Forward*

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, 8.4449912823477279956 $\times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, 8.4089769694500675703 $\times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, 8.4089769694500675703 $\times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, 8.4089410389468866916 $\times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, 8.4089410389468866916 $\times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, 8.4089410030164671810 $\times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, 8.4089410030164671810 $\times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, 8.4089410029805367616 $\times 10^{-74}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, 8.4089410029805367616 $\times 10^{-74}$, *New Error:*, 8.4089410029805008312 $\times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dx I^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{46656000000 \Delta x I^6} (2985984 u_{i_l-30} - 111974400 u_{i_l-29} + 2048198400 u_{i_l-28} - 24359097600 u_{i_l-27} + 211870047600 u_{i_l-26}$$

– 1437385514904 u_{i_l-25} + 7921873787625 u_{i_l-24} – 36470394342000 u_{i_l-23} + 143105177763000 u_{i_l-22} – 485843906088000 u_{i_l-21}

+ 1443522737591010 u_{i_l-20} – 3786448392594000 u_{i_l-19} + 8827031667259000 u_{i_l-18} – 18379465266951000 u_{i_l-17} + 34302921279735375 u_{i_l-16}

– 57518956733059680 u_{i_l-15} + 86750899800894000 u_{i_l-14} – 117689471164584000 u_{i_l-13} + 143458638676813500 u_{i_l-12}

– 156760879523076000 u_{i_l-11} + 152992637544929760 u_{i_l-10} – 132653232179597000 u_{i_l-9} + 101436089513376375 u_{i_l-8}

– 67726860155838000 u_{i_l-7} + 38951304889263000 u_{i_l-6} – 18937203462635904 u_{i_l-5} + 7577410523155650 u_{i_l-4} – 2397588164048400 u_{i_l-3}

+ 562442841372600 u_{i_l-2} – 86871104022600 u_{i_l-1} + 6611856250609 u_{i_l}), $O(\Delta x I^5)$, *Backward*

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, 8.3730582320989932655 $\times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, 8.4089050366784421377 $\times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, 8.4089050366784421377 $\times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, 8.4089409670141150664 $\times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, 8.4089409670141150664 $\times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, 8.4089410029445344094 $\times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, 8.4089410029445344094 $\times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, 8.4089410029804648288 $\times 10^{-74}$

Error order:, 5, *Error:*, 8.4089410029804648288 $\times 10^{-74}$, *New Error:*, 8.4089410029805007593 $\times 10^{-89}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dx I^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{46656000000 \Delta x I^6} (u_{i_l-18} - 54 u_{i_l-17} + 1485 u_{i_l-16} - 26730 u_{i_l-15} + 347220 u_{i_l-14} - 3403890 u_{i_l-13} + 25691655 u_{i_l-12}$$

– 149512770 u_{i_l-11} + 659011005 u_{i_l-10} – 2087301960 u_{i_l-9} + 4067760114 u_{i_l-8} – 1392201216 u_{i_l-7} – 16896538425 u_{i_l-6} + 43745134050 u_{i_l-5}

– 15692700375 u_{i_l-4} – 99694251630 u_{i_l-3} + 132338201895 u_{i_l-2} + 59581564200 u_{i_l-1} – 209003549150 u_{i_l} + 59581564200 u_{i_l+1}

+ 132338201895 u_{i_l+2} – 99694251630 u_{i_l+3} – 15692700375 u_{i_l+4} + 43745134050 u_{i_l+5} – 16896538425 u_{i_l+6} – 1392201216 u_{i_l+7}

+ 4067760114 u_{i_l+8} – 2087301960 u_{i_l+9} + 659011005 u_{i_l+10} – 149512770 u_{i_l+11} + 25691655 u_{i_l+12} – 3403890 u_{i_l+13} + 347220 u_{i_l+14}

$- 26730 u_{i_l+15} + 1485 u_{i_l+16} - 54 u_{i_l+17} + u_{i_l+18}$), $O(\Delta x l^6)$, *Centered*

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.1932827349765182084 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $7.1932771625209709151 \times 10^{-36}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.1932771625209709151 \times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, $7.1932771625153984617 \times 10^{-54}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.1932771625153984617 \times 10^{-54}$, *New Error:*, $7.1932771625153984561 \times 10^{-72}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.1932771625153984561 \times 10^{-72}$, *New Error:*, $7.1932771625153984561 \times 10^{-90}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $7.1932771625153984561 \times 10^{-90}$, *New Error:*, $7.1932771625153984561 \times 10^{-108}$

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=5, x2=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x l^5 \partial x 2} u(x l, x 2)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Delta x l^5 \Delta x 2} (u_{i_l, i_2} - u_{i_l, i_2+1} - 5 u_{i_l+1, i_2} + 5 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} + 10 u_{i_l+2, i_2} - 10 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} - 10 u_{i_l+3, i_2} + 10 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} + 5 u_{i_l+4, i_2} - 5 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1}$$

$- u_{i_l+5, i_2} + u_{i_l+5, i_2+1}$), $O(\Delta x l \Delta x 2)$, *Forward*

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.046081737397151095994, *New Error:*, 0.000045924079594151087520

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000045924079594151087520, *New Error:*, $4.5923922313856488749 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5923922313856488749 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $4.5923922156576570953 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5923922156576570953 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.5923922156419291035 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5923922156419291035 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $4.5923922156419133755 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x l^5 \partial x 2} u(x l, x 2)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Delta x l^5 \Delta x 2} (u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - u_{i_l-5, i_2} - 5 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 5 u_{i_l-4, i_2} + 10 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 10 u_{i_l-3, i_2} - 10 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 10 u_{i_l-2, i_2} + 5 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 5 u_{i_l-1, i_2}$$

$- u_{i_l, i_2-1} + u_{i_l, i_2}$), $O(\Delta x l \Delta x 2)$, *Backward*

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.045766861275919091620, *New Error:*, 0.000045923764719441537718

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000045923764719441537718, *New Error:*, $4.5923921998981779201 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5923921998981779201 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $4.5923922156261696243 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.5923922156261696243 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.5923922156418976160 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, Error:., 4.5923922156418976160 $\times 10^{-14}$, New Error:., 4.5923922156419133440 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^5 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^5 \Delta x_2} (729 u_{i_1, i_2} - 972 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 243 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 4860 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 6480 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 1620 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 14175 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 18900 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 4725 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 23760 u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 31680 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 7920 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + 25290 u_{i_1+4, i_2} - 33720 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} + 8430 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} - 17832 u_{i_1+5, i_2} + 23776 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} - 5944 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} + 8430 u_{i_1+6, i_2} - 11240 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} + 2810 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} - 2640 u_{i_1+7, i_2} + 3520 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} - 880 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} + 525 u_{i_1+8, i_2} - 700 u_{i_1+8, i_2+1} + 175 u_{i_1+8, i_2+2} - 60 u_{i_1+9, i_2} + 80 u_{i_1+9, i_2+1} - 20 u_{i_1+9, i_2+2} + 3 u_{i_1+10, i_2} - 4 u_{i_1+10, i_2+1} + u_{i_1+10, i_2+2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2), Forward$$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 0.000068251931984000745780, New Error:., 6.8134428312242281315 $\times 10^{-11}$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 6.8134428312242281315 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:., 6.8134310674509048680 $\times 10^{-17}$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 6.8134310674509048680 $\times 10^{-17}$, New Error:., 6.8134310556871182167 $\times 10^{-23}$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 6.8134310556871182167 $\times 10^{-23}$, New Error:., 6.8134310556753544300 $\times 10^{-29}$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 6.8134310556753544300 $\times 10^{-29}$, New Error:., 6.8134310556753426663 $\times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^5 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^5 \Delta x_2} (u_{i_1-10, i_2-2} - 4 u_{i_1-10, i_2-1} + 3 u_{i_1-10, i_2} - 20 u_{i_1-9, i_2-2} + 80 u_{i_1-9, i_2-1} - 60 u_{i_1-9, i_2} + 175 u_{i_1-8, i_2-2} - 700 u_{i_1-8, i_2-1} + 525 u_{i_1-8, i_2} - 880 u_{i_1-7, i_2-2} + 3520 u_{i_1-7, i_2-1} - 2640 u_{i_1-7, i_2} + 2810 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 11240 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 8430 u_{i_1-6, i_2} - 5944 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 23776 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 17832 u_{i_1-5, i_2} + 8430 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 33720 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 25290 u_{i_1-4, i_2} - 7920 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 31680 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 23760 u_{i_1-3, i_2} + 4725 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 18900 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 14175 u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 1620 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 6480 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 4860 u_{i_1-1, i_2} + 243 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 972 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 729 u_{i_1, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2), Backward$$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 0.000068016422301391934613, New Error:., 6.8134192800997745871 $\times 10^{-11}$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 6.8134192800997745871 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:., 6.8134310438997804143 $\times 10^{-17}$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 6.8134310438997804143 $\times 10^{-17}$, New Error:., 6.8134310556635670923 $\times 10^{-23}$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 6.8134310556635670923 $\times 10^{-23}$, New Error:., 6.8134310556753308789 $\times 10^{-29}$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 6.8134310556753308789 $\times 10^{-29}$, New Error:., 6.8134310556753426427 $\times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^5 \partial x_2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^5 \Delta x_2} (u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - u_{i_1-5, i_2+1} - 5 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} + 5 u_{i_1-3, i_2+1} + 10 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 10 u_{i_1-1, i_2+1} - 10 u_{i_1+1, i_2-1} + 10 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1})$$

$$+ 5 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} - 5 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - u_{i_l+5, i_2-1} + u_{i_l+5, i_2+1}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Centered}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 0.000034067230957851050186, \text{ New Error:}, 3.4067155278452392643 \times 10^{-11}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 3.4067155278452392643 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.4067155278376713348 \times 10^{-17}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 3.4067155278376713348 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.4067155278376713272 \times 10^{-23}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 3.4067155278376713272 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.4067155278376713272 \times 10^{-29}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 3.4067155278376713272 \times 10^{-29}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.4067155278376713272 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^5 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = & \frac{1}{46656 \Delta x I^5 \Delta x^2} (1771561 u_{i_l, i_2} - 2898918 u_{i_l, i_2+1} + 1449459 u_{i_l, i_2+2} - 322102 u_{i_l, i_2+3} - 14494590 u_{i_l+1, i_2} + 23718420 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} \\ & - 11859210 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} + 2635380 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} + 54684135 u_{i_l+2, i_2} - 89483130 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 44741565 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 9942570 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} \\ & - 126671270 u_{i_l+3, i_2} + 207280260 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - 103640130 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 23031140 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} + 202347090 u_{i_l+4, i_2} - 331113420 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} \\ & + 165556710 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} - 36790380 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} - 237169548 u_{i_l+5, i_2} + 388095624 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} - 194047812 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} + 43121736 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} \\ & + 211618990 u_{i_l+6, i_2} - 346285620 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} + 173142810 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} - 38476180 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} - 146949660 u_{i_l+7, i_2} + 240463080 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} \\ & - 120231540 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} + 26718120 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} + 80357805 u_{i_l+8, i_2} - 131494590 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} + 65747295 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} - 14610510 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} \\ & - 34721830 u_{i_l+9, i_2} + 56817540 u_{i_l+9, i_2+1} - 28408770 u_{i_l+9, i_2+2} + 6313060 u_{i_l+9, i_2+3} + 11796939 u_{i_l+10, i_2} - 19304082 u_{i_l+10, i_2+1} \\ & + 9652041 u_{i_l+10, i_2+2} - 2144898 u_{i_l+10, i_2+3} - 3105630 u_{i_l+11, i_2} + 5081940 u_{i_l+11, i_2+1} - 2540970 u_{i_l+11, i_2+2} + 564660 u_{i_l+11, i_2+3} + 615560 u_{i_l+12, i_2} \\ & - 1007280 u_{i_l+12, i_2+1} + 503640 u_{i_l+12, i_2+2} - 111920 u_{i_l+12, i_2+3} - 87120 u_{i_l+13, i_2} + 142560 u_{i_l+13, i_2+1} - 71280 u_{i_l+13, i_2+2} + 15840 u_{i_l+13, i_2+3} \\ & + 7920 u_{i_l+14, i_2} - 12960 u_{i_l+14, i_2+1} + 6480 u_{i_l+14, i_2+2} - 1440 u_{i_l+14, i_2+3} - 352 u_{i_l+15, i_2} + 576 u_{i_l+15, i_2+1} - 288 u_{i_l+15, i_2+2} + 64 u_{i_l+15, i_2+3}), \end{aligned}$$

$$O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^3), \text{ Forward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.1809481969984713531 \times 10^{-7}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1775596087815004675 \times 10^{-16}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.1775596087815004675 \times 10^{-16}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1775562260711166674 \times 10^{-25}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.1775562260711166674 \times 10^{-25}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1775562226884121461 \times 10^{-34}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.1775562226884121461 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1775562226850294415 \times 10^{-43}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.1775562226850294415 \times 10^{-43}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1775562226850260588 \times 10^{-52}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^5 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = & \frac{1}{46656 \Delta x I^5 \Delta x^2} (64 u_{i_l-15, i_2-3} - 288 u_{i_l-15, i_2-2} + 576 u_{i_l-15, i_2-1} - 352 u_{i_l-15, i_2} - 1440 u_{i_l-14, i_2-3} + 6480 u_{i_l-14, i_2-2} \\ & - 12960 u_{i_l-14, i_2-1} + 7920 u_{i_l-14, i_2} + 15840 u_{i_l-13, i_2-3} - 71280 u_{i_l-13, i_2-2} + 142560 u_{i_l-13, i_2-1} - 87120 u_{i_l-13, i_2} - 111920 u_{i_l-12, i_2-3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 503640 u_{i_l-12, i_2-2} - 1007280 u_{i_l-12, i_2-1} + 615560 u_{i_l-12, i_2} + 564660 u_{i_l-11, i_2-3} - 2540970 u_{i_l-11, i_2-2} + 5081940 u_{i_l-11, i_2-1} - 3105630 u_{i_l-11, i_2} \\
& - 2144898 u_{i_l-10, i_2-3} + 9652041 u_{i_l-10, i_2-2} - 19304082 u_{i_l-10, i_2-1} + 11796939 u_{i_l-10, i_2} + 6313060 u_{i_l-9, i_2-3} - 28408770 u_{i_l-9, i_2-2} \\
& + 56817540 u_{i_l-9, i_2-1} - 34721830 u_{i_l-9, i_2} - 14610510 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 65747295 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 131494590 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 80357805 u_{i_l-8, i_2} \\
& + 26718120 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 120231540 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 240463080 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 146949660 u_{i_l-7, i_2} - 38476180 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 173142810 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} \\
& - 346285620 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 211618990 u_{i_l-6, i_2} + 43121736 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 194047812 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 388095624 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 237169548 u_{i_l-5, i_2} \\
& - 36790380 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 165556710 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 331113420 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 202347090 u_{i_l-4, i_2} + 23031140 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 103640130 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} \\
& + 207280260 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 126671270 u_{i_l-3, i_2} - 9942570 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 44741565 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 89483130 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 54684135 u_{i_l-2, i_2} \\
& + 2635380 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 11859210 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 23718420 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 14494590 u_{i_l-1, i_2} - 322102 u_{i_l, i_2-3} + 1449459 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 2898918 u_{i_l, i_2-1} \\
& + 1771561 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^3), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.1741759851094487278 \times 10^{-7}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1775528366002882806 \times 10^{-16}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.1775528366002882806 \times 10^{-16}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1775562192989354552 \times 10^{-25}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.1775562192989354552 \times 10^{-25}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1775562226816399648 \times 10^{-34}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.1775562226816399648 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1775562226850226694 \times 10^{-43}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.1775562226850226694 \times 10^{-43}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1775562226850260521 \times 10^{-52}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^5 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{2985984 \Delta x I^5 \Delta x^2} (244140625 u_{i_l, i_2} - 468750000 u_{i_l, i_2+1} + 351562500 u_{i_l, i_2+2} - 156250000 u_{i_l, i_2+3} + 29296875 u_{i_l, i_2+4} \\
&- 2343750000 u_{i_l+1, i_2} + 4500000000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - 3375000000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} + 1500000000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} - 281250000 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} + 10757812500 u_{i_l+2, i_2} \\
&- 20655000000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 15491250000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 6885000000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} + 1290937500 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} - 31561250000 u_{i_l+3, i_2} \\
&+ 60597600000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - 45448200000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 20199200000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} - 3787350000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} + 66677784375 u_{i_l+4, i_2} \\
&- 128021346000 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} + 96016009500 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} - 42673782000 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} + 8001334125 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4} - 108201499200 u_{i_l+5, i_2} \\
&+ 207746878464 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} - 155810158848 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} + 69248959488 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} - 12984179904 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4} + 140287222000 u_{i_l+6, i_2} \\
&- 269351466240 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} + 202013599680 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} - 89783822080 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} + 16834466640 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4} - 149070840000 u_{i_l+7, i_2} \\
&+ 286216012800 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} - 214662009600 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} + 95405337600 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} - 17888500800 u_{i_l+7, i_2+4} + 132016664250 u_{i_l+8, i_2} \\
&- 253471995360 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} + 190103996520 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} - 84490665120 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} + 15841999710 u_{i_l+8, i_2+4} - 98487460000 u_{i_l+9, i_2} \\
&+ 189095923200 u_{i_l+9, i_2+1} - 141821942400 u_{i_l+9, i_2+2} + 63031974400 u_{i_l+9, i_2+3} - 11818495200 u_{i_l+9, i_2+4} + 62274953400 u_{i_l+10, i_2} \\
&- 119567910528 u_{i_l+10, i_2+1} + 89675932896 u_{i_l+10, i_2+2} - 39855970176 u_{i_l+10, i_2+3} + 7472994408 u_{i_l+10, i_2+4} - 33451596000 u_{i_l+11, i_2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 64227064320 u_{i_l+11, i_2+1} - 48170298240 u_{i_l+11, i_2+2} + 21409021440 u_{i_l+11, i_2+3} - 4014191520 u_{i_l+11, i_2+4} + 15244454750 u_{i_l+12, i_2} \\
& - 29269353120 u_{i_l+12, i_2+1} + 21952014840 u_{i_l+12, i_2+2} - 9756451040 u_{i_l+12, i_2+3} + 1829334570 u_{i_l+12, i_2+4} - 5863656000 u_{i_l+13, i_2} \\
& + 11258219520 u_{i_l+13, i_2+1} - 8443664640 u_{i_l+13, i_2+2} + 3752739840 u_{i_l+13, i_2+3} - 703638720 u_{i_l+13, i_2+4} + 1885446000 u_{i_l+14, i_2} \\
& - 3620056320 u_{i_l+14, i_2+1} + 2715042240 u_{i_l+14, i_2+2} - 1206685440 u_{i_l+14, i_2+3} + 226253520 u_{i_l+14, i_2+4} - 499038400 u_{i_l+15, i_2} + 958153728 u_{i_l+15, i_2+1} \\
& - 718615296 u_{i_l+15, i_2+2} + 319384576 u_{i_l+15, i_2+3} - 59884608 u_{i_l+15, i_2+4} + 106153125 u_{i_l+16, i_2} - 203814000 u_{i_l+16, i_2+1} + 152860500 u_{i_l+16, i_2+2} \\
& - 67938000 u_{i_l+16, i_2+3} + 12738375 u_{i_l+16, i_2+4} - 17478000 u_{i_l+17, i_2} + 33557760 u_{i_l+17, i_2+1} - 25168320 u_{i_l+17, i_2+2} + 11185920 u_{i_l+17, i_2+3} \\
& - 2097360 u_{i_l+17, i_2+4} + 2092500 u_{i_l+18, i_2} - 4017600 u_{i_l+18, i_2+1} + 3013200 u_{i_l+18, i_2+2} - 1339200 u_{i_l+18, i_2+3} + 251100 u_{i_l+18, i_2+4} - 162000 u_{i_l+19, i_2} \\
& + 311040 u_{i_l+19, i_2+1} - 233280 u_{i_l+19, i_2+2} + 103680 u_{i_l+19, i_2+3} - 19440 u_{i_l+19, i_2+4} + 6075 u_{i_l+20, i_2} - 11664 u_{i_l+20, i_2+1} + 8748 u_{i_l+20, i_2+2} \\
& - 3888 u_{i_l+20, i_2+3} + 729 u_{i_l+20, i_2+4} \Big), O(\Delta x l^4 \Delta x_2^4), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.2668057110946897620 \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2574031267177160839 \times 10^{-22}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.2574031267177160839 \times 10^{-22}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2573937467747154848 \times 10^{-34}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.2573937467747154848 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2573937373947950847 \times 10^{-46}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.2573937373947950847 \times 10^{-46}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2573937373854151643 \times 10^{-58}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.2573937373854151643 \times 10^{-58}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2573937373854057844 \times 10^{-70}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x l^5 \partial x_2} u(xl, x_2) &= \frac{1}{2985984 \Delta x l^5 \Delta x_2} (729 u_{i_l-20, i_2-4} - 3888 u_{i_l-20, i_2-3} + 8748 u_{i_l-20, i_2-2} - 11664 u_{i_l-20, i_2-1} + 6075 u_{i_l-20, i_2} - 19440 u_{i_l-19, i_2-4} \\
& + 103680 u_{i_l-19, i_2-3} - 233280 u_{i_l-19, i_2-2} + 311040 u_{i_l-19, i_2-1} - 162000 u_{i_l-19, i_2} + 251100 u_{i_l-18, i_2-4} - 1339200 u_{i_l-18, i_2-3} + 3013200 u_{i_l-18, i_2-2} \\
& - 4017600 u_{i_l-18, i_2-1} + 2092500 u_{i_l-18, i_2} - 2097360 u_{i_l-17, i_2-4} + 11185920 u_{i_l-17, i_2-3} - 25168320 u_{i_l-17, i_2-2} + 33557760 u_{i_l-17, i_2-1} \\
& - 17478000 u_{i_l-17, i_2} + 12738375 u_{i_l-16, i_2-4} - 67938000 u_{i_l-16, i_2-3} + 152860500 u_{i_l-16, i_2-2} - 203814000 u_{i_l-16, i_2-1} + 106153125 u_{i_l-16, i_2} \\
& - 59884608 u_{i_l-15, i_2-4} + 319384576 u_{i_l-15, i_2-3} - 718615296 u_{i_l-15, i_2-2} + 958153728 u_{i_l-15, i_2-1} - 499038400 u_{i_l-15, i_2} + 226253520 u_{i_l-14, i_2-4} \\
& - 1206685440 u_{i_l-14, i_2-3} + 2715042240 u_{i_l-14, i_2-2} - 3620056320 u_{i_l-14, i_2-1} + 1885446000 u_{i_l-14, i_2} - 703638720 u_{i_l-13, i_2-4} \\
& + 3752739840 u_{i_l-13, i_2-3} - 8443664640 u_{i_l-13, i_2-2} + 11258219520 u_{i_l-13, i_2-1} - 5863656000 u_{i_l-13, i_2} + 1829334570 u_{i_l-12, i_2-4} \\
& - 9756451040 u_{i_l-12, i_2-3} + 21952014840 u_{i_l-12, i_2-2} - 29269353120 u_{i_l-12, i_2-1} + 15244454750 u_{i_l-12, i_2} - 4014191520 u_{i_l-11, i_2-4} \\
& + 21409021440 u_{i_l-11, i_2-3} - 48170298240 u_{i_l-11, i_2-2} + 64227064320 u_{i_l-11, i_2-1} - 33451596000 u_{i_l-11, i_2} + 7472994408 u_{i_l-10, i_2-4} \\
& - 39855970176 u_{i_l-10, i_2-3} + 89675932896 u_{i_l-10, i_2-2} - 119567910528 u_{i_l-10, i_2-1} + 62274953400 u_{i_l-10, i_2} - 11818495200 u_{i_l-9, i_2-4} \\
& + 63031974400 u_{i_l-9, i_2-3} - 141821942400 u_{i_l-9, i_2-2} + 189095923200 u_{i_l-9, i_2-1} - 98487460000 u_{i_l-9, i_2} + 15841999710 u_{i_l-8, i_2-4}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 84490665120 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 190103996520 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 253471995360 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 132016664250 u_{i_l-8, i_2} - 17888500800 u_{i_l-7, i_2-4} \\
& + 95405337600 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 214662009600 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 286216012800 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 149070840000 u_{i_l-7, i_2} + 16834466640 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4} \\
& - 89783822080 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 202013599680 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 269351466240 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 140287222000 u_{i_l-6, i_2} - 12984179904 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4} \\
& + 69248959488 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} - 155810158848 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 207746878464 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 108201499200 u_{i_l-5, i_2} + 8001334125 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} \\
& - 42673782000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 96016009500 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 128021346000 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 66677784375 u_{i_l-4, i_2} - 3787350000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} \\
& + 20199200000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 45448200000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 60597600000 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 31561250000 u_{i_l-3, i_2} + 1290937500 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} \\
& - 6885000000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 15491250000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 20655000000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 10757812500 u_{i_l-2, i_2} - 281250000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} \\
& + 1500000000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 3375000000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 4500000000 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 2343750000 u_{i_l-1, i_2} + 29296875 u_{i_l, i_2-4} - 156250000 u_{i_l, i_2-3} \\
& + 351562500 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 468750000 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 244140625 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^4), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.2480270099137036932 \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2573843480983416318 \times 10^{-22}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.2573843480983416318 \times 10^{-22}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2573937279960961105 \times 10^{-34}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.2573937279960961105 \times 10^{-34}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2573937373760164653 \times 10^{-46}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.2573937373760164653 \times 10^{-46}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2573937373853963857 \times 10^{-58}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 2.2573937373853963857 \times 10^{-58}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2573937373854057656 \times 10^{-70}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^5 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{2985984 \Delta x I^5 \Delta x^2} (u_{i_l-10, i_2-2} - 8 u_{i_l-10, i_2-1} + 8 u_{i_l-10, i_2+1} - u_{i_l-10, i_2+2} - 40 u_{i_l-9, i_2-2} + 320 u_{i_l-9, i_2-1} - 320 u_{i_l-9, i_2+1} \\
& + 40 u_{i_l-9, i_2+2} + 640 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 5120 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 5120 u_{i_l-8, i_2+1} - 640 u_{i_l-8, i_2+2} - 5080 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} + 40640 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 40640 u_{i_l-7, i_2+1} \\
& + 5080 u_{i_l-7, i_2+2} + 19195 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 153560 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 153560 u_{i_l-6, i_2+1} - 19195 u_{i_l-6, i_2+2} - 17248 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 137984 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} \\
& - 137984 u_{i_l-5, i_2+1} + 17248 u_{i_l-5, i_2+2} - 83200 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} + 665600 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} - 665600 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1} + 83200 u_{i_l-4, i_2+2} + 158560 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} \\
& - 1268480 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} + 1268480 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1} - 158560 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2} + 106250 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 850000 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 850000 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1} - 106250 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2} \\
& - 353520 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 2828160 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 2828160 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1} + 353520 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2} + 353520 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2} - 2828160 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1} + 2828160 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} \\
& - 353520 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} - 106250 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2} + 850000 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1} - 850000 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 106250 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 158560 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2} + 1268480 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} \\
& - 1268480 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} + 158560 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 83200 u_{i_l+4, i_2-2} - 665600 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1} + 665600 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} - 83200 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} + 17248 u_{i_l+5, i_2-2} \\
& - 137984 u_{i_l+5, i_2-1} + 137984 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} - 17248 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} - 19195 u_{i_l+6, i_2-2} + 153560 u_{i_l+6, i_2-1} - 153560 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} + 19195 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} \\
& + 5080 u_{i_l+7, i_2-2} - 40640 u_{i_l+7, i_2-1} + 40640 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} - 5080 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} - 640 u_{i_l+8, i_2-2} + 5120 u_{i_l+8, i_2-1} - 5120 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} + 640 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} \\
& + 40 u_{i_l+9, i_2-2} - 320 u_{i_l+9, i_2-1} + 320 u_{i_l+9, i_2+1} - 40 u_{i_l+9, i_2+2} - u_{i_l+10, i_2-2} + 8 u_{i_l+10, i_2-1} - 8 u_{i_l+10, i_2+1} + u_{i_l+10, i_2+2}), O(\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^4),
\end{aligned}$$

Centered

Error order:, 4, Error:, $3.7623257960318576052 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $3.7623228956452433536 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 4, Error:, $3.7623228956452433536 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $3.7623228956423429613 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 4, Error:, $3.7623228956423429613 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $3.7623228956423429584 \times 10^{-47}$
Error order:, 4, Error:, $3.7623228956423429584 \times 10^{-47}$, New Error:, $3.7623228956423429584 \times 10^{-59}$
Error order:, 4, Error:, $3.7623228956423429584 \times 10^{-59}$, New Error:, $3.7623228956423429584 \times 10^{-71}$

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=4, x2=2 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^2} (u_{i_1, i_2} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 8 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 6 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 12 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 6 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 4 u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 8 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 4 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + u_{i_1+4, i_2} - 2 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} + u_{i_1+4, i_2+2}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.049580392356263064364, New Error:, 0.000049397659522313143228
Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000049397659522313143228, New Error:, $4.9397477261047404161 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.9397477261047404161 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $4.9397477078786609039 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.9397477078786609039 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $4.9397477078604348244 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.9397477078604348244 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $4.9397477078604165983 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^2} (u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 2 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + u_{i_1-4, i_2} - 4 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 8 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 4 u_{i_1-3, i_2} + 6 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 12 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 6 u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 4 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 8 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 4 u_{i_1-1, i_2} + u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + u_{i_1, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.049215503979607418844, New Error:, 0.000049397294635837363856
Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000049397294635837363856, New Error:, $4.9397476896160928383 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.9397476896160928383 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $4.9397477078421722563 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.9397477078421722563 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $4.9397477078603983358 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.9397477078603983358 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $4.9397477078604165618 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^2} (729 u_{i_1, i_2} - 1944 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 1782 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 648 u_{i_1, i_2+3} + 81 u_{i_1, i_2+4} - 3888 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 10368 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 9504 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} + 3456 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} - 432 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} + 8748 u_{i_l+2, i_2} - 23328 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 21384 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 7776 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} + 972 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} \\
& - 10800 u_{i_l+3, i_2} + 28800 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - 26400 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 9600 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} - 1200 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} + 7974 u_{i_l+4, i_2} - 21264 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} + 19492 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} \\
& - 7088 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} + 886 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4} - 3600 u_{i_l+5, i_2} + 9600 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} - 8800 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} + 3200 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} - 400 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4} + 972 u_{i_l+6, i_2} \\
& - 2592 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} + 2376 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} - 864 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} + 108 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4} - 144 u_{i_l+7, i_2} + 384 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} - 352 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} + 128 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} \\
& - 16 u_{i_l+7, i_2+4} + 9 u_{i_l+8, i_2} - 24 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} + 22 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} - 8 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} + u_{i_l+8, i_2+4}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000079917817414770321550, New Error:, 7.9767250147955966312 $\times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9767250147955966312 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, 7.9767099402324107477 $\times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9767099402324107477 $\times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, 7.9767099251578298420 $\times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9767099251578298420 $\times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, 7.9767099251427552611 $\times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9767099251427552611 $\times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, 7.9767099251427401865 $\times 10^{-35}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{64 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} (u_{i_l-8, i_2-4} - 8 u_{i_l-8, i_2-3} + 22 u_{i_l-8, i_2-2} - 24 u_{i_l-8, i_2-1} + 9 u_{i_l-8, i_2} - 16 u_{i_l-7, i_2-4} + 128 u_{i_l-7, i_2-3} - 352 u_{i_l-7, i_2-2} \\
& + 384 u_{i_l-7, i_2-1} - 144 u_{i_l-7, i_2} + 108 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4} - 864 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} + 2376 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} - 2592 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} + 972 u_{i_l-6, i_2} - 400 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4} + 3200 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} \\
& - 8800 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} + 9600 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} - 3600 u_{i_l-5, i_2} + 886 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} - 7088 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} + 19492 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 21264 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} + 7974 u_{i_l-4, i_2} \\
& - 1200 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 9600 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 26400 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} + 28800 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} - 10800 u_{i_l-3, i_2} + 972 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} - 7776 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 21384 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} \\
& - 23328 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 8748 u_{i_l-2, i_2} - 432 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} + 3456 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 9504 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 10368 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 3888 u_{i_l-1, i_2} + 81 u_{i_l, i_2-4} - 648 u_{i_l, i_2-3} \\
& + 1782 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 1944 u_{i_l, i_2-1} + 729 u_{i_l, i_2}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000079616026335160180815, New Error:, 7.9766948354544087913 $\times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9766948354544087913 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, 7.9767099100530695596 $\times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9767099100530695596 $\times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, 7.9767099251276505008 $\times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9767099251276505008 $\times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, 7.9767099251427250818 $\times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9767099251427250818 $\times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, 7.9767099251427401563 $\times 10^{-35}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{64 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} (u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} - 2 u_{i_l-4, i_2} + u_{i_l-4, i_2+2} - 4 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} + 8 u_{i_l-2, i_2} - 4 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2} + 6 u_{i_l, i_2-2} - 12 u_{i_l, i_2} + 6 u_{i_l, i_2+2} \\
& - 4 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2} + 8 u_{i_l+2, i_2} - 4 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} + u_{i_l+4, i_2-2} - 2 u_{i_l+4, i_2} + u_{i_l+4, i_2+2}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000039883653274003454056, New Error:, 3.9883549625817348981 $\times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.9883549625817348981 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.9883549625713700961 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.9883549625713700961 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.9883549625713700857 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.9883549625713700857 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $3.9883549625713700857 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.9883549625713700857 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $3.9883549625713700857 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = & \frac{1}{46656 \Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^2} (1771561 u_{i_1, i_2} - 5797836 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} + 7642602 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 5387888 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} + 2240073 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} - 527076 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} \\
& + 58564 u_{i_1+6, i_2+6} - 11595672 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 37949472 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 50024304 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 35266176 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} - 14662296 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} + 3449952 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} \\
& - 383328 u_{i_1+1, i_2+6} + 34259940 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 112123440 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 147799080 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 104195520 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} + 43320420 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} \\
& - 10193040 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} + 1132560 u_{i_1+2, i_2+6} - 60800080 u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 198982080 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 262294560 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + 184912640 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} \\
& - 76879440 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} + 18089280 u_{i_1+3, i_2+5} - 2009920 u_{i_1+3, i_2+6} + 72716886 u_{i_1+4, i_2} - 237982536 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} + 313704252 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} \\
& - 221155488 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} + 91947798 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} - 21634776 u_{i_1+4, i_2+5} + 2403864 u_{i_1+4, i_2+6} - 62203680 u_{i_1+5, i_2} + 203575680 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} \\
& - 268349760 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} + 189181440 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} - 78654240 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} + 18506880 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} - 2056320 u_{i_1+5, i_2+6} + 39280956 u_{i_1+6, i_2} \\
& - 128555856 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} + 169459992 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} - 119466048 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} + 49669308 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} - 11686896 u_{i_1+6, i_2+5} + 1298544 u_{i_1+6, i_2+6} \\
& - 18556560 u_{i_1+7, i_2} + 60730560 u_{i_1+7, i_2+1} - 80053920 u_{i_1+7, i_2+2} + 56436480 u_{i_1+7, i_2+3} - 23464080 u_{i_1+7, i_2+4} + 5520960 u_{i_1+7, i_2+5} \\
& - 613440 u_{i_1+7, i_2+6} + 6543801 u_{i_1+8, i_2} - 21416076 u_{i_1+8, i_2+1} + 28230282 u_{i_1+8, i_2+2} - 19901808 u_{i_1+8, i_2+3} + 8274393 u_{i_1+8, i_2+4} \\
& - 1946916 u_{i_1+8, i_2+5} + 216324 u_{i_1+8, i_2+6} - 1689160 u_{i_1+9, i_2} + 5528160 u_{i_1+9, i_2+1} - 7287120 u_{i_1+9, i_2+2} + 5137280 u_{i_1+9, i_2+3} - 2135880 u_{i_1+9, i_2+4} \\
& + 502560 u_{i_1+9, i_2+5} - 55840 u_{i_1+9, i_2+6} + 304920 u_{i_1+10, i_2} - 997920 u_{i_1+10, i_2+1} + 1315440 u_{i_1+10, i_2+2} - 927360 u_{i_1+10, i_2+3} + 385560 u_{i_1+10, i_2+4} \\
& - 90720 u_{i_1+10, i_2+5} + 10080 u_{i_1+10, i_2+6} - 34848 u_{i_1+11, i_2} + 114048 u_{i_1+11, i_2+1} - 150336 u_{i_1+11, i_2+2} + 105984 u_{i_1+11, i_2+3} - 44064 u_{i_1+11, i_2+4} \\
& + 10368 u_{i_1+11, i_2+5} - 1152 u_{i_1+11, i_2+6} + 1936 u_{i_1+12, i_2} - 6336 u_{i_1+12, i_2+1} + 8352 u_{i_1+12, i_2+2} - 5888 u_{i_1+12, i_2+3} + 2448 u_{i_1+12, i_2+4} - 576 u_{i_1+12, i_2+5} \\
& + 64 u_{i_1+12, i_2+6}), O(\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5137203659969145477 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $1.5089718037704468906 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5089718037704468906 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $1.5089670641480142287 \times 10^{-25}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5089670641480142287 \times 10^{-25}$, *New Error:*, $1.5089670594084007106 \times 10^{-34}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5089670594084007106 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.5089670594036610971 \times 10^{-43}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.5089670594036610971 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $1.5089670594036563575 \times 10^{-52}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2^2} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{46656 \Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^2} (64 u_{i_1-12, i_2-6} - 576 u_{i_1-12, i_2-5} + 2448 u_{i_1-12, i_2-4} - 5888 u_{i_1-12, i_2-3} + 8352 u_{i_1-12, i_2-2} - 6336 u_{i_1-12, i_2-1} + 1936 u_{i_1-12, i_2} - 1152 u_{i_1-11, i_2-6} + 10368 u_{i_1-11, i_2-5} - 44064 u_{i_1-11, i_2-4} + 105984 u_{i_1-11, i_2-3} - 150336 u_{i_1-11, i_2-2} + 114048 u_{i_1-11, i_2-1} - 34848 u_{i_1-11, i_2} + 10080 u_{i_1-10, i_2-6} - 90720 u_{i_1-10, i_2-5} + 385560 u_{i_1-10, i_2-4} - 927360 u_{i_1-10, i_2-3} + 1315440 u_{i_1-10, i_2-2} - 997920 u_{i_1-10, i_2-1} + 304920 u_{i_1-10, i_2} - 55840 u_{i_1-9, i_2-6} + 502560 u_{i_1-9, i_2-5} - 2135880 u_{i_1-9, i_2-4} + 5137280 u_{i_1-9, i_2-3} - 7287120 u_{i_1-9, i_2-2} + 5528160 u_{i_1-9, i_2-1} - 1689160 u_{i_1-9, i_2} + 216324 u_{i_1-8, i_2-6} - 1946916 u_{i_1-8, i_2-5} + 8274393 u_{i_1-8, i_2-4} - 19901808 u_{i_1-8, i_2-3} + 28230282 u_{i_1-8, i_2-2} - 21416076 u_{i_1-8, i_2-1} + 6543801 u_{i_1-8, i_2} - 613440 u_{i_1-7, i_2-6} + 5520960 u_{i_1-7, i_2-5} - 23464080 u_{i_1-7, i_2-4} + 56436480 u_{i_1-7, i_2-3} - 80053920 u_{i_1-7, i_2-2} + 60730560 u_{i_1-7, i_2-1} - 18556560 u_{i_1-7, i_2} + 1298544 u_{i_1-6, i_2-6} - 11686896 u_{i_1-6, i_2-5} + 49669308 u_{i_1-6, i_2-4} - 119466048 u_{i_1-6, i_2-3} + 169459992 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 128555856 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 39280956 u_{i_1-6, i_2} - 2056320 u_{i_1-5, i_2-6} + 18506880 u_{i_1-5, i_2-5} - 78654240 u_{i_1-5, i_2-4} + 189181440 u_{i_1-5, i_2-3} - 268349760 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 203575680 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 62203680 u_{i_1-5, i_2} + 2403864 u_{i_1-4, i_2-6} - 21634776 u_{i_1-4, i_2-5} + 91947798 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4} - 221155488 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3} + 313704252 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 237982536 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 72716886 u_{i_1-4, i_2} - 2009920 u_{i_1-3, i_2-6} + 18089280 u_{i_1-3, i_2-5} - 76879440 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4} + 184912640 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 262294560 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 198982080 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 60800080 u_{i_1-3, i_2} + 1132560 u_{i_1-2, i_2-6} - 10193040 u_{i_1-2, i_2-5} + 43320420 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4} - 104195520 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 147799080 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 112123440 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 34259940 u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 383328 u_{i_1-1, i_2-6} + 3449952 u_{i_1-1, i_2-5} - 14662296 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4} + 35266176 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} - 50024304 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 37949472 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 11595672 u_{i_1-1, i_2} + 58564 u_{i_1, i_2-6} - 527076 u_{i_1, i_2-5} + 2240073 u_{i_1, i_2-4} - 5387888 u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 7642602 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 5797836 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 1771561 u_{i_1, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order: 3, Error: 1.5042315999819826621 $\times 10^{-7}$, New Error: 1.5089623150547128044 $\times 10^{-16}$
 Error order: 3, Error: 1.5089623150547128044 $\times 10^{-16}$, New Error: 1.5089670546592984946 $\times 10^{-25}$
 Error order: 3, Error: 1.5089670546592984946 $\times 10^{-25}$, New Error: 1.5089670593989119948 $\times 10^{-34}$
 Error order: 3, Error: 1.5089670593989119948 $\times 10^{-34}$, New Error: 1.5089670594036516084 $\times 10^{-43}$
 Error order: 3, Error: 1.5089670594036516084 $\times 10^{-43}$, New Error: 1.5089670594036563480 $\times 10^{-52}$

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=4, x2=1, x3=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} (u_{i_1, i_2, i_3} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1} - u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3} + u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3} + 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1} + 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3} - 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 6 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3} - 6 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1} - 6 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3} + 6 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 4 u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3} + 4 u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3+1} + 4 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3}$$

$$- 4 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+1} + u_{il+4, i2, i3} - u_{il+4, i2, i3+1} - u_{il+4, i2+1, i3} + u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+1}), O(\Delta x1 \Delta x2 \Delta x3), \text{ Forward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 0.14926931884570863620, \text{ New Error:}, 0.00014863682481205603140$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 0.00014863682481205603140, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4863619420353735923 \times 10^{-7}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 1.4863619420353735923 \times 10^{-7}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4863619357293072167 \times 10^{-10}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 1.4863619357293072167 \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4863619357230011503 \times 10^{-13}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 1.4863619357230011503 \times 10^{-13}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4863619357229948442 \times 10^{-16}$$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x1^4 \partial x2^2 \partial x3} u(x1, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x1^4 \Delta x2 \Delta x3} (u_{il-4, i2-1, i3-1} - u_{il-4, i2-1, i3} - u_{il-4, i2, i3-1} + u_{il-4, i2, i3} - 4 u_{il-3, i2-1, i3-1} + 4 u_{il-3, i2-1, i3} + 4 u_{il-3, i2, i3-1} - 4 u_{il-3, i2, i3} + 6 u_{il-2, i2-1, i3-1} - 6 u_{il-2, i2-1, i3} - 6 u_{il-2, i2, i3-1} + 6 u_{il-2, i2, i3} - 4 u_{il-1, i2-1, i3-1} + 4 u_{il-1, i2-1, i3} + 4 u_{il-1, i2, i3-1} - 4 u_{il-1, i2, i3} + u_{il, i2-1, i3-1} - u_{il, i2-1, i3} - u_{il, i2, i3-1} + u_{il, i2, i3}), O(\Delta x1 \Delta x2 \Delta x3), \text{ Backward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 0.14800683429439308194, \text{ New Error:}, 0.00014863556233630891459$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 0.00014863556233630891459, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4863619294106161212 \times 10^{-7}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 1.4863619294106161212 \times 10^{-7}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4863619357166824592 \times 10^{-10}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 1.4863619357166824592 \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4863619357229885255 \times 10^{-13}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 1.4863619357229885255 \times 10^{-13}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.4863619357229948316 \times 10^{-16}$$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x1^4 \partial x2^2 \partial x3} u(x1, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x1^4 \Delta x2 \Delta x3} (729 u_{il, i2, i3} - 972 u_{il, i2, i3+1} + 243 u_{il, i2, i3+2} - 972 u_{il, i2+1, i3} + 1296 u_{il, i2+1, i3+1} - 324 u_{il, i2+1, i3+2} + 243 u_{il, i2+2, i3} - 324 u_{il, i2+2, i3+1} + 81 u_{il, i2+2, i3+2} - 3888 u_{il+1, i2, i3} + 5184 u_{il+1, i2, i3+1} - 1296 u_{il+1, i2, i3+2} + 5184 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3} - 6912 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3+1} + 1728 u_{il+1, i2+1, i3+2} - 1296 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3} + 1728 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3+1} - 432 u_{il+1, i2+2, i3+2} + 8748 u_{il+2, i2, i3} - 11664 u_{il+2, i2, i3+1} + 2916 u_{il+2, i2, i3+2} - 11664 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3} + 15552 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3+1} - 3888 u_{il+2, i2+1, i3+2} + 2916 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3} - 3888 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3+1} + 972 u_{il+2, i2+2, i3+2} - 10800 u_{il+3, i2, i3} + 14400 u_{il+3, i2, i3+1} - 3600 u_{il+3, i2, i3+2} + 14400 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3} - 19200 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+1} + 4800 u_{il+3, i2+1, i3+2} - 3600 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3} + 4800 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+1} - 1200 u_{il+3, i2+2, i3+2} + 7974 u_{il+4, i2, i3} - 10632 u_{il+4, i2, i3+1} + 2658 u_{il+4, i2, i3+2} - 10632 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3} + 14176 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+1} - 3544 u_{il+4, i2+1, i3+2} + 2658 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3} - 3544 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+1} + 886 u_{il+4, i2+2, i3+2} - 3600 u_{il+5, i2, i3} + 4800 u_{il+5, i2, i3+1} - 1200 u_{il+5, i2, i3+2} + 4800 u_{il+5, i2+1, i3} - 6400 u_{il+5, i2+1, i3+1} + 1600 u_{il+5, i2+1, i3+2} - 1200 u_{il+5, i2+2, i3} + 1600 u_{il+5, i2+2, i3+1} - 400 u_{il+5, i2+2, i3+2} + 972 u_{il+6, i2, i3} - 1296 u_{il+6, i2, i3+1} + 324 u_{il+6, i2, i3+2} - 1296 u_{il+6, i2+1, i3} + 1728 u_{il+6, i2+1, i3+1} - 432 u_{il+6, i2+1, i3+2} + 324 u_{il+6, i2+2, i3} - 432 u_{il+6, i2+2, i3+1} + 108 u_{il+6, i2+2, i3+2} - 144 u_{il+7, i2, i3} + 192 u_{il+7, i2, i3+1} - 48 u_{il+7, i2, i3+2} + 192 u_{il+7, i2+1, i3} - 256 u_{il+7, i2+1, i3+1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 64 u_{iI+7, i2+1, i3+2} - 48 u_{iI+7, i2+2, i3} + 64 u_{iI+7, i2+2, i3+1} - 16 u_{iI+7, i2+2, i3+2} + 9 u_{iI+8, i2, i3} - 12 u_{iI+8, i2, i3+1} + 3 u_{iI+8, i2, i3+2} - 12 u_{iI+8, i2+1, i3} \\
& + 16 u_{iI+8, i2+1, i3+1} - 4 u_{iI+8, i2+1, i3+2} + 3 u_{iI+8, i2+2, i3} - 4 u_{iI+8, i2+2, i3+1} + u_{iI+8, i2+2, i3+2}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x 2^2 \Delta x 3^2), \text{ Forward} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 0.00030920047474127398142, New Error: , 3.0835478988294571580} \times 10^{-10} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 3.0835478988294571580} \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error: , 3.0835394406850737805} \times 10^{-16} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 3.0835394406850737805} \times 10^{-16}, \text{ New Error: , 3.0835394322269281619} \times 10^{-22} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 3.0835394322269281619} \times 10^{-22}, \text{ New Error: , 3.0835394322184700163} \times 10^{-28} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 3.0835394322184700163} \times 10^{-28}, \text{ New Error: , 3.0835394322184615582} \times 10^{-34}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^4 \partial x 2 \partial x 3} u(xI, x2, x3) &= \frac{1}{64 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x 2 \Delta x 3} (u_{iI-8, i2-2, i3-2} - 4 u_{iI-8, i2-2, i3-1} + 3 u_{iI-8, i2-2, i3} - 4 u_{iI-8, i2-1, i3-2} + 16 u_{iI-8, i2-1, i3-1} - 12 u_{iI-8, i2-1, i3} \\
& + 3 u_{iI-8, i2, i3-2} - 12 u_{iI-8, i2, i3-1} + 9 u_{iI-8, i2, i3} - 16 u_{iI-7, i2-2, i3-2} + 64 u_{iI-7, i2-2, i3-1} - 48 u_{iI-7, i2-2, i3} + 64 u_{iI-7, i2-1, i3-2} - 256 u_{iI-7, i2-1, i3-1} \\
& + 192 u_{iI-7, i2-1, i3} - 48 u_{iI-7, i2, i3-2} + 192 u_{iI-7, i2, i3-1} - 144 u_{iI-7, i2, i3} + 108 u_{iI-6, i2-2, i3-2} - 432 u_{iI-6, i2-2, i3-1} + 324 u_{iI-6, i2-2, i3} \\
& - 432 u_{iI-6, i2-1, i3-2} + 1728 u_{iI-6, i2-1, i3-1} - 1296 u_{iI-6, i2-1, i3} + 324 u_{iI-6, i2, i3-2} - 1296 u_{iI-6, i2, i3-1} + 972 u_{iI-6, i2, i3} - 400 u_{iI-5, i2-2, i3-2} \\
& + 1600 u_{iI-5, i2-2, i3-1} - 1200 u_{iI-5, i2-2, i3} + 1600 u_{iI-5, i2-1, i3-2} - 6400 u_{iI-5, i2-1, i3-1} + 4800 u_{iI-5, i2-1, i3} - 1200 u_{iI-5, i2, i3-2} + 4800 u_{iI-5, i2, i3-1} \\
& - 3600 u_{iI-5, i2, i3} + 886 u_{iI-4, i2-2, i3-2} - 3544 u_{iI-4, i2-2, i3-1} + 2658 u_{iI-4, i2-2, i3} - 3544 u_{iI-4, i2-1, i3-2} + 14176 u_{iI-4, i2-1, i3-1} - 10632 u_{iI-4, i2-1, i3} \\
& + 2658 u_{iI-4, i2, i3-2} - 10632 u_{iI-4, i2, i3-1} + 7974 u_{iI-4, i2, i3} - 1200 u_{iI-3, i2-2, i3-2} + 4800 u_{iI-3, i2-2, i3-1} - 3600 u_{iI-3, i2-2, i3} + 4800 u_{iI-3, i2-1, i3-2} \\
& - 19200 u_{iI-3, i2-1, i3-1} + 14400 u_{iI-3, i2-1, i3} - 3600 u_{iI-3, i2, i3-2} + 14400 u_{iI-3, i2, i3-1} - 10800 u_{iI-3, i2, i3} + 972 u_{iI-2, i2-2, i3-2} - 3888 u_{iI-2, i2-2, i3-1} \\
& + 2916 u_{iI-2, i2-2, i3} - 3888 u_{iI-2, i2-1, i3-2} + 15552 u_{iI-2, i2-1, i3-1} - 11664 u_{iI-2, i2-1, i3} + 2916 u_{iI-2, i2, i3-2} - 11664 u_{iI-2, i2, i3-1} + 8748 u_{iI-2, i2, i3} \\
& - 432 u_{iI-1, i2-2, i3-2} + 1728 u_{iI-1, i2-2, i3-1} - 1296 u_{iI-1, i2-2, i3} + 1728 u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-2} - 6912 u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + 5184 u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} - 1296 u_{iI-1, i2, i3-2} \\
& + 5184 u_{iI-1, i2, i3-1} - 3888 u_{iI-1, i2, i3} + 81 u_{iI, i2-2, i3-2} - 324 u_{iI, i2-2, i3-1} + 243 u_{iI, i2-2, i3} - 324 u_{iI, i2-1, i3-2} + 1296 u_{iI, i2-1, i3-1} - 972 u_{iI, i2-1, i3} \\
& + 243 u_{iI, i2, i3-2} - 972 u_{iI, i2, i3-1} + 729 u_{iI, i2, i3}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x 2^2 \Delta x 3^2), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 0.00030750716440268958509, New Error: , 3.0835309656049932805} \times 10^{-10} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 3.0835309656049932805} \times 10^{-10}, \text{ New Error: , 3.0835394237518493165} \times 10^{-16} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 3.0835394237518493165} \times 10^{-16}, \text{ New Error: , 3.0835394322099949375} \times 10^{-22} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 3.0835394322099949375} \times 10^{-22}, \text{ New Error: , 3.0835394322184530831} \times 10^{-28} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 3.0835394322184530831} \times 10^{-28}, \text{ New Error: , 3.0835394322184615412} \times 10^{-34}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^4 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3^3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3} (u_{i_1-4, i_2-1, i_3-1} - u_{i_1-4, i_2-1, i_3+1} - u_{i_1-4, i_2+1, i_3-1} + u_{i_1-4, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 4 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 4 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3+1} + 4 u_{i_1-2, i_2+1, i_3-1} - 4 u_{i_1-2, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 6 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 6 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3+1} - 6 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3-1} + 6 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 4 u_{i_1+2, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 4 u_{i_1+2, i_2-1, i_3+1} + 4 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3-1} - 4 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} + u_{i_1+4, i_2-1, i_3-1} - u_{i_1+4, i_2-1, i_3+1} - u_{i_1+4, i_2+1, i_3-1} + u_{i_1+4, i_2+1, i_3+1}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.00015417753102118281845, New Error:, 1.5417697161148248653 $\times 10^{-10}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, 1.5417697161148248653 $\times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, 1.5417697161092307804 $\times 10^{-16}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, 1.5417697161092307804 $\times 10^{-16}$, New Error:, 1.5417697161092307748 $\times 10^{-22}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, 1.5417697161092307748 $\times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, 1.5417697161092307748 $\times 10^{-28}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, 1.5417697161092307748 $\times 10^{-28}$, New Error:, 1.5417697161092307748 $\times 10^{-34}$

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=3, x2=3 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^3} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3} (u_{i_1, i_2} - 3 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 3 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - u_{i_1, i_2+3} - 3 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 9 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 9 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 3 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} + 3 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 9 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 9 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 3 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} - u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 3 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 3 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + u_{i_1+3, i_2+3}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.053073788012225459292, New Error:, 0.000052864269169164599921
 Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000052864269169164599921, New Error:, 5.2864060229472018201 $\times 10^{-8}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.2864060229472018201 $\times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, 5.2864060020532903518 $\times 10^{-11}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.2864060020532903518 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, 5.2864060020323964404 $\times 10^{-14}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.2864060020323964404 $\times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, 5.2864060020323755465 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^3} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3} (u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 3 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 3 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - u_{i_1-3, i_2} - 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 9 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 9 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2} + 3 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} - 9 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 9 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 3 u_{i_1-1, i_2} - u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 3 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 3 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + u_{i_1, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.052655488987190290318, New Error:, 0.000052863850872639864879
 Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000052863850872639864879, New Error:, 5.2864059811175493468 $\times 10^{-8}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.2864059811175493468 $\times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, 5.2864060020114606993 $\times 10^{-11}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.2864060020114606993 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, 5.2864060020323546107 $\times 10^{-14}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.2864060020323546107 $\times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, 5.2864060020323755047 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^3} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3} (729 u_{i_1, i_2} - 2916 u_{i_1, i_2+1} + 4617 u_{i_1, i_2+2} - 3672 u_{i_1, i_2+3} + 1539 u_{i_1, i_2+4} - 324 u_{i_1, i_2+5} + 27 u_{i_1, i_2+6} - 2916 u_{i_1+1, i_2} + 11664 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1} - 18468 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2} + 14688 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3} - 6156 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4} + 1296 u_{i_1+1, i_2+5} - 108 u_{i_1+1, i_2+6} + 4617 u_{i_1+2, i_2} - 18468 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1} + 29241 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2} - 23256 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3} + 9747 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4} - 2052 u_{i_1+2, i_2+5} + 171 u_{i_1+2, i_2+6} - 3672 u_{i_1+3, i_2} + 14688 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1} - 23256 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2} + 18496 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3} - 7752 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4} + 1632 u_{i_1+3, i_2+5} - 136 u_{i_1+3, i_2+6} + 1539 u_{i_1+4, i_2} - 6156 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1} + 9747 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2} - 7752 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3} + 3249 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4} - 684 u_{i_1+4, i_2+5} + 57 u_{i_1+4, i_2+6} - 324 u_{i_1+5, i_2} + 1296 u_{i_1+5, i_2+1} - 2052 u_{i_1+5, i_2+2} + 1632 u_{i_1+5, i_2+3} - 684 u_{i_1+5, i_2+4} + 144 u_{i_1+5, i_2+5} - 12 u_{i_1+5, i_2+6} + 27 u_{i_1+6, i_2} - 108 u_{i_1+6, i_2+1} + 171 u_{i_1+6, i_2+2} - 136 u_{i_1+6, i_2+3} + 57 u_{i_1+6, i_2+4} - 12 u_{i_1+6, i_2+5} + u_{i_1+6, i_2+6}),$$

$O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2)$, Forward

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000091560353571816342353, New Error:, 9.1376808200691363206 $\times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, 9.1376808200691363206 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, 9.1376624413314891803 $\times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, 9.1376624413314891803 $\times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, 9.1376624229527274988 $\times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, 9.1376624229527274988 $\times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, 9.1376624229343487371 $\times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, 9.1376624229343487371 $\times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, 9.1376624229343303584 $\times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^3} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3} (u_{i_1-6, i_2-6} - 12 u_{i_1-6, i_2-5} + 57 u_{i_1-6, i_2-4} - 136 u_{i_1-6, i_2-3} + 171 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 108 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 27 u_{i_1-6, i_2} - 12 u_{i_1-5, i_2-6} + 144 u_{i_1-5, i_2-5} - 684 u_{i_1-5, i_2-4} + 1632 u_{i_1-5, i_2-3} - 2052 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 1296 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 324 u_{i_1-5, i_2} + 57 u_{i_1-4, i_2-6} - 684 u_{i_1-4, i_2-5} + 3249 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4} - 7752 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3} + 9747 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2} - 6156 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 1539 u_{i_1-4, i_2} - 136 u_{i_1-3, i_2-6} + 1632 u_{i_1-3, i_2-5} - 7752 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4} + 18496 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 23256 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 14688 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 3672 u_{i_1-3, i_2} + 171 u_{i_1-2, i_2-6} - 2052 u_{i_1-2, i_2-5} + 9747 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4} - 23256 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 29241 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 18468 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 4617 u_{i_1-2, i_2} - 108 u_{i_1-1, i_2-6} + 1296 u_{i_1-1, i_2-5} - 6156 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4} + 14688 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} - 18468 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2} + 11664 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 2916 u_{i_1-1, i_2} + 27 u_{i_1, i_2-6} - 324 u_{i_1, i_2-5} + 1539 u_{i_1, i_2-4} - 3672 u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 4617 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 2916 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 729 u_{i_1, i_2}),$$

$O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2)$, Backward

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000091192413715429698003, New Error:, 9.1376440257514077774 $\times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, 9.1376440257514077774 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, 9.1376624045371714515 $\times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, 9.1376624045371714515 $\times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, 9.1376624229159331811 $\times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, 9.1376624229159331811 $\times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, 9.1376624229343119428 $\times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, 9.1376624229343119428 $\times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, 9.1376624229343303216 $\times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^3} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3} (u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} - 3 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} + 3 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1} - u_{i_l-3, i_2+3} - 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} + 9 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 9 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1} + 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2+3} + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2-3} - 9 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1} + 9 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} - u_{i_l+3, i_2-3} + 3 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} - 3 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} + u_{i_l+3, i_2+3}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000045688448509567106719, New Error: $4.5688312114808046344 \times 10^{-11}$
 Error order: 2, Error: $4.5688312114808046344 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error: $4.5688312114671651836 \times 10^{-17}$
 Error order: 2, Error: $4.5688312114671651836 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error: $4.5688312114671651700 \times 10^{-23}$
 Error order: 2, Error: $4.5688312114671651700 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error: $4.5688312114671651700 \times 10^{-29}$
 Error order: 2, Error: $4.5688312114671651700 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error: $4.5688312114671651700 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^3} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{46656 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3} (1771561 u_{i_l, i_2} - 8696754 u_{i_l, i_2+1} + 18579429 u_{i_l, i_2+2} - 22959750 u_{i_l, i_2+3} + 18363807 u_{i_l, i_2+4} - 9990486 u_{i_l, i_2+5} + 3733455 u_{i_l, i_2+6} - 934362 u_{i_l, i_2+7} + 143748 u_{i_l, i_2+8} - 10648 u_{i_l, i_2+9} - 8696754 u_{i_l+1, i_2} + 42693156 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - 91208106 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} + 112711500 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} - 90149598 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} + 49044204 u_{i_l+1, i_2+5} - 18327870 u_{i_l+1, i_2+6} + 4586868 u_{i_l+1, i_2+7} - 705672 u_{i_l+1, i_2+8} + 52272 u_{i_l+1, i_2+9} + 18579429 u_{i_l+2, i_2} - 91208106 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 194853681 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} - 240792750 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} + 192592323 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} - 104776254 u_{i_l+2, i_2+5} + 39154995 u_{i_l+2, i_2+6} - 9799218 u_{i_l+2, i_2+7} + 1507572 u_{i_l+2, i_2+8} - 111672 u_{i_l+2, i_2+9} - 22959750 u_{i_l+3, i_2} + 112711500 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} - 240792750 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 297562500 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} - 237998250 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} + 129478500 u_{i_l+3, i_2+5} - 48386250 u_{i_l+3, i_2+6} + 12109500 u_{i_l+3, i_2+7} - 1863000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+8} + 138000 u_{i_l+3, i_2+9} + 18363807 u_{i_l+4, i_2} - 90149598 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} + 192592323 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} - 237998250 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} + 190357209 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4} - 103560282 u_{i_l+4, i_2+5} + 38700585 u_{i_l+4, i_2+6} - 9685494 u_{i_l+4, i_2+7} + 1490076 u_{i_l+4, i_2+8} - 110376 u_{i_l+4, i_2+9} - 9990486 u_{i_l+5, i_2} + 49044204 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} - 104776254 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} + 129478500 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} - 103560282 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4} + 56340036 u_{i_l+5, i_2+5} - 21054330 u_{i_l+5, i_2+6} + 5269212 u_{i_l+5, i_2+7} - 810648 u_{i_l+5, i_2+8} + 60048 u_{i_l+5, i_2+9} + 3733455 u_{i_l+6, i_2} - 18327870 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} + 39154995 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} - 48386250 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} + 38700585 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4} - 21054330 u_{i_l+6, i_2+5} + 7868025 u_{i_l+6, i_2+6} - 1969110 u_{i_l+6, i_2+7} + 302940 u_{i_l+6, i_2+8} - 22440 u_{i_l+6, i_2+9} - 934362 u_{i_l+7, i_2} + 4586868 u_{i_l+7, i_2+1} - 9799218 u_{i_l+7, i_2+2} + 12109500 u_{i_l+7, i_2+3} - 9685494 u_{i_l+7, i_2+4} + 5269212 u_{i_l+7, i_2+5} - 1969110 u_{i_l+7, i_2+6} + 492804 u_{i_l+7, i_2+7} - 75816 u_{i_l+7, i_2+8} + 5616 u_{i_l+7, i_2+9} + 143748 u_{i_l+8, i_2} - 705672 u_{i_l+8, i_2+1} + 1507572 u_{i_l+8, i_2+2} - 1863000 u_{i_l+8, i_2+3} + 1490076 u_{i_l+8, i_2+4} - 810648 u_{i_l+8, i_2+5} + 302940 u_{i_l+8, i_2+6} - 75816 u_{i_l+8, i_2+7} + 11664 u_{i_l+8, i_2+8} - 864 u_{i_l+8, i_2+9} - 10648 u_{i_l+9, i_2} + 52272 u_{i_l+9, i_2+1} - 111672 u_{i_l+9, i_2+2} + 138000 u_{i_l+9, i_2+3} - 110376 u_{i_l+9, i_2+4} + 60048 u_{i_l+9, i_2+5} - 22440 u_{i_l+9, i_2+6} + 5616 u_{i_l+9, i_2+7} - 864 u_{i_l+9, i_2+8} + 64 u_{i_l+9, i_2+9}), O(\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.8458278089990818117 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $1.8397219863690900398 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.8397219863690900398 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $1.8397158925436779961 \times 10^{-25}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.8397158925436779961 \times 10^{-25}$, *New Error:*, $1.8397158864498645447 \times 10^{-34}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.8397158864498645447 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.8397158864437707313 \times 10^{-43}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.8397158864437707313 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, $1.8397158864437646375 \times 10^{-52}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^3} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{46656 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3} (64 u_{i_1-9, i_2-9} - 864 u_{i_1-9, i_2-8} + 5616 u_{i_1-9, i_2-7} - 22440 u_{i_1-9, i_2-6} + 60048 u_{i_1-9, i_2-5} - 110376 u_{i_1-9, i_2-4}$$

$$+ 138000 u_{i_1-9, i_2-3} - 111672 u_{i_1-9, i_2-2} + 52272 u_{i_1-9, i_2-1} - 10648 u_{i_1-9, i_2} - 864 u_{i_1-8, i_2-9} + 11664 u_{i_1-8, i_2-8} - 75816 u_{i_1-8, i_2-7}$$

$$+ 302940 u_{i_1-8, i_2-6} - 810648 u_{i_1-8, i_2-5} + 1490076 u_{i_1-8, i_2-4} - 1863000 u_{i_1-8, i_2-3} + 1507572 u_{i_1-8, i_2-2} - 705672 u_{i_1-8, i_2-1} + 143748 u_{i_1-8, i_2}$$

$$+ 5616 u_{i_1-7, i_2-9} - 75816 u_{i_1-7, i_2-8} + 492804 u_{i_1-7, i_2-7} - 1969110 u_{i_1-7, i_2-6} + 5269212 u_{i_1-7, i_2-5} - 9685494 u_{i_1-7, i_2-4} + 12109500 u_{i_1-7, i_2-3}$$

$$- 9799218 u_{i_1-7, i_2-2} + 4586868 u_{i_1-7, i_2-1} - 934362 u_{i_1-7, i_2} - 22440 u_{i_1-6, i_2-9} + 302940 u_{i_1-6, i_2-8} - 1969110 u_{i_1-6, i_2-7} + 7868025 u_{i_1-6, i_2-6}$$

$$- 21054330 u_{i_1-6, i_2-5} + 38700585 u_{i_1-6, i_2-4} - 48386250 u_{i_1-6, i_2-3} + 39154995 u_{i_1-6, i_2-2} - 18327870 u_{i_1-6, i_2-1} + 3733455 u_{i_1-6, i_2}$$

$$+ 60048 u_{i_1-5, i_2-9} - 810648 u_{i_1-5, i_2-8} + 5269212 u_{i_1-5, i_2-7} - 21054330 u_{i_1-5, i_2-6} + 56340036 u_{i_1-5, i_2-5} - 103560282 u_{i_1-5, i_2-4}$$

$$+ 129478500 u_{i_1-5, i_2-3} - 104776254 u_{i_1-5, i_2-2} + 49044204 u_{i_1-5, i_2-1} - 9990486 u_{i_1-5, i_2} - 110376 u_{i_1-4, i_2-9} + 1490076 u_{i_1-4, i_2-8}$$

$$- 9685494 u_{i_1-4, i_2-7} + 38700585 u_{i_1-4, i_2-6} - 103560282 u_{i_1-4, i_2-5} + 190357209 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4} - 237998250 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3} + 192592323 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2}$$

$$- 90149598 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1} + 18363807 u_{i_1-4, i_2} + 138000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-9} - 1863000 u_{i_1-3, i_2-8} + 12109500 u_{i_1-3, i_2-7} - 48386250 u_{i_1-3, i_2-6}$$

$$+ 129478500 u_{i_1-3, i_2-5} - 237998250 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4} + 297562500 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3} - 240792750 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2} + 112711500 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1} - 22959750 u_{i_1-3, i_2}$$

$$- 111672 u_{i_1-2, i_2-9} + 1507572 u_{i_1-2, i_2-8} - 9799218 u_{i_1-2, i_2-7} + 39154995 u_{i_1-2, i_2-6} - 104776254 u_{i_1-2, i_2-5} + 192592323 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4}$$

$$- 240792750 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3} + 194853681 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2} - 91208106 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1} + 18579429 u_{i_1-2, i_2} + 52272 u_{i_1-1, i_2-9} - 705672 u_{i_1-1, i_2-8}$$

$$+ 4586868 u_{i_1-1, i_2-7} - 18327870 u_{i_1-1, i_2-6} + 49044204 u_{i_1-1, i_2-5} - 90149598 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4} + 112711500 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3} - 91208106 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2}$$

$$+ 42693156 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1} - 8696754 u_{i_1-1, i_2} - 10648 u_{i_1, i_2-9} + 143748 u_{i_1, i_2-8} - 934362 u_{i_1, i_2-7} + 3733455 u_{i_1, i_2-6} - 9990486 u_{i_1, i_2-5}$$

$$+ 18363807 u_{i_1, i_2-4} - 22959750 u_{i_1, i_2-3} + 18579429 u_{i_1, i_2-2} - 8696754 u_{i_1, i_2-1} + 1771561 u_{i_1, i_2}), O(\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.8336279093233496199 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $1.8397097865423843693 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.8397097865423843693 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $1.8397158803438512905 \times 10^{-25}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.8397158803438512905 \times 10^{-25}$, *New Error:*, $1.8397158864376647180 \times 10^{-34}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $1.8397158864376647180 \times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, $1.8397158864437585315 \times 10^{-43}$

Error order:, 3, Error:., $1.8397158864437585315 \times 10^{-43}$, New Error:., $1.8397158864437646253 \times 10^{-52}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^3} u(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{2985984 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^3} (u_{i_l-6, i_2-6} - 24 u_{i_l-6, i_2-5} + 192 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4} - 488 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3} - 387 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2} + 1584 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1} - 1584 u_{i_l-6, i_2+1} + 387 u_{i_l-6, i_2+2} + 488 u_{i_l-6, i_2+3} - 192 u_{i_l-6, i_2+4} + 24 u_{i_l-6, i_2+5} - u_{i_l-6, i_2+6} - 24 u_{i_l-5, i_2-6} + 576 u_{i_l-5, i_2-5} - 4608 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4} + 11712 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3} + 9288 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2} - 38016 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1} + 38016 u_{i_l-5, i_2+1} - 9288 u_{i_l-5, i_2+2} - 11712 u_{i_l-5, i_2+3} + 4608 u_{i_l-5, i_2+4} - 576 u_{i_l-5, i_2+5} + 24 u_{i_l-5, i_2+6} + 192 u_{i_l-4, i_2-6} - 4608 u_{i_l-4, i_2-5} + 36864 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4} - 93696 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3} - 74304 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2} + 304128 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1} - 304128 u_{i_l-4, i_2+1} + 74304 u_{i_l-4, i_2+2} + 93696 u_{i_l-4, i_2+3} - 36864 u_{i_l-4, i_2+4} + 4608 u_{i_l-4, i_2+5} - 192 u_{i_l-4, i_2+6} - 488 u_{i_l-3, i_2-6} + 11712 u_{i_l-3, i_2-5} - 93696 u_{i_l-3, i_2-4} + 238144 u_{i_l-3, i_2-3} + 188856 u_{i_l-3, i_2-2} - 772992 u_{i_l-3, i_2-1} + 772992 u_{i_l-3, i_2+1} - 188856 u_{i_l-3, i_2+2} - 238144 u_{i_l-3, i_2+3} + 93696 u_{i_l-3, i_2+4} - 11712 u_{i_l-3, i_2+5} + 488 u_{i_l-3, i_2+6} - 387 u_{i_l-2, i_2-6} + 9288 u_{i_l-2, i_2-5} - 74304 u_{i_l-2, i_2-4} + 188856 u_{i_l-2, i_2-3} + 149769 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2} - 613008 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1} + 613008 u_{i_l-2, i_2+1} - 149769 u_{i_l-2, i_2+2} - 188856 u_{i_l-2, i_2+3} + 74304 u_{i_l-2, i_2+4} - 9288 u_{i_l-2, i_2+5} + 387 u_{i_l-2, i_2+6} + 1584 u_{i_l-1, i_2-6} - 38016 u_{i_l-1, i_2-5} + 304128 u_{i_l-1, i_2-4} - 772992 u_{i_l-1, i_2-3} - 613008 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2} + 2509056 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1} - 2509056 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1} + 613008 u_{i_l-1, i_2+2} + 772992 u_{i_l-1, i_2+3} - 304128 u_{i_l-1, i_2+4} + 38016 u_{i_l-1, i_2+5} - 1584 u_{i_l-1, i_2+6} - 1584 u_{i_l+1, i_2-6} + 38016 u_{i_l+1, i_2-5} - 304128 u_{i_l+1, i_2-4} + 772992 u_{i_l+1, i_2-3} + 613008 u_{i_l+1, i_2-2} - 2509056 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1} + 2509056 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1} - 613008 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2} - 772992 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3} + 304128 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4} - 38016 u_{i_l+1, i_2+5} + 1584 u_{i_l+1, i_2+6} + 387 u_{i_l+2, i_2-6} - 9288 u_{i_l+2, i_2-5} + 74304 u_{i_l+2, i_2-4} - 188856 u_{i_l+2, i_2-3} - 149769 u_{i_l+2, i_2-2} + 613008 u_{i_l+2, i_2-1} - 613008 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1} + 149769 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2} + 188856 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3} - 74304 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4} + 9288 u_{i_l+2, i_2+5} - 387 u_{i_l+2, i_2+6} + 488 u_{i_l+3, i_2-6} - 11712 u_{i_l+3, i_2-5} + 93696 u_{i_l+3, i_2-4} - 238144 u_{i_l+3, i_2-3} - 188856 u_{i_l+3, i_2-2} + 772992 u_{i_l+3, i_2-1} - 772992 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1} + 188856 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2} + 238144 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3} - 93696 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4} + 11712 u_{i_l+3, i_2+5} - 488 u_{i_l+3, i_2+6} - 192 u_{i_l+4, i_2-6} + 4608 u_{i_l+4, i_2-5} - 36864 u_{i_l+4, i_2-4} + 93696 u_{i_l+4, i_2-3} + 74304 u_{i_l+4, i_2-2} - 304128 u_{i_l+4, i_2-1} + 304128 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1} - 74304 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2} - 93696 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3} + 36864 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4} - 4608 u_{i_l+4, i_2+5} + 192 u_{i_l+4, i_2+6} + 24 u_{i_l+5, i_2-6} - 576 u_{i_l+5, i_2-5} + 4608 u_{i_l+5, i_2-4} - 11712 u_{i_l+5, i_2-3} - 9288 u_{i_l+5, i_2-2} + 38016 u_{i_l+5, i_2-1} - 38016 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1} + 9288 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2} + 11712 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3} - 4608 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4} + 576 u_{i_l+5, i_2+5} - 24 u_{i_l+5, i_2+6} - u_{i_l+6, i_2-6} + 24 u_{i_l+6, i_2-5} - 192 u_{i_l+6, i_2-4} + 488 u_{i_l+6, i_2-3} + 387 u_{i_l+6, i_2-2} - 1584 u_{i_l+6, i_2-1} + 1584 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1} - 387 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2} - 488 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3} + 192 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4} - 24 u_{i_l+6, i_2+5} + u_{i_l+6, i_2+6}), $O(\Delta x_1^4 \Delta x_2^4)$, Centered$$

Error order:., 4, Error:., $6.7776880588854362728 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:., $6.7776815031162548828 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:., 4, Error:., $6.7776815031162548828 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:., $6.7776815031096990922 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:., 4, Error:., $6.7776815031096990922 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:., $6.7776815031096990857 \times 10^{-47}$

Error order:., 4, Error:., $6.7776815031096990857 \times 10^{-47}$, New Error:., $6.7776815031096990857 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 4, Error:., 6.7776815031096990857 × 10⁻⁵⁹, New Error:., 6.7776815031096990857 × 10⁻⁷¹

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=3, x2=2, x3=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3} (u_{i_1, i_2, i_3} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3} + 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3} - u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 3 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3} + 3 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1} + 6 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3} - 6 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 3 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3} + 3 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 3 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3} - 3 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1} - 6 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3} + 6 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 3 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3} - 3 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+1} - u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3} + u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3+1} + 2 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3} - 2 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3+1} - u_{i_1+3, i_2+2, i_3} + u_{i_1+3, i_2+2, i_3+1}),$$

$O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3)$, Forward

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.15846400482395278962, New Error:., 0.00015775182709288713126

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.00015775182709288713126, New Error:., 1.5775111716470043118 × 10⁻⁷

Error order:., 1, Error:., 1.5775111716470043118 × 10⁻⁷, New Error:., 1.5775111645477448845 × 10⁻¹⁰

Error order:., 1, Error:., 1.5775111645477448845 × 10⁻¹⁰, New Error:., 1.5775111645406456251 × 10⁻¹³

Error order:., 1, Error:., 1.5775111645406456251 × 10⁻¹³, New Error:., 1.5775111645406385259 × 10⁻¹⁶

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3} (u_{i_1-3, i_2-2, i_3-1} - u_{i_1-3, i_2-2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 2 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3} + u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3-1} - u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3} - 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3} + 6 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 6 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3} - 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1} + 3 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3} + 3 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 3 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3} - 6 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 6 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3} + 3 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1} - 3 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3} - u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3-1} + u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3} + 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3}),$$

$O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3)$, Backward

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.15704272054815305428, New Error:., 0.00015775040581973301361

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.00015775040581973301361, New Error:., 1.5775111574342727707 × 10⁻⁷

Error order:., 1, Error:., 1.5775111574342727707 × 10⁻⁷, New Error:., 1.5775111645335321530 × 10⁻¹⁰

Error order:., 1, Error:., 1.5775111645335321530 × 10⁻¹⁰, New Error:., 1.5775111645406314124 × 10⁻¹³

Error order:., 1, Error:., 1.5775111645406314124 × 10⁻¹³, New Error:., 1.5775111645406385117 × 10⁻¹⁶

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3} (729 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3} - 972 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1} + 243 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+2} - 1944 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3} + 2592 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 648 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 1782 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3} - 2376 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 594 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 648 u_{i_1, i_2+3, i_3} + 864 u_{i_1, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 216 u_{i_1, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 81 u_{i_1, i_2+4, i_3} - 108 u_{i_1, i_2+4, i_3+1})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 27 u_{i_l, i_2+4, i_3+2} - 2916 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3} + 3888 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1} - 972 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+2} + 7776 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3} - 10368 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 2592 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+2} \\
& - 7128 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3} + 9504 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 2376 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 2592 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3} - 3456 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 864 u_{i_l+1, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 324 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4, i_3} \\
& + 432 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4, i_3+1} - 108 u_{i_l+1, i_2+4, i_3+2} + 4617 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3} - 6156 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1} + 1539 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+2} - 12312 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3} + 16416 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} \\
& - 4104 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 11286 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3} - 15048 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 3762 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 4104 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3} + 5472 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3+1} \\
& - 1368 u_{i_l+2, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 513 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4, i_3} - 684 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4, i_3+1} + 171 u_{i_l+2, i_2+4, i_3+2} - 3672 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3} + 4896 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+1} - 1224 u_{i_l+3, i_2, i_3+2} \\
& + 9792 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3} - 13056 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 3264 u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 8976 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3} + 11968 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 2992 u_{i_l+3, i_2+2, i_3+2} \\
& + 3264 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3} - 4352 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 1088 u_{i_l+3, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 408 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4, i_3} + 544 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4, i_3+1} - 136 u_{i_l+3, i_2+4, i_3+2} + 1539 u_{i_l+4, i_2, i_3} \\
& - 2052 u_{i_l+4, i_2, i_3+1} + 513 u_{i_l+4, i_2, i_3+2} - 4104 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3} + 5472 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 1368 u_{i_l+4, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 3762 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3} - 5016 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3+1} \\
& + 1254 u_{i_l+4, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 1368 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3, i_3} + 1824 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 456 u_{i_l+4, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 171 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4, i_3} - 228 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4, i_3+1} + 57 u_{i_l+4, i_2+4, i_3+2} \\
& - 324 u_{i_l+5, i_2, i_3} + 432 u_{i_l+5, i_2, i_3+1} - 108 u_{i_l+5, i_2, i_3+2} + 864 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1, i_3} - 1152 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 288 u_{i_l+5, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 792 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2, i_3} \\
& + 1056 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 264 u_{i_l+5, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 288 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3, i_3} - 384 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 96 u_{i_l+5, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 36 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4, i_3} + 48 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4, i_3+1} \\
& - 12 u_{i_l+5, i_2+4, i_3+2} + 27 u_{i_l+6, i_2, i_3} - 36 u_{i_l+6, i_2, i_3+1} + 9 u_{i_l+6, i_2, i_3+2} - 72 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1, i_3} + 96 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 24 u_{i_l+6, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 66 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2, i_3} \\
& - 88 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 22 u_{i_l+6, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 24 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3, i_3} + 32 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 8 u_{i_l+6, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 3 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4, i_3} - 4 u_{i_l+6, i_2+4, i_3+1} \\
& + u_{i_l+6, i_2+4, i_3+2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.00033977638917572364834, New Error: $3.3884442847979285722 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order: 2, Error: $3.3884442847979285722 \times 10^{-10}$, New Error: $3.3884349605820572891 \times 10^{-16}$

Error order: 2, Error: $3.3884349605820572891 \times 10^{-16}$, New Error: $3.3884349512578368946 \times 10^{-22}$

Error order: 2, Error: $3.3884349512578368946 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error: $3.3884349512485126742 \times 10^{-28}$

Error order: 2, Error: $3.3884349512485126742 \times 10^{-28}$, New Error: $3.3884349512485033500 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) &= \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3} (u_{i_l-6, i_2-4, i_3-2} - 4 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4, i_3-1} + 3 u_{i_l-6, i_2-4, i_3} - 8 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3, i_3-2} + 32 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3, i_3-1} \\
& - 24 u_{i_l-6, i_2-3, i_3} + 22 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 88 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 66 u_{i_l-6, i_2-2, i_3} - 24 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 96 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 72 u_{i_l-6, i_2-1, i_3} \\
& + 9 u_{i_l-6, i_2, i_3-2} - 36 u_{i_l-6, i_2, i_3-1} + 27 u_{i_l-6, i_2, i_3} - 12 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4, i_3-2} + 48 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4, i_3-1} - 36 u_{i_l-5, i_2-4, i_3} + 96 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3, i_3-2} - 384 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3, i_3-1} \\
& + 288 u_{i_l-5, i_2-3, i_3} - 264 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 1056 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 792 u_{i_l-5, i_2-2, i_3} + 288 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 1152 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 864 u_{i_l-5, i_2-1, i_3} \\
& - 108 u_{i_l-5, i_2, i_3-2} + 432 u_{i_l-5, i_2, i_3-1} - 324 u_{i_l-5, i_2, i_3} + 57 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4, i_3-2} - 228 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4, i_3-1} + 171 u_{i_l-4, i_2-4, i_3} - 456 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3, i_3-2} \\
& + 1824 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 1368 u_{i_l-4, i_2-3, i_3} + 1254 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 5016 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 3762 u_{i_l-4, i_2-2, i_3} - 1368 u_{i_l-4, i_2-1, i_3-2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 5472 u_{i1-4, i2-1, i3-1} - 4104 u_{i1-4, i2-1, i3} + 513 u_{i1-4, i2, i3-2} - 2052 u_{i1-4, i2, i3-1} + 1539 u_{i1-4, i2, i3} - 136 u_{i1-3, i2-4, i3-2} + 544 u_{i1-3, i2-4, i3-1} \\
& - 408 u_{i1-3, i2-4, i3} + 1088 u_{i1-3, i2-3, i3-2} - 4352 u_{i1-3, i2-3, i3-1} + 3264 u_{i1-3, i2-3, i3} - 2992 u_{i1-3, i2-2, i3-2} + 11968 u_{i1-3, i2-2, i3-1} \\
& - 8976 u_{i1-3, i2-2, i3} + 3264 u_{i1-3, i2-1, i3-2} - 13056 u_{i1-3, i2-1, i3-1} + 9792 u_{i1-3, i2-1, i3} - 1224 u_{i1-3, i2, i3-2} + 4896 u_{i1-3, i2, i3-1} - 3672 u_{i1-3, i2, i3} \\
& + 171 u_{i1-2, i2-4, i3-2} - 684 u_{i1-2, i2-4, i3-1} + 513 u_{i1-2, i2-4, i3} - 1368 u_{i1-2, i2-3, i3-2} + 5472 u_{i1-2, i2-3, i3-1} - 4104 u_{i1-2, i2-3, i3} + 3762 u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3-2} \\
& - 15048 u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3-1} + 11286 u_{i1-2, i2-2, i3} - 4104 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3-2} + 16416 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3-1} - 12312 u_{i1-2, i2-1, i3} + 1539 u_{i1-2, i2, i3-2} \\
& - 6156 u_{i1-2, i2, i3-1} + 4617 u_{i1-2, i2, i3} - 108 u_{i1-1, i2-4, i3-2} + 432 u_{i1-1, i2-4, i3-1} - 324 u_{i1-1, i2-4, i3} + 864 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3-2} - 3456 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3-1} \\
& + 2592 u_{i1-1, i2-3, i3} - 2376 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-2} + 9504 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-1} - 7128 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3} + 2592 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-2} - 10368 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1} \\
& + 7776 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3} - 972 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-2} + 3888 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-1} - 2916 u_{i1-1, i2, i3} + 27 u_{i1, i2-4, i3-2} - 108 u_{i1, i2-4, i3-1} + 81 u_{i1, i2-4, i3} - 216 u_{i1, i2-3, i3-2} \\
& + 864 u_{i1, i2-3, i3-1} - 648 u_{i1, i2-3, i3} + 594 u_{i1, i2-2, i3-2} - 2376 u_{i1, i2-2, i3-1} + 1782 u_{i1, i2-2, i3} - 648 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-2} + 2592 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-1} - 1944 u_{i1, i2-1, i3} \\
& + 243 u_{i1, i2, i3-2} - 972 u_{i1, i2, i3-1} + 729 u_{i1, i2, i3}), O(\Delta x1^2 \Delta x2^2 \Delta x3^2), \textit{Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.00033790969549832378801, New Error: 3.3884256176900228114 × 10⁻¹⁰

Error order: 2, Error: 3.3884256176900228114 × 10⁻¹⁰, New Error: 3.3884349419149493832 × 10⁻¹⁶

Error order: 2, Error: 3.3884349419149493832 × 10⁻¹⁶, New Error: 3.3884349512391697867 × 10⁻²²

Error order: 2, Error: 3.3884349512391697867 × 10⁻²², New Error: 3.3884349512484940071 × 10⁻²⁸

Error order: 2, Error: 3.3884349512484940071 × 10⁻²⁸, New Error: 3.3884349512485033314 × 10⁻³⁴

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\delta^6}{\Delta x1^3 \Delta x2^2 \Delta x3} u(x1, x2, x3) &= \frac{1}{64 \Delta x1^3 \Delta x2^2 \Delta x3} (u_{i1-3, i2-2, i3-1} - u_{i1-3, i2-2, i3+1} - 2 u_{i1-3, i2, i3-1} + 2 u_{i1-3, i2, i3+1} + u_{i1-3, i2+2, i3-1} - u_{i1-3, i2+2, i3+1} \\
& - 3 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3-1} + 3 u_{i1-1, i2-2, i3+1} + 6 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-1} - 6 u_{i1-1, i2, i3+1} - 3 u_{i1-1, i2+2, i3-1} + 3 u_{i1-1, i2+2, i3+1} + 3 u_{i1+1, i2-2, i3-1} - 3 u_{i1+1, i2-2, i3+1} \\
& - 6 u_{i1+1, i2, i3-1} + 6 u_{i1+1, i2, i3+1} + 3 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3-1} - 3 u_{i1+1, i2+2, i3+1} - u_{i1+3, i2-2, i3-1} + u_{i1+3, i2-2, i3+1} + 2 u_{i1+3, i2, i3-1} - 2 u_{i1+3, i2, i3+1} \\
& - u_{i1+3, i2+2, i3-1} + u_{i1+3, i2+2, i3+1}), O(\Delta x1^2 \Delta x2^2 \Delta x3^2), \textit{Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.00016942243352825182220, New Error: 1.6942174756311113118 × 10⁻¹⁰

Error order: 2, Error: 1.6942174756311113118 × 10⁻¹⁰, New Error: 1.6942174756242516772 × 10⁻¹⁶

Error order: 2, Error: 1.6942174756242516772 × 10⁻¹⁶, New Error: 1.6942174756242516703 × 10⁻²²

Error order: 2, Error: 1.6942174756242516703 × 10⁻²², New Error: 1.6942174756242516703 × 10⁻²⁸

Error order: 2, Error: 1.6942174756242516703 × 10⁻²⁸, New Error: 1.6942174756242516703 × 10⁻³⁴

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=3, x2=1, x3=1, x4=1 ---"

$$\frac{\delta^6}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} \\ + u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 3u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4} + 3u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} + 3u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} - 3u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + 3u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} - 3u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} \\ - 3u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} + 3u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} + 3u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4} - 3u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} - 3u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} + 3u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 3u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} \\ + 3u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} + 3u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} - 3u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} - u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} + u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} - u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} \\ - u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} - u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} + u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.50884400346829592599, New Error:, 0.00050600152545111624658

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.00050600152545111624658, New Error:, 5.0599869419220850514 × 10⁻⁷

Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.0599869419220850514 × 10⁻⁷, New Error:, 5.0599869136096078170 × 10⁻¹⁰

Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.0599869136096078170 × 10⁻¹⁰, New Error:, 5.0599869135812953399 × 10⁻¹³

Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.0599869135812953399 × 10⁻¹³, New Error:, 5.0599869135812670274 × 10⁻¹⁶

$$\frac{\delta^6}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} - u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} + u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} \\ + u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} + u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} - u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3, i_4} - 3u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 3u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} + 3u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} - 3u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} \\ + 3u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 3u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} - 3u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + 3u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4} + 3u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 3u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} - 3u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} \\ + 3u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} - 3u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 3u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} + 3u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} - 3u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} \\ - u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.50317577037463717303, New Error:, 0.00050599585728752810041

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.00050599585728752810041, New Error:, 5.0599868852404491707 × 10⁻⁷

Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.0599868852404491707 × 10⁻⁷, New Error:, 5.0599869135529261812 × 10⁻¹⁰

Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.0599869135529261812 × 10⁻¹⁰, New Error:, 5.0599869135812386583 × 10⁻¹³

Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.0599869135812386583 × 10⁻¹³, New Error:, 5.0599869135812669708 × 10⁻¹⁶

$$\frac{\delta^6}{\Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^3 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1} - u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1} + u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1} \\ - u_{i_1-3, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + u_{i_1-3, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1} + u_{i_1-3, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1-3, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 3u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 3u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1} - 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1} + 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1} - 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1} + 3 u_{i_l-1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} \\
& + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1} + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1} \\
& + 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1} - 3 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} - u_{i_l+3, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + u_{i_l+3, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1} + u_{i_l+3, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1} - u_{i_l+3, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1} \\
& + u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1} - u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1} + u_{i_l+3, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1}), O(\Delta x l^2 \Delta x 2^2 \Delta x 3^2 \Delta x 4^2), \textit{Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.00075816861634971878610, *New Error:*, $7.5816350623220664121 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.5816350623220664121 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $7.5816350622709654395 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.5816350622709654395 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $7.5816350622709653884 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.5816350622709653884 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $7.5816350622709653884 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $7.5816350622709653884 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $7.5816350622709653884 \times 10^{-34}$

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=2, x2=2, x3=2 ---"

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x l^2 \partial x 2^2 \partial x 3^2} u(x l, x 2, x 3) &= \frac{1}{\Delta x l^2 \Delta x 2^2 \Delta x 3^2} (u_{i_l, i_2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+2} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3} + 4 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+2} + u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3} \\
&- 2 u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+1} + u_{i_l, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3} + 4 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+2} + 4 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3} - 8 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 4 u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3} \\
&+ 4 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 2 u_{i_l+1, i_2+2, i_3+2} + u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+1} + u_{i_l+2, i_2, i_3+2} - 2 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3} + 4 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 2 u_{i_l+2, i_2+1, i_3+2} \\
&+ u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+1} + u_{i_l+2, i_2+2, i_3+2}), O(\Delta x l \Delta x 2 \Delta x 3), \textit{Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.18591457175244473386, *New Error:*, 0.00018493245019564074836
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00018493245019564074836, *New Error:*, $1.8493147172068649414 \times 10^{-7}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8493147172068649414 \times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, $1.8493147074221517588 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8493147074221517588 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $1.8493147074123670456 \times 10^{-13}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8493147074123670456 \times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, $1.8493147074123572609 \times 10^{-16}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x l^2 \partial x 2^2 \partial x 3^2} u(x l, x 2, x 3) &= \frac{1}{\Delta x l^2 \Delta x 2^2 \Delta x 3^2} (u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 2 u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l-2, i_2-2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 4 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 2 u_{i_l-2, i_2-1, i_3} \\
&+ u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-2} - 2 u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l-2, i_2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 4 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2-2, i_3} + 4 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 8 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} \\
&+ 4 u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3} - 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-2} + 4 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1} - 2 u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3} + u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l, i_2-2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 4 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1} \\
&- 2 u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-2} - 2 u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3}), O(\Delta x l \Delta x 2 \Delta x 3), \textit{Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:., 0.18395564903491281227, New Error:., 0.00018493049129410995554

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.00018493049129410995554, New Error:., $1.8493146976178496337 \times 10^{-7}$

Error order:., 1, Error:., $1.8493146976178496337 \times 10^{-7}$, New Error:., $1.8493147074025627435 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order:., 1, Error:., $1.8493147074025627435 \times 10^{-10}$, New Error:., $1.8493147074123474566 \times 10^{-13}$

Error order:., 1, Error:., $1.8493147074123474566 \times 10^{-13}$, New Error:., $1.8493147074123572413 \times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3^2} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2} (729 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3} - 1944 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1} + 1782 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+2} - 648 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+3} + 81 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+4} - 1944 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3} + 5184 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 4752 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 1728 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+3} - 216 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+4} + 1782 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3} - 4752 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 4356 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 1584 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+3} + 198 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+4} - 648 u_{i_1, i_2+3, i_3} + 1728 u_{i_1, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 1584 u_{i_1, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 576 u_{i_1, i_2+3, i_3+3} - 72 u_{i_1, i_2+3, i_3+4} + 81 u_{i_1, i_2+4, i_3} - 216 u_{i_1, i_2+4, i_3+1} + 198 u_{i_1, i_2+4, i_3+2} - 72 u_{i_1, i_2+4, i_3+3} + 9 u_{i_1, i_2+4, i_3+4} - 1944 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3} + 5184 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1} - 4752 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+2} + 1728 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+3} - 216 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+4} + 5184 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3} - 13824 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 12672 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 4608 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+3} + 576 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+4} - 4752 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3} + 12672 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 11616 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 4224 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+3} - 528 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+4} + 1728 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3, i_3} - 4608 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 4224 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 1536 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3, i_3+3} + 192 u_{i_1+1, i_2+3, i_3+4} - 216 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4, i_3} + 576 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4, i_3+1} - 528 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4, i_3+2} + 192 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4, i_3+3} - 24 u_{i_1+1, i_2+4, i_3+4} + 1782 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3} - 4752 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1} + 4356 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+2} - 1584 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+3} + 198 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+4} - 4752 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3} + 12672 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 11616 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 4224 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+3} - 528 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+4} + 4356 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3} - 11616 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 10648 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 3872 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+3} + 484 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+4} - 1584 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3, i_3} + 4224 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 3872 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 1408 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3, i_3+3} - 176 u_{i_1+2, i_2+3, i_3+4} + 198 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4, i_3} - 528 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4, i_3+1} + 484 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4, i_3+2} - 176 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4, i_3+3} + 22 u_{i_1+2, i_2+4, i_3+4} - 648 u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3} + 1728 u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3+1} - 1584 u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3+2} + 576 u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3+3} - 72 u_{i_1+3, i_2, i_3+4} + 1728 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3} - 4608 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3+1} + 4224 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3+2} - 1536 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3+3} + 192 u_{i_1+3, i_2+1, i_3+4} - 1584 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2, i_3} + 4224 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2, i_3+1} - 3872 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2, i_3+2} + 1408 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2, i_3+3} - 176 u_{i_1+3, i_2+2, i_3+4} + 576 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3, i_3} - 1536 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3, i_3+1} + 1408 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3, i_3+2} - 512 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3, i_3+3} + 64 u_{i_1+3, i_2+3, i_3+4} - 72 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4, i_3} + 192 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4, i_3+1} - 176 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4, i_3+2} + 64 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4, i_3+3} - 8 u_{i_1+3, i_2+4, i_3+4} + 81 u_{i_1+4, i_2, i_3} - 216 u_{i_1+4, i_2, i_3+1} + 198 u_{i_1+4, i_2, i_3+2} - 72 u_{i_1+4, i_2, i_3+3} + 9 u_{i_1+4, i_2, i_3+4} - 216 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1, i_3} + 576 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1, i_3+1} - 528 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1, i_3+2} + 192 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1, i_3+3} - 24 u_{i_1+4, i_2+1, i_3+4} + 198 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2, i_3} - 528 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2, i_3+1} + 484 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 176 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2, i_3+3} + 22 u_{i_1+4, i_2+2, i_3+4} - 72 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3, i_3} + 192 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3, i_3+1} - 176 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3, i_3+2} + 64 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3, i_3+3} - 8 u_{i_1+4, i_2+3, i_3+4} + 9 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4, i_3} - 24 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4, i_3+1} + 22 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4, i_3+2} - 8 u_{i_1+4, i_2+4, i_3+3} + u_{i_1+4, i_2+4, i_3+4}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), Forward$$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 0.00046780285905716889249, New Error:., $4.6634051758131905703 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.6634051758131905703 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $4.6633905389273833063 \times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.6633905389273833063 \times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, $4.6633905242904842425 \times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.6633905242904842425 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, $4.6633905242758473434 \times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.6633905242758473434 \times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, $4.6633905242758327065 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^6}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = & \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2} (u_{i_1-4, i_2-4, i_3-4} - 8 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4, i_3-3} + 22 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4, i_3-2} - 24 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4, i_3-1} + 9 u_{i_1-4, i_2-4, i_3} \\
& - 8 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3, i_3-4} + 64 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3, i_3-3} - 176 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3, i_3-2} + 192 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 72 u_{i_1-4, i_2-3, i_3} + 22 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2, i_3-4} - 176 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2, i_3-3} \\
& + 484 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 528 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 198 u_{i_1-4, i_2-2, i_3} - 24 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1, i_3-4} + 192 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1, i_3-3} - 528 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 576 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1, i_3-1} \\
& - 216 u_{i_1-4, i_2-1, i_3} + 9 u_{i_1-4, i_2, i_3-4} - 72 u_{i_1-4, i_2, i_3-3} + 198 u_{i_1-4, i_2, i_3-2} - 216 u_{i_1-4, i_2, i_3-1} + 81 u_{i_1-4, i_2, i_3} - 8 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4, i_3-4} + 64 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4, i_3-3} \\
& - 176 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4, i_3-2} + 192 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4, i_3-1} - 72 u_{i_1-3, i_2-4, i_3} + 64 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3, i_3-4} - 512 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3, i_3-3} + 1408 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3, i_3-2} - 1536 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3, i_3-1} \\
& + 576 u_{i_1-3, i_2-3, i_3} - 176 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2, i_3-4} + 1408 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2, i_3-3} - 3872 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 4224 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 1584 u_{i_1-3, i_2-2, i_3} + 192 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3-4} \\
& - 1536 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3-3} + 4224 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3-2} - 4608 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 1728 u_{i_1-3, i_2-1, i_3} - 72 u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3-4} + 576 u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3-3} - 1584 u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3-2} \\
& + 1728 u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3-1} - 648 u_{i_1-3, i_2, i_3} + 22 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4, i_3-4} - 176 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4, i_3-3} + 484 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4, i_3-2} - 528 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4, i_3-1} + 198 u_{i_1-2, i_2-4, i_3} \\
& - 176 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3, i_3-4} + 1408 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3, i_3-3} - 3872 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3, i_3-2} + 4224 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 1584 u_{i_1-2, i_2-3, i_3} + 484 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-4} \\
& - 3872 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-3} + 10648 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 11616 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 4356 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3} - 528 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-4} + 4224 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-3} \\
& - 11616 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 12672 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 4752 u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3} + 198 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-4} - 1584 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-3} + 4356 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-2} - 4752 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1} \\
& + 1782 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3} - 24 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4, i_3-4} + 192 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4, i_3-3} - 528 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4, i_3-2} + 576 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4, i_3-1} - 216 u_{i_1-1, i_2-4, i_3} + 192 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3, i_3-4} \\
& - 1536 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3, i_3-3} + 4224 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3, i_3-2} - 4608 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3, i_3-1} + 1728 u_{i_1-1, i_2-3, i_3} - 528 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-4} + 4224 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-3} \\
& - 11616 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 12672 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-1} - 4752 u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3} + 576 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-4} - 4608 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-3} + 12672 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-2} \\
& - 13824 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1} + 5184 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3} - 216 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-4} + 1728 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-3} - 4752 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-2} + 5184 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1} - 1944 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3} \\
& + 9 u_{i_1, i_2-4, i_3-4} - 72 u_{i_1, i_2-4, i_3-3} + 198 u_{i_1, i_2-4, i_3-2} - 216 u_{i_1, i_2-4, i_3-1} + 81 u_{i_1, i_2-4, i_3} - 72 u_{i_1, i_2-3, i_3-4} + 576 u_{i_1, i_2-3, i_3-3} - 1584 u_{i_1, i_2-3, i_3-2} \\
& + 1728 u_{i_1, i_2-3, i_3-1} - 648 u_{i_1, i_2-3, i_3} + 198 u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3-4} - 1584 u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3-3} + 4356 u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 4752 u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3-1} + 1782 u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3} \\
& - 216 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-4} + 1728 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-3} - 4752 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-2} + 5184 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1} - 1944 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3} + 81 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-4} - 648 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-3} + 1782 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-2} \\
& - 1944 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1} + 729 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $0.00046487259173845290042$, *New Error:*, $4.6633758727119355475 \times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.6633758727119355475 \times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, $4.6633905096242820509 \times 10^{-16}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $4.6633905096242820509 \times 10^{-16}$, New Error:, $4.6633905242611811412 \times 10^{-22}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $4.6633905242611811412 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, $4.6633905242758180403 \times 10^{-28}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $4.6633905242758180403 \times 10^{-28}$, New Error:, $4.6633905242758326772 \times 10^{-34}$

$$\frac{\delta^6}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2} u(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2} (u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 2 u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3} + u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3+2} - 2 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-2} + 4 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3+2} \\ + u_{i_1-2, i_2+2, i_3-2} - 2 u_{i_1-2, i_2+2, i_3} + u_{i_1-2, i_2+2, i_3+2} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3-2} + 4 u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3+2} + 4 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-2} - 8 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3} + 4 u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+2} \\ - 2 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3-2} + 4 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+2} + u_{i_1+2, i_2-2, i_3-2} - 2 u_{i_1+2, i_2-2, i_3} + u_{i_1+2, i_2-2, i_3+2} - 2 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3-2} + 4 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3} - 2 u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+2} \\ + u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3-2} - 2 u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+2}), O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $0.00023317084445851140823$, New Error:, $2.3316952621510987481 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.3316952621510987481 \times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, $2.3316952621379163591 \times 10^{-16}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.3316952621379163591 \times 10^{-16}$, New Error:, $2.3316952621379163459 \times 10^{-22}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.3316952621379163459 \times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, $2.3316952621379163459 \times 10^{-28}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.3316952621379163459 \times 10^{-28}$, New Error:, $2.3316952621379163459 \times 10^{-34}$

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=2, x2=2, x3=1, x4=1 ---"

$$\frac{\delta^6}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} + 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} \\ + 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3, i_4+1} - u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} \\ + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} - 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} - 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} + 4 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3, i_4} \\ + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3, i_4+1} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4} - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4} + u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} \\ - 2 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4} + 2 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1} + 2 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4} - 2 u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3, i_4} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3, i_4+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4} \\ + u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+1}), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.53266524378556272412 , New Error:, $0.00052955680714851698846$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $0.00052955680714851698846$, New Error:, $5.2955371150642343759 \times 10^{-7}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $5.2955371150642343759 \times 10^{-7}$, New Error:, $5.2955370841079409723 \times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $5.2955370841079409723 \times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, $5.2955370840769846790 \times 10^{-13}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.2955370840769846790 $\times 10^{-13}$, New Error:, 5.2955370840769537227 $\times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{\delta^6}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3, i_4} - 2u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 2u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} + 2u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} - 2u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} - u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4} - 2u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 2u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} + 2u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1} - 2u_{i_1-1, i_2-2, i_3, i_4} + 4u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 4u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} - 4u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} + 4u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} - 2u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 2u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} + 2u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} - 2u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3, i_4-1} + u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3, i_4} - 2u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 2u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4} + 2u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1} - 2u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4}),$$

$O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4)$, Backward

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.52646770511033559400, New Error:, 0.00052955060969240560839

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.00052955060969240560839, New Error:, 5.2955370530896732629 $\times 10^{-7}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.2955370530896732629 $\times 10^{-7}$, New Error:, 5.2955370840459664112 $\times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.2955370840459664112 $\times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, 5.2955370840769227044 $\times 10^{-13}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 5.2955370840769227044 $\times 10^{-13}$, New Error:, 5.2955370840769536607 $\times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{\delta^6}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4} (u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4+1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3+1, i_4-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2-2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 2u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 2u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4+1} + 2u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4-1} - 2u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2+2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2+2, i_3-1, i_4+1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 2u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 2u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4+1} + 2u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3+1, i_4-1} - 2u_{i_1, i_2-2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + 4u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - 4u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4+1} - 4u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4-1} + 4u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 2u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 2u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3-1, i_4+1} + 2u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4-1} - 2u_{i_1, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2-2, i_3-1, i_4+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2-2, i_3+1, i_4-1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2-2, i_3+1, i_4+1} - 2u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1} + 2u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4+1} + 2u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4-1} - 2u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3-1, i_4-1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3-1, i_4+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4-1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+2, i_3+1, i_4+1}),$$

$O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2 \Delta x_4^2)$, Centered

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.00079740853369186957131, New Error:, 7.9740280296465544808 $\times 10^{-10}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9740280296465544808 $\times 10^{-10}$, New Error:, 7.9740280295892474530 $\times 10^{-16}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9740280295892474530 $\times 10^{-16}$, New Error:, 7.9740280295892473957 $\times 10^{-22}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9740280295892473957 $\times 10^{-22}$, New Error:, 7.9740280295892473957 $\times 10^{-28}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 7.9740280295892473957 $\times 10^{-28}$, New Error:, 7.9740280295892473957 $\times 10^{-34}$

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=2, x2=1, x3=1, x4=1, x5=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4 \partial x_5} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5} \left(u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5+1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5} \right. \\ \left. + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5+1} + u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5} - u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1} \right. \\ \left. + u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1} - u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5} + u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5+1} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5} \right. \\ \left. - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5} - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1} - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5} \right. \\ \left. - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5+1} - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1} - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1} + 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5} \right. \\ \left. - 2 u_{i_1+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5} + u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1} \right. \\ \left. + u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5} - u_{i_1+2, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1} \right. \\ \left. + u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} \right), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order: 1, Error: 1.8396745244452657404, New Error: 0.0018249506221897310074

Error order: 1, Error: 0.0018249506221897310074, New Error: 1.8249359819023371322 × 10⁻⁶

Error order: 1, Error: 1.8249359819023371322 × 10⁻⁶, New Error: 1.8249359672621329790 × 10⁻⁹

Error order: 1, Error: 1.8249359672621329790 × 10⁻⁹, New Error: 1.8249359672474927749 × 10⁻¹²

Error order: 1, Error: 1.8249359672474927749 × 10⁻¹², New Error: 1.8249359672474781347 × 10⁻¹⁵

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4 \partial x_5} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5} \left(u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1} \right. \\ \left. + u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5} + u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} \right. \\ \left. + u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5} + u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5} - u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5} \right. \\ \left. - 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5} + 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1} - 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5} + 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1} \right. \\ \left. - 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5} - 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5-1} + 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5} + 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5} - 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1} \right. \\ \left. + 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5} - 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1} + 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5} + 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5-1} - 2 u_{i_1-1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5} \right. \\ \left. - u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1} + u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5} + u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5-1} - u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} \right. \\ \left. + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5-1} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5} \right), O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5),$$

Backward

Error order: 1, Error: 1.8103640602478560574, New Error: 0.0018249213124718726461

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.0018249213124718726461, *New Error:*, $1.8249359525926192745 \times 10^{-6}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8249359525926192745 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $1.8249359672328232611 \times 10^{-9}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8249359672328232611 \times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, $1.8249359672474634652 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8249359672474634652 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $1.8249359672474781054 \times 10^{-15}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2 \partial x_3^2 \partial x_4^2 \partial x_5^2} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5} \left(u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5-1} \right. \\
 + u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5+1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} \\
 - u_{i_1-2, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5+1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5-1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5+1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5-1} \\
 - u_{i_1-2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1-2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5-1} + u_{i_1-2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5+1} \\
 + 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5-1} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5+1} + 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5+1} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5-1} \\
 + 2 u_{i_1, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} + 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5+1} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5-1} + 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5+1} \\
 - 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5+1} + 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5-1} - 2 u_{i_1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} \\
 - u_{i_1+2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5-1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5+1} \\
 + u_{i_1+2, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5-1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2-1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5-1} \\
 \left. - u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3-1, i_4+1, i_5+1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5-1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4-1, i_5+1} - u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5-1} + u_{i_1+2, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1} \right), \\
 O(\Delta x_1^2 \Delta x_2^2 \Delta x_3^2 \Delta x_4^2 \Delta x_5^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.0042549759724099660658, *New Error:*, $4.2549137108324547855 \times 10^{-9}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.2549137108324547855 \times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, $4.2549137107701937369 \times 10^{-15}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.2549137107701937369 \times 10^{-15}$, *New Error:*, $4.2549137107701936747 \times 10^{-21}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.2549137107701936747 \times 10^{-21}$, *New Error:*, $4.2549137107701936747 \times 10^{-27}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.2549137107701936747 \times 10^{-27}$, *New Error:*, $4.2549137107701936747 \times 10^{-33}$

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=1, x2=1, x3=1, x4=1, x5=1, x6=1 ---"

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2 \partial x_3 \partial x_4 \partial x_5 \partial x_6} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6) = \frac{1}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5 \Delta x_6} \left(u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6+1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5+1, i_6} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5+1, i_6+1} \right. \\
 \left. - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5, i_6} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5, i_6+1} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6+1} - u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5, i_6} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5, i_6+1} + u_{i_1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1, i_6} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1, i_6+1} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5, i_6+1} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6+1} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6+1} + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5+1, i_6} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5+1, i_6+1} + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5, i_6+1} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6+1} + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5, i_6+1} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1, i_6} + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1, i_6+1} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5, i_6+1} + u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6} - u_{i_l, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5+1, i_6} \\
& - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5+1, i_6+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5, i_6+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5, i_6} \\
& - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5, i_6+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1, i_6} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1, i_6+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5, i_6} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5, i_6+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6} \\
& - u_{i_l+1, i_2, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5+1, i_6} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4, i_5+1, i_6+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5, i_6+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5, i_6} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5, i_6+1} \\
& + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1, i_6} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4, i_5+1, i_6+1} + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5, i_6+1} - u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l+1, i_2+1, i_3+1, i_4+1, i_5+1, i_6+1}), \quad O(\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5 \Delta x_6), \quad \text{Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 6.2886594943336027746, New Error:, 0.0062203143117778255026

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.0062203143117778255026, New Error:, 6.2202464927035935609 $\times 10^{-6}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 6.2202464927035935609 $\times 10^{-6}$, New Error:, 6.2202464248850422488 $\times 10^{-9}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 6.2202464248850422488 $\times 10^{-9}$, New Error:, 6.2202464248172236980 $\times 10^{-12}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 6.2202464248172236980 $\times 10^{-12}$, New Error:, 6.2202464248171558795 $\times 10^{-15}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\delta^6}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5 \Delta x_6} u(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6) &= \frac{1}{\Delta x_1 \Delta x_2 \Delta x_3 \Delta x_4 \Delta x_5 \Delta x_6} (u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6} \\
& - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5, i_6-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1, i_6-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1, i_6} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5, i_6-1} \\
& - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5, i_6-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5-1, i_6-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5-1, i_6} - u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5, i_6-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5, i_6} + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1, i_6-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1, i_6} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5, i_6-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5, i_6-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4-1, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5-1, i_6-1} + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5-1, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6-1} - u_{i_l-1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6-1} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5, i_6-1} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1, i_6-1} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1, i_6} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5, i_6-1} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3-1, i_4, i_5, i_6} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6-1} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6} \\
& - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5, i_6-1} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4-1, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5-1, i_6-1} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5-1, i_6} + u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6-1} - u_{i_l, i_2-1, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6} \\
& + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6-1} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5-1, i_6} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5, i_6-1} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4-1, i_5, i_6} - u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1, i_6-1} + u_{i_l, i_2, i_3-1, i_4, i_5-1, i_6}
\end{aligned}$$

$$+ u_{i1, i2, i3-1, i4, i5, i6-1} - u_{i1, i2, i3-1, i4, i5, i6} - u_{i1, i2, i3, i4-1, i5-1, i6-1} + u_{i1, i2, i3, i4-1, i5-1, i6} + u_{i1, i2, i3, i4-1, i5, i6-1} - u_{i1, i2, i3, i4-1, i5, i6} + u_{i1, i2, i3, i4, i5-1, i6-1} - u_{i1, i2, i3, i4, i5-1, i6} - u_{i1, i2, i3, i4, i5, i6-1} + u_{i1, i2, i3, i4, i5, i6}), O(\Delta x1 \Delta x2 \Delta x3 \Delta x4 \Delta x5 \Delta x6), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order: 1, Error: 6.1528802687173735446, New Error: 0.0062201785389033674475

Error order: 1, Error: 0.0062201785389033674475, New Error: 6.2202463569307191092 × 10⁻⁶

Error order: 1, Error: 6.2202463569307191092 × 10⁻⁶, New Error: 6.2202464247492693744 × 10⁻⁹

Error order: 1, Error: 6.2202464247492693744 × 10⁻⁹, New Error: 6.2202464248170879252 × 10⁻¹²

Error order: 1, Error: 6.2202464248170879252 × 10⁻¹², New Error: 6.2202464248171557437 × 10⁻¹⁵

$$\frac{\delta^6}{\Delta x1 \Delta x2 \Delta x3 \Delta x4 \Delta x5 \Delta x6} u(x1, x2, x3, x4, x5, x6) = \frac{1}{64 \Delta x1 \Delta x2 \Delta x3 \Delta x4 \Delta x5 \Delta x6} (u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1, i5-1, i6-1} - u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1, i5-1, i6+1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & - u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1, i5+1, i6-1} + u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1, i5+1, i6+1} - u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1, i5-1, i6-1} + u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & + u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1, i5+1, i6-1} - u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1, i5+1, i6+1} - u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1, i5-1, i6-1} + u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & + u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1, i5+1, i6-1} - u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1, i5+1, i6+1} + u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1, i5-1, i6-1} - u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & - u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1, i5+1, i6-1} + u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1, i5+1, i6+1} - u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1, i5-1, i6-1} + u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & + u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1, i5+1, i6-1} - u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1, i5+1, i6+1} + u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1, i5-1, i6-1} - u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & - u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1, i5+1, i6-1} + u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1, i5+1, i6+1} + u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1, i5-1, i6-1} - u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & - u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1, i5+1, i6-1} + u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1, i5+1, i6+1} - u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1, i5-1, i6-1} + u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & + u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1, i5+1, i6-1} - u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1, i5+1, i6+1} - u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1, i5-1, i6-1} + u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & + u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1, i5+1, i6-1} - u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1, i4-1, i5+1, i6+1} + u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1, i5-1, i6-1} - u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & - u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1, i5+1, i6-1} + u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1, i4+1, i5+1, i6+1} + u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1, i5-1, i6-1} - u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & - u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1, i5+1, i6-1} + u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+1, i4-1, i5+1, i6+1} - u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1, i5-1, i6-1} + u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & + u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1, i5+1, i6-1} - u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+1, i4+1, i5+1, i6+1} + u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1, i5-1, i6-1} - u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & - u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1, i5+1, i6-1} + u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1, i4-1, i5+1, i6+1} - u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1, i5-1, i6-1} + u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & + u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1, i5+1, i6-1} - u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1, i4+1, i5+1, i6+1} - u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1, i5-1, i6-1} + u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & + u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1, i5+1, i6-1} - u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4-1, i5+1, i6+1} + u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1, i5-1, i6-1} - u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1, i5-1, i6+1} \\ & - u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1, i5+1, i6-1} + u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1, i4+1, i5+1, i6+1} \end{aligned}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.018836393501927704571, New Error: 1.8835889332505556247 × 10⁻⁸

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.8835889332505556247 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.8835889332001394756 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.8835889332001394756 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.8835889332001394252 \times 10^{-20}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.8835889332001394252 \times 10^{-20}$, *New Error:*, $1.8835889332001394252 \times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.8835889332001394252 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $1.8835889332001394252 \times 10^{-32}$

"--- Derivative Order: 7 - x1=7 ---"

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI} + 7 u_{iI+1} - 21 u_{iI+2} + 35 u_{iI+3} - 35 u_{iI+4} + 21 u_{iI+5} - 7 u_{iI+6} + u_{iI+7}}{\Delta xI^7}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.018573035813632058397, *New Error:*, 0.000018505214393484725379
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000018505214393484725379, *New Error:*, $1.8505146744258531464 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8505146744258531464 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.8505146676609477124 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8505146676609477124 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.8505146676541828070 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8505146676541828070 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.8505146676541760421 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI-7} + 7 u_{iI-6} - 21 u_{iI-5} + 35 u_{iI-4} - 35 u_{iI-3} + 21 u_{iI-2} - 7 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI}}{\Delta xI^7}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.018437601592380598962, *New Error:*, 0.000018505078959942847148
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000018505078959942847148, *New Error:*, $1.8505146608824989586 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8505146608824989586 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $1.8505146676474043582 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8505146676474043582 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.8505146676541692636 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $1.8505146676541692636 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $1.8505146676541760285 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{128 \Delta xI^7} (-2187 u_{iI} + 20412 u_{iI+1} - 86751 u_{iI+2} + 222264 u_{iI+3} - 383103 u_{iI+4} + 469476 u_{iI+5} - 421491 u_{iI+6} + 281488 u_{iI+7} - 140497 u_{iI+8} + 52164 u_{iI+9} - 14189 u_{iI+10} + 2744 u_{iI+11} - 357 u_{iI+12} + 28 u_{iI+13} - u_{iI+14}), O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000024661078999182276814, *New Error:*, $2.4624317204004288345 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.4624317204004288345 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.4624280378235629659 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.4624280378235629659 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.4624280341409797296 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.4624280341409797296 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $2.4624280341372971464 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.4624280341372971464 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $2.4624280341372934638 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{128 \Delta xI^7} (u_{iI-14} - 28 u_{iI-13} + 357 u_{iI-12} - 2744 u_{iI-11} + 14189 u_{iI-10} - 52164 u_{iI-9} + 140497 u_{iI-8} - 281488 u_{iI-7} + 421491 u_{iI-6} - 469476 u_{iI-5} + 383103 u_{iI-4} - 222264 u_{iI-3} + 86751 u_{iI-2} - 20412 u_{iI-1} + 2187 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $0.000024587354147434610421$, New Error:, $2.4624243478614045252 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.4624243478614045252 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $2.4624280304510239416 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.4624280304510239416 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $2.4624280341336071906 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.4624280341336071906 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $2.4624280341372897738 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.4624280341372897738 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $2.4624280341372934564 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI-7} + 7 u_{iI-5} - 21 u_{iI-3} + 35 u_{iI-1} - 35 u_{iI+1} + 21 u_{iI+3} - 7 u_{iI+5} + u_{iI+7}}{128 \Delta xI^7}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $0.000012312167149409331709$, New Error:, $1.2312140170713445986 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.2312140170713445986 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $1.2312140170686467328 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.2312140170686467328 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $1.2312140170686467301 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.2312140170686467301 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $1.2312140170686467301 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.2312140170686467301 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $1.2312140170686467301 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{279936 \Delta xI^7} (-19487171 u_{iI} + 223216686 u_{iI+1} - 1207399347 u_{iI+2} + 4109113778 u_{iI+3} - 9890545203 u_{iI+4} + 17941325094 u_{iI+5} - 25514619207 u_{iI+6} + 29205052146 u_{iI+7} - 27399715749 u_{iI+8} + 21334969474 u_{iI+9} - 13902429177 u_{iI+10} + 7617645126 u_{iI+11} - 3515577793 u_{iI+12} + 1364530482 u_{iI+13} - 443272797 u_{iI+14} + 119447286 u_{iI+15} - 26318628 u_{iI+16} + 4637304 u_{iI+17} - 630896 u_{iI+18} + 62496 u_{iI+19} - 4032 u_{iI+20} + 128 u_{iI+21}), O(\Delta xI^3), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $3.6951111734611776295 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $3.6862783415818687620 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $3.6862783415818687620 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $3.6862695210109651015 \times 10^{-26}$

Error order:, 3, Error:, $3.6862695210109651015 \times 10^{-26}$, New Error:, $3.6862695121904064242 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.6862695121904064242 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $3.6862695121815858655 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.6862695121815858655 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $3.6862695121815770449 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{279936 \Delta xI^7} \left(-128 u_{iI-21} + 4032 u_{iI-20} - 62496 u_{iI-19} + 630896 u_{iI-18} - 4637304 u_{iI-17} + 26318628 u_{iI-16} - 119447286 u_{iI-15} \right. \\ \left. + 443272797 u_{iI-14} - 1364530482 u_{iI-13} + 3515577793 u_{iI-12} - 7617645126 u_{iI-11} + 13902429177 u_{iI-10} - 21334969474 u_{iI-9} \right. \\ \left. + 27399715749 u_{iI-8} - 29205052146 u_{iI-7} + 25514619207 u_{iI-6} - 17941325094 u_{iI-5} + 9890545203 u_{iI-4} - 4109113778 u_{iI-3} + 1207399347 u_{iI-2} \right. \\ \left. - 223216686 u_{iI-1} + 19487171 u_{iI} \right), O(\Delta xI^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.6774523282572609278 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.6862606828057624339 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.6862606828057624339 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.6862695033521889952 \times 10^{-26}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.6862695033521889952 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $3.6862695121727476481 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.6862695121727476481 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $3.6862695121815682067 \times 10^{-44}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $3.6862695121815682067 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $3.6862695121815770273 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{35831808 \Delta xI^7} \left(-6103515625 u_{iI} + 82031250000 u_{iI+1} - 534023437500 u_{iI+2} + 2248093750000 u_{iI+3} - 6890948203125 u_{iI+4} \right. \\ \left. + 16412234580000 u_{iI+5} - 31636138006200 u_{iI+6} + 50737391832672 u_{iI+7} - 69044440344453 u_{iI+8} + 80874697390256 u_{iI+9} \right. \\ \left. - 82411156175460 u_{iI+10} + 73628866611216 u_{iI+11} - 58003574731697 u_{iI+12} + 40447018143168 u_{iI+13} - 25023820704912 u_{iI+14} \right. \\ \left. + 13748468946240 u_{iI+15} - 6704944585227 u_{iI+16} + 2897183041200 u_{iI+17} - 1105443596740 u_{iI+18} + 370559722512 u_{iI+19} - 108342883215 u_{iI+20} \right. \\ \left. + 27355473952 u_{iI+21} - 5884141368 u_{iI+22} + 1058152032 u_{iI+23} - 154892871 u_{iI+24} + 17735760 u_{iI+25} - 1490076 u_{iI+26} + 81648 u_{iI+27} \right. \\ \left. - 2187 u_{iI+28} \right), O(\Delta xI^4), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $5.9058767432094105276 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $5.8862782838215864339 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $5.8862782838215864339 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $5.8862587216680495354 \times 10^{-35}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $5.8862587216680495354 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $5.8862587021059322556 \times 10^{-47}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $5.8862587021059322556 \times 10^{-47}$, *New Error:*, $5.8862587020863701384 \times 10^{-59}$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $5.8862587020863701384 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $5.8862587020863505762 \times 10^{-71}$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{35831808 \Delta xI^7} (2187 u_{iI-28} - 81648 u_{iI-27} + 1490076 u_{iI-26} - 17735760 u_{iI-25} + 154892871 u_{iI-24} - 1058152032 u_{iI-23}$$

$$+ 5884141368 u_{iI-22} - 27355473952 u_{iI-21} + 108342883215 u_{iI-20} - 370559722512 u_{iI-19} + 1105443596740 u_{iI-18} - 2897183041200 u_{iI-17}$$

$$+ 6704944585227 u_{iI-16} - 13748468946240 u_{iI-15} + 25023820704912 u_{iI-14} - 40447018143168 u_{iI-13} + 58003574731697 u_{iI-12}$$

$$- 73628866611216 u_{iI-11} + 82411156175460 u_{iI-10} - 80874697390256 u_{iI-9} + 69044440344453 u_{iI-8} - 50737391832672 u_{iI-7}$$

$$+ 31636138006200 u_{iI-6} - 16412234580000 u_{iI-5} + 6890948203125 u_{iI-4} - 2248093750000 u_{iI-3} + 534023437500 u_{iI-2} - 82031250000 u_{iI-1}$$

$$+ 6103515625 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^4), \text{ Backward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 5.8667132478072220835 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.8862391204237015303 \times 10^{-23}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 5.8862391204237015303 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.8862586825046516505 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 5.8862586825046516505 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.8862587020667688577 \times 10^{-47}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 5.8862587020667688577 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.8862587020863309750 \times 10^{-59}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 5.8862587020863309750 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.8862587020863505371 \times 10^{-71}$$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{35831808 \Delta xI^7} (u_{iI-14} - 56 u_{iI-13} + 1344 u_{iI-12} - 17864 u_{iI-11} + 140665 u_{iI-10} - 634032 u_{iI-9} + 1256192 u_{iI-8} + 1361072 u_{iI-7}$$

$$- 10566507 u_{iI-6} + 8977080 u_{iI-5} + 26843712 u_{iI-4} - 43931832 u_{iI-3} - 27724067 u_{iI-2} + 83286112 u_{iI-1} - 83286112 u_{iI+1} + 27724067 u_{iI+2}$$

$$+ 43931832 u_{iI+3} - 26843712 u_{iI+4} - 8977080 u_{iI+5} + 10566507 u_{iI+6} - 1361072 u_{iI+7} - 1256192 u_{iI+8} + 634032 u_{iI+9} - 140665 u_{iI+10}$$

$$+ 17864 u_{iI+11} - 1344 u_{iI+12} + 56 u_{iI+13} - u_{iI+14}), O(\Delta xI^4), \text{ Centered}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 9.8104358231326926788 \times 10^{-12}, \text{ New Error:}, 9.8104311701485705977 \times 10^{-24}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 9.8104311701485705977 \times 10^{-24}, \text{ New Error:}, 9.8104311701439175991 \times 10^{-36}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 9.8104311701439175991 \times 10^{-36}, \text{ New Error:}, 9.8104311701439175944 \times 10^{-48}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 9.8104311701439175944 \times 10^{-48}, \text{ New Error:}, 9.8104311701439175944 \times 10^{-60}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 9.8104311701439175944 \times 10^{-60}, \text{ New Error:}, 9.8104311701439175944 \times 10^{-72}$$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{2799360000000 \Delta xI^7} (-u_{iI-21} + 63 u_{iI-20} - 2016 u_{iI-19} + 42525 u_{iI-18} - 654570 u_{iI-17} + 7729281 u_{iI-16} - 71884253 u_{iI-15}$$

$$+ 532696446 u_{iI-14} - 3144883455 u_{iI-13} + 14590148895 u_{iI-12} - 51321866274 u_{iI-11} + 124967927007 u_{iI-10} - 147655675839 u_{iI-9}$$

$$- 233174125170 u_{iI-8} + 1372237069725 u_{iI-7} - 2111417281701 u_{iI-6} - 1067161607757 u_{iI-5} + 7736911253064 u_{iI-4} - 6326755720075 u_{iI-3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 8923045781475 u_{iI-2} + 16645830237225 u_{iI-1} - 16645830237225 u_{iI+1} + 8923045781475 u_{iI+2} + 6326755720075 u_{iI+3} - 7736911253064 u_{iI+4} \\
& + 1067161607757 u_{iI+5} + 2111417281701 u_{iI+6} - 1372237069725 u_{iI+7} + 233174125170 u_{iI+8} + 147655675839 u_{iI+9} - 124967927007 u_{iI+10} \\
& + 51321866274 u_{iI+11} - 14590148895 u_{iI+12} + 3144883455 u_{iI+13} - 532696446 u_{iI+14} + 71884253 u_{iI+15} - 7729281 u_{iI+16} + 654570 u_{iI+17} \\
& - 42525 u_{iI+18} + 2016 u_{iI+19} - 63 u_{iI+20} + u_{iI+21}), O(\Delta xI^6), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $8.3754123660737903310 \times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, $8.3754058778520952106 \times 10^{-36}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $8.3754058778520952106 \times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, $8.3754058778456069913 \times 10^{-54}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $8.3754058778456069913 \times 10^{-54}$, *New Error:*, $8.3754058778456069849 \times 10^{-72}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $8.3754058778456069849 \times 10^{-72}$, *New Error:*, $8.3754058778456069849 \times 10^{-90}$

Error order:, 6, *Error:*, $8.3754058778456069849 \times 10^{-90}$, *New Error:*, $8.3754058778456069849 \times 10^{-108}$

"--- Derivative Order: 8 - x1=8 ---"

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI} - 8 u_{iI+1} + 28 u_{iI+2} - 56 u_{iI+3} + 70 u_{iI+4} - 56 u_{iI+5} + 28 u_{iI+6} - 8 u_{iI+7} + u_{iI+8}}{\Delta xI^8}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.021194547159563288789, *New Error:*, 0.000021106613775465074202

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000021106613775465074202, *New Error:*, $2.1106526094659408772 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.1106526094659408772 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.1106526006978855123 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.1106526006978855123 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.1106526006891174569 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.1106526006891174569 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $2.1106526006891086889 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-8} - 8 u_{iI-7} + 28 u_{iI-6} - 56 u_{iI-5} + 70 u_{iI-4} - 56 u_{iI-3} + 28 u_{iI-2} - 8 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI}}{\Delta xI^8}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.021019009392739417946, *New Error:*, 0.000021106438238821635860

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000021106438238821635860, *New Error:*, $2.1106525919122765335 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.1106525919122765335 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.1106526006803318479 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.1106526006803318479 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.1106526006890999033 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.1106526006890999033 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $2.1106526006891086713 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{256 \Delta xI^8} (6561 u_{iI} - 69984 u_{iI+1} + 344088 u_{iI+2} - 1034208 u_{iI+3} + 2125116 u_{iI+4} - 3163104 u_{iI+5} + 3525480 u_{iI+6} - 2999904 u_{iI+7} + 1968934 u_{iI+8} - 999968 u_{iI+9} + 391720 u_{iI+10} - 117152 u_{iI+11} + 26236 u_{iI+12} - 4256 u_{iI+13} + 472 u_{iI+14} - 32 u_{iI+15} + u_{iI+16}), O(\Delta xI^2),$$

Forward

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000028127815910481114017, *New Error:*, $2.8085904994568505934 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.8085904994568505934 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.8085862991999577580 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.8085862991999577580 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.8085862949996917361 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.8085862949996917361 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.8085862949954914701 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.8085862949954914701 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $2.8085862949954872698 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{256 \Delta xI^8} (u_{iI-16} - 32 u_{iI-15} + 472 u_{iI-14} - 4256 u_{iI-13} + 26236 u_{iI-12} - 117152 u_{iI-11} + 391720 u_{iI-10} - 999968 u_{iI-9} + 1968934 u_{iI-8} - 2999904 u_{iI-7} + 3525480 u_{iI-6} - 3163104 u_{iI-5} + 2125116 u_{iI-4} - 1034208 u_{iI-3} + 344088 u_{iI-2} - 69984 u_{iI-1} + 6561 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^2),$$

Backward

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000028043727226318296466, *New Error:*, $2.8085820905158476855 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.8085820905158476855 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.8085862907910167550 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.8085862907910167550 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.8085862949912827951 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.8085862949912827951 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.8085862949954830611 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.8085862949954830611 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $2.8085862949954872614 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-8} - 8 u_{iI-6} + 28 u_{iI-4} - 56 u_{iI-2} + 70 u_{iI} - 56 u_{iI+2} + 28 u_{iI+4} - 8 u_{iI+6} + u_{iI+8}}{256 \Delta xI^8}, O(\Delta xI^2), \textit{Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000014042966908584512705, *New Error:*, $1.4042931475012869878 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.4042931475012869878 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.4042931474977436363 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.4042931474977436363 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.4042931474977436328 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.4042931474977436328 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.4042931474977436328 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.4042931474977436328 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $1.4042931474977436328 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1679616 \Delta xI^8} (214358881 u_{iI} - 2806152624 u_{iI+1} + 17474677704 u_{iI+2} - 68981364320 u_{iI+3} + 194073072732 u_{iI+4} - 414781212384 u_{iI+5} + 700837797352 u_{iI+6} - 961771735584 u_{iI+7} + 1092602034918 u_{iI+8} - 1041754255424 u_{iI+9} + 841963717512 u_{iI+10} - 580851978336 u_{iI+11} + 343580769532 u_{iI+12} - 174653900064 u_{iI+13} + 76313039832 u_{iI+14} - 28604760416 u_{iI+15} + 9158072193 u_{iI+16} - 2486316816 u_{iI+17} + 566173552 u_{iI+18} - 106416576 u_{iI+19} + 16121952 u_{iI+20} - 1898240 u_{iI+21} + 163584 u_{iI+22} - 9216 u_{iI+23} + 256 u_{iI+24}),$$

$O(\Delta xI^3)$, Forward

Error order:, 3, Error:, $4.2145550922646323494 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $4.2044805720922369725 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, Error:, $4.2044805720922369725 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $4.2044705115608384391 \times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, Error:, $4.2044705115608384391 \times 10^{-26}$, New Error:, $4.2044705015003209856 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, Error:, $4.2044705015003209856 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $4.2044705014902604682 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, Error:, $4.2044705014902604682 \times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, $4.2044705014902504077 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1679616 \Delta xI^8} (256 u_{iI-24} - 9216 u_{iI-23} + 163584 u_{iI-22} - 1898240 u_{iI-21} + 16121952 u_{iI-20} - 106416576 u_{iI-19} + 566173552 u_{iI-18} - 2486316816 u_{iI-17} + 9158072193 u_{iI-16} - 28604760416 u_{iI-15} + 76313039832 u_{iI-14} - 174653900064 u_{iI-13} + 343580769532 u_{iI-12} - 580851978336 u_{iI-11} + 841963717512 u_{iI-10} - 1041754255424 u_{iI-9} + 1092602034918 u_{iI-8} - 961771735584 u_{iI-7} + 700837797352 u_{iI-6} - 414781212384 u_{iI-5} + 194073072732 u_{iI-4} - 68981364320 u_{iI-3} + 17474677704 u_{iI-2} - 2806152624 u_{iI-1} + 214358881 u_{iI}),$$

$O(\Delta xI^3)$, Backward

Error order:, 3, Error:, $4.1944138290396679344 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $4.2044604309161818423 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, Error:, $4.2044604309161818423 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $4.2044704914196623840 \times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, Error:, $4.2044704914196623840 \times 10^{-26}$, New Error:, $4.2044705014801798096 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, Error:, $4.2044705014801798096 \times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, $4.2044705014902403270 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, Error:, $4.2044705014902403270 \times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, $4.2044705014902503875 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{429981696 \Delta xI^8} (u_{iI-16} - 64 u_{iI-15} + 1792 u_{iI-14} - 28608 u_{iI-13} + 283128 u_{iI-12} - 1748544 u_{iI-11} + 6184192 u_{iI-10} - 7545280 u_{iI-9} - 26668004 u_{iI-8} + 104192704 u_{iI-7} - 35340544 u_{iI-6} - 344574656 u_{iI-5} + 406113736 u_{iI-4} + 510851264 u_{iI-3} - 1044587264 u_{iI-2} - 261146816 u_{iI-1} + 1388025926 u_{iI} - 261146816 u_{iI+1} - 1044587264 u_{iI+2} + 510851264 u_{iI+3} + 406113736 u_{iI+4} - 344574656 u_{iI+5})$$

$$- 35340544 u_{i_l+6} + 104192704 u_{i_l+7} - 26668004 u_{i_l+8} - 7545280 u_{i_l+9} + 6184192 u_{i_l+10} - 1748544 u_{i_l+11} + 283128 u_{i_l+12} - 28608 u_{i_l+13} \\ + 1792 u_{i_l+14} - 64 u_{i_l+15} + u_{i_l+16}), O(\Delta x I^4), \text{ Centered}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.1189547559886053477 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1189542252807038036 \times 10^{-23}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.1189542252807038036 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1189542252801730937 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.1189542252801730937 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1189542252801730932 \times 10^{-47}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.1189542252801730932 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1189542252801730932 \times 10^{-59}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.1189542252801730932 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.1189542252801730932 \times 10^{-71}$$

$$\frac{d^8}{dx I^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{167961600000000 \Delta x I^8} (u_{i_l-24} - 72 u_{i_l-23} + 2628 u_{i_l-22} - 63504 u_{i_l-21} + 1127970 u_{i_l-20} - 15531192 u_{i_l-19} + 170812144 u_{i_l-18} \\ - 1525540536 u_{i_l-17} + 11144102463 u_{i_l-16} - 66511688760 u_{i_l-15} + 320847952320 u_{i_l-14} - 1218795396120 u_{i_l-13} + 3435465093490 u_{i_l-12} \\ - 6033890324880 u_{i_l-11} + 729761010660 u_{i_l-10} + 31054430202552 u_{i_l-9} - 87506800687269 u_{i_l-8} + 68633445330576 u_{i_l-7} \\ + 187682808935032 u_{i_l-6} - 503775847516320 u_{i_l-5} + 160103485388844 u_{i_l-4} + 907003575877392 u_{i_l-3} - 1087819900726608 u_{i_l-2} \\ - 495594865349136 u_{i_l-1} + 1646086033976650 u_{i_l} - 495594865349136 u_{i_l+1} - 1087819900726608 u_{i_l+2} + 907003575877392 u_{i_l+3} \\ + 160103485388844 u_{i_l+4} - 503775847516320 u_{i_l+5} + 187682808935032 u_{i_l+6} + 68633445330576 u_{i_l+7} - 87506800687269 u_{i_l+8} \\ + 31054430202552 u_{i_l+9} + 729761010660 u_{i_l+10} - 6033890324880 u_{i_l+11} + 3435465093490 u_{i_l+12} - 1218795396120 u_{i_l+13} + 320847952320 u_{i_l+14} \\ - 66511688760 u_{i_l+15} + 11144102463 u_{i_l+16} - 1525540536 u_{i_l+17} + 170812144 u_{i_l+18} - 15531192 u_{i_l+19} + 1127970 u_{i_l+20} - 63504 u_{i_l+21} \\ + 2628 u_{i_l+22} - 72 u_{i_l+23} + u_{i_l+24}), O(\Delta x I^6), \text{ Centered}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 9.5527942584246254153 \times 10^{-18}, \text{ New Error:}, 9.5527868581147364820 \times 10^{-36}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 9.5527868581147364820 \times 10^{-36}, \text{ New Error:}, 9.5527868581073361749 \times 10^{-54}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 9.5527868581073361749 \times 10^{-54}, \text{ New Error:}, 9.5527868581073361675 \times 10^{-72}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 9.5527868581073361675 \times 10^{-72}, \text{ New Error:}, 9.5527868581073361675 \times 10^{-90}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 6, \text{ Error:}, 9.5527868581073361675 \times 10^{-90}, \text{ New Error:}, 9.5527868581073361675 \times 10^{-108}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 9 - x1=9 ---"

$$\frac{d^9}{dx I^9} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{i_l} + 9 u_{i_l+1} - 36 u_{i_l+2} + 84 u_{i_l+3} - 126 u_{i_l+4} + 126 u_{i_l+5} - 84 u_{i_l+6} + 36 u_{i_l+7} - 9 u_{i_l+8} + u_{i_l+9}}{\Delta x I^9}, O(\Delta x I), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.023808169137912433476, *New Error:*, 0.000023697557231729132910
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000023697557231729132910, *New Error:*, $2.3697446974391774822 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.3697446974391774822 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.3697446864134791154 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.3697446864134791154 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.3697446864024534171 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.3697446864024534171 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $2.3697446864024423914 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^9}{dxI^9} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI-9} + 9u_{iI-8} - 36u_{iI-7} + 84u_{iI-6} - 126u_{iI-5} + 126u_{iI-4} - 84u_{iI-3} + 36u_{iI-2} - 9u_{iI-1} + u_{iI}}{\Delta xI^9}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.023587432681930448056, *New Error:*, 0.000023697336497027802917
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000023697336497027802917, *New Error:*, $2.3697446753657073493 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.3697446753657073493 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.3697446863914056453 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.3697446863914056453 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.3697446864024313436 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.3697446864024313436 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $2.3697446864024423693 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^9}{dxI^9} u(xI) = \frac{1}{512 \Delta xI^9} (-19683 u_{iI} + 236196 u_{iI+1} - 1318761 u_{iI+2} + 4548960 u_{iI+3} - 10856268 u_{iI+4} + 19023984 u_{iI+5} - 25353972 u_{iI+6} + 26264736 u_{iI+7} - 21431898 u_{iI+8} + 13875544 u_{iI+9} - 7143966 u_{iI+10} + 2918304 u_{iI+11} - 939036 u_{iI+12} + 234864 u_{iI+13} - 44676 u_{iI+14} + 6240 u_{iI+15} - 603 u_{iI+16} + 36 u_{iI+17} - u_{iI+18}), O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000031580610634839257809, *New Error:*, $3.1533575966934719283 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1533575966934719283 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.1533528808382759238 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1533528808382759238 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.1533528761224083863 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1533528761224083863 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $3.1533528761176925188 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1533528761176925188 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $3.1533528761176878029 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^9}{dxI^9} u(xI) = \frac{1}{512 \Delta xI^9} (u_{iI-18} - 36u_{iI-17} + 603u_{iI-16} - 6240u_{iI-15} + 44676u_{iI-14} - 234864u_{iI-13} + 939036u_{iI-12} - 2918304u_{iI-11} + 7143966u_{iI-10} - 13875544u_{iI-9} + 21431898u_{iI-8} - 26264736u_{iI-7} + 25353972u_{iI-6} - 19023984u_{iI-5} + 10856268u_{iI-4} - 4548960u_{iI-3} + 1318761u_{iI-2} - 236196u_{iI-1} + 19683u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000031486199812431083301, *New Error:*, $3.1533481555171962208 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1533481555171962208 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.1533528713970996480 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1533528713970996480 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.1533528761129672101 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1533528761129672101 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $3.1533528761176830776 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.1533528761176830776 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $3.1533528761176877935 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^9}{dx^9} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI-9} + 9u_{iI-7} - 36u_{iI-5} + 84u_{iI-3} - 126u_{iI-1} + 126u_{iI+1} - 84u_{iI+3} + 36u_{iI+5} - 9u_{iI+7} + u_{iI+9}}{512 \Delta x I^9}, O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000015766809398476896713, *New Error:*, $1.5766764380633456798 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.5766764380633456798 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.5766764380588439036 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.5766764380588439036 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.5766764380588438991 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.5766764380588438991 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.5766764380588438991 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.5766764380588438991 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $1.5766764380588438991 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^9}{dx^9} u(xI) = & \frac{1}{10077696 \Delta x I^9} \left(-2357947691 u_{iI} + 34726138722 u_{iI+1} - 244661431905 u_{iI+2} + 1099023297570 u_{iI+3} - 3539352762396 u_{iI+4} \right. \\ & + 8711690279688 u_{iI+5} - 17059897977012 u_{iI+6} + 27315746500680 u_{iI+7} - 36467616225546 u_{iI+8} + 41183754653148 u_{iI+9} \\ & - 39770139275694 u_{iI+10} + 33105711045564 u_{iI+11} - 23895906043356 u_{iI+12} + 15017241992328 u_{iI+13} - 8237144521764 u_{iI+14} \\ & + 3947333721192 u_{iI+15} - 1651749640227 u_{iI+16} + 602263707858 u_{iI+17} - 190613782329 u_{iI+18} + 52054702002 u_{iI+19} - 12161035440 u_{iI+20} \\ & \left. + 2401172064 u_{iI+21} - 393898464 u_{iI+22} + 52373952 u_{iI+23} - 5437440 u_{iI+24} + 414720 u_{iI+25} - 20736 u_{iI+26} + 512 u_{iI+27} \right), O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Forward} \end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $4.7319106621976601118 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $4.7205994447143379230 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $4.7205994447143379230 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $4.7205881492075281876 \times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $4.7205881492075281876 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $4.7205881379120370348 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $4.7205881379120370348 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $4.7205881379007415436 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $4.7205881379007415436 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $4.7205881379007302481 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^9}{dx^9} u(xI) = & \frac{1}{10077696 \Delta x I^9} \left(-512 u_{iI-27} + 20736 u_{iI-26} - 414720 u_{iI-25} + 5437440 u_{iI-24} - 52373952 u_{iI-23} + 393898464 u_{iI-22} \right. \\ & \left. - 2401172064 u_{iI-21} + 12161035440 u_{iI-20} - 52054702002 u_{iI-19} + 190613782329 u_{iI-18} - 602263707858 u_{iI-17} + 1651749640227 u_{iI-16} \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 3947333721192 u_{i_l-15} + 8237144521764 u_{i_l-14} - 15017241992328 u_{i_l-13} + 23895906043356 u_{i_l-12} - 33105711045564 u_{i_l-11} \\
& + 39770139275694 u_{i_l-10} - 41183754653148 u_{i_l-9} + 36467616225546 u_{i_l-8} - 27315746500680 u_{i_l-7} + 17059897977012 u_{i_l-6} \\
& - 8711690279688 u_{i_l-5} + 3539352762396 u_{i_l-4} - 1099023297570 u_{i_l-3} + 244661431905 u_{i_l-2} - 34726138722 u_{i_l-1} + 2357947691 u_{i_l}),
\end{aligned}$$

$O(\Delta x I^3)$, Backward

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 4.7092969590721851420 \times 10^{-8}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.7205768311184676326 \times 10^{-17} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 4.7205768311184676326 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.7205881265939323174 \times 10^{-26} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 4.7205881265939323174 \times 10^{-26}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.7205881378894234389 \times 10^{-35} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 4.7205881378894234389 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.7205881379007189300 \times 10^{-44} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 4.7205881379007189300 \times 10^{-44}, \text{ New Error:}, 4.7205881379007302255 \times 10^{-53}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^9}{dx I^9} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{5159780352 \Delta x I^9} (u_{i_l-18} - 72 u_{i_l-17} + 2304 u_{i_l-16} - 42936 u_{i_l-15} + 511479 u_{i_l-14} - 3999168 u_{i_l-13} + 19941888 u_{i_l-12} \\
& - 54725184 u_{i_l-11} + 19422756 u_{i_l-10} + 368758816 u_{i_l-9} - 935428608 u_{i_l-8} - 267649056 u_{i_l-7} + 4022920620 u_{i_l-6} - 3124975680 u_{i_l-5} \\
& - 7852654080 u_{i_l-4} + 11689035840 u_{i_l-3} + 7157896830 u_{i_l-2} - 20232903600 u_{i_l-1} + 20232903600 u_{i_l+1} - 7157896830 u_{i_l+2} - 11689035840 u_{i_l+3} \\
& + 7852654080 u_{i_l+4} + 3124975680 u_{i_l+5} - 4022920620 u_{i_l+6} + 267649056 u_{i_l+7} + 935428608 u_{i_l+8} - 368758816 u_{i_l+9} - 19422756 u_{i_l+10} \\
& + 54725184 u_{i_l+11} - 19941888 u_{i_l+12} + 3999168 u_{i_l+13} - 511479 u_{i_l+14} + 42936 u_{i_l+15} - 2304 u_{i_l+16} + 72 u_{i_l+17} - u_{i_l+18}), O(\Delta x I^4), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.2563114775317844328 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.2563108816774369052 \times 10^{-23} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.2563108816774369052 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.2563108816768410483 \times 10^{-35} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.2563108816768410483 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.2563108816768410477 \times 10^{-47} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.2563108816768410477 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.2563108816768410477 \times 10^{-59} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.2563108816768410477 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.2563108816768410477 \times 10^{-71}
\end{aligned}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 10 - x1=10 ---"

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx I^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{u_{i_l} - 10 u_{i_l+1} + 45 u_{i_l+2} - 120 u_{i_l+3} + 210 u_{i_l+4} - 252 u_{i_l+5} + 210 u_{i_l+6} - 120 u_{i_l+7} + 45 u_{i_l+8} - 10 u_{i_l+9} + u_{i_l+10}}{\Delta x I^{10}}, O(\Delta x I),$$

Forward

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 0.026413920150958095078, \text{ New Error:}, 0.000026278076133157124777$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000026278076133157124777, *New Error:*, $2.6277940769812428682 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.6277940769812428682 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.6277940634449563348 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.6277940634449563348 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.6277940634314200483 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.6277940634314200483 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $2.6277940634314065121 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-10} - 10 u_{iI-9} + 45 u_{iI-8} - 120 u_{iI-7} + 210 u_{iI-6} - 252 u_{iI-5} + 210 u_{iI-4} - 120 u_{iI-3} + 45 u_{iI-2} - 10 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI}}{\Delta x I^{10}}, O(\Delta x I),$$

Backward

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.026142920805456132119, *New Error:*, 0.000026277805136430687116
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000026277805136430687116, *New Error:*, $2.6277940498815702247 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.6277940498815702247 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.6277940634178566622 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.6277940634178566622 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.6277940634313929487 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.6277940634313929487 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $2.6277940634314064850 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1024 \Delta x I^{10}} (59049 u_{iI} - 787320 u_{iI+1} + 4920750 u_{iI+2} - 19158120 u_{iI+3} + 52083405 u_{iI+4} - 105045984 u_{iI+5} + 163014120 u_{iI+6} - 199234080 u_{iI+7} + 194708610 u_{iI+8} - 153618960 u_{iI+9} + 98365972 u_{iI+10} - 51206320 u_{iI+11} + 21634290 u_{iI+12} - 7379040 u_{iI+13} + 2012520 u_{iI+14} - 432288 u_{iI+15} + 71445 u_{iI+16} - 8760 u_{iI+17} + 750 u_{iI+18} - 40 u_{iI+19} + u_{iI+20}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000035019505027365182847, *New Error:*, $3.4967371886131936910 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4967371886131936910 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.4967319592351695738 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4967319592351695738 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.4967319540057755448 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4967319540057755448 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $3.4967319540005461508 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4967319540005461508 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $3.4967319540005409214 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1024 \Delta x I^{10}} (u_{iI-20} - 40 u_{iI-19} + 750 u_{iI-18} - 8760 u_{iI-17} + 71445 u_{iI-16} - 432288 u_{iI-15} + 2012520 u_{iI-14} - 7379040 u_{iI-13} + 21634290 u_{iI-12} - 51206320 u_{iI-11} + 98365972 u_{iI-10} - 153618960 u_{iI-9} + 194708610 u_{iI-8} - 199234080 u_{iI-7} + 163014120 u_{iI-6} - 105045984 u_{iI-5} + 52083405 u_{iI-4} - 19158120 u_{iI-3} + 4920750 u_{iI-2} - 787320 u_{iI-1} + 59049 u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000034914813635671990382, *New Error:*, $3.4967267193558465021 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4967267193558465021 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.4967319487659122265 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4967319487659122265 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.4967319539953062875 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4967319539953062875 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $3.4967319540005356815 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4967319540005356815 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $3.4967319540005409109 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-10} - 10 u_{iI-8} + 45 u_{iI-6} - 120 u_{iI-4} + 210 u_{iI-2} - 252 u_{iI} + 210 u_{iI+2} - 120 u_{iI+4} + 45 u_{iI+6} - 10 u_{iI+8} + u_{iI+10}}{1024 \Delta x I^{10}}, O(\Delta x I^2),$$

Centered

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000017483715494706358060, *New Error:*, $1.7483659770058429171 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7483659770058429171 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.7483659770002704637 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7483659770002704637 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.7483659770002704581 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7483659770002704581 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.7483659770002704581 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.7483659770002704581 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $1.7483659770002704581 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{60466176 \Delta x I^{10}} (25937424601 u_{iI} - 424430584380 u_{iI+1} + 3337567777170 u_{iI+2} - 16810413191440 u_{iI+3} + 60986704907205 u_{iI+4} - 169917475341636 u_{iI+5} + 378521524238220 u_{iI+6} - 693035293135680 u_{iI+7} + 1063789677845730 u_{iI+8} - 1389399907704600 u_{iI+9} + 1561619154820572 u_{iI+10} - 1523614352793120 u_{iI+11} + 1299056528084610 u_{iI+12} - 972807648657480 u_{iI+13} + 642193522082640 u_{iI+14} - 374636262342528 u_{iI+15} + 193390037704485 u_{iI+16} - 88356686844780 u_{iI+17} + 35697912551490 u_{iI+18} - 12727522455120 u_{iI+19} + 3990807482553 u_{iI+20} - 1095031413300 u_{iI+21} + 261112703220 u_{iI+22} - 53598905280 u_{iI+23} + 9349973280 u_{iI+24} - 1361598336 u_{iI+25} + 161377920 u_{iI+26} - 14986240 u_{iI+27} + 1025280 u_{iI+28} - 46080 u_{iI+29} + 1024 u_{iI+30}), O(\Delta x I^3), Forward$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.2471841504907677186 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $5.2346412117036348721 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.2346412117036348721 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $5.2346286861915371342 \times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.2346286861915371342 \times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, $5.2346286736660423983 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.2346286736660423983 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $5.2346286736535169036 \times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, $5.2346286736535169036 \times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, $5.2346286736535043781 \times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{60466176 \Delta x I^{10}} (1024 u_{iI-30} - 46080 u_{iI-29} + 1025280 u_{iI-28} - 14986240 u_{iI-27} + 161377920 u_{iI-26} - 1361598336 u_{iI-25}$$

$$+ 9349973280 u_{iI-24} - 53598905280 u_{iI-23} + 261112703220 u_{iI-22} - 1095031413300 u_{iI-21} + 3990807482553 u_{iI-20} - 12727522455120 u_{iI-19}$$

$$+ 35697912551490 u_{iI-18} - 88356686844780 u_{iI-17} + 193390037704485 u_{iI-16} - 374636262342528 u_{iI-15} + 642193522082640 u_{iI-14}$$

$$- 972807648657480 u_{iI-13} + 1299056528084610 u_{iI-12} - 1523614352793120 u_{iI-11} + 1561619154820572 u_{iI-10} - 1389399907704600 u_{iI-9}$$

$$+ 1063789677845730 u_{iI-8} - 693035293135680 u_{iI-7} + 378521524238220 u_{iI-6} - 169917475341636 u_{iI-5} + 60986704907205 u_{iI-4}$$

$$- 16810413191440 u_{iI-3} + 3337567777170 u_{iI-2} - 424430584380 u_{iI-1} + 25937424601 u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order: 3, Error: 5.2221079556467378004 × 10⁻⁸, New Error: 5.2346161356381322110 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order: 3, Error: 5.2346161356381322110 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 5.2346286611154716316 × 10⁻²⁶
Error order: 3, Error: 5.2346286611154716316 × 10⁻²⁶, New Error: 5.2346286736409663328 × 10⁻³⁵
Error order: 3, Error: 5.2346286736409663328 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error: 5.2346286736534918275 × 10⁻⁴⁴
Error order: 3, Error: 5.2346286736534918275 × 10⁻⁴⁴, New Error: 5.2346286736535043530 × 10⁻⁵³

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{61917364224 \Delta x I^{10}} (u_{iI-20} - 80 u_{iI-19} + 2880 u_{iI-18} - 61360 u_{iI-17} + 854390 u_{iI-16} - 8072496 u_{iI-15} + 51589440 u_{iI-14}$$

$$- 210125520 u_{iI-13} + 424719405 u_{iI-12} + 376911040 u_{iI-11} - 4343242496 u_{iI-10} + 7425887040 u_{iI-9} + 9094760840 u_{iI-8} - 43160528320 u_{iI-7}$$

$$+ 15941387520 u_{iI-6} + 106961282496 u_{iI-5} - 115377115950 u_{iI-4} - 137192335200 u_{iI-3} + 263228169600 u_{iI-2} + 65807042400 u_{iI-1}$$

$$- 338042251260 u_{iI} + 65807042400 u_{iI+1} + 263228169600 u_{iI+2} - 137192335200 u_{iI+3} - 115377115950 u_{iI+4} + 106961282496 u_{iI+5}$$

$$+ 15941387520 u_{iI+6} - 43160528320 u_{iI+7} + 9094760840 u_{iI+8} + 7425887040 u_{iI+9} - 4343242496 u_{iI+10} + 376911040 u_{iI+11} + 424719405 u_{iI+12}$$

$$- 210125520 u_{iI+13} + 51589440 u_{iI+14} - 8072496 u_{iI+15} + 854390 u_{iI+16} - 61360 u_{iI+17} + 2880 u_{iI+18} - 80 u_{iI+19} + u_{iI+20}), O(\Delta x I^4), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order: 4, Error: 1.3931154108798537182 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 1.3931147501413139335 × 10⁻²³
Error order: 4, Error: 1.3931147501413139335 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 1.3931147501406531918 × 10⁻³⁵
Error order: 4, Error: 1.3931147501406531918 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error: 1.3931147501406531911 × 10⁻⁴⁷
Error order: 4, Error: 1.3931147501406531911 × 10⁻⁴⁷, New Error: 1.3931147501406531911 × 10⁻⁵⁹
Error order: 4, Error: 1.3931147501406531911 × 10⁻⁵⁹, New Error: 1.3931147501406531911 × 10⁻⁷¹

$$\frac{d^{11}}{dx^{11}} u(xl) = \frac{-u_{il} + 11 u_{il+1} - 55 u_{il+2} + 165 u_{il+3} - 330 u_{il+4} + 462 u_{il+5} - 462 u_{il+6} + 330 u_{il+7} - 165 u_{il+8} + 55 u_{il+9} - 11 u_{il+10} + u_{il+11}}{\Delta x^{11}},$$

$O(\Delta x)$, Forward

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.029011818561594514186, New Error:, 0.000028848201767063585794
 Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000028848201767063585794, New Error:, $2.8848038783650390186 \times 10^{-8}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $2.8848038783650390186 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $2.8848038620667608485 \times 10^{-11}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $2.8848038620667608485 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $2.8848038620504625704 \times 10^{-14}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $2.8848038620504625704 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $2.8848038620504462722 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{11}}{dx^{11}} u(xl) = \frac{-u_{il-11} + 11 u_{il-10} - 55 u_{il-9} + 165 u_{il-8} - 330 u_{il-7} + 462 u_{il-6} - 462 u_{il-5} + 330 u_{il-4} - 165 u_{il-3} + 55 u_{il-2} - 11 u_{il-1} + u_{il}}{\Delta x^{11}},$$

$O(\Delta x)$, Backward

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.028685522940242429526, New Error:, 0.000028847875475209590958
 Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000028847875475209590958, New Error:, $2.8848038457358536195 \times 10^{-8}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $2.8848038457358536195 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $2.8848038620341316631 \times 10^{-11}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $2.8848038620341316631 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $2.8848038620504299413 \times 10^{-14}$
 Error order:, 1, Error:, $2.8848038620504299413 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $2.8848038620504462395 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{11}}{dx^{11}} u(xl) = \frac{1}{2048 \Delta x^{11}} (-177147 u_{il} + 2598156 u_{il+1} - 17970579 u_{il+2} + 77944680 u_{il+3} - 237803445 u_{il+4} + 542629692 u_{il+5} - 961309701 u_{il+6} + 1354804704 u_{il+7} - 1544076270 u_{il+8} + 1438925400 u_{il+9} - 1104282366 u_{il+10} + 700701808 u_{il+11} - 368094122 u_{il+12} + 159880600 u_{il+13} - 57188010 u_{il+14} + 16725984 u_{il+15} - 3956007 u_{il+16} + 744348 u_{il+17} - 108735 u_{il+18} + 11880 u_{il+19} - 913 u_{il+20} + 44 u_{il+21} - u_{il+22}),$$

$O(\Delta x^2)$, Forward

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000038444540831608824685, New Error:, $3.8387334405907774538 \times 10^{-11}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.8387334405907774538 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $3.8387276997591681923 \times 10^{-17}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.8387276997591681923 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $3.8387276940183164664 \times 10^{-23}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.8387276940183164664 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $3.8387276940125756147 \times 10^{-29}$
 Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.8387276940125756147 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $3.8387276940125698738 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{11}}{dx^{11}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{2048 \Delta x I^{11}} (u_{iI-22} - 44 u_{iI-21} + 913 u_{iI-20} - 11880 u_{iI-19} + 108735 u_{iI-18} - 744348 u_{iI-17} + 3956007 u_{iI-16} - 16725984 u_{iI-15} \\ + 57188010 u_{iI-14} - 159880600 u_{iI-13} + 368094122 u_{iI-12} - 700701808 u_{iI-11} + 1104282366 u_{iI-10} - 1438925400 u_{iI-9} + 1544076270 u_{iI-8} \\ - 1354804704 u_{iI-7} + 961309701 u_{iI-6} - 542629692 u_{iI-5} + 237803445 u_{iI-4} - 77944680 u_{iI-3} + 17970579 u_{iI-2} - 2598156 u_{iI-1} + 177147 u_{iI}),$$

$O(\Delta x I^2)$, Backward

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000038329610314715335857, New Error:, $3.8387219473940889384 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.8387219473940889384 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $3.8387276882659715036 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.8387276882659715036 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $3.8387276940068232697 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.8387276940068232697 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $3.8387276940125641215 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $3.8387276940125641215 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $3.8387276940125698623 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{11}}{dx^{11}} u(xI) = \frac{-u_{iI-11} + 11 u_{iI-9} - 55 u_{iI-7} + 165 u_{iI-5} - 330 u_{iI-3} + 462 u_{iI-1} - 462 u_{iI+1} + 330 u_{iI+3} - 165 u_{iI+5} + 55 u_{iI+7} - 11 u_{iI+9} + u_{iI+11}}{2048 \Delta x I^{11}},$$

$O(\Delta x I^2)$, Centered

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000019193706017279688473, New Error:, $1.9193638470130396404 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.9193638470130396404 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $1.9193638470062849408 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.9193638470062849408 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $1.9193638470062849340 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.9193638470062849340 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $1.9193638470062849340 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $1.9193638470062849340 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $1.9193638470062849340 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{11}}{dx^{11}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{743008370688 \Delta x I^{11}} (u_{iI-22} - 88 u_{iI-21} + 3520 u_{iI-20} - 84392 u_{iI-19} + 1344629 u_{iI-18} - 14884496 u_{iI-17} + 115675648 u_{iI-16} \\ - 615944560 u_{iI-15} + 2040289207 u_{iI-14} - 2600056184 u_{iI-13} - 9091124416 u_{iI-12} + 45779707768 u_{iI-11} - 47721766565 u_{iI-10} \\ - 151041466048 u_{iI-9} + 424975952896 u_{iI-8} + 44762382016 u_{iI-7} - 1325446363318 u_{iI-6} + 956516220880 u_{iI-5} + 2200515723648 u_{iI-4} \\ - 3069996524496 u_{iI-3} - 1846660156110 u_{iI-2} + 5013162744480 u_{iI-1} - 5013162744480 u_{iI+1} + 1846660156110 u_{iI+2} + 3069996524496 u_{iI+3} \\ - 2200515723648 u_{iI+4} - 956516220880 u_{iI+5} + 1325446363318 u_{iI+6} - 44762382016 u_{iI+7} - 424975952896 u_{iI+8} + 151041466048 u_{iI+9} \\ + 47721766565 u_{iI+10} - 45779707768 u_{iI+11} + 9091124416 u_{iI+12} + 2600056184 u_{iI+13} - 2040289207 u_{iI+14} + 615944560 u_{iI+15} - 115675648 u_{iI+16} \\ + 14884496 u_{iI+17} - 1344629 u_{iI+18} + 84392 u_{iI+19} - 3520 u_{iI+20} + 88 u_{iI+21} - u_{iI+22}), O(\Delta x I^4), Centered$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.5293682155363609736 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.5293674901750951365 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.5293674901750951365 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.5293674901743697714 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.5293674901743697714 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $1.5293674901743697707 \times 10^{-47}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.5293674901743697707 \times 10^{-47}$, *New Error:*, $1.5293674901743697707 \times 10^{-59}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.5293674901743697707 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $1.5293674901743697707 \times 10^{-71}$

"--- Derivative Order: 12 - x1=12 ---"

$$\frac{d^{12}}{dx^{12}} u(xI) = \frac{u_{il} - 12 u_{il+1} + 66 u_{il+2} - 220 u_{il+3} + 495 u_{il+4} - 792 u_{il+5} + 924 u_{il+6} - 792 u_{il+7} + 495 u_{il+8} - 220 u_{il+9} + 66 u_{il+10} - 12 u_{il+11} + u_{il+12}}{\Delta x I^{12}},$$

$O(\Delta x I)$, Forward

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.031601882693412832356, *New Error:*, 0.000031407965337405956274
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000031407965337405956274, *New Error:*, $3.1407772235215698589 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1407772235215698589 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.1407772042114320865 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1407772042114320865 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.1407772041921219488 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1407772041921219488 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $3.1407772041921026386 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{12}}{dx^{12}} u(xI) = \frac{u_{il-12} - 12 u_{il-11} + 66 u_{il-10} - 220 u_{il-9} + 495 u_{il-8} - 792 u_{il-7} + 924 u_{il-6} - 792 u_{il-5} + 495 u_{il-4} - 220 u_{il-3} + 66 u_{il-2} - 12 u_{il-1} + u_{il}}{\Delta x I^{12}},$$

$O(\Delta x I)$, Backward

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.031215288095184937955, *New Error:*, 0.000031407578748062786988
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000031407578748062786988, *New Error:*, $3.1407771848626355425 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1407771848626355425 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.1407772041727731522 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1407772041727731522 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.1407772041920832899 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.1407772041920832899 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $3.1407772041921026000 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{12}}{dxI^{12}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{4096 \Delta xI^{12}} (531441 u_{iI} - 8503056 u_{iI+1} + 64481508 u_{iI+2} - 308314512 u_{iI+3} + 1043159634 u_{iI+4} - 2657047536 u_{iI+5} + 5292251316 u_{iI+6} - 8452282608 u_{iI+7} + 11012757327 u_{iI+8} - 11847885984 u_{iI+9} + 10612624968 u_{iI+10} - 7958160288 u_{iI+11} + 5011371964 u_{iI+12} - 2652720096 u_{iI+13} + 1179180552 u_{iI+14} - 438810592 u_{iI+15} + 135959967 u_{iI+16} - 34783056 u_{iI+17} + 7259604 u_{iI+18} - 1214928 u_{iI+19} + 158994 u_{iI+20} - 15664 u_{iI+21} + 1092 u_{iI+22} - 48 u_{iI+23} + u_{iI+24}), O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000041855759679840207665, New Error: 4.1793505069006298316 × 10⁻¹¹

Error order: 2, Error: 4.1793505069006298316 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 4.1793442566784629175 × 10⁻¹⁷

Error order: 2, Error: 4.1793442566784629175 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 4.1793442504282160766 × 10⁻²³

Error order: 2, Error: 4.1793442504282160766 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 4.1793442504219658298 × 10⁻²⁹

Error order: 2, Error: 4.1793442504219658298 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 4.1793442504219595795 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{d^{12}}{dxI^{12}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{4096 \Delta xI^{12}} (u_{iI-24} - 48 u_{iI-23} + 1092 u_{iI-22} - 15664 u_{iI-21} + 158994 u_{iI-20} - 1214928 u_{iI-19} + 7259604 u_{iI-18} - 34783056 u_{iI-17} + 135959967 u_{iI-16} - 438810592 u_{iI-15} + 1179180552 u_{iI-14} - 2652720096 u_{iI-13} + 5011371964 u_{iI-12} - 7958160288 u_{iI-11} + 10612624968 u_{iI-10} - 11847885984 u_{iI-9} + 11012757327 u_{iI-8} - 8452282608 u_{iI-7} + 5292251316 u_{iI-6} - 2657047536 u_{iI-5} + 1043159634 u_{iI-4} - 308314512 u_{iI-3} + 64481508 u_{iI-2} - 8503056 u_{iI-1} + 531441 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000041730631357288530400, New Error: 4.1793379938938922158 × 10⁻¹¹

Error order: 2, Error: 4.1793379938938922158 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 4.1793442441654561797 × 10⁻¹⁷

Error order: 2, Error: 4.1793442441654561797 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 4.1793442504157030699 × 10⁻²³

Error order: 2, Error: 4.1793442504157030699 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 4.1793442504219533168 × 10⁻²⁹

Error order: 2, Error: 4.1793442504219533168 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 4.1793442504219595670 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{d^{12}}{dxI^{12}} u(xI) = \frac{u_{iI-12} - 12 u_{iI-10} + 66 u_{iI-8} - 220 u_{iI-6} + 495 u_{iI-4} - 792 u_{iI-2} + 924 u_{iI} - 792 u_{iI+2} + 495 u_{iI+4} - 220 u_{iI+6} + 66 u_{iI+8} - 12 u_{iI+10} + u_{iI+12}}{4096 \Delta xI^{12}},$$

O(\Delta xI^2), Centered

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000020896801730729426674, *New Error:*, $2.0896721252190276286 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.0896721252190276286 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.0896721252109797947 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.0896721252109797947 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.0896721252109797866 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.0896721252109797866 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.0896721252109797866 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.0896721252109797866 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $2.0896721252109797866 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{12}}{dx^{12}} u(xI) = & \frac{1}{8916100448256 \Delta x I^{12}} (u_{iI-24} - 96 u_{iI-23} + 4224 u_{iI-22} - 112544 u_{iI-21} + 2019060 u_{iI-20} - 25613280 u_{iI-19} + 234072960 u_{iI-18} \\
& - 1530508320 u_{iI-17} + 6847425090 u_{iI-16} - 17982080160 u_{iI-15} + 6666092928 u_{iI-14} + 135446961312 u_{iI-13} - 436800167388 u_{iI-12} \\
& + 160603727328 u_{iI-11} + 2008636467840 u_{iI-10} - 3782599081440 u_{iI-9} - 2844155381265 u_{iI-8} + 15110936216640 u_{iI-7} - 5518490940160 u_{iI-6} \\
& - 31322455602240 u_{iI-5} + 31690888170216 u_{iI-4} + 36434053561664 u_{iI-3} - 66865789875456 u_{iI-2} - 16716447468864 u_{iI-1} + 83903924223900 u_{iI} \\
& - 16716447468864 u_{iI+1} - 66865789875456 u_{iI+2} + 36434053561664 u_{iI+3} + 31690888170216 u_{iI+4} - 31322455602240 u_{iI+5} \\
& - 5518490940160 u_{iI+6} + 15110936216640 u_{iI+7} - 2844155381265 u_{iI+8} - 3782599081440 u_{iI+9} + 2008636467840 u_{iI+10} + 160603727328 u_{iI+11} \\
& - 436800167388 u_{iI+12} + 135446961312 u_{iI+13} + 6666092928 u_{iI+14} - 17982080160 u_{iI+15} + 6847425090 u_{iI+16} - 1530508320 u_{iI+17} \\
& + 234072960 u_{iI+18} - 25613280 u_{iI+19} + 2019060 u_{iI+20} - 112544 u_{iI+21} + 4224 u_{iI+22} - 96 u_{iI+23} + u_{iI+24}), O(\Delta x I^4), \textit{Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.6650715465824239393 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.6650707568591128324 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.6650707568591128324 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.6650707568583231044 \times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.6650707568583231044 \times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, $1.6650707568583231036 \times 10^{-47}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.6650707568583231036 \times 10^{-47}$, *New Error:*, $1.6650707568583231036 \times 10^{-59}$
Error order:, 4, *Error:*, $1.6650707568583231036 \times 10^{-59}$, *New Error:*, $1.6650707568583231036 \times 10^{-71}$

"--- Derivative Order: 13 - x1=13 ---"

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{13}}{dx^{13}} u(xI) = & \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{13}} (-u_{iI} + 13 u_{iI+1} - 78 u_{iI+2} + 286 u_{iI+3} - 715 u_{iI+4} + 1287 u_{iI+5} - 1716 u_{iI+6} + 1716 u_{iI+7} - 1287 u_{iI+8} + 715 u_{iI+9} \\
& - 286 u_{iI+10} + 78 u_{iI+11} - 13 u_{iI+12} + u_{iI+13}), O(\Delta x I), \textit{Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.034184130830782190260, *New Error:*, 0.000033957397964992672727
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000033957397964992672727, *New Error:*, $3.3957172260607710880 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.3957172260607710880 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.3957172034904350821 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.3957172034904350821 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.3957172034678647462 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.3957172034678647462 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $3.3957172034678421759 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{13}}{dx^{13}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{13}} \left(-u_{iI-13} + 13 u_{iI-12} - 78 u_{iI-11} + 286 u_{iI-10} - 715 u_{iI-9} + 1287 u_{iI-8} - 1716 u_{iI-7} + 1716 u_{iI-6} - 1287 u_{iI-5} + 715 u_{iI-4} - 286 u_{iI-3} + 78 u_{iI-2} - 13 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI} \right), O(\Delta x I), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.033732265111693297923, *New Error:*, 0.000033956946106416023157
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000033956946106416023157, *New Error:*, $3.3957171808749134238 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.3957171808749134238 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.3957172034452492245 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.3957172034452492245 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.3957172034678195604 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.3957172034678195604 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $3.3957172034678421307 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{13}}{dx^{13}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{8192 \Delta x I^{13}} \left(-1594323 u_{iI} + 27634932 u_{iI+1} - 227988189 u_{iI+2} + 1191372624 u_{iI+3} - 4427218458 u_{iI+4} + 12452095656 u_{iI+5} - 27548103726 u_{iI+6} + 49182900624 u_{iI+7} - 72139653729 u_{iI+8} + 88046969868 u_{iI+9} - 90242176167 u_{iI+10} + 78172866720 u_{iI+11} - 57479382012 u_{iI+12} + 35961808432 u_{iI+13} - 19159794004 u_{iI+14} + 8685874080 u_{iI+15} - 3342302821 u_{iI+16} + 1086999628 u_{iI+17} - 296871003 u_{iI+18} + 67466256 u_{iI+19} - 12596298 u_{iI+20} + 1897896 u_{iI+21} - 224926 u_{iI+22} + 20176 u_{iI+23} - 1287 u_{iI+24} + 52 u_{iI+25} - u_{iI+26} \right), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000045253203093327404921, *New Error:*, $4.5185925307445202237 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.5185925307445202237 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.5185857731886242424 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.5185857731886242424 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $4.5185857664310386724 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.5185857664310386724 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $4.5185857664242810868 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.5185857664242810868 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $4.5185857664242743292 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{13}}{dx^{13}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{8192 \Delta x I^{13}} \left(u_{iI-26} - 52 u_{iI-25} + 1287 u_{iI-24} - 20176 u_{iI-23} + 224926 u_{iI-22} - 1897896 u_{iI-21} + 12596298 u_{iI-20} - 67466256 u_{iI-19} + 296871003 u_{iI-18} - 1086999628 u_{iI-17} + 3342302821 u_{iI-16} - 8685874080 u_{iI-15} + 19159794004 u_{iI-14} - 35961808432 u_{iI-13} \right)$$

$$+ 57479382012 u_{i_l-12} - 78172866720 u_{i_l-11} + 90242176167 u_{i_l-10} - 88046969868 u_{i_l-9} + 72139653729 u_{i_l-8} - 49182900624 u_{i_l-7} \\ + 27548103726 u_{i_l-6} - 12452095656 u_{i_l-5} + 4427218458 u_{i_l-4} - 1191372624 u_{i_l-3} + 227988189 u_{i_l-2} - 27634932 u_{i_l-1} + 1594323 u_{i_l}),$$

$O(\Delta x I^2)$, Backward

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Error order: } 2, \text{ Error: } 0.000045117918160449205137, \text{ New Error: } 4.5185790020446209565 \times 10^{-11} \\ \text{Error order: } 2, \text{ Error: } 4.5185790020446209565 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error: } 4.5185857596599243430 \times 10^{-17} \\ \text{Error order: } 2, \text{ Error: } 4.5185857596599243430 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error: } 4.5185857664175099725 \times 10^{-23} \\ \text{Error order: } 2, \text{ Error: } 4.5185857664175099725 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error: } 4.5185857664242675581 \times 10^{-29} \\ \text{Error order: } 2, \text{ Error: } 4.5185857664242675581 \times 10^{-29}, \text{ New Error: } 4.5185857664242743156 \times 10^{-35} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{d^{13}}{dx I^{13}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{8192 \Delta x I^{13}} (-u_{i_l-13} + 13 u_{i_l-11} - 78 u_{i_l-9} + 286 u_{i_l-7} - 715 u_{i_l-5} + 1287 u_{i_l-3} - 1716 u_{i_l-1} + 1716 u_{i_l+1} - 1287 u_{i_l+3} + 715 u_{i_l+5} \\ - 286 u_{i_l+7} + 78 u_{i_l+9} - 13 u_{i_l+11} + u_{i_l+13}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Centered}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Error order: } 2, \text{ Error: } 0.000022593023344252355363, \text{ New Error: } 2.2592928832215883488 \times 10^{-11} \\ \text{Error order: } 2, \text{ Error: } 2.2592928832215883488 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error: } 2.2592928832121371707 \times 10^{-17} \\ \text{Error order: } 2, \text{ Error: } 2.2592928832121371707 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error: } 2.2592928832121371612 \times 10^{-23} \\ \text{Error order: } 2, \text{ Error: } 2.2592928832121371612 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error: } 2.2592928832121371612 \times 10^{-29} \\ \text{Error order: } 2, \text{ Error: } 2.2592928832121371612 \times 10^{-29}, \text{ New Error: } 2.2592928832121371612 \times 10^{-35} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{d^{13}}{dx I^{13}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{106993205379072 \Delta x I^{13}} (u_{i_l-26} - 104 u_{i_l-25} + 4992 u_{i_l-24} - 146328 u_{i_l-23} + 2918643 u_{i_l-22} - 41731872 u_{i_l-21} + 438074624 u_{i_l-20} \\ - 3386826976 u_{i_l-19} + 18884566350 u_{i_l-18} - 70863283920 u_{i_l-17} + 138044594688 u_{i_l-16} + 138428126928 u_{i_l-15} - 1671079924254 u_{i_l-14} \\ + 3726315890016 u_{i_l-13} + 1800716246784 u_{i_l-12} - 23481539124576 u_{i_l-11} + 29138267256267 u_{i_l-10} + 53772667282152 u_{i_l-9} \\ - 158675409792640 u_{i_l-8} - 6145172049640 u_{i_l-7} + 406002178102521 u_{i_l-6} - 276351915537984 u_{i_l-5} - 603399372246528 u_{i_l-4} \\ + 803059432498752 u_{i_l-3} + 477417044297908 u_{i_l-2} - 1259308213825376 u_{i_l-1} + 1259308213825376 u_{i_l+1} - 477417044297908 u_{i_l+2} \\ - 803059432498752 u_{i_l+3} + 603399372246528 u_{i_l+4} + 276351915537984 u_{i_l+5} - 406002178102521 u_{i_l+6} + 6145172049640 u_{i_l+7} \\ + 158675409792640 u_{i_l+8} - 53772667282152 u_{i_l+9} - 29138267256267 u_{i_l+10} + 23481539124576 u_{i_l+11} - 1800716246784 u_{i_l+12} \\ - 3726315890016 u_{i_l+13} + 1671079924254 u_{i_l+14} - 138428126928 u_{i_l+15} - 138044594688 u_{i_l+16} + 70863283920 u_{i_l+17} - 18884566350 u_{i_l+18})$$

$$+ 3386826976 u_{i_l+19} - 438074624 u_{i_l+20} + 41731872 u_{i_l+21} - 2918643 u_{i_l+22} + 146328 u_{i_l+23} - 4992 u_{i_l+24} + 104 u_{i_l+25} - u_{i_l+26}), O(\Delta x l^4),$$

Centered

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.8002270546877731960 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8002262008623142732 \times 10^{-23}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.8002262008623142732 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8002262008614604422 \times 10^{-35}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.8002262008614604422 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8002262008614604414 \times 10^{-47}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.8002262008614604414 \times 10^{-47}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8002262008614604414 \times 10^{-59}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 4, \text{ Error:}, 1.8002262008614604414 \times 10^{-59}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8002262008614604414 \times 10^{-71}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 14 - x1=14 ---"

$$\frac{d^{14}}{dx l^{14}} u(xl) = \frac{1}{\Delta x l^{14}} (u_{i_l} - 14 u_{i_l+1} + 91 u_{i_l+2} - 364 u_{i_l+3} + 1001 u_{i_l+4} - 2002 u_{i_l+5} + 3003 u_{i_l+6} - 3432 u_{i_l+7} + 3003 u_{i_l+8} - 2002 u_{i_l+9}$$

$$+ 1001 u_{i_l+10} - 364 u_{i_l+11} + 91 u_{i_l+12} - 14 u_{i_l+13} + u_{i_l+14}), O(\Delta x l), \text{ Forward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 0.036758581218930661311, \text{ New Error:}, 0.000036496530687690761165$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 0.000036496530687690761165, \text{ New Error:}, 3.6496269912922900911 \times 10^{-8}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 3.6496269912922900911 \times 10^{-8}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.6496269652149404057 \times 10^{-11}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 3.6496269652149404057 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.6496269651888630562 \times 10^{-14}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 3.6496269651888630562 \times 10^{-14}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.6496269651888369788 \times 10^{-17}$$

$$\frac{d^{14}}{dx l^{14}} u(xl) = \frac{1}{\Delta x l^{14}} (u_{i_l-14} - 14 u_{i_l-13} + 91 u_{i_l-12} - 364 u_{i_l-11} + 1001 u_{i_l-10} - 2002 u_{i_l-9} + 3003 u_{i_l-8} - 3432 u_{i_l-7} + 3003 u_{i_l-6} - 2002 u_{i_l-5}$$

$$+ 1001 u_{i_l-4} - 364 u_{i_l-3} + 91 u_{i_l-2} - 14 u_{i_l-1} + u_{i_l}), O(\Delta x l), \text{ Backward}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 0.036236502664233885461, \text{ New Error:}, 0.000036496008618630528384$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 0.000036496008618630528384, \text{ New Error:}, 3.6496269390853840688 \times 10^{-8}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 3.6496269390853840688 \times 10^{-8}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.6496269651627334997 \times 10^{-11}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 3.6496269651627334997 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.6496269651888108493 \times 10^{-14}$$

$$\text{Error order:}, 1, \text{ Error:}, 3.6496269651888108493 \times 10^{-14}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.6496269651888369266 \times 10^{-17}$$

$$\frac{d^{14}}{dx^{14}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{16384 \Delta x I^{14}} (4782969 u_{iI} - 89282088 u_{iI+1} + 796098618 u_{iI+2} - 4513705560 u_{iI+3} + 18275134059 u_{iI+4} - 56256533424 u_{iI+5} + 136879912260 u_{iI+6} - 270193212432 u_{iI+7} + 440698667409 u_{iI+8} - 601882425144 u_{iI+9} + 695054061702 u_{iI+10} - 683534274696 u_{iI+11} + 575371789083 u_{iI+12} - 415975820064 u_{iI+13} + 258805997752 u_{iI+14} - 138658606688 u_{iI+15} + 63930198787 u_{iI+16} - 25316084248 u_{iI+17} + 8580914342 u_{iI+18} - 2476882408 u_{iI+19} + 604524921 u_{iI+20} - 123545136 u_{iI+21} + 20862660 u_{iI+22} - 2858128 u_{iI+23} + 309491 u_{iI+24} - 25480 u_{iI+25} + 1498 u_{iI+26} - 56 u_{iI+27} + u_{iI+28}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000048636912482613832010, *New Error:*, $4.8564636442792321302 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.8564636442792321302 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.8564563814402532897 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.8564563814402532897 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $4.8564563741773791965 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.8564563741773791965 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $4.8564563741701163223 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.8564563741701163223 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $4.8564563741701090595 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{14}}{dx^{14}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{16384 \Delta x I^{14}} (u_{iI-28} - 56 u_{iI-27} + 1498 u_{iI-26} - 25480 u_{iI-25} + 309491 u_{iI-24} - 2858128 u_{iI-23} + 20862660 u_{iI-22} - 123545136 u_{iI-21} + 604524921 u_{iI-20} - 2476882408 u_{iI-19} + 8580914342 u_{iI-18} - 25316084248 u_{iI-17} + 63930198787 u_{iI-16} - 138658606688 u_{iI-15} + 258805997752 u_{iI-14} - 415975820064 u_{iI-13} + 575371789083 u_{iI-12} - 683534274696 u_{iI-11} + 695054061702 u_{iI-10} - 601882425144 u_{iI-9} + 440698667409 u_{iI-8} - 270193212432 u_{iI-7} + 136879912260 u_{iI-6} - 56256533424 u_{iI-5} + 18275134059 u_{iI-4} - 4513705560 u_{iI-3} + 796098618 u_{iI-2} - 89282088 u_{iI-1} + 4782969 u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000048491512010861675215, *New Error:*, $4.8564491039906869521 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.8564491039906869521 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.8564563668999647443 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.8564563668999647443 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $4.8564563741628389079 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.8564563741628389079 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $4.8564563741701017820 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $4.8564563741701017820 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $4.8564563741701090449 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{14}}{dx^{14}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{16384 \Delta x I^{14}} (u_{iI-14} - 14 u_{iI-12} + 91 u_{iI-10} - 364 u_{iI-8} + 1001 u_{iI-6} - 2002 u_{iI-4} + 3003 u_{iI-2} - 3432 u_{iI} + 3003 u_{iI+2} - 2002 u_{iI+4} + 1001 u_{iI+6} - 364 u_{iI+8} + 91 u_{iI+10} - 14 u_{iI+12} + u_{iI+14}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000024282391511847666341, *New Error:*, $2.4282281870960185937 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.4282281870960185937 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.4282281870850545371 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.4282281870850545371 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.4282281870850545261 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.4282281870850545261 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.4282281870850545261 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.4282281870850545261 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $2.4282281870850545261 \times 10^{-35}$

"--- Derivative Order: 15 - x1=15 ---"

$$\frac{d^{15}}{dx^{15}} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Delta x^{15}} \left(-u_{il} + 15 u_{il+1} - 105 u_{il+2} + 455 u_{il+3} - 1365 u_{il+4} + 3003 u_{il+5} - 5005 u_{il+6} + 6435 u_{il+7} - 6435 u_{il+8} + 5005 u_{il+9} - 3003 u_{il+10} + 1365 u_{il+11} - 455 u_{il+12} + 105 u_{il+13} - 15 u_{il+14} + u_{il+15} \right), O(\Delta x), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.039325252064026021100, *New Error:*, 0.000039025394460632933011
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000039025394460632933011, *New Error:*, $3.9025096162462160496 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.9025096162462160496 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.9025095864165542952 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.9025095864165542952 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.9025095863867246336 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.9025095863867246336 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $3.9025095863866948039 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{15}}{dx^{15}} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Delta x^{15}} \left(-u_{il-15} + 15 u_{il-14} - 105 u_{il-13} + 455 u_{il-12} - 1365 u_{il-11} + 3003 u_{il-10} - 5005 u_{il-9} + 6435 u_{il-8} - 6435 u_{il-7} + 5005 u_{il-6} - 3003 u_{il-5} + 1365 u_{il-4} - 455 u_{il-3} + 105 u_{il-2} - 15 u_{il-1} + u_{il} \right), O(\Delta x), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.038728049260870798202, *New Error:*, 0.000039024797270210519473
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000039024797270210519473, *New Error:*, $3.9025095565271738095 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.9025095565271738095 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $3.9025095863568352530 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.9025095863568352530 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.9025095863866649146 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.9025095863866649146 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $3.9025095863866947442 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{15}}{dx^{15}} u(x) = \frac{1}{32768 \Delta x^{15}} \left(-14348907 u_{il} + 286978140 u_{il+1} - 2750207175 u_{il+2} + 16814793240 u_{il+3} - 73676323035 u_{il+4} + 246383842068 u_{il+5} - 653941004535 u_{il+6} + 1414355819760 u_{il+7} - 2539748764215 u_{il+8} + 3838635157500 u_{il+9} - 4933390553091 u_{il+10} + 5432701496040 u_{il+11} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - 5155306527735 u_{i_l+12} + 4232948891220 u_{i_l+13} - 3015693062595 u_{i_l+14} + 1867175631136 u_{i_l+15} - 1005231020865 u_{i_l+16} + 470327654580 u_{i_l+17} \\
& - 190937278805 u_{i_l+18} + 67070388840 u_{i_l+19} - 20302018737 u_{i_l+20} + 5265617500 u_{i_l+21} - 1161293445 u_{i_l+22} + 215570160 u_{i_l+23} \\
& - 33223645 u_{i_l+24} + 4172532 u_{i_l+25} - 415905 u_{i_l+26} + 31640 u_{i_l+27} - 1725 u_{i_l+28} + 60 u_{i_l+29} - u_{i_l+30}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000052006929147794875768, *New Error:*, $5.1929679686441481980 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.1929679686441481980 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $5.1929602025665668162 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.1929602025665668162 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $5.1929601948004482426 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.1929601948004482426 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $5.1929601947926821240 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.1929601947926821240 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $5.1929601947926743578 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{15}}{dx I^{15}} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{32768 \Delta x I^{15}} (u_{i_l-30} - 60 u_{i_l-29} + 1725 u_{i_l-28} - 31640 u_{i_l-27} + 415905 u_{i_l-26} - 4172532 u_{i_l-25} + 33223645 u_{i_l-24} - 215570160 u_{i_l-23} \\
& + 1161293445 u_{i_l-22} - 5265617500 u_{i_l-21} + 20302018737 u_{i_l-20} - 67070388840 u_{i_l-19} + 190937278805 u_{i_l-18} - 470327654580 u_{i_l-17} \\
& + 1005231020865 u_{i_l-16} - 1867175631136 u_{i_l-15} + 3015693062595 u_{i_l-14} - 4232948891220 u_{i_l-13} + 5155306527735 u_{i_l-12} - 5432701496040 u_{i_l-11} \\
& + 4933390553091 u_{i_l-10} - 3838635157500 u_{i_l-9} + 2539748764215 u_{i_l-8} - 1414355819760 u_{i_l-7} + 653941004535 u_{i_l-6} - 246383842068 u_{i_l-5} \\
& + 73676323035 u_{i_l-4} - 16814793240 u_{i_l-3} + 2750207175 u_{i_l-2} - 286978140 u_{i_l-1} + 14348907 u_{i_l}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000051851454085072740570, *New Error:*, $5.1929524208591341274 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.1929524208591341274 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $5.1929601870187818019 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.1929601870187818019 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $5.1929601947849004576 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.1929601947849004576 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $5.1929601947926665762 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.1929601947926665762 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $5.1929601947926743423 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{15}}{dx I^{15}} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{32768 \Delta x I^{15}} (-u_{i_l-15} + 15 u_{i_l-13} - 105 u_{i_l-11} + 455 u_{i_l-9} - 1365 u_{i_l-7} + 3003 u_{i_l-5} - 5005 u_{i_l-3} + 6435 u_{i_l-1} - 6435 u_{i_l+1} \\
& + 5005 u_{i_l+3} - 3003 u_{i_l+5} + 1365 u_{i_l+7} - 455 u_{i_l+9} + 105 u_{i_l+11} - 15 u_{i_l+13} + u_{i_l+15}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000025964926832454794558, *New Error:*, $2.5964800974089229846 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5964800974089229846 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.5964800973963371876 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5964800973963371876 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.5964800973963371750 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.5964800973963371750 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.5964800973963371750 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 2.5964800973963371750 $\times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, 2.5964800973963371750 $\times 10^{-35}$

"--- Derivative Order: 16 - x1=16 ---"

$$\frac{d^{16}}{dxI^{16}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta xI^{16}} (u_{iI} - 16 u_{iI+1} + 120 u_{iI+2} - 560 u_{iI+3} + 1820 u_{iI+4} - 4368 u_{iI+5} + 8008 u_{iI+6} - 11440 u_{iI+7} + 12870 u_{iI+8} - 11440 u_{iI+9} + 8008 u_{iI+10} - 4368 u_{iI+11} + 1820 u_{iI+12} - 560 u_{iI+13} + 120 u_{iI+14} - 16 u_{iI+15} + u_{iI+16}), O(\Delta xI), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.041884161533256352982, New Error:, 0.000041544020156424184751

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000041544020156424184751, New Error:, 4.1543681896937603655 $\times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 4.1543681896937603655 $\times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, 4.1543681558679991008 $\times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 4.1543681558679991008 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, 4.1543681558341733397 $\times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 4.1543681558341733397 $\times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, 4.1543681558341395139 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{16}}{dxI^{16}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta xI^{16}} (u_{iI-16} - 16 u_{iI-15} + 120 u_{iI-14} - 560 u_{iI-13} + 1820 u_{iI-12} - 4368 u_{iI-11} + 8008 u_{iI-10} - 11440 u_{iI-9} + 12870 u_{iI-8} - 11440 u_{iI-7} + 8008 u_{iI-6} - 4368 u_{iI-5} + 1820 u_{iI-4} - 560 u_{iI-3} + 120 u_{iI-2} - 16 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.041206953243805140159, New Error:, 0.000041543342964010210549

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000041543342964010210549, New Error:, 4.1543681219745189697 $\times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 4.1543681219745189697 $\times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, 4.1543681558002798594 $\times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 4.1543681558002798594 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, 4.1543681558341056204 $\times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 4.1543681558341056204 $\times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, 4.1543681558341394462 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{16}}{dxI^{16}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{65536 \Delta xI^{16}} (43046721 u_{iI} - 918330048 u_{iI+1} + 9412882992 u_{iI+2} - 61732186560 u_{iI+3} + 291038349240 u_{iI+4} - 1050671611584 u_{iI+5} + 3021034704912 u_{iI+6} - 7105215319488 u_{iI+7} + 13930610576220 u_{iI+8} - 23089256349120 u_{iI+9} + 32694461053488 u_{iI+10} - 39870301857984 u_{iI+11} + 42130116120456 u_{iI+12} - 38752774280640 u_{iI+13} + 31134181280400 u_{iI+14} - 21897248035008 u_{iI+15} + 13500088649734 u_{iI+16} - 7299082678336 u_{iI+17} + 3459353475600 u_{iI+18} - 1435287936320 u_{iI+19} + 520124890376 u_{iI+20} - 164075316288 u_{iI+21} + 44848369072 u_{iI+22} - 10557501760 u_{iI+23} + 2123245020 u_{iI+24} - 360982336 u_{iI+25} + 51161488 u_{iI+26} - 5931072 u_{iI+27} + 547640 u_{iI+28})$$

$- 38720 u_{i_l+29} + 1968 u_{i_l+30} - 64 u_{i_l+31} + u_{i_l+32}$), $O(\Delta x I^2)$, *Forward*

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000055363294278793859899, *New Error:*, $5.5281096139887691504 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.5281096139887691504 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $5.5281013467109161014 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.5281013467109161014 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $5.5281013384435909435 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.5281013384435909435 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $5.5281013384353236183 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.5281013384353236183 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $5.5281013384353153510 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{16}}{dx I^{16}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{65536 \Delta x I^{16}} (u_{i_l-32} - 64 u_{i_l-31} + 1968 u_{i_l-30} - 38720 u_{i_l-29} + 547640 u_{i_l-28} - 5931072 u_{i_l-27} + 51161488 u_{i_l-26} - 360982336 u_{i_l-25} \\ + 2123245020 u_{i_l-24} - 10557501760 u_{i_l-23} + 44848369072 u_{i_l-22} - 164075316288 u_{i_l-21} + 520124890376 u_{i_l-20} - 1435287936320 u_{i_l-19} \\ + 3459353475600 u_{i_l-18} - 7299082678336 u_{i_l-17} + 13500088649734 u_{i_l-16} - 21897248035008 u_{i_l-15} + 31134181280400 u_{i_l-14} \\ - 38752774280640 u_{i_l-13} + 42130116120456 u_{i_l-12} - 39870301857984 u_{i_l-11} + 32694461053488 u_{i_l-10} - 23089256349120 u_{i_l-9} \\ + 13930610576220 u_{i_l-8} - 7105215319488 u_{i_l-7} + 3021034704912 u_{i_l-6} - 1050671611584 u_{i_l-5} + 291038349240 u_{i_l-4} - 61732186560 u_{i_l-3} \\ + 9412882992 u_{i_l-2} - 918330048 u_{i_l-1} + 43046721 u_{i_l}), O(\Delta x I^2), \textit{Backward}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000055197785449786825421, *New Error:*, $5.5280930627871573874 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.5280930627871573874 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $5.5281013301597144893 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.5281013301597144893 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $5.5281013384270397419 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.5281013384270397419 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $5.5281013384353070671 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $5.5281013384353070671 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $5.5281013384353153344 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{16}}{dx I^{16}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{65536 \Delta x I^{16}} (u_{i_l-16} - 16 u_{i_l-14} + 120 u_{i_l-12} - 560 u_{i_l-10} + 1820 u_{i_l-8} - 4368 u_{i_l-6} + 8008 u_{i_l-4} - 11440 u_{i_l-2} + 12870 u_{i_l}$$

$- 11440 u_{i_l+2} + 8008 u_{i_l+4} - 4368 u_{i_l+6} + 1820 u_{i_l+8} - 560 u_{i_l+10} + 120 u_{i_l+12} - 16 u_{i_l+14} + u_{i_l+16}$), $O(\Delta x I^2)$, *Centered*

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000027640649850090921851, *New Error:*, $2.7640506692319734146 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.7640506692319734146 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.7640506692176576857 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.7640506692176576857 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.7640506692176576714 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.7640506692176576714 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.7640506692176576714 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.7640506692176576714 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $2.7640506692176576714 \times 10^{-35}$

"--- Derivative Order: 17 - x1=17 ---"

$$\frac{d^{17}}{dx^{17}} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Delta x^{17}} \left(-u_{il} + 17 u_{il+1} - 136 u_{il+2} + 680 u_{il+3} - 2380 u_{il+4} + 6188 u_{il+5} - 12376 u_{il+6} + 19448 u_{il+7} - 24310 u_{il+8} + 24310 u_{il+9} \right. \\ \left. - 19448 u_{il+10} + 12376 u_{il+11} - 6188 u_{il+12} + 2380 u_{il+13} - 680 u_{il+14} + 136 u_{il+15} - 17 u_{il+16} + u_{il+17} \right), O(\Delta x), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.044435327754910490121, New Error:, 0.000044052438565347902502

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000044052438565347902502, New Error:, $4.4052057921678875153 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.4052057921678875153 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $4.4052057541037441591 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.4052057541037441591 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $4.4052057540656800160 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.4052057540656800160 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $4.4052057540656419518 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{17}}{dx^{17}} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Delta x^{17}} \left(-u_{il-17} + 17 u_{il-16} - 136 u_{il-15} + 680 u_{il-14} - 2380 u_{il-13} + 6188 u_{il-12} - 12376 u_{il-11} + 19448 u_{il-10} - 24310 u_{il-9} \right. \\ \left. + 24310 u_{il-8} - 19448 u_{il-7} + 12376 u_{il-6} - 6188 u_{il-5} + 2380 u_{il-4} - 680 u_{il-3} + 136 u_{il-2} - 17 u_{il-1} + u_{il} \right), O(\Delta x), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.043673262789912610437, New Error:, 0.000044051676520440326179

Error order:, 1, Error:, 0.000044051676520440326179, New Error:, $4.4052057159633967597 \times 10^{-8}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.4052057159633967597 \times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, $4.4052057540275396684 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.4052057540275396684 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $4.4052057540656038115 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, Error:, $4.4052057540656038115 \times 10^{-14}$, New Error:, $4.4052057540656418756 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{17}}{dx^{17}} u(x) = \frac{1}{131072 \Delta x^{17}} \left(-129140163 u_{il} + 2927177028 u_{il+1} - 31955015889 u_{il+2} + 223766421696 u_{il+3} - 1129456676952 u_{il+4} \right. \\ \left. + 4377900418272 u_{il+5} - 13556828910312 u_{il+6} + 34450456389696 u_{il+7} - 73233727711524 u_{il+8} + 132095426671728 u_{il+9} \right. \\ \left. - 204371019133164 u_{il+10} + 273478006137024 u_{il+11} - 318566016846792 u_{il+12} + 324649089181728 u_{il+13} - 290543757084216 u_{il+14} \right. \\ \left. + 228981243507264 u_{il+15} - 159223439369634 u_{il+16} + 97794850668952 u_{il+17} - 53074479789878 u_{il+18} + 25442360389696 u_{il+19} \right. \\ \left. - 10760879892008 u_{il+20} + 4008013446688 u_{il+21} - 1310971262744 u_{il+22} + 375141297856 u_{il+23} - 93448111172 u_{il+24} + 20133428848 u_{il+25} \right. \\ \left. - 3720658828 u_{il+26} + 583421504 u_{il+27} - 76528696 u_{il+28} + 8237792 u_{il+29} - 708424 u_{il+30} + 46784 u_{il+31} - 2227 u_{il+32} + 68 u_{il+33} - u_{il+34} \right),$$

$O(\Delta x I^2)$, Forward

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000058706048955637348874, New Error:, $5.8618926795001667548 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8618926795001667548 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $5.8618839130542398741 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8618839130542398741 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $5.8618839042877398977 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8618839042877398977 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $5.8618839042789733977 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8618839042789733977 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $5.8618839042789646312 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{17}}{dx^{17}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{131072 \Delta x I^{17}} (u_{iI-34} - 68 u_{iI-33} + 2227 u_{iI-32} - 46784 u_{iI-31} + 708424 u_{iI-30} - 8237792 u_{iI-29} + 76528696 u_{iI-28} - 583421504 u_{iI-27} \\ + 3720658828 u_{iI-26} - 20133428848 u_{iI-25} + 93448111172 u_{iI-24} - 375141297856 u_{iI-23} + 1310971262744 u_{iI-22} - 4008013446688 u_{iI-21} \\ + 10760879892008 u_{iI-20} - 25442360389696 u_{iI-19} + 53074479789878 u_{iI-18} - 97794850668952 u_{iI-17} + 159223439369634 u_{iI-16} \\ - 228981243507264 u_{iI-15} + 290543757084216 u_{iI-14} - 324649089181728 u_{iI-13} + 318566016846792 u_{iI-12} - 273478006137024 u_{iI-11} \\ + 204371019133164 u_{iI-10} - 132095426671728 u_{iI-9} + 73233727711524 u_{iI-8} - 34450456389696 u_{iI-7} + 13556828910312 u_{iI-6} \\ - 4377900418272 u_{iI-5} + 1129456676952 u_{iI-4} - 223766421696 u_{iI-3} + 31955015889 u_{iI-2} - 2927177028 u_{iI-1} + 129140163 u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^2),$$

Backward

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000058530547062140458061, New Error:, $5.8618751289495555024 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8618751289495555024 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $5.8618838955036892625 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8618838955036892625 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $5.8618839042701893471 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8618839042701893471 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $5.8618839042789558471 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $5.8618839042789558471 \times 10^{-29}$, New Error:, $5.8618839042789646136 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{17}}{dx^{17}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{131072 \Delta x I^{17}} (-u_{iI-17} + 17 u_{iI-15} - 136 u_{iI-13} + 680 u_{iI-11} - 2380 u_{iI-9} + 6188 u_{iI-7} - 12376 u_{iI-5} + 19448 u_{iI-3} - 24310 u_{iI-1} \\ + 24310 u_{iI+1} - 19448 u_{iI+3} + 12376 u_{iI+5} - 6188 u_{iI+7} + 2380 u_{iI+9} - 680 u_{iI+11} + 136 u_{iI+13} - 17 u_{iI+15} + u_{iI+17}), O(\Delta x I^2), Centered$$

Error order:, 2, Error:, 0.000029309581053988151148, New Error:, $2.9309419521556355126 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.9309419521556355126 \times 10^{-11}$, New Error:, $2.9309419521394823273 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.9309419521394823273 \times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, $2.9309419521394823112 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, Error:, $2.9309419521394823112 \times 10^{-23}$, New Error:, $2.9309419521394823112 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, Error:., 2.9309419521394823112 $\times 10^{-29}$, New Error:., 2.9309419521394823112 $\times 10^{-35}$

"--- Derivative Order: 18 - x1=18 ---"

$$\frac{d^{18}}{dx^{18}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{18}} (u_{iI} - 18 u_{iI+1} + 153 u_{iI+2} - 816 u_{iI+3} + 3060 u_{iI+4} - 8568 u_{iI+5} + 18564 u_{iI+6} - 31824 u_{iI+7} + 43758 u_{iI+8} - 48620 u_{iI+9} + 43758 u_{iI+10} - 31824 u_{iI+11} + 18564 u_{iI+12} - 8568 u_{iI+13} + 3060 u_{iI+14} - 816 u_{iI+15} + 153 u_{iI+16} - 18 u_{iI+17} + u_{iI+18}), O(\Delta x I), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.046978768818458294351, New Error:., 0.000046550680395571472644

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.000046550680395571472644, New Error:., 4.6550254959838964485 $\times 10^{-8}$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 4.6550254959838964485 $\times 10^{-8}$, New Error:., 4.6550254534405872126 $\times 10^{-11}$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 4.6550254534405872126 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:., 4.6550254533980439037 $\times 10^{-14}$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 4.6550254533980439037 $\times 10^{-14}$, New Error:., 4.6550254533980013604 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{18}}{dx^{18}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{18}} (u_{iI-18} - 18 u_{iI-17} + 153 u_{iI-16} - 816 u_{iI-15} + 3060 u_{iI-14} - 8568 u_{iI-13} + 18564 u_{iI-12} - 31824 u_{iI-11} + 43758 u_{iI-10} - 48620 u_{iI-9} + 43758 u_{iI-8} - 31824 u_{iI-7} + 18564 u_{iI-6} - 8568 u_{iI-5} + 3060 u_{iI-4} - 816 u_{iI-3} + 153 u_{iI-2} - 18 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.046127025911279401131, New Error:., 0.000046549828677674119324

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.000046549828677674119324, New Error:., 4.6550254108121067156 $\times 10^{-8}$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 4.6550254108121067156 $\times 10^{-8}$, New Error:., 4.6550254533554154229 $\times 10^{-11}$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 4.6550254533554154229 $\times 10^{-11}$, New Error:., 4.6550254533979587319 $\times 10^{-14}$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 4.6550254533979587319 $\times 10^{-14}$, New Error:., 4.6550254533980012752 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{18}}{dx^{18}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{262144 \Delta x I^{18}} (387420489 u_{iI} - 9298091736 u_{iI+1} + 107702895942 u_{iI+2} - 802046505672 u_{iI+3} + 4315390733529 u_{iI+4} - 17875294384320 u_{iI+5} + 59311545080976 u_{iI+6} - 161956585228608 u_{iI+7} + 371059837603668 u_{iI+8} - 723671647250976 u_{iI+9} + 1214728491797928 u_{iI+10} - 1770013521615456 u_{iI+11} + 2253981094221636 u_{iI+12} - 2521689341069376 u_{iI+13} + 2488793644826352 u_{iI+14} - 2173767848040384 u_{iI+15} + 1684139049222174 u_{iI+16} - 1159259552992656 u_{iI+17} + 709626281415076 u_{iI+18} - 386419850997552 u_{iI+19})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 187126561024686 u_{il+20} - 80509920297792 u_{il+21} + 30725847466992 u_{il+22} - 10377322391232 u_{il+23} + 3091880787684 u_{il+24} \\
& - 809334029088 u_{il+25} + 185143803048 u_{il+26} - 36766328672 u_{il+27} + 6283930932 u_{il+28} - 914249664 u_{il+29} + 111605136 u_{il+30} \\
& - 11211840 u_{il+31} + 902241 u_{il+32} - 55896 u_{il+33} + 2502 u_{il+34} - 72 u_{il+35} + u_{il+36}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Forward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order: 2, Error: } 0.0000620352341487297916663, \text{ New Error: } 6.1943212534303709815 \times 10^{-11} \\
& \text{Error order: 2, Error: } 6.1943212534303709815 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error: } 6.1943119898424514303 \times 10^{-17} \\
& \text{Error order: 2, Error: } 6.1943119898424514303 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error: } 6.1943119805788022871 \times 10^{-23} \\
& \text{Error order: 2, Error: } 6.1943119805788022871 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error: } 6.1943119805695386379 \times 10^{-29} \\
& \text{Error order: 2, Error: } 6.1943119805695386379 \times 10^{-29}, \text{ New Error: } 6.1943119805695293743 \times 10^{-35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{18}}{dx^{18}} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{262144 \Delta x I^{18}} (u_{il-36} - 72 u_{il-35} + 2502 u_{il-34} - 55896 u_{il-33} + 902241 u_{il-32} - 11211840 u_{il-31} + 111605136 u_{il-30} \\
& - 914249664 u_{il-29} + 6283930932 u_{il-28} - 36766328672 u_{il-27} + 185143803048 u_{il-26} - 809334029088 u_{il-25} + 3091880787684 u_{il-24} \\
& - 10377322391232 u_{il-23} + 30725847466992 u_{il-22} - 80509920297792 u_{il-21} + 187126561024686 u_{il-20} - 386419850997552 u_{il-19} \\
& + 709626281415076 u_{il-18} - 1159259552992656 u_{il-17} + 1684139049222174 u_{il-16} - 2173767848040384 u_{il-15} + 2488793644826352 u_{il-14} \\
& - 2521689341069376 u_{il-13} + 2253981094221636 u_{il-12} - 1770013521615456 u_{il-11} + 1214728491797928 u_{il-10} - 723671647250976 u_{il-9} \\
& + 371059837603668 u_{il-8} - 161956585228608 u_{il-7} + 59311545080976 u_{il-6} - 17875294384320 u_{il-5} + 4315390733529 u_{il-4} \\
& - 802046505672 u_{il-3} + 107702895942 u_{il-2} - 9298091736 u_{il-1} + 387420489 u_{il}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Backward}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order: 2, Error: } 0.000061849779769976092442, \text{ New Error: } 6.1943027075861181857 \times 10^{-11} \\
& \text{Error order: 2, Error: } 6.1943027075861181857 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error: } 6.1943119712966071771 \times 10^{-17} \\
& \text{Error order: 2, Error: } 6.1943119712966071771 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error: } 6.1943119805602564429 \times 10^{-23} \\
& \text{Error order: 2, Error: } 6.1943119805602564429 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error: } 6.1943119805695200921 \times 10^{-29} \\
& \text{Error order: 2, Error: } 6.1943119805695200921 \times 10^{-29}, \text{ New Error: } 6.1943119805695293557 \times 10^{-35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{18}}{dx^{18}} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{262144 \Delta x I^{18}} (u_{il-18} - 18 u_{il-16} + 153 u_{il-14} - 816 u_{il-12} + 3060 u_{il-10} - 8568 u_{il-8} + 18564 u_{il-6} - 31824 u_{il-4} + 43758 u_{il-2} \\
& - 48620 u_{il} + 43758 u_{il+2} - 31824 u_{il+4} + 18564 u_{il+6} - 8568 u_{il+8} + 3060 u_{il+10} - 816 u_{il+12} + 153 u_{il+14} - 18 u_{il+16} + u_{il+18}), O(\Delta x I^2), \\
& \text{Centered}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Error order: 2, Error: } 0.000030971740878730351896, \text{ New Error: } 3.0971559903028622018 \times 10^{-11}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.0971559903028622018 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.0971559902847647006 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.0971559902847647006 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.0971559902847646825 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.0971559902847646825 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $3.0971559902847646825 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.0971559902847646825 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $3.0971559902847646825 \times 10^{-35}$

"--- Derivative Order: 19 - x1=19 ---"

$$\frac{d^{19}}{dx^{19}} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Delta x^{19}} \left(-u_{il} + 19 u_{il+1} - 171 u_{il+2} + 969 u_{il+3} - 3876 u_{il+4} + 11628 u_{il+5} - 27132 u_{il+6} + 50388 u_{il+7} - 75582 u_{il+8} + 92378 u_{il+9} - 92378 u_{il+10} + 75582 u_{il+11} - 50388 u_{il+12} + 27132 u_{il+13} - 11628 u_{il+14} + 3876 u_{il+15} - 969 u_{il+16} + 171 u_{il+17} - 19 u_{il+18} + u_{il+19} \right),$$

$O(\Delta x)$, Forward

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.049514502774630772147, *New Error:*, 0.000049038776273351399662
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000049038776273351399662, *New Error:*, $4.9038303652599526470 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.9038303652599526470 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $4.9038303179981864889 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.9038303179981864889 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.9038303179509247230 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.9038303179509247230 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $4.9038303179508774613 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{19}}{dx^{19}} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Delta x^{19}} \left(-u_{il-19} + 19 u_{il-18} - 171 u_{il-17} + 969 u_{il-16} - 3876 u_{il-15} + 11628 u_{il-14} - 27132 u_{il-13} + 50388 u_{il-12} - 75582 u_{il-11} + 92378 u_{il-10} - 92378 u_{il-9} + 75582 u_{il-8} - 50388 u_{il-7} + 27132 u_{il-6} - 11628 u_{il-5} + 3876 u_{il-4} - 969 u_{il-3} + 171 u_{il-2} - 19 u_{il-1} + u_{il} \right),$$

$O(\Delta x)$, Backward

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.048568290455736409618, *New Error:*, 0.000049037830091852895286
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000049037830091852895286, *New Error:*, $4.9038302706418027996 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.9038302706418027996 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $4.9038303179035683390 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.9038303179035683390 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $4.9038303179508301049 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $4.9038303179508301049 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $4.9038303179508773666 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{19}}{dx^{19}} u(x) = \frac{1}{524288 \Delta x^{19}} \left(-u_{il-19} + 19 u_{il-17} - 171 u_{il-15} + 969 u_{il-13} - 3876 u_{il-11} + 11628 u_{il-9} - 27132 u_{il-7} + 50388 u_{il-5} - 75582 u_{il-3} \right)$$

$$+ 92378 u_{i_{l-1}} - 92378 u_{i_{l+1}} + 75582 u_{i_{l+3}} - 50388 u_{i_{l+5}} + 27132 u_{i_{l+7}} - 11628 u_{i_{l+9}} + 3876 u_{i_{l+11}} - 969 u_{i_{l+13}} + 171 u_{i_{l+15}} - 19 u_{i_{l+17}} + u_{i_{l+19}}), O(\Delta x l^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000032627149704389677485, *New Error:*, $3.2626948223427544317 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.2626948223427544317 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.2626948223226064167 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.2626948223226064167 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.2626948223226063965 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.2626948223226063965 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $3.2626948223226063965 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.2626948223226063965 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $3.2626948223226063965 \times 10^{-35}$

"--- Derivative Order: 20 - x1=20 ---"

$$\frac{d^{20}}{dx l^{20}} u(x l) = \frac{1}{\Delta x l^{20}} (u_{i_l} - 20 u_{i_{l+1}} + 190 u_{i_{l+2}} - 1140 u_{i_{l+3}} + 4845 u_{i_{l+4}} - 15504 u_{i_{l+5}} + 38760 u_{i_{l+6}} - 77520 u_{i_{l+7}} + 125970 u_{i_{l+8}} - 167960 u_{i_{l+9}} + 184756 u_{i_{l+10}} - 167960 u_{i_{l+11}} + 125970 u_{i_{l+12}} - 77520 u_{i_{l+13}} + 38760 u_{i_{l+14}} - 15504 u_{i_{l+15}} + 4845 u_{i_{l+16}} - 1140 u_{i_{l+17}} + 190 u_{i_{l+18}} - 20 u_{i_{l+19}} + u_{i_{l+20}}), O(\Delta x l), \text{ Forward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.052042547635500028074, *New Error:*, 0.000051516756743237932350
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000051516756743237932350, *New Error:*, $5.1516234559375709594 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.1516234559375709594 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $5.1516234037195435550 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.1516234037195435550 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $5.1516234036673255279 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.1516234036673255279 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $5.1516234036672733099 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{20}}{dx l^{20}} u(x l) = \frac{1}{\Delta x l^{20}} (u_{i_{l-20}} - 20 u_{i_{l-19}} + 190 u_{i_{l-18}} - 1140 u_{i_{l-17}} + 4845 u_{i_{l-16}} - 15504 u_{i_{l-15}} + 38760 u_{i_{l-14}} - 77520 u_{i_{l-13}} + 125970 u_{i_{l-12}} - 167960 u_{i_{l-11}} + 184756 u_{i_{l-10}} - 167960 u_{i_{l-9}} + 125970 u_{i_{l-8}} - 77520 u_{i_{l-7}} + 38760 u_{i_{l-6}} - 15504 u_{i_{l-5}} + 4845 u_{i_{l-4}} - 1140 u_{i_{l-3}} + 190 u_{i_{l-2}} - 20 u_{i_{l-1}} + u_{i_l}), O(\Delta x l), \text{ Backward}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.050997104107391770461, *New Error:*, 0.000051515711337291042794
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000051515711337291042794, *New Error:*, $5.1516233513969762742 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.1516233513969762742 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $5.1516234036150029603 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.1516234036150029603 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $5.1516234036672209873 \times 10^{-14}$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $5.1516234036672209873 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $5.1516234036672732054 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^{20}}{dx^{20}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1048576 \Delta x I^{20}} (u_{iI-20} - 20 u_{iI-18} + 190 u_{iI-16} - 1140 u_{iI-14} + 4845 u_{iI-12} - 15504 u_{iI-10} + 38760 u_{iI-8} - 77520 u_{iI-6} + 125970 u_{iI-4} - 167960 u_{iI-2} + 184756 u_{iI} - 167960 u_{iI+2} + 125970 u_{iI+4} - 77520 u_{iI+6} + 38760 u_{iI+8} - 15504 u_{iI+10} + 4845 u_{iI+12} - 1140 u_{iI+14} + 190 u_{iI+16} - 20 u_{iI+18} + u_{iI+20}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Centered}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000034275827856662755442, *New Error:*, $3.4275604815041891579 \times 10^{-11}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4275604815041891579 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $3.4275604814818850906 \times 10^{-17}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4275604814818850906 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $3.4275604814818850683 \times 10^{-23}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4275604814818850683 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $3.4275604814818850683 \times 10^{-29}$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $3.4275604814818850683 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $3.4275604814818850683 \times 10^{-35}$
